

**SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ADOPTION BY BUSINESS-TO-
BUSINESS (B2B) ORGANISATIONS IN GREECE: A MIXED-
METHOD APPROACH**

MARIA ZOITSA CHRONI

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the
requirements of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

OCTOBER 2021

Student Declaration

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

Signed:

Date:

Abstract

Social media (SM) is an essential part of everyday life used by individuals, businesses, and governments worldwide. The overwhelming reliance on SM for communication and information reflects SM's power over people's decisions. While B2B businesses are hesitant to embrace social media marketing (SMM), B2C businesses are profiting from it. However, the factors that influence the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations remain underexplored. Therefore, this study aimed to close this gap in knowledge by examining the factors that influence SM adoption by Business-to-Business organisations in Greece and the perceived benefits and barriers they face. Built on the Diffusion of Innovation theory (DOI), Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) framework and Hofstede's Cultural model, the study developed an integrated conceptual framework containing eighteen (18) variables to examine the factors that influence the SM adoption by the Greek B2B organisations. The study employed a sequential exploratory mixed-method approach. This study relied on semi-structured individual interview data from eleven (11) employees of the case study company, a leading telecommunications company in Greece, for the qualitative phase and survey responses from participants of seventy-two (72) Greek B2B companies, for the quantitative phase. The qualitative findings informed the construction of a refined conceptual framework quantitatively tested through online survey, which validated and generalised the qualitative findings. Descriptive statistics and Logistic Regression (LR) were used to analyse the quantitative data. The LR tested the hypotheses and examined the influence of the eighteen (18) identified factors of SM adoption by Greek B2B organisations. Statistical analysis revealed that four (4) of the eighteen (18) hypotheses were statistically significant in influencing adoption. The researcher concluded that technological, organisational, and cultural factors influence SM adoption decisions,

while environmental factors were insignificant. The four (4) influential factors include interactivity, innovativeness, masculinity, and short-term orientation. Additionally, both phases of the study revealed benefits and barriers to SM adoption among B2B organisations.

Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to my mother, Evaggelia Chroni. Although she is no longer with us, this thesis embodies her love for education and encouragement to persevere to make my dreams a reality. To my husband, Pavlos Theodoropoulos, and our children, Anastasia, and Panagiotis, please know that without your endless love, support, and encouragement, I never would have completed my PhD studies.

Acknowledgements

The completion of this project would not have been possible without the support of many people. Firstly, I would like to thank my Director of Studies, Dr Pravin Balaraman, for his continuous support, guidance, encouragement, and insightful discussions, for which I am sincerely appreciative. Thank you, Dr Emma Reid, for serving as my direct supervisor. Your help and support were critical throughout this arduous process.

I want to thank my husband and soul mate Pavlos. You made this thesis possible through your endless love, emotional support, and unwavering faith in me. I am eternally grateful. To Anastasia and Panagiotis, my beloved children, I want to thank you for your bravery, love, and patience. You followed me to Scotland, stood by me on this adventure, and remained patient with the process. Words cannot express my appreciation and love for you and Pavlos.

To my parents, Apostolos and Evaggelia, thank you for your unconditional love and support throughout my life. You taught me the value of being optimist, patient and diligent in my endeavours, which proved critical in my doctoral pursuit. I would also like to thank my aunt, Christina, my guardian angel, for your persistent presence and wisdom throughout this process. I would also like to thank Mr Nondas Pitticas for his support and advice. Thank you for being a treasured friend to my children and me through our stay in Scotland. Thank you also to my friends Argyris Baklezos and Kyriaki Panagiotaki for their help and support.

I am very thankful to the case study company and its employees for providing their valuable expertise during the interviews. I am grateful for the survey participants who dedicated their valuable time and contributed to this project's empirical side. I praise

the Holy Mother for giving me the strength and patience to persevere over this journey.
I would also like to extend my appreciation to everyone who contributed to the success
of this project.

THANK YOU ALL

Table of Contents

STUDENT DECLARATION.....	I
ABSTRACT.....	II
DEDICATION.....	4
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	V
LIST OF TABLES	XIII
LIST OF FIGURES	XVI
PUBLICATIONS	XIX
CHAPTER 1- INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND.....	1
1.2 RESEARCH MOTIVATION	3
1.3 THEORETICAL APPROACH.....	4
1.4 RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES.....	5
1.5 RESEARCH DESIGN.....	6
1.6 ORIGINALITY AND RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION	7
1.6.1 Originality.....	7
1.6.2 Contribution to the knowledge and practice	8
1.7 THE STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS	8
1.8 SUMMARY	12
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE ANALYSIS	13
2.1 INTRODUCTION	13
2.2 SOCIAL MEDIA AND SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING.....	13
2.2.1 Social media definitions.....	14

2.2.2 <i>Social media marketing definitions</i>	17
2.3 BUSINESS-TO-BUSINESS MARKETING	19
2.4 B2B BUYING PROCESS	23
2.5 BUSINESS-TO-CONSUMER (B2C) MARKETING AND DIFFERENCES WITH B2B .	25
2.6 OVERVIEW OF ICT ADOPTION MODELS AND THEORIES	26
2.6.1 <i>Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory</i>	27
2.6.2 <i>Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)</i>	29
2.7 RESULTS OF THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW	31
2.7.1 <i>Descriptive analysis</i>	32
2.7.2 <i>Thematic analysis</i>	45
2.7.3 <i>Research gaps</i>	52
2.8 SUMMARY	53
CHAPTER 3- THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	55
3.1 INTRODUCTION	55
3.2 THE TECHNOLOGY-ORGANISATION- ENVIRONMENT (TOE) FRAMEWORK ...	55
3.2.1 <i>Technological context</i>	59
3.2.2 <i>Organisational context</i>	60
3.2.3 <i>Environmental context</i>	61
3.3 HOFSTEDE’S CULTURAL DIMENSIONS THEORY- THE CULTURAL CONTEXT	62
3.4 SUMMARY	69
CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH CONTEXT- GREECE	70
4.1 INTRODUCTION	70
4.2 GREEK ECONOMIC CONTEXT	70
4.3 DIGITAL STATUS IN GREECE	74

4.4 SUMMARY	78
CHAPTER 5-RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY	80
5.1 INTRODUCTION	80
5.2 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY	81
5.2.1 <i>Epistemology</i>	82
5.2.2 <i>Ontology</i>	84
5.2.3 <i>Axiology</i>	85
5.3 RESEARCH APPROACH.....	86
5.3.1 <i>Inductive: from specific to general</i>	87
5.3.2 <i>Deductive: from general to specific</i>	87
5.4 RESEARCH STRATEGIES	89
5.4.1 <i>Qualitative research strategy</i>	89
5.4.2 <i>Quantitative research strategy</i>	92
5.4.3 <i>Mixed-method strategy</i>	93
5.5 RESEARCH DESIGN.....	96
5.5.1 <i>Systematic literature review</i>	98
5.6 DATA COLLECTION	102
5.6.1 <i>Qualitative study</i>	102
5.6.2 <i>Analysis of the qualitative data</i>	109
5.6.3 <i>Quantitative study</i>	127
5.7 SUMMARY	141
CHAPTER 6 – THE QUALITATIVE STUDY	144
6.1 INTRODUCTION	144

6.2 FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ADOPTION OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING BY B2B ORGANISATIONS.....	144
<i>6.2.1 Technological context.....</i>	<i>146</i>
<i>6.2.2 Organisational context.....</i>	<i>156</i>
<i>6.2.3 Environmental context.....</i>	<i>165</i>
<i>6.2.4 Cultural context.....</i>	<i>170</i>
6.3 RESEARCH HYPOTHESES.....	180
6.4 BENEFITS OF ADOPTING SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IN A B2B ORGANISATION	183
6.5 BARRIERS TO THE ADOPTION OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING	192
6.6 DISCUSSION ON THE QUALITATIVE FINDINGS ABOUT THE BENEFITS AND BARRIERS	200
<i>6.6.1 Benefits.....</i>	<i>200</i>
<i>6.6.2 Barriers.....</i>	<i>201</i>
6.7 CONCLUSION.....	203
CHAPTER 7 – THE QUANTITATIVE STUDY.....	204
7.1 INTRODUCTION	204
7.2 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS: CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SAMPLE	204
<i>7.2.1 Respondent’s characteristics</i>	<i>205</i>
<i>7.2.2 Companies’ demographics.....</i>	<i>208</i>
7.3 INFERENCE STATISTICS- LOGISTIC REGRESSION	225
<i>7.3.1 Assessing the Logistic Regression Model accuracy.....</i>	<i>228</i>
7.4 FINDINGS.....	235
<i>7.4.1 Technology Context</i>	<i>237</i>
<i>7.4.2 Organisational Context.....</i>	<i>238</i>

7.4.3 <i>Environmental Context</i>	239
7.4.4 <i>Cultural context</i>	239
7.5 DISCUSSION ON THE QUANTITATIVE FINDINGS	241
7.5.1 <i>Technological context</i>	242
7.5.2. <i>Organisational context</i>	246
7.5.3 <i>Environmental context</i>	249
7.5.4. <i>Cultural context</i>	251
7.5.5 <i>Benefits</i>	253
7.5.6 <i>Barriers</i>	255
7.6 REVISED RESEARCH FRAMEWORK	256
7.7 SUMMARY OF THE CHAPTER	258
CHAPTER 8- CONCLUSION	259
8.1 INTRODUCTION	259
8.2 RESULTS AGAINST THE RESEARCH OBJECTIVES	260
8.3 THEORETICAL CONTRIBUTIONS	264
8.4 PRACTICAL CONTRIBUTIONS	265
8.4.1 <i>Implications for B2B companies</i>	265
8.4.2 <i>Implications for policy makers</i>	268
8.4.3 <i>Implications for Academics</i>	270
8.5 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS	272
8.6 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH	273
8.7 SUMMARY	274
REFERENCES	276
APPENDIX A	333

APPENDIX B	336
APPENDIX C	338
APPENDIX D	339
APPENDIX E	340
APPENDIX F	341
APPENDIX G.....	352

List of Tables

Table 2.1: Social Media tools and their objectives	15
Table 2.2: Summary of different definitions of social media	16
Table 2.3: Social media marketing definitions	17
Table 2.4: Some key differences between B2B and B2C marketing.....	21
Table 2.5: Differences between business and consumer markets.....	22
Table 2.6: B2B buying process	24
Table 2.7: Social media in the B2B context- a systematic literature review	34
Table 2.8: Determinants-factors of SM adoption	46
Table 2.9: Benefits of SM adoption.....	50
Table 2.10: Barriers of SM adoption	51
Table 3.1: Some studies used TOE Framework.....	58
Table 3.2: Definitions of the TOE framework constructs.....	58
Table 3.3: Definitions of Hofstede’s cultural dimensions	65
Table 4.1: Some studies conducted in Greece	73
Table 4.2: DESI 2020 scores for Greece	75
Table 5.1: Ontology of research philosophies	85
Table 5.2: Axiology of research philosophies and relevant data collection techniques	86
Table 5.3: Major differences between inductive and deductive research approaches .	88
Table 5.4: Systematic Literature Review Database Used	99
Table 5.5: Systematic Literature keyword search.....	99
Table 5.6: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for the SLR	100
Table 5.7: Data extraction instrument.....	101
Table 5.8: Interview instrument.....	105

Table 5.9: Participants demographic characteristics.....	110
Table 5.10: Advantages of Thematic Analysis	113
Table 5.11: Main themes classification	118
Table 5.12: Subthemes.....	119
Table 5.13: Identified benefits	120
Table 5.14: Identified barriers.....	121
Table 5.15: Coding frequency for analysing the Technological Context	122
Table 5.16: Research criteria for the participated companies.....	132
Table 5.17: Survey structure	133
Table 5.18: Types of validity, adapted from.....	135
Table 5.19: Factor analysis	137
Table 5.20: Reliability assessment of research variables.....	138
Table 5.21: Survey responses	141
Table 6.1: Coding frequency for analysing the Technological Context	146
Table 6.2: Coding frequency for analysing the Organisational context	157
Table 6.3: Coding frequency for analysing the Environmental Context	165
Table 6.4 Coding frequency for analysing the Cultural Context.....	171
Table 6.5: A summary of factors influencing the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations in Greece.....	179
Table 6.6: Proposed hypotheses.....	181
Table 6.7: Benefits of social media marketing	184
Table 6.8: Barriers to social media marketing adoption.....	193
Table 7.1: Descriptive statistics on respondent’s demographic characteristics.....	205
Table 7.2: Descriptive statistics on company’s demographic characteristics.....	209
Table 7.3: EU SMEs definition.....	210

Table 7.4: Crosstabulation between Number of employees and SM adoption.....	211
Table 7.5: Crosstabulation between Turnover and SM adoption	213
Table 7.6: Crosstabulation between Company orientation and SM adoption	214
Table 7.7: Crosstabulation between Industry and SM adoption	216
Table 7.8: Crosstabulation between Company scope and SM adoption.....	217
Table 7.9: Non-adopters' classification	218
Table 7.10: Adopters versus Non-adopters.....	218
Table 7.11: Adopted SM platforms	219
Table 7.12: Purposes of SMM marketing use.....	220
Table 7.13: Intention of the company in terms of adoption of SMM.....	222
Table 7.14: When they intend to use SMM	222
Table 7.15: Benefits of SMM adoption	223
Table 7.16: Barriers of SM adoption	224
Table 7.17: Ways to facilitate SM adoption	224
Table 7.18: Classification table- Null model (Baseline model).....	229
Table 7.19: Classification table- Full model.....	230
Table 7.20: Correlation Matrix	233
Table 7.21: Collinearity statistics- TOL & VIF.....	234
Table 7.22: Logistic Regression	236
Table 7.23: Hypotheses related to the technological context	237
Table 7.24: Hypotheses related to the organisational context	238
Table 7.25: Hypotheses related to the environmental context.....	239
Table 7.26: Hypotheses related to the cultural context.....	240
Table 7.27: Summary of hypotheses.....	241

List of Figures

Figure 1.1: The Structure of the Thesis	11
Figure 2.1: Key concept definitions.....	14
Figure 2.2: Diffusion of innovations (DOI) Theory	28
Figure 2.3: Original Technology Acceptance Model	29
Figure 2.4: First modified version of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)	30
Figure 2.5: The final version of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).....	31
Figure 2.6: Journal publishing B2B social media research.....	32
Figure 2.7: Publications per year	33
Figure 2.8: Type of studies	33
Figure 3.1: Technology, Organization and Environment (TOE) framework	56
Figure 3.2: Hofstede’s Cultural Dimensions Theory.....	64
Figure 3.3: Hofstede’s score for the Greek culture.....	67
Figure 3.4: The preliminary conceptual framework	68
Figure 4.1: DESI index	75
Figure 4.2: DESI 2020 scores for the Integration of digital technology.....	77
Figure 5.1: The Honeycomb Research Methodology	81
Figure 5.2: Research philosophy.....	82
Figure 5.3: How theory fits into your research	87
Figure 5.4: Different types of mixed method research	95
Figure 5.5: Research design map for this research	97
Figure 5.6: The Qualitative phase	103
Figure 5.7: Case study structure.....	115
Figure 5.8: Data analysis process.....	116
Figure 5.9: Data reduction process	117

Figure 5.10: A word cloud of the study	123
Figure 5.11: An example of organising the themes and subthemes	123
Figure 5.12: An example of text search query	124
Figure 5.13: Strengths and potential weaknesses of online surveys	129
Figure 5.14: Summary of the Research Methodology	143
Figure 6.1: The updated conceptual framework	145
Figure 6.2: Technological factors	146
Figure 6.3: Organisational factors.....	157
Figure 6.4: Environmental factors	165
Figure 6.5: Cultural factors	171
Figure 6.6: The updated preliminary framework of SMM adoption by Greek B2B organisations	182
Figure 7.1: Respondent’s job status	206
Figure 7.2: Respondent’s age.....	207
Figure 7.3: Table of employment status in Greece	207
Figure 7.4: Education level	208
Figure 7.5: Size-Number of employees	211
Figure 7.6: Turnover	212
Figure 7.7: Company’s age	213
Figure 7.8: Company orientation	214
Figure 7.10: Adopted SM platforms	219
Figure 7.11: Purposes of SM use	221
Figure 7.12: The Revised conceptual research framework of social media marketing adoption by Greek B2B organisations	258

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full term
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
DOI	Diffusion of Innovation
EDI	Electronic Data Interchange
eWOM	Electronic word-of-mouth
FA	Factor analysis
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IS	Information Systems
IT	Information Technology
LR	Logistic Regression
SM	Social media
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SMM	Social media marketing
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
TA	Thematic Analysis
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TOE	Technology-Organisation-Environment
VIF	Variance Inflation Factor

Publications

- Chroni, Z. M. and Balaraman, P. (2018) ‘Adoption of social media in Business-to-Business (B2B) small medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Greece’, in *Conference Proceedings of 3rd International Conference of Development and Economy (ICODECON)*, pp. 171–179.
- Chroni, Z. M. and Balaraman, P. (2018) ‘Adoption and use of social media by business-to-business SMEs in Greece’, in *British Academy of Management Annual Conference 2018 : Driving Productivity in Uncertain and Challenging Times*, pp. 818.
- Chroni, Z. M. and Balaraman, P. (2019) ‘Determinants of social media marketing adoption in a major telecom multinational corporation in Greece: an internal and external perspective’, in *52nd Annual Academy of Marketing Conference Proceedings, 2-4 July 2019*, pp. 61–62.

CHAPTER 1- INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research background

Social media (SM) is a worldwide phenomenon that has altered how we live, work, and learn (Chroni and Balaraman, 2018). SM is rapidly dominating all forms of communication, offering unprecedented opportunities for improving performance at individual and organisational levels (Itani *et al.*, 2017). For B2B marketers, social media marketing (SMM) provides tools that lower marketing costs, increase sales and provide a quantifiable return on investment (ROI) (Bodnar and Cohen, 2012). Marketers contend SM is an essential component of their marketing strategy (Mangold and Faulds, 2009).

To demonstrate the influence of SM, Facebook reported 2.85 billion active users on a monthly basis during the 2021 first quarter, Twitter has approximately 330 million users and LinkedIn has around half a billion users worldwide (Statista, 2021). These statistics demonstrate the popularity and the vast influence of those applications. The newer use of SM through mobile technology gives users access to the media anytime and anywhere (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). McCann and Barlow (2015) argue the businesses should not ignore the dynamic of SM and its value and potential to create business opportunities. However, it is not enough for firms to introduce SM in their businesses by assigning up for Facebook or Twitter. To effectively use SM, companies need a SM strategy that supports their business objectives (Stockdale *et al.*, 2012).

In marketing perspective, SM is “the technological component of the communication, transaction and relationship building functions of a business which leverages the network of customers and prospects to promote value co-creation” (Andzulis *et al.*, 2012, p. 308). We are moving from “one-to-one communication” (Ananda, Hernández-

García and Lamberti, 2016) to “one-to-many” with SM use, and “word of mouth” (WOM) conversations to “word of mouse” (Stokes and Nelson, 2013) or “electronic word of mouth” (eWOM) (Bulearca and Bulearca, 2010). Large and small organisations can identify new marketing opportunities through SM integration and use.

In the industrial context, companies benefit from the versatility of SM, using SM for communication and improving customer relationships, as a recruiting tool, and to increase sales and build their brands (Vasudevan and Kumar, 2018). Business-to-Business (B2B) companies utilise SM in their marketing efforts, gain valuable customer information, and maintain communication with their users (Keinänen and Kuivalainen, 2015). The use of SM also impacts customer retention and profitability (Ahmad, Abu Bakar and Ahmad, 2019; Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2015). According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), B2B marketers use SM in branding, to effectively target customers and manage customer relationships (Moore, Hopkins and Raymond, 2013).

Many business executives and academics worldwide consider SM to be one of the most important topics. Despite this interest, there seems to be a low level of SM adoption and understanding in the business sector (Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen, 2014) with little known about how to improve company promotional and marketing activities (Melanthiou *et al.*, 2015). The primarily identified barriers to adopting B2B SM in the literature include insufficient technical knowledge and skills (Michaelidou *et al.*, 2011), determining the return on investment (ROI) (Kärkkäinen *et al.*, 2010) and inadequate resources (Jussila *et al.*, 2014). Mangold and Faulds (2009), supported that B2B marketers are hesitant to use SM channels because of inadequate communication control.

1.2 Research motivation

Traditionally, Business-to-Consumer (B2C) enterprises more commonly and frequently use SM than B2B companies (Katona and Sarvary, 2014). However, B2B online communities are expanding in response to the growing importance of SM. According to Kietzmann *et al.* (2011), adopting new technologies outpaced current academic research, and SM has become ingrained in everyday life. To minimise the theory-practice gap, researchers must evaluate the result of new technologies on business needs (Ainin *et al.*, 2015).

Current SM marketing researchers predominantly conduct consumer-based studies that overshadow the company's perspective, which leaves a gap in the literature that researchers also identified (Agnihotri *et al.*, 2016; Järvinen *et al.*, 2012; Katona and Sarvary, 2014). Therefore, SM adoption research in the industrial context is emerging (Siamagka *et al.*, 2015). Previous B2B researchers identified challenges in SM use given the significant differences in B2C and B2B companies (Lehtimäki *et al.*, 2009; Jussila *et al.*, 2014). Given, these differences (Jussila, 2015) and the growing importance of SM tools for B2B marketing (Brennan and Croft, 2012), it is imperative to investigate SM adoption in the B2B context to fill the literature gap (Lacka and Chong, 2016). Additionally, the factors influencing SM adoption decisions and how SM use enhances business performance remains underexplored. Companies that understand factors influencing SM adoption will likely select the most appropriate SM tools and ways to organise SM content (Ahmad, Ahmad and Abu Bakar, 2018). Moreover, several researchers suggested the need to investigate the benefits and the barriers B2B organisations experience from SM adoption (Siamagka *et al.*, 2015; Michaelidou *et al.*, 2011).

Research on SM adoption by Greek B2B organisations is scarce. To date, the few studies related to SM use in Greece were from the food industry (Vlachvei and Notta, 2014) and the tourist industry (Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020). Greece has been in the most profound and most prolonged recession in its post-war history from 2010-2018 (Alogoskoufis and Featherstone, 2021). According to Giotopoulos *et al.* (2017), because the financial crisis had such a negative impact on Greece, this country has particular research and policy interest. Many scholars and policymakers emphasised the critical role that ICT can influence the country's efforts to revive and grow. A positive sign of the importance of ICT in the recovery of the Greek economy is the fact that in acknowledgement of the use of innovation by the city to overcome the recent economic and social crisis, the Greek capital, Athens, was granted the title of the **European Capital of Innovation 2018** (European Commission, 2018).

1.3 Theoretical approach

Researchers used various theoretical perspectives to investigate new technologies adoption (Chong *et al.*, 2009; Oliveira and Martins, 2011). The Technology, Organisation, and Environment (TOE) framework (DePietro, Wiarda and Fleischer, 1990) and Rogers' (1983) Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) theory are popular models for understanding technology adoption, particularly by firms (Oliveira and Martins, 2011). The TOE framework investigated SM (Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2018; Mikalef and Pateli, 2017; Ahmad, Abu Bakar and Ahmad, 2019; Matikiti, Mpinganjira and Roberts-Lombard, 2018) and ICT adoption and new technologies at the firm level (Konstantinidis, 2016; Giotopoulos *et al.*, 2017; Awa and Ojiabo, 2016). In addition, this study employed Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory (Hofstede, 1991) cooperatively to provide a comprehensive insight into SM adoption by Greek B2B companies. Previous studies also integrated the TOE framework and Hofstede's theory;

for example, Eitle and Buxmann (2020) employed both theories to examine the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) and Nguyen (2016) to investigate the adoption of e-Government services.

1.4 Research aim and objectives

The research examined the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations within the Greek context. More specifically, it explored the main determinants, benefits, and barriers to the adoption decision. In addition, this study's findings contribute to the limited but growing body of research in the B2B context by developing and empirically tested a relevant conceptual framework. This study's findings provides insight into the potential that SMM has for B2B organisations, as many are still sceptical (Michaelidou *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, to operationalise this aim, the researcher implanted the following objectives.

RO1: To critically explore a B2B organisation's perceptions on the factors influencing the adoption of SMM.

RO2: To critically examine the factors that influence the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations by testing the developed conceptual framework quantitatively with a larger sample of companies.

RO3: To critically identify the potential benefits from the adoption of SMM for B2B organisations.

RO4: To critically examine the barriers faced by B2B organisations for the adoption of SMM.

RO5: To develop an empirical framework for studying the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations in the Greek context.

RO6: To develop practical implications for practitioners and policy makers on the adoption of SMM.

1.5 Research design

This study adopted a pragmatic philosophy to provide unique and imaginative perspectives on research work (Saunders *et al.*, 2016), which is best suited for mixed methods researchers (Wilson, 2014; Saunders *et al.*, 2016). Pragmatic research contributes to a robust understanding of B2B SMM adoption (Jussila *et al.*, 2014).

Molina-Azorín and Cameron (2010, p. 95) explain, “the overall purpose and central premise of mixed methods is that the use of quantitative and qualitative approaches in combination provides a better understanding of research problems and complex phenomena than either approach alone”. The combination of methodologies enhances the study’s strengths, validity, reliability, and trustworthiness, as the two methods are complementary. Therefore, the mixed methods design mitigates the limitations and weaknesses of the two methods through using multiple data collection and analysis processes and data sources.

The researcher conducted a mixed methods study to meet the study’s purpose. Creswell and Plano Clark (2006, p. 75) explain how mixed methods researchers “develop and test an instrument...or identify important variables to study quantitatively when the variables are unknown”, which is consistent with the study’s purpose. The qualitative portion of this study led to the creation of a conceptual framework and tested through quantitative means.

The researcher employed a sequential exploratory mixed-method approach. This approach aimed to generalise the qualitative findings through a quantitative method. First, the researcher investigated the topic through a qualitative case study research

approach to gather detailed descriptions of the research topic and organisational contexts. The sample was the biggest telecommunication provider in Greece. An online survey validated and generalised the qualitative findings in the second phase and gained quantitative insights into the research topic (Blaikie, 2010).

1.6 Originality and research contribution

1.6.1 Originality

According to Delamont, Atkinson and Parry (2000) “the originality of postgraduate research is always defined in terms of the essential tension between accepted prior knowledge and new discoveries of ideas”. Multiple components of this study demonstrate originality. The integration of multiple technology adoption theories demonstrate originality through advancing knowledge on B2B organisation’s SM adoption and using a newly constructed conceptual framework from merging components of the DOI and TOE framework and Hofstede’s cultural theory into a single conceptual framework. The newly created conceptual framework reflects originality, as the researcher constructed an original conceptual framework utilizing the essential components of established theories and models but with a new interpretation. Using various methodologies to collect and analyse data increases originality, and this study relied on qualitative and quantitative methodologies. From a systematic literature review, the researcher drafted the new conceptual framework and tested it, qualitatively, through conducting eleven (11) semi-structured individual interviews that led to conceptual framework refinements. The researcher tested the refined conceptual framework using statistical analysis as part of the quantitative phase of research. Therefore, the findings are original, as they advance the current body of literature by introducing a researcher-created conceptual framework restricted to Greek B2B organisations.

1.6.2 Contribution to the knowledge and practice

The study contributes to theory and practice. It advances the emerging but limited research in industrial contexts (Alves, Fernandes and Raposo, 2016; Drummond, McGrath and O’Toole, 2018) by developing and testing a conceptual framework to explore SM adoption and identify factors promoting Greek B2B organisations’ adoption and use of SMM. Further, this study triangulates data from qualitative interviews and quantitative survey from Greek B2B companies to elucidate the primary determinants, benefits, and barriers to SM adoption. Additionally, future researchers can use this study as a base for creating new theories and guidelines for B2B organisations in using SMM.

In terms of practical implications, Greek B2B managers, owners, and policymakers can use this study’s findings to inform their decision-making process. It can also help them create and adopt more effective SMM strategies. Greek B2B firms would benefit from SMM, as it enables them to analyse sizeable and growing markets and expand their local and global, thereby furthering the country’s economic recovery and growth.

1.7 The Structure of the Thesis

The thesis structure is illustrated in Figure 1.1. The thesis has eight (8) chapters. This section contains the chapter summaries:

Chapter 1: Chapter 1 summarises the research motivation for researching industrial SMM adoption, this study’s aims and objectives, its contribution to current research and the research structure.

Chapter 2: Chapter 2 presents a systematic literature review about SM in the B2B context. The chapter contains several definitions of SM and SMM followed by the steps for conducting the systematic literature review and outlines the literature about SMM

in the B2B context. The chapter also explores the determinants, benefits, and barriers to SM adoption by B2B companies. A summary concludes this chapter by summarising the existing ICT adoption models and theories literature.

Chapter 3: Chapter 3 outlines the theoretical frameworks and models that formed the theoretical basis for developing the conceptual framework used to study the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations. The chapter ends by describing the conceptual framework and summarising the chapter.

Chapter 4: This chapter explains this study's research context. It discusses the economic context of Greece and gives details of the adoption of ICT technologies in Greece

Chapter 5: This chapter details overall the study's research design, documents components of the qualitative and quantitative exploratory research, and examines the research philosophy. It also discusses the sampling and the methods the researcher followed to perform data collection and analysis.

Chapter 6: Chapter 6 describes the qualitative phase of the study. This chapter presents the qualitative analyses and findings used to update the conceptual framework and develop the research hypotheses the researcher tested during the quantitative phase of the study. This chapter concludes with a summary of the qualitative findings.

Chapter 7: This chapter outlines the quantitative findings. It details the descriptive and inferential statistical analyses the researcher employed to analyse the data derived from the online survey. Finally, it discusses the quantitative findings and concludes with the revised conceptual framework that depicts the factors influencing a B2B organisation to adopt SMM.

Chapter 8: The final chapter documents the research's conclusions based on the revised research objectives defined in Chapter 1. In addition, it discusses how the thesis contributes to the literature and its implications for academics, B2B companies and policymakers. The chapter concludes with the study's limitations and offers recommendations for further research.

Figure 1.1: The Structure of the Thesis

1.8 Summary

Chapter 1 introduced the study, including the research problem, study's aims and objectives, theoretical frameworks that addressing the research problem and the study's contribution to theory and practice. Chapter 2 presents a systematic literature review about SM in the B2B context and specifies the gaps in the literature.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE ANALYSIS

2.1 Introduction

Chapter 1 provided a detailed overview of the research by describing the research background, research objectives, methodology, research structure and identified the research gap that this study addressed. This chapter elucidates the research problem by synthesising the extant literature in social media (SM) in the business-to-business (B2B) context. Section 2.2 commences broadly with the concepts of social media (SM) and social media marketing (SMM) and their definitions. Sections 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5 provide a foundation for understanding the concepts of B2B and B2C marketing, respectively. Section 2.6 explains the various theories and models of ICT adoption. Section 2.7 provides a systematic literature review on SM in the B2B context and illuminates the determinants, perceived benefits, and perceived barriers to SM adoption. Finally, Section 2.9 summarises the chapter.

2.2 Social media and Social media marketing

The term “social media” introduced in 2005, was used to describe various web-based services only supported by Web 2.0, a more current version of the World Wide Web (WWW), also known as Web 1.0 (O’Reilly, 2007). This platform provides a place where all operators are collaboratively sharing content (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). Campbell *et al.* (2011, p.87) advocated that interactivity, interoperability, and cooperation have expanded as the Internet has progressed from simple information retrieval:

“It is much more to do with what people are doing with the technology than the technology itself, for rather than merely retrieving information, users are now creating and consuming it, and hence adding value to the website that permit them to do so”

2.2.1 Social media definitions

Fischer and Reuber (2011) suggested that there is no singular or definitive typology for SM. However, several researchers propose varying definitions of SM that researchers use to create new definitions with aspects they deem suitable. This research uses Kaplan and Haenlein's (2010, p. 61) definition of SM:

“...a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content.”

Additionally, SM incorporates the concept of user-generated content (UGC), which distinguishes between Web 1.0 and Web 2.0 technologies. Web 2.0 allows end-users access to media material, such as text, audio, videos, images and photos (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010), and publish material since Web 1.0 only supports passive viewing (Hanna, Rohm and Crittenden, 2011). SM, a by-product of Web 2.0 technology, includes social networks, podcasting, blogs, wikis (among other sites), that consumers use daily (Lai and Turban, 2008). Figure 2.1 depicts the relationship between SM, Web 2.0, and user-generated content and defines each concept.

Figure 2.1: Key concept definitions (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010), cited in (Nakara et al., 2012, p. 392)

According to Agarwal and Yiliyasi (2010), and cited in Habibi *et al.* (2015) and Castronovo and Huang (2012, p. 123), there are classifications of SM platforms and their goals, seen in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Social Media tools and their objectives (Castronovo and Huang, 2012, p. 123; Agarwal and Yiliyasi, 2010, cited in Habibi *et al.*, 2015)

Tools	Objectives
Chat Rooms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • enhance customer service • foster community • solicit feedback from customers
Blogs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • influence WOM recommendations • cultivate positive relationships • boost loyalty
You Tube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use video's power to increase content embedding on other sites
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • advertise • create communities • target audiences
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • interact with professionals in groups
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • involve customers • spread conversations
Amazon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • build business communities

According to Stockdale *et al.* (2012), SM assists companies in increasing their business value and competitiveness and helps Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) access resources formerly reserved for large corporations (Kim, Lee and Lee, 2013).

Table 2.2 lists some of the many definitions of SM:

Table 2.2: Summary of different definitions of social media (source: by the researcher)

	Author(s)	Definition
1.	Palen (2008, p. 76) cited in Melanthiou, Papasolomou and Komodromos (2015)	SM includes “blogs, social networking environments, person-to-person broadcasting messaging and other Web 2.0 applications”.
2.	Mangold and Faulds (2009, p. 359)	“SM is a hybrid in that it springs from mixed technology and media origins that enable instantaneous, real-time communications, and utilizes multi-media formats and numerous delivery platforms with global reach capabilities”.
3.	Strauss and Frost (2009, p. 326)	“Online tools and platforms that allow users to collaborate online content, share insights and experiences, and connect to business or pleasure”.
4.	Henderson and Bowley (2010, p. 239)	“SM is collaborative online applications and technologies that enable participation, connectivity user-generated content, sharing of information, and collaboration amongst a community of users”.
5.	Hennig-Thurau <i>et al.</i> (2010, p. 312)	“Channels in which active consumers engage in behaviors that can be consumed by others both in real time and long afterwards regardless of their spatial location”.
6.	Berthon <i>et al.</i> (2012, p. 263)	“SM content comprises text, pictures videos, and networks”.
7.	Mohammadian and Mohammadreza (2012, p. 58)	“SM refers to activities, practices, and behaviours among communities of people who gather online to share information, knowledge, and opinions using conversational media”.
8.	Daj (2013, p. 16)	SM is “the term commonly given to websites, online tools, and other interactive communication technologies which allow users to interact with each other in some way, either by sharing information, opinions, knowledge, or interests”.
9.	Constantinides (2014, p. 42)	“...is a collection of interactive, open source and user-controlled Internet applications enhancing the experiences, collaboration, knowledge and market power of the users as participants in business and social process”.
10.	Filo, Lock and Karg (2015, p.167)	“New media technologies facilitating interactivity and co-creation that allow for the development and sharing of user-generated content among and between organizations (e.g., teams, governing bodies, agencies and media groups) and individuals (e.g., consumers, athletes and journalists)”.
11.	Carr and Hayes (2015, p. 50)	“Internet-based channels that allow users to opportunistically interact and selectively self-present, either in real-time or asynchronously, with both broad and narrow audiences who derive value from user-generated content and the perception of interaction with others”.

2.2.2 Social media marketing definitions

It is also critical to distinguish between SM and SMM. Table 2.3 summarizes the various SMM definitions identified during a review of the literature.

Table 2.3: Social media marketing definitions (source: by the researcher)

	Author(s)	Definition
1.	Weinberg (2009) cited in Khan and Jan (2015, p. 14)	“SMM is the process that empowers individuals to promote their websites, products, or services through online social channels and tap into a much larger community that may have not been available via traditional channels”.
2.	Gunelius (2011, p. 10)	“SMM is any form of direct or indirect marketing that is used to build awareness, recognition, recall, and action for a brand, business, product, person, or other entity and is carried out using the tools of the social Web, such as blogging, micro blogging, social networking, social bookmarking, and content sharing”.
3.	Chi (2011, p. 46)	“SMM is a connection between the brands and consumers, that offers a personal channel and currency for user-centered networking and social interaction”.
4.	Mohammadian and Mohammadreza (2012, p. 58)	“SMM is defined as the possibility to notify the customers of our product or our business through the use of social networking tools”.
5.	Järvinen <i>et al.</i> (2012, p. 103)	“The use of technologies in marketing effort”.
6.	Dahnil <i>et al.</i> (2014, p. 120)	“SMM makes use of the SM platforms and its related technologies and features to help achieve marketing objectives in conjunction with other marketing communication tools”.
7.	Moretti and Tuan (2014, p. 256)	“SMM refers to the process that empowers individuals to promote their websites by gaining attention through SM sites and by tapping into a larger community that may not have been available via traditional communication channels”.
8.	Dwivedi, Kapoor and Chen (2015, p. 291)	“SMM can be defined as a dialogue often triggered by consumers/ audiences, or a business/product/service that circulate amongst the stated parties to set in motion a revealing communication on some promotional information so that it allows learning from one another’s use and experiences, eventually benefitting all of the involved parties”.
9.	Tuten and Solomon, (2015, p. 21)	“The utilization of SM technologies, channels, and software is to create, communicate, deliver and exchange offerings that have value for an organization’s stakeholders”.
10.	Khan and Jan (2015, p. 15)	“SMM is a process where seven functional blocks (identity, conversation, sharing, presence, relationship, reputation and groups) of a SM website are utilized for promotion of a brand, organization, political party, a personality, an idea or an event”.

11.	Felix, Rauschnabel and Hinsch (2017, p. 123)	“SMM is an interdisciplinary and cross-functional concept that uses SM (often in combination with other communications channels) to achieve organizational goals by creating value for stakeholders”.
-----	--	---

The most important goal of SMM is to foster company engagement with customers (Mohammadian and Mohammadreza, 2012). Moreover, Gunelius (2011), cited in Mohammadian and Mohammadreza (2012), explained that the primary objectives of SMM are:

- *Building relationships*: The ability to cultivate relationships with consumers who are actively engaged, influencers, and others is the primary benefit of SMM
- *Building a brand*: SM conversations increase brand awareness, recognition, recall, and loyalty.
- *Publicity*: Businesses can use SMM to distribute valuable information and improve negative perceptions.
- *Promotions*: Businesses can use SMM to incentivise their target audience through offering discounts and opportunities and making them feel valued and special while meeting short-term goals.
- *Market analysis*: Companies can use SM tools to better understand their customers, including their demands and needs, create customer demographic and behavioural profiles, discover niche markets and learn about their competition.

While there is no singular definition of SM, most scholars and practitioners describe it as online tools and platforms that enable communication, collaboration, and information dissemination (Strauss and Frost, 2009; Daj, 2013). SM predates the 1990s, only gaining widespread popularity in the early 2000s following the creation of SM platforms like Facebook and YouTube in 2005 (Edosomwan *et al.*, 2011). Businesses

identified the power and influence of SM, which led to the integration of SM in their marketing strategy. Now, businesses across industries are exploring SMM adoption and integration into their existing marketing approach. The following section presents B2B marketing and strategies.

2.3 Business-to-Business marketing

This section covers the B2B environment and describes the nature of B2B marketing, also called “industrial marketing” (Webster, 1978). This marketing focuses “on transactions in businesses and organisations that produce products for consumption and items necessary for production” (Lilien and Grewal, 2012, p. 3). After the 1980s and 1990s, the term “business-to-business marketing” gradually replaced “industrial marketing” and includes mutually beneficial relationships between organisations.

The terms “business-to-business marketing” and “business marketing” are interchangeable (Brennan, Canning and Mcdowell, 2014). Some authors, for example, Wilson (1999) argue that the term “organisational marketing” is superior to “business marketing” because it encompasses all organisations, as opposed to “business marketing”, which appears to exclude organisations that are not “businesses”. According to Biemans (2010, p. 5) “B2B marketing is the marketing of products or services to companies, government bodies, institutions and other organisations that use them to produce their own products or services or sell them to other B2B customers”. In a B2B market the customer is an organisation rather than a consumer (Brennan, Canning and Mcdowell, 2014), ranging from small family-owned local businesses to large multinational corporations with multiple business units and massive purchasing budgets (Biemans, 2010). According to Hutt and Speh (2014, p. 3) “the business markets are markets for local to international products and services purchased by

businesses, government bodies, and institutions for incorporation, consumption, use and sale”.

The B2B purchasing decisions are far more complicated than those made in the B2C context. A failed product launch or an inferior product purchase decision can lead to financial problems and harm their reputation. According to Leake, Vaccarello and Ginty (2012), B2B marketing is fundamentally about increasing B2B confidence and decreasing fear, and therefore trust is a critical marketing and communication goal.

According to Biemans (2010), B2B marketing has several characteristics:

1. Customers in the B2B context are organisations (companies, government agencies, institutions, and other organisations).
2. B2B customers purchase products to use in their businesses, whether to manufacture their goods and services, support their business processes or sell to other B2B customers.
3. Demand for downstream products influences the demand for B2B products. The actual marketing application of derived demand is for B2B suppliers to closely monitor the improvements in their downstream markets.
4. Joint demand for B2B products is frequently dependent on the demand for other related B2B products. Joint demand can also result from B2B customers’ desire to purchase products and services from a single supplier, which lowers purchasing costs and strengthen the relationship with the supplier.
5. Customers are few and geographically concentrated.
6. Purchasing behaviour is complicated. The critical feature of organisational buying behaviour is that multiple individuals from various backgrounds, perspectives and buying motives may be involved in the purchasing decision. This group represents a buying centre or decision-making unit (DMU).

7. Marketing characteristics influence market strategy. Suppliers develop close personal relationships with crucial DMU members when there are only a few B2B customers, each of whom represents a significant transaction volume. Personal selling provides superior value to customers, and suppliers emphasise their customer share rather than market share.

Table 2.4 documents the primary marketing differences between B2B and B2C companies suggested by Lilien and Grewal (2012).

Table 2.4: Some key differences between B2B and B2C marketing, adapted from Lilien and Grewal (2012, p. 4)

Business-to-Consumer	Business-to-Business
Marketing culture	Manufacturing/ Tech culture
Market to end of chain	Market to value chain
Perceptual proposition	Technical proposition
Value in brand relationship	Value in use, quantifiable
Large customer segments	Small number of customers
Smaller unit transactions	Large-unit transactions
Transaction linkage	Process linkage
More direct purchase	Complex buying sequence
Consumer decides	Web of decision participants

Table 2.5, documents the comprehensive synthesis of B2B marketing dimensions and characteristics by Brennan, Canning and Mcdowell (2014). They identify the measurements that distinguish business markets from other markets, such as the consumer market, and features of the business and consumer market dimensions. The table below contains three (3) columns. The first (left) column specifies the business and consumer markets differing dimension, the second (middle) represents the predicted traits of a corporate market, and the third (right) shows the consumer market's expected characteristic. Table 2.5 also contains three (3) sections: market structure differences, buying behaviour differences and marketing practices differences.

Table 2.5: Differences between business and consumer markets (Brennan, Canning and Mcdowell, 2014)

Market structure differences		
Dimension	Business marketing	Consumer marketing
Nature of demand	Derived	Direct
Demand volatility	Greater volatility	Less volatility
Demand elasticity	Less elastic	More elastic
Reverse elasticity	More common	Less common
Nature of customers	Greater heterogeneity	Greater homogeneity
Market fragmentation	Greater fragmentation	Less fragmentation
Market complexity	More complex	Less complex
Market size	Larger overall value	Smaller overall value
Number of buyers per seller	Few	Many
Number of buyers per segment	Few	Many
Relative size of buyer/seller	Often similar	Seller much larger
Geographic concentration	Often clustered	Usually dispersed
Buying behaviour differences		
Dimension	Business marketing	Consumer marketing
Buying influences	Many	Few
Purchase cycles	Often long	Usually short
Transaction value	Often high	Usually small
Buying process complexity	Often complex	Usually simple
Buyer/seller interdependence	Often high	Usually low
Purchase professionalism	Often high	Usually low
Importance of relationships	Often important	Usually unimportant
Degree of interactivity	Often high	Usually low
Formal, written rules	Common	Uncommon
Marketing practice differences		
Dimension	Business marketing	Consumer marketing
Selling process	Systems selling	Product selling
Personal selling	Used extensively	Limited
Use of relationships	Used extensively	Limited
Promotional strategies	Limited, customer-specific	Mass market
Web integration	Greater	Limited
Branding	Limited	Extensive, sophisticated
Market research	Limited	Extensive
Segmentation	Unsophisticated	Sophisticated
Competitor awareness	Lower	Higher

According to Brennan, Canning and Mcdowell (2014) interpersonal networking is a critical component of corporate marketing, and SM use in interpersonal networking is a significant contemporary development.

2.4 B2B buying process

According to Robinson, Farris and Wind (1967), there are eight (8) stages or “buy phases” in the industrial buying process. Srinivasan (2012, p. 720-721) described the B2B buying stages involved in a new task buying situation (Table 2.6), although not all strategies are mandatory when pursuing a straightforward process. The below activities outline the process.

1. A buyer firm or company executive identifies a problem or a need warranting a good or service purchase and evaluates whether the need is available internally.
2. A buyer firm or company executive identifies a problem or a need warranting a good or service purchase and defines the necessary characteristics and quantity of the goods or services.
3. The company consults with managers, technical personnel, and end-users and develops the product specifications through cross-departmental collaboration.
4. The company uses product or service specifications to identify and evaluate potential suppliers using Internet search engines, trade directories, trade advertisements and contacts with other firms and trade shows.
5. The company invites the identified suppliers to submit their proposals, and this process varies by product or service.
6. The company identifies their preferred supplier traits, orders traits by importance, ranks suppliers, and hires the highest-ranked supplier.

7. The company arranges the final order by specifying the quantity, technical specifications, return policies, delivery schedule, and other relevant information for purchasing.
8. After order completion and product delivery, the company regularly reviews its supplier's performance and determines whether the buyer maintains, revises, or ends a supplier relationship.

Table 2.6: B2B buying process (Srinivasan, 2012, p. 721), cited in (Lilien and Grewal, 2012)

Buying Phases	Buying Phase Description
1. Problem Recognition	Starts the buying process by recognizing a problem and justifying its need.
2. General need description	The buyer identifies the necessary general characteristics and quantity.
3. Product Specification	The buyer outlines specifications, which may involve multiple managers in the buyer's firm including technical, production, marketing, and sales managers.
4. Supplier Search	The buyer searches for supplies typically through trade directories and B2B electronic exchanges.
5. Proposal solicitation	The buyer requests qualified suppliers submit quotations and asks desired supplies provide a formal presentation.
6. Supplier selection	The buyer specifies desired supplier attributes, rates their importance and suppliers, and selects a supplier.
7. Order-routine specification	After determining the supplier, the buyer finalises and submits their order.
8. Performance review	Periodically, the buyer evaluates the supplier's performance based on preset supplier requirements.

Furthermore, Robinson, Farris and Wind (1967) identified three (3) buying situations: *straight rebuy*, *modified rebuy* and *new task*. The *straight rebuy* is a recurring purchase in which the buyer company establishes a reordering schedule for purchasing the same product or service from their existing suppliers. This buying situation requires minimal

preparation, and the decision is simple. A *modified rebuy* refers to a change or modification to the order during a repurchase, as it requires the buyer company to follow the supplier's protocols governing order changes. This type of purchase is more complicated than a simple repurchase but does not necessitate as much effort as a new task. Finally, a *new task* references the first time the buyer company buys the product after selecting a new supplier. Therefore, the buyer must gather and review product information, adding complexity to the decision-making process (Wright, 2004).

2.5 Business-to-Consumer (B2C) marketing and differences with B2B

The customer type distinguishes between B2B and B2C marketing; B2C customers are individuals, whereas B2B customers are organisations (Brennan, Canning and Mcdowell, 2014). In B2B marketing, companies market their products or services to other businesses, whereas B2C businesses market to consumers (Kumar and Raheja, 2012).

The B2C sellers experience frequent constraints in the market size due to geography and the city, county, or country population, whereas B2B sellers have complex orders, manage higher volumes of sales and products, and sales cycles are longer (Rėklaitis and Pilelienė, 2019). B2C companies sell their goods and services to end-users; they purchase products at wholesale prices and resell them at an inflated price to consumers buying for personal use rather than for reselling (Saha, Islam and Rodela, 2014). According to Gummesson (2008, p. 174) the most significant difference between B2C and B2B companies relates to the degree of separation of buyers and sellers, as B2C companies experience a “greater degree of independence between [their] buyers and sellers”. Further, Kumar and Reinartz (2012) assert that the B2B market is narrower, which substantially increases item and transaction totals.

2.6 Overview of ICT adoption models and theories

This section presents an overview of existing ICT adoption theories and models. It is necessary to refer to existing technology adoption theories to realise the process of SMM adoption.

According to Rogers (2003, p.12), “an innovation is an idea, practice, or object that is perceived as new by an individual or other unit of adaption”. According to Sträub (2009, p. 626), “adoption theory examines the individual and the choices an individual makes to accept or reject a particular innovation’ and ‘diffusion theory’ describes how an innovation spreads through a population”. Various definitions of technology adoption were present in prior literature, such as the “decision to accept and implement the innovation” (Bruque and Moyano, 2007).

Researchers employed various theoretical approaches when investigating the adoption of new technologies (Chong *et al.*, 2009; Oliveira and Martins, 2011). The Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) Theory by Rogers (1983) and the Technology, Organisation and Environment (TOE) framework (DePietro, Wiarda and Fleischer, 1990) are the most widely used models to understand technology adoption, particularly among businesses (Oliveira and Martins, 2011). Other theoretical models described in the technology adoption literature are on individual level and use behavioural theories to focus on the individual analysis level. Ajzen (1985) proposed the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), which claimed that attitudes and norms influence behavioural intention. Davis (1989) used the TRA Theory in the individual level of technology adoption theory. The result was the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), one of the most popular, well-known behavioural models for technology adoption. Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) are the two fundamental concepts influencing an individual’s decision to adopt a technology. Other theories are the Theory of Planned

Behaviour (Ajzen, 1985), the Theory of Reasoned Action (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) conceptualized by (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003). The following sections present the two (2) most widely used theories and models for new technologies adoptions and innovations and present the justification for why this study adopted the TOE framework and the DOI theory for the proposed conceptual framework (more details in Chapter 3).

2.6.1 Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory

Rogers (2003) proposed the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory, which states that internal and external characteristics of the organisation are essential determinants to organisational innovativeness (Figure 2.5). The firm innovativeness relates to individual (leader), internal and external organisational factors:

- *individual factors*, such as leaders' perceptions of change,
- *internal factors* of organisational structure include company size and culture, industry type, change and financial flexibility, and
- *external factors*, such as the system's openness, how the environment influences their openness, and the access and availability of external support and competitive pressure.

Figure 2.2: Diffusion of innovations (DOI) Theory, Rogers (1995)

Rogers (1995) identified five (5) characteristics that describe the diffusion of innovation within the organisations: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and observability. Researchers have used the DOI in various domains, including economics, history, technology and education (Namankani, Moxham and Tickle, 2016), and it remains a popular theory for studying the diffusion of innovation across industries (Kendall *et al.*, 2001). Even though over four thousand (4,000) articles on Diffusion of Innovations disciplines exist few offer widely accepted refinements to the theory (Greenhalgh *et al.*, 2004). According to Mallat *et al.* (2006), cited in Kapoor, Dwivedi and Williams (2014), the DOI is a frequently used theory in the Information Systems (IS) adoption studies. For example, Brancheau and Wetherbe (1990) provided evidence that the DOI theory may predict the adoption of spreadsheet software in the context of end-user computing. Furthermore, Ainin *et al.* (2015) based their study on the DOI theory to investigate the factors influencing SM use by SMEs in Malaysia.

The DOI critics contend the theory focuses on the innovation's technological characteristics ignoring other potentially significant internal and external factors (Al Rahbi, 2017). Additionally, according to Tehrani and Shirazi (2014) the DOI excludes organisational and environmental factors. Several researchers, including Parker and Castleman (2009), suggested adding a social context to the theory and integrating it with other theories. Hossain and Quaddus (2011), cited in Awa and Ojiabo (2016), asserted that the TOE framework is an adoption framework that attempts moving toward the socio-economic features and therefore can provide “a more holistic picture about adoption factors, user adoption processes, and implementation” (Awa and Ojiabo, 2016; 903). Therefore, the researcher determined that the TOE best suited this study.

2.6.2 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

In his dissertation, Davis (1986) created the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) after applying the Theory of Reasonable Action to understand user adoption of information systems and technologies (Lai, 2017). Figure 2.6 shows the original TAM Davis proposed.

Figure 2.3: Original Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1986)

Davis (1989) developed the TAM model based on the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975) to understand better how users adopt and use new technology by assessing factors influencing its adoption (Davis,1989).

According to the model, two factors largely determine technology acceptance: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEU). Davis (1989) defined PU as “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance”. The PU has to do with productivity, performance, and effectiveness and it stems from the advantages of improving job efficiency and learning performance (Davis, 1989). The term PEU refers to “the degree to which using the technology will be free of effort” (Davis, 1989). Other studies have added dimensions such as perceived playfulness (Moon and Kim, 2001), perceived enjoyment (Koufaris, 2002), perceived credibility (Wang *et al.*, 2003) and perceived trust (Ahamat, Shahkat Ali and Hamid, 2017) to the original TAM. TAM is a widely acknowledged model in multiple technology fields and is used to predict and explain individuals’ behaviour regarding a given technology; and has provided a foundation for analysing organisational technology adoption (Dahnil *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 2.4: First modified version of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989)

The final TAM was developed by Venkatesh and Davis (1996), seen in Figure 2.5. In their study, the researchers found that perceived usefulness and ease of use directly influence behavioural intention, negating the need for the attitude construct from the previous model.

Figure 2.5: The final version of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Venkatesh and Davis, 1996)

Despite criticism from several researchers, TAM and its constructs of “perceived usefulness” and “perceived ease of use” remain popular among present-date researchers (Williams *et al.*, 2009). The continued use of TAM suggests that IS adoption and diffusion research is rapidly becoming more homogeneous and saturated (Chuttur, 2009), which may hinder research on technology adoption. Additionally, TOE has superior predictive and explanatory potential compared to the predictive capacity of TAM, which led to the use of TOE as a theoretical lens to analyse B2B SM adoption. Chapter 3 presents the rationale for TOE.

2.7 Results of the systematic literature review

This section presents a systematic review and synthesis of studies relate to SM in the B2B context and the essential aspects of these studies. Section 5.5.1 presents the five (5) steps followed to conduct the systematic literature review, which is expounded upon in the methodology chapter (Chapter 5).

2.7.1 Descriptive analysis

This section presents the quantitative results of the SLR. As shown in Figure 2.6, most of the 42 identified articles in the SLR were from the Industrial Marketing Management Journal and the Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing, as seventeen (17) were from the former and eleven (11) from the latter.

Figure 2.6: Journal publishing B2B social media research

The annual studies published about SM in the B2B context (Figure 2.7) reflect a growing interest in the field, as there were six (6) articles published in 2015, ten (10) in 2017, and eight (8) in 2016. Therefore, the highest concentration of citations was found between the years 2015 and 2017.

Figure 2.7: Publications per year

According to the SLR findings (Figure 2.8), 49% of the 42 studies were quantitative, 28% were qualitative, 14% were literature reviews, 7% were mixed-method studies, and one (1) study representing 2% used content analysis.

Figure 2.8: Type of studies

The findings from the SLR are in Table 2.7 below:

Table 2.7: Social media in the B2B context- a systematic literature review (source: by the researcher)

No	Author(s)	Year	Main topics	Theoretical perspective	Type of study	Method	Main findings
1.	Steyn <i>et al.</i>	2010	Factors influencing SM Release (SMR) use by B2B Bloggers; Public Relations tools; Technology Acceptance Theory	TAM	Quantitative	Email survey with B2B bloggers (N=332); covariance-based structural equation modelling (SEM) technique	According to the study, SMR is a new PR technique, which explains why only half of the respondents use it. Bloggers' perceptions of SMR effectiveness and usefulness, on the other hand, influence their willingness to use the new PR tools. According to the researchers, public relations professionals should educate bloggers about the effectiveness of SRMs and other organisations that are already using them and how they work.
2.	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides	2011	Social Networking Sites (SNS); B2B branding		Quantitative	Questionnaire with marketing directors (N=102)	The study investigated SNS as a marketing tool, perceived barriers, and SNS effectiveness measurement. According to the findings, B2B SMEs use SM to achieve brand goals such as attracting new customers. The primary barrier to SNS adoption is a lack of perceived relevance for specific industries. Furthermore, the study addressed B2B SMEs' insufficient use of metrics to assess the effectiveness of SNSs
3.	Järvinen <i>et al.</i>	2012	Usage, measurement, practices, and barriers of B2B digital and SMM	-	Quantitative	Online survey with general manager or marketing director; communication tool of B2B firms (N=145); 5 point Likert scale	According to this study's findings, businesses continue one-way communications through newsletters and email marketing with digital tools. The advances in digital measurement tools remain unexplored; companies lack human resources, expertise and knowledge of how to capitalize on the opportunities of the digital environment. Furthermore, the study suggests that large-sized B2B firms' value SM tools more than SMEs.

4.	Agnihotri <i>et al.</i>	2012	Salespeople's SM use	Task-technology fit theory	Research paper	-	The researchers used the Task-technology theory, literature on relationship marketing and sales service behaviour to build a theoretical framework for explaining how SM platforms facilitate salespeople providing valuable service.
5.	Brennan and Croft	2012	SM use in B2B marketing and branding		Content analysis	Content analysis (n=20 professional articles and n=10 B2B companies-SM material)	The researchers used content analysis from twenty (20) B2B professional articles and SM material from ten (10) large B2B companies. They concluded that large organisations heavily utilise most SM channels; however, adopting these tools is not universal. Firms based in the United States were among the first to use SMM. B2B SM pioneers use SM to become "thought leaders", forge partnerships with stakeholders, and assume a leadership position within their industry.
6.	Swani, Milne and Brown	2013	Online WOM in SM; SM messages; One-click social plug-in	Social network theory; Hansen's psychological choice model	Quantitative	HLM Poisson model; content analysis; Corporate Wall posts from (N=1.143)	The study used content analysis and hierarchical linear modelling to explore the message strategies that B2B companies can employ to boost eWOM activity. They concluded compelling B2B Facebook posts feature corporate brand names to avoid hard selling and emphasise emotional sentiment.
7.	Swani, Brown and Milne	2014	Customer experience in B2B context	Communication and WOM theories; Organisation buying literature	Quantitative	Longitudinal content analysis; Regression models; sample of tweets (N=7000)	The researchers examined how SM marketers use Twitter across contexts and factors influencing SM strategies through communication and WOM theories. The researchers found that B2B marketers, unlike B2C, are reluctant to utilise SM as a marketing tool due to insufficient understanding of implementing SM strategies successfully. Further, B2B marketers use tweets to communicate emotional rather than functional messages, as researchers found no instances of "hard sell" messages by B2B or B2C marketers.
8.	Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen	2014	Challenges and opportunities in B2B SMM;	-	Quantitative	Online survey to managers of SMEs and business development,	The researchers found B2B Finnish technology companies use SM for branding, marketing, recruitment, communications, sales and customer research and development. However, perceptions of SM potential extent beyond its current uses. The researchers also discovered that the size and income of the companies do not affect their external use of SM. Common

			Differences between B2B and B2C			product development and communication managers in large companies (N= 125)	barriers include ranking SM low in priority, insufficient resources and time, and an inability to measure or understand the benefits of its use for their businesses.
9.	Bruhn, Schnebelen and Schäfer	2014	B2B brand communities	Social Exchange Theory	Quantitative	Online survey (N=330); Structural equation modelling (SEM)	The researchers analysed B2B brand communities and developed a conceptual model of interaction quality in C2C. Researchers concluded that brand trust positively affects brand community trust. Higher trust improves the quality of communications and interactions between customers in B2B brand communities. Further, interactions positively affect the experiential, functional and symbolic community benefits, thus increasing brand loyalty.
10	Huotari <i>et al.</i>	2015	Content creation in SM by B2B companies	-	Qualitative	Semi-structured interviews with experts (N=4)	The research investigated how B2B marketers can impact SM content development. The researchers found that a company can influence content creation directly by controlling employee SM behaviour and corporate user accounts or indirectly by training staff to create positive preferred content, that influence users.
11	Siamagka <i>et al.</i>	2015	Determinants of SM adoption in B2B context	TAM; Theory of Reasoned Action	Mixed (quantitative and qualitative)	Structural equation modeling (SEM); mailed questionnaire to senior marketing executives (N=105); interviews with 9 B2B senior	The study focuses on factors that influence B2B's adoption of SMM. From the findings, the primary motivations for B2B SM adoption are organisational innovativeness and perceived usefulness. The researchers concluded perceived ease of use is a minor adoption driver. Furthermore, perceived barriers negatively impact perceived usefulness, while image enhancement had a positive impact. Finally, perceived pressures from stakeholders may influence the adoption.

						Managers; 7-point Likert scales	
12	Keinänen and Kuivalainen	2015	Antecedents of B2B SM use	Theory of planned behavior; TAM; Task-Technology Fit Model	Quantitative	Online questionnaire to customers (N= 82); Partial least squares (PLS) path Modelling	The authors investigate the B2B customer behaviour regarding B2B SM use and the antecedents of this behaviour in the context of industrial marketing. They investigated the effect of colleagues' support, corporate culture, and psychological and personal factors on customer behaviour regarding the business use of SM. According to the study, there is an association between private social use and SM business use. Furthermore, they found that the determinants of SM usage in B2B organisations are personal characteristics and work colleagues. Finally, perceived usability does not affect B2B firm's use of SM.
13	Karjaluoto, Mustonen and Ulkuniemi	2015	Digital channels in industrial marketing communications; DMC	-	Qualitative	Empirical multiple case study (N= 6 industrial firms)	The study yielded the following three (3) research findings. While businesses do not always realise the full potential of digital marketing communications, it is an essential industrial marketing communication tool. Secondly, businesses use digital marketing communication for three (3) reasons: promoting customer relationship communications, raising awareness, and increasing sales. Lastly, companies that rely on traditional digital tools rather than SM tools for digital marketing communications do not realise or know the benefits of SM use.
14	Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin	2015	SM usage and organisational performance	NO	Qualitative	Interviews (N= 6 senior managers)	The study investigated the purposes of SM use and the perspectives of SM managers its impact on organisational performance. The researchers found that organisations use SM for various purposes, such as promotion and advertising, information search, branding, and building customer relations. Furthermore, the study found that SM can benefit businesses through offer cost savings in customer service and marketing, improved customer relationships, accessibility and information sharing and, competitive advantage and revenue generation.
15	Lipiäinen and Karjaluoto	2015	Industrial branding; digital media	Digital branding	Qualitative	Singe case study: component supplier of generators and	The study used a single company as a case study to develop a model and to investigate how a B2B company can use SM for branding. According to the study findings, branding in the digital age necessitates strong internal and external communications and positioning the

						full-power converter packages; semi- structured interviews N=5; content analysis	brand at the forefront of conversations by becoming an opinion leader and regularly delivering content via various SM channels.
16	Lacka and Chong	2016	SM sites adoption; Technology Acceptance Model	TAM; Nielsen's Model of Attributes of System Acceptability	Quantitative	Online survey with B2B marketing professionals (N= 181); 7-point Likert scale questions	The researchers found that how marketers of B2B SM sites influence SM adoption and use. Furthermore, the paper argued that users' perception of the usefulness of SM sites influence their intention to use those sites. Finally, the study suggested that perceived utility and perceived usability impact perceived usefulness.
17	Guesalaga	2016	B2B SM in sales	Interactional Psychology Theory; Task-Technology fit theory	Quantitative	Multiple regression analysis; mailed survey (N= 220 sales executives)	The researchers examined individual, organisational and customer-related factors of SM usage for sales. The findings show that organisational commitment and competence, and individual commitment to SM, are the most relevant antecedents of SM use in sales.
18	Wang, Pauleen and Zhang	2016	SM app (SMA); B2B communication and business performance	Media Synchronicity Theory (MST)	Qualitative	Face-to-face interviews (N= 5 SMEs senior managers/owners)	The study investigates the connection between SMA capabilities, B2B communication and business performance. The findings reveal a missing SMA capability, information security and control. The researchers added the missing capability to their proposed model, implying it could significantly add to MST.
19	Agnihotri <i>et al.</i>	2016	SM and customer satisfaction in B2B sales	Information communication in buyer-seller processes	Quantitative	Online survey (N= 111 B2B sales professionals); 5 point Linkert format; Structural	The researchers used SM to examine the relationship between salesperson information communication behaviours and customer satisfaction, finding SM use by salespeople influences their communication behaviour, increases their reactivity, and improves

						Equation Modelling (SEM)	customer satisfaction. SM is a catalyst for providing customers information and is a precursor to improving salespeople behaviour and customer satisfaction.
20	Rooderkerk and Pauwels	2016	SM and B2B Online Discussion forums	Grice's Theory of Conversation	Quantitative	Posts and comments collection from a LinkedIn healthcare discussion group (N= 316 posts); Negative-Binomial analysis; Count data models	The study examined the characteristics and features that influence comments on an online discussion forum post. The researchers conducted this study assuming the content, author, and timing influence the comments in the posts. The findings revealed that the post's readability, degree of the content's controversy, and the author's status generally influence the number of comments.
21	Cawsey and Rowley	2016	SM brand building strategies and B2B firms		Qualitative	Semi-structured interviews (N= 14 SM practitioners in B2B firms)	The study investigates the B2B's companies use of SM for marketing and branding. Summarised in the B2B Social Media Engagement Taxonomy, the findings show that the level of engagement with SMM varied. The most common SM goals are to facilitate customer engagement, increase brand awareness extension and improve brand image. Finally, the researchers proposed a six-component B2B SM strategy framework: empowerment and engagement of employees, monitoring and listening, compelling content creation, eWOM stimulation, evaluation and selection of channels, and brand visibility through integration into SM.
22	Leek, Canning and Houghton	2016	Web 2.0; Twitter use and SM interaction	Task Media Fit Model; Media Richness Theory	Quantitative	Quantitative content analysis; Non-participant observation; Twitter accounts (N=4); Tweet content and functions (N=	To create a Twitter-specific version of the Task Media Fit Model, researchers analysed corporate marketers' usage of Twitter and followers' responses to tweeted messages. According to the findings, businesses utilise Twitter for the following broad purposes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information exchange • Solving problems • Public relations

						838); Tweet Archivist Desktop	B2B marketers embed media within their tweets, using various embedded links to respond to posts.
23	Quinton and Wilson	2016	SM networking in building networks and relationships; LinkedIn		Qualitative (two-stage)	Netnography (N= 554 LinkedIn group interactions; Interviews (N= 12 industry professionals	The researchers created a four-stage model to explain how SM networks enhance business performance improvement. The stages emphasise: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. SM network behaviours that reflect trust, sharing, reciprocity and altruism 2. recognising emerging and strategic network development possibilities 3. creating valuable relationships through relational, transactional, and other value-based relationship-building approaches, and 4. improving business performance through a joint resolution of problems and forming new business contracts.
24	Bernard	2016	B2B Chief Marketing Officers and SM	-	Conceptual paper	Theory building	The researchers concluded that Chief Marketing Officers unwilling to adopt SM because they lack an implementation strategy. However, they believe that SM has multiple purposes, such as generating sales leads, providing after-sales support, engaging with leading influencers, elevating key individuals' industry status, and growing its reputation.
25	Mehmet and Clarke	2016	B2B SMM conversations	Social Semiotic Multimodal (SSMM) framework	Qualitative	Single case study: Australian Fairtrade Fortnight 2012 campaign	The study used Fairtrade Australia as a case study to map and analyse SM conversations (Facebook and Twitter) between the company and its B2B stakeholders. This study aimed to provide a more in-depth understanding of how B2B SMM posts can generate virtual conversation. Furthermore, the researchers acknowledge how messages from stakeholders can confuse or distract from the intended business message.
26	Brink	2017	Antecedents to the application of SM in B2B SMEs	Action research	Qualitative	Case study; in-depth interviews with SMEs managers (N= 4 plastic-producing SMEs); follow-up interviews	The study identified two (2) significant antecedents to SM use in B2B SMEs including innovation in open, collaborative business models and critical yet distributed leadership. The findings emphasise the importance of incorporating critical antecedents before implementing SM applications to improve business in B2B SMEs.

27	Itani, Agnihotri and Dingus	2017	SM use in B2B sales		Quantitative	Survey N=120 salesperson-supervisor dyads	The researchers examined how SM is part of a B2B salespersons job, using the theory of reasoned actions to build a model for testing factors that influence their SM use. The researchers concluded that perceptions of SM usefulness and learning orientation influence SM use in the workplace.
28	Swani <i>et al.</i>	2017	Popularity of SM communications	Traditional Communication model; Word-of-Mouth (WOM) psychological motivation theory	Quantitative	Logistic regression with the use of Bayesian analysis; Bivariate Poisson Bayesian regression model; B2B messages, N=326; B2C messages, N=1141	According to the study, B2B viewers rarely comment on messages while B2C viewers frequently respond to messages. Further, corporate branding increases the popularity of B2B messages compared to B2C messages. Additionally, B2B marketers benefit from using functional and emotional appeals to viewers searching for new offers or building customer relationships. The researchers also concluded that B2B viewers use SM as a source of knowledge about brands and offerings.
29	Salo	2017	Review of the literature in the SMM use by industrial companies	Conceptual paper	Literature Review	N= 40 articles	This study was a literature review on the use of SMM in the industrial context. The researcher organised forty (40) articles into eight (8) categories including: buyer-seller relationships and business networks domain; advertising; computers in business marketing; public relations and marketing and other functions; decision support and management science; sales; marketing communications. The researcher concluded that current SM research examines tactical rather than strategic SM use. Marketing communications, sales, advertising, and computers in business marketing are research areas with steady theory development increases, whereas others, such as pricing and ethics are limited. Finally, advertising and marketing communications research is customer-oriented, whereas business marketing is more organisation-oriented in sales and computers.
30	Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant	2017	SM adoption in B2B	Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)	Mixed (quantitative)	Survey with B2B companies (N=92);	The study compared research findings from IT and industrial companies in the United States, UK, and the Netherlands to SM adoption among B2B companies in Belgium. The researchers concluded that IT B2B companies are more apt to adopt SM due to their technical knowledge and background than industrial B2B companies. Further, IT B2B

					and qualitative)	in-depth interviews with B2B enterprises (N=11)	company stakeholders frequently use SM, unlike industrial B2B company stakeholders who fear negative SM comments and maintain low perceptions of SM usefulness.
31	Shaltoni	2017	Internet marketing adoption in B2B markets	TOE	Mixed (qualitative and quantitative)	Unstructured interviews (N=3, members of Amman chamber of Industry); online questionnaire (N=480 SMEs marketing managers or owners)	The researchers investigated factors associated with internet marketing adoption of B2B firms, concluding they use interview marketing for one-way communication. Further, B2B markets are passionate about SM, particularly favouring Facebook. Upon analysis, the researchers concluded that factors impacting internet marketing adoption include perceived relative advantage, company innovativeness, SM compatibility, and competitor and customer pressure for SM marketing.
32	Andersson and Wikström	2017	SM use in B2B; stakeholders	-	Qualitative	Case study, semi-structured interviews (N= 3 companies); web site observation	The researchers' findings confirm that B2B firms use various SM platforms to communicate with stakeholders, boost sales, and create brand awareness. Further, the researchers found B2B companies use SM for identifying and improving products and services and to communicate with diverse stakeholders.
33	Wang <i>et al.</i>	2017	SM capability in B2B marketing		Literature review	Literature review	The researchers investigated the feasibility of SM in B2B marketing and how these companies use and enhance SM. The researchers conducted a thematic literature review of B2B marketing and Information Systems and concluded that a firm's technological capability greatly influences an organisation's use of SM. The researchers proposed a four-level "Social Media Capability Maturity Model" to transfer technological capabilities to dynamic organisational capabilities.

34	Buratti, Parola and Satta	2018	SM use in “conservative” B2B industries	-	Literature review and quantitative	Descriptive statistics on their SM activities on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn (N=60 firms- tanker shipping companies and ocean carries)	The researchers conducted a literature review of SMM in B2B services and identified potential benefits of SM tools for B2B service firms in conservative industries. The researchers organised the results of their literature review by scanning and categorising the potential benefits of SM tools for B2B service companies in conservative industries. The study involved analysing empirical research of sixty (60) B2B conservative firms, analysing their current use of SMM tools such as Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter. The researchers concluded SM is a low-cost, readily available option to create a competitive advantage, even within conservative industries.
35	Lashgari <i>et al.</i>	2018	Adoption strategies of SM in B2B firms		Qualitative	Multi case studies (N=4 multinational corporations)	This study explored factors influencing B2B firms to adopt and use SM using a multi-case study approach. The researchers interviewed top executives from four (4) international companies and examined their use of SM platforms and websites. The study proposed a model that depicts the various adoption, selection and integration processes for developing a B2B’s company’s SM communication strategy.
36	Iankova <i>et al.</i>	2018	Comparison of B2B, B2C and mixed business models for SMM	Sashi’s customer engagement cycle	Quantitative	Survey with two panels; university panel (N=137); Qualtrics Panels (N=377); total sample N=449	Using Sashi’s customer engagement cycle, the researchers compared SMM organisational practices in B2B, B2C, mixed B2B/B2C and B2B2C contexts. The findings revealed significant differences in the importance of SM and the perceived efficiency of SM marketing across different business contexts. Overall, the researchers concluded that B2B organisations do not believe SM is effective and consider SM unnecessary for building relationships within their industry compared to SM use in other business contexts.
37	Mudambi, Sinha and Shae Taylor	2019	B2B CEOs use of SM	-	-	-	The study presented the significance of B2B’s CEOs presence and use of SM. It stresses the benefits of the CEO’s presence on SM and the platforms they should use, and the post’s content will determine the frequency of posts.
38	Pandey, Nayal and Rathore	2020	Digital marketing for B2B organisations		Literature Review and qualitative	Semi-structured interviews (B2B marketing experts: n=11 and marketing	This study examined existing literature on digital marketing use in the B2B context to identify current research gaps and develop a collaborative conceptual framework. The researchers conducted eleven (11) semi-structured interviews with B2B marketing experts from various industries and three (3) with marketing academicians to clarify emerging digital marketing themes. The study concluded that most B2B companies do not fully

						academicians: n=3)	benefit from the technology use due to insufficient research on the subject. Furthermore, only digital marketing communication and sales management tools exist, while critical success factors, decision support systems, electronic marketing orientation (EMO), and other topics have received less attention.
39	Eid, Abdelmoety and Agag	2020	Antecedents and consequences of B2B SMM	TAM and IDT	Quantitative	Survey (n= 277 B2B SMEs)	The study used a survey completed by two hundred seventy-seven (277) UK B2B SMEs to investigate the antecedences and consequences of SMM use in international B2B SMEs and its impact on their export performance. According to the findings, impactful antecedents affecting B2B SME's export performance are customers' preferences and views, brand awareness, and understanding of their international competition.
40	Lin <i>et al</i>	2020	Adoption of technological innovations in B2B context and ethical leadership perspective	-	Quantitative	System Generalized Method of Moment (SYS-GMM) N=465 IT service companies	The study examined secondary data from four hundred sixty-five (465) employees in IT service companies using GMM, a rarely used method in marketing studies, to understand the adoption of technological innovations, in this case SM, in a B2B context. Researchers concluded that ethical leadership significantly impacts the company's technology adoption and performance
41	Dwivedi <i>et al.</i>	2021	SM adoption, usage and impact in B2B context	-	Literature review	Systematic literature review	The researchers conducted an extensive review of the literature on the use of SM in the B2B context. The review included seventy (70) articles and conference papers organised into six (6) themes: SM adoption; effect of SM; SM use; SM strategies; SM tools and assessing the effectiveness of SM use.
42	Cartwright, Davies and Archer-Brown	2021	Relationships on SM in B2B organisations	Customer Engagement Cycle and Relationship Marketing theory	Qualitative	Multiple case study (N=12), interviews (N=47)	The researchers investigated employee utilisation of SM for establishing contacts with current and potential business partners using Sashi's Customer Engagement Cycle and Relationship Marketing theory, identifying four (4) SM engagement strategies: dissemination, call-to-action, cocreation and thought Leadership. Further, they identified three (3) ways B2B organisations can examine their SM usage: defining engagement strategies, investing in superior content marketing, merging company resources and instituting strategic delivery modalities.

2.7.2 Thematic analysis

After the SLR, the researcher divided SM research in the B2B context into six (6) themes: SM adoption, SM use, SM strategies, SM tools, benefits, and barriers. This section captures the findings associated with the keywords used to conduct the SLR. Its organisation reflects the progression and order of the SLR based on the keywords from Table 2.8.

1. Social media adoption

Several studies focused on SM adoption by investigating the factors influencing B2B companies' adoption decisions (Lacka and Chong, 2016; Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant, 2017; Shaltoni, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2017; Buratti, Parola and Satta, 2018; Lin *et al.*, 2020). Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011) were among the first to analyse SMM in a B2B context. Their research examined how the B2B companies in the UK use SM, what obstacles they face, and how they measure its efficacy. According to their findings, the B2B companies using SM primarily for attracting new customers. However, the lack of staff's familiarity with these tools and technical skills prevents B2B companies from adopting Social Networking Service (SNS). Additionally, most of businesses considered SM irrelevant with their business.

Table 2.8 summarises the main factors influencing a B2B company to adopt SM presented in the SLR:

Table 2.8: Determinants-factors of SM adoption (source: by the researcher)

DETERMINANTS-FACTORS	REFERENCE
Brand awareness	Järvinen <i>et al.</i> (2012); Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant (2017)
Enhancing brand image	Siamagka <i>et al.</i> (2015); Järvinen <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Perceived usefulness	Siamagka <i>et al.</i> (2015); Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant (2017); Lacka and Chong (2016)
Perceived ease of use	Siamagka <i>et al.</i> (2015); Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant (2017); Lacka and Chong (2016)
Top management support	Brink (2017)
Relative advantage	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011); Shaltoni (2017)
Firm size	Fosso Wamba and Carter (2014)
Competitive pressure	Shaltoni (2017); Wang <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Customer pressure	Shaltoni (2017)
Company strategy	Gazal <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Compatibility	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2010); Shaltoni (2017)
Innovativeness of the firm	Siamagka <i>et al.</i> (2015); Brink (2017); Shaltoni (2017)
Attract and build relationships with new customers	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011)
Ethical leadership	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2020)

Lacka and Chong (2016), for example, found that the perceived usability, usefulness, and utility of SM platforms are the main factors influencing B2B organisations' adoption decisions. According to Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant (2017), B2B companies used SM to build brand awareness, increase traffic and recruit employees. Additionally, they identified that the main advantages of using SM as a marketing tool are increasing their communication reach, networking, thought leadership, and enhance business credibility at a low cost. Furthermore, the study found that the examined B2B companies believe that SM is easy to use and beneficial.

Shaltoni's (2017) study is among the few articles within the surveyed literature to have adopted the TOE framework to identify factors influencing B2B company adoption of SMM. The study

used survey data collected from four hundred eighty (480) B2B managers or business owners from Jordan. The researcher concluded that half of the participating B2B companies statically use their websites without two-way communication. Additionally, the perceived compatibility, relative advantage, innovativeness of the firm, customer, and competitor pressure positively influences the adoption of SM by the B2B organisations.

Other significant predictors of SM adoption by the B2B organisations are perceived usefulness (Siamagka *et al.*, 2015; Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant, 2017; Lacka and Chong, 2016; Pascucci, Ancillai and Cardinali, 2018), perceived ease of use (Siamagka *et al.*, 2015; Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant, 2017; Lacka and Chong, 2016; Gazal *et al.*, 2016; Pascucci, Ancillai and Cardinali, 2018) and perceived utility (Lacka and Chong, 2016; Pascucci, Ancillai and Cardinali, 2018). Other studies emphasised the role, personal characteristics, and support of the managers, as they can affect the adoption of SM (Brink, 2017; Pascucci, Ancillai and Cardinali, 2018). Fosso Wamba and Carter (2014) found organisational, management and environmental elements influence SM adoption.

Company size is another factor influencing the adoption decision by the B2B companies (Brennan and Croft, 2012; Verheyden and Goeman, 2013). Larger companies typically have the resources and expertise needed to effectively implement the latest technologies (Barnes *et al.*, 2012). In contrast, SMEs with insufficient resources and technical expertise, limited capabilities, few employees, and unstable organisational structures are less likely to adopt SM and new technologies (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010; Stockdale *et al.*, 2012; Zeiller and Schauer, 2011).

2. Social media use

This section reports on studies about SM use and how B2B companies utilise SM. For instance, B2B companies use SM to create brand awareness and enhance the brand image (Järvinen *et al.*,

2012) through advertising and promotion tools (Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2015). SM use also includes information searching, improving customer relations (Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2015), becoming thought leaders, building stakeholder relationships, and drive the market in their sector (Brennan and Croft, 2012). Businesses use SM to discover customer needs, shorten the development time of new products, improve the quality of their products or services, raise customer satisfaction (Kärkkäinen *et al.*, 2010), and enhance customer engagement and sales (Guesalaga, 2016). Therefore, SM use improves communication and business performance (Wang *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, Andersson and Wikström (2017) explained how B2B companies use SM for communication purposes such as building rapport with stakeholders, improving sales, promoting their brand, recruiting prospective buyers and employees, and enhancing product information and services. Other SM uses include sharing information, collaboration for the purpose of problem solving, and bolstering public relations (Leek, Canning and Houghton, 2016); getting sales leads, engaging with successful influencers, providing after-sales service, building the company's reputation (Bernard, 2016), and creating an online community and leveraging relationships with stakeholders (Mehmet and Clarke, 2016).

3. Social media strategies

Some researchers explored SM strategies B2B companies use. Swani *et al.* (2013) used content analysis and HLM to measure message strategies that promote eWOM activity for B2B companies. Cawsey and Rowley (2016) also explored B2B companies' SM strategies and proposed a B2B SM strategy framework. Huotari *et al.* (2015) proposed that B2B marketers can impact SM content creation in two (2) different ways: directly and indirectly. Swani *et al.* (2014) examined Twitter use among B2B and B2C businesses and predicted factors influencing messaging and

communication strategies. Swani *et al.* (2017) examined how B2B and B2C SM message strategies differ concerning information search, selling, appeals to the message and branding.

4. Social media tools

Businesses can benefit from SM tools, given the diversity of tools available. Keinänen and Kuivalainen (2015) found that B2B companies use SM as a tool for initiating, enhancing, and improving customer relationships, developing content and brand building. According to Karjaluoto *et al.* (2015), by using digital marketing communication tools, B2B companies can improve their business communications and relationships, support sales and promote awareness.

5. Benefits

B2B SM adoption is beneficial for companies (Table 2.9), as SM use expands brand awareness (Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011; Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Leino, 2011; Järvinen *et al.*, 2012; Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant, 2017) and elevates their competitive advantage (Agnihotri *et al.*, 2016; Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2015). Further, SM allows businesses to integrate customer services and interact with them (Kietzmann *et al.*, 2011; Michaelidou *et al.*, 2011; Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Leino, 2011) and increase sales (Guesalaga, 2016; Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Leino, 2011; Agnihotri *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, several researchers posit that SM use enhances customer relationships with B2B companies (Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011; Iankova *et al.*, 2018; Cartwright, Davies and Archer-Brown, 2021; Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2015; Andersson and Wikström, 2017; Gáti, 2015), and improves communication with stakeholders (Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant, 2017; Agnihotri *et al.*, 2016).

Table 2.9: Benefits of SM adoption (source: by the researcher)

BENEFITS	REFERENCE
Brand awareness	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, (2011); Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Leino (2011); Järvinen <i>et al.</i> (2012); Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant (2017)
Attract new customers	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011)
Competitive advantage	Agnihotri <i>et al.</i> (2016); Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin (2015)
Integrating customer services, interactivity	Kietzmann <i>et al.</i> (2011); Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011); Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Leino (2011)
Increase reach	Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant (2017)
Promotion and advertising	Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin (2015)
eWOM branding	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011)
Cost effectiveness/ reduction	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011); Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin (2015); Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant (2017); Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Leino (2011)
Carry marketing activities with lower cost	Odoom <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Performance benefits	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011); Wamba and Carter (2014)
Increase sales transactions	Guesalaga (2016); Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Leino (2011); Agnihotri <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Recruiting	Andersson and Wikström (2017)
Enhance relationships	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011); Iankova <i>et al.</i> (2018); Cartwright, Davies and Archer-Brown (2021); Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin (2015); Andersson and Wikström (2017); Gáti (2015)
Creation of valuable content and information for the customers	Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant (2017)
Improves communication	Veldeman, Van Praet and Mechant (2017); Agnihotri <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Thought Leadership	Veldeman <i>et al.</i> (2017)

6. Barriers

By conducting the SLR, the researcher located barriers B2B companies experience when adopting SM (Table 2.10). Many B2B companies are reluctant to adopt SM due to insufficient knowledge and technical skills among their personnel (Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen, 2014;

Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011; Järvinen *et al.*, 2012; Verheyden and Goeman, 2013; Siamagka *et al.*, 2015); inability to measure and evaluate the ROI and benefits of SM (Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen, 2014; Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011; Beier and Wagner, 2016; Kärkkäinen, Jussila and Väisänen, 2010; Gazal *et al.*, 2016); inadequate financial resources (Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen, 2014; Kuikka and Äkkinen, 2011; Verheyden and Goeman, 2013; Gazal *et al.*, 2016); company size (Brennan and Croft, 2012; Verheyden and Goeman, 2013); and lack of time (Jussila, *et al.*, 2014; Michaelidou *et al.*, 2011). Other significant barriers include the perceived irrelevance of SM for certain B2B companies and industries (Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011; Nakara, Benmoussa and Jaouen, 2012; Kärkkäinen *et al.*, 2010; Järvinen *et al.*, 2012; Swani and Brown, 2011); inadequate control over communication hinders SM adoption by B2B marketers (Mangold and Faulds, 2009; Järvinen *et al.*, 2012; Lacka and Chong, 2016; Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010); and insufficient top management support (Siamagka *et al.*, 2015). Finally, security risks and legal issues can negatively impact SM adoption among B2B organisations (Kärkkäinen *et al.*, 2010; Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen, 2014; Karjaluoto *et al.*, 2015; Siamagka *et al.*, 2015).

Table 2.10: Barriers of SM adoption (source: by the researcher)

BARRIERS	REFERENCE
Lack of knowledge, technological skills	Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen (2014); Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011); Järvinen <i>et al.</i> (2012); Verheyden and Goeman (2013); Siamagka <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Lack of ROI measurement	Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen (2014); Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011); Beier and Wagner (2016); Kärkkäinen <i>et al.</i> (2010); Gazal <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Lack of resources	Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen (2014); Kuikka and Äkkinen (2011); Verheyden and Goeman (2013); Gazal <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Company size	Brennan and Croft (2012); Verheyden and Goeman (2013)

Lack of time	Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen (2014); Michaelidou <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Lack of relevance/ compatibility	Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011); Nakara, Benmoussa and Jaouen (2012); Kärkkäinen <i>et al.</i> (2010); Järvinen <i>et al.</i> (2012); Swani and Brown (2011)
Lack of control over communication	Mangold and Faulds (2009); Järvinen <i>et al.</i> (2012); Lacka and Chong (2016); Kaplan and Haenlein (2010)
Lack of top management support	Siamagka <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Security and legal issues	Kärkkäinen, <i>et al.</i> (2010); Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen (2014); Karjaluoto <i>et al.</i> (2015); Siamagka <i>et al.</i> (2015)

2.7.3 Research gaps

Further, the researcher identified a gap in SMM research in the B2B context, as this field of study is a relatively new and emerging research area. Despite the significant effort and attention devoted to SM in the B2B context, there are still numerous and significant gaps (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021), including:

- Several researchers identified that SM adoption research is from the B2C context (Huotari *et al.*, 2015; Lacka and Chong, 2016; Bulearca and Bulearca, 2010), while research in the B2B context is in its “embryonic stage” (Siamagka *et al.*, 2015, p. 89).
- According to Dahnil *et al.*, (2014), the SM trend creates a research opportunity to investigate factors that influence B2B companies’ adoption of SMM activities.
- According to Jussila *et al.* (2014) a gap exists between SM’s perceived usefulness and its genuine use. The researchers suggested further studies explore and examine B2B SM use to holistically elucidate its benefits.
- Research on SM tools used by B2B organisations (Mehmet and Clarke, 2016; Keinänen and Kuivalainen, 2015) recommend future researchers examine the barriers to the adoption decision.

- According to Chatzithomas *et al.* (2014), cultural differences influence SM adoption; however, research in this area is limited. The researchers also argued that collective societies, like Greece avert situations that lack certainty and structure, have an intermediate Power Distance and is a masculine still in its infancy with SM adoption and use.
- Several studies suggested that the slow adoption of SM in the B2B context is due to marketers perceptions of SM's poor usability in B2B marketing communications (Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides 2011; Lacka and Chong, 2016; Swani *et al.*, 2014).
- Dwivedi *et al.*, (2021) concluded that most studies on SM use in the B2B context involved online surveys and online content analysis, which necessitates further research using qualitative and or quantitative methods (Canovi and Pucciarelli, 2019). Canovi and Pucciarelli (2019) proposed using semi-structured interviews, surveys, observations, and or focus groups to better understand B2B SM use.
- Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen (2014) recommended case study research to gather evidence of how SM can aid with Business-to-Business transactions.

2.8 Summary

Chapter 2 documented the researcher's SLR process and presented the significant findings from the forty-two (42) articles extensively analysed. The researcher defined SM and SMM and identified the classifications and goals of SM platforms. Additionally, the researcher described B2B marketing and distinguished B2B from B2C companies and marketing strategies. Chapter 2 also detailed the B2B buying process and offered a critical review of SM research in the B2B context. Based upon the critical SLR process, the researcher identified types of SM use by B2B companies, SM strategies and tools, and benefits and barriers to using SM.

Further, Chapter 2 discussed the ICT adoption models and theories relevant to this study. While Chapter 3 elucidates the conceptual framework and refinement process, Chapter 2 documents the use of the notable models and theories to justify the researcher's selection of TOE and DOI and discarding of TAM. Chapter 3 describes the process for developing the conceptual framework and use of multiple theories and models.

CHAPTER 3- THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Introduction

This chapter informs the development of an initial theoretical framework based on the SLR. This framework will serve as the theoretical basis for developing and testing a conceptual framework that investigates technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural factors that influence B2B SM adoption in Greece. The chapter presents the Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) framework and explains the integration of the TOE, the DOI, and Hofstede's model used in this study.

3.2 The Technology-Organisation- Environment (TOE) framework

DePietro, Wiarda and Fleischer (1990), developed the TOE framework, which identifies three main context groups that influence an organisation's technology adoption (Figure 3.1):

1. The *technological context* represents characteristics and usefulness of relevant innovative technologies.
2. The *organisational context* refers to a company's internal attributes and traits.
3. The *environmental context* refers to the organisation's environment, including factors of the environment such as its size, structure, competitors, policies and laws, technical support and its infrastructures.

Figure 3.1: Technology, Organization and Environment (TOE) framework, adapted from DePietro, Wiarda and Fleischer (1990)

Researchers have used the TOE framework to evaluate how companies employ new technologies (Oliveira and Martins, 2011) and understand SM adoption in the industrial context (Shaltoni, 2017). Oliveira and Martins, (2011) conducted a comprehensive SLR and concluded that the TOE framework and the DOI theory are the most employed theories in technology adoption research. According to Thong (1999), IS (SM) is a technological innovation in this study. Therefore, technological innovation theories should be a point for empirical investigations of IS adoption.

The DOI (Rogers, 1983) is a well-established theory for analysing technology adoption; however, critics contend that it is incapable of evaluating innovation adoption based only on technological factors (Chong and Olesen, 2017). The TOE framework (DePietro, Wiarda and Fleischer, 1990) is a more comprehensive framework that considers all aspects of technology adoption inside an organisation (Abubakar *et al.*, 2017). The TOE framework provides a valuable analytical framework for analysing the adoption and integration of various forms of innovation (Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2018). The TOE's technological and organisational contexts are consistent with the DOI theory, but the TOE framework contains the environmental context (Tajudeen, Jaafar and

Ainin, 2018). The TOE framework is more comprehensive for studying IT adoption at the organisational level (Oliveira and Martins, 2011).

This study used the TOE framework to develop and test a conceptual framework capable of investigating the impact of different technological, organisational, and environmental characteristics of Greek B2B organisations regarding SM adoption. The researcher selected the TOE framework because of its strong theoretical foundation, reliable empirical support and use in understanding the rollout of technological and innovative advancements in organisations (Oliveira and Martins, 2011). Researchers have used the TOE framework to study SM adoption (Abubakar *et al.*, 2017; Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020; Parveen, 2012) and within the B2B context (Shaltoni, 2017). This conceptual framework was central to examining the problem under investigation. It provided a base for generating the interview guide for this study's qualitative phase and provided the inductive themes used during the thematic analysis of the interview findings.

Several authors used the TOE framework to understand different IT adoptions (Table 3.1), such as SM (Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2018; Abubakar *et al.*, 2017; Shaltoni, 2017; Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020; Parveen, 2012); broadband mobile applications (Chiu, Chen and Chen, 2017); e-Commerce (Le *et al.*, 2012; Al-Qirim, 2007); e-Government (Nguyen, 2016); cloud computing (Alshamaila, Papagiannidis and Li, 2012; Low, Chen and Wu, 2011); RFID technology (Wang, 2010); SCRM technologies (Hasani, 2017); and Enterprise Systems (Ramdani, 2009).

Table 3.1: Some studies used TOE Framework (source: by the researcher)

Author(s)	Domain
Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin (2018)	Social media
Abubakar <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Social media
Shaltoni (2017)	Social media and websites
Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou (2020)	Social media
Parveen (2012)	Social media
Chiu <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Broadband mobile applications
Le <i>et al.</i> (2012)	e-Commerce
Nguyen (2016)	e-Government
Alshamaila (2012)	Cloud computing
Wang (2010)	RFID technology
Hasani (2017)	SCRM technologies
Al-Qirim (2007)	e-Commerce
Ramdani (2009)	Enterprise Systems
Low, Chen and Wu (2011)	Cloud Computing

Table 3.2 illustrates the definitions of the TOE framework constructs:

Table 3.2: Definitions of the TOE framework constructs

Technological	Relative Advantage	“The degree to which an innovation is perceived as being better than the idea it supersedes” (Rogers, 1995, p. 213)
	Complexity	“The degree to which an innovation is perceived as relatively difficult to understand and use” (Rogers, 1995, p. 230)
	Compatibility	“The degree to which an innovation is perceived as consistent with the existing values, past experiences, and needs of potential adopters” (Rogers, 1995, p. 223)
Organisational	Size	The size of the company (Oliveira and Martins, 2011)
	Top management support	“Top management’s leadership describes the role of executive leadership in encouraging and facilitating innovation within the organisation’s overall strategy” (Chong and Olesen, 2017, p. 6)
	Employee knowledge	Refers to the employees level of IT knowledge or experience (Le <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
	Innovativeness	“The degree to which an individual or other unit of adoption is relatively earlier in adopting new ideas than other members of a social system” (Rogers, 1995, p. 990)
Environmental	Competitive pressure	The degree of competition a company faces within its industry (Oliveira and Martins, 2011)
	Government support	“Refers to the assistance provided by the authority to encourage the spread of IS innovations in business” (Ifinedo, 2011, p. 739)

3.2.1 Technological context

The technological context includes “the internal and external technologies relevant to the firm” (Oliveira and Martins, 2011, p. 112). The TOE framework aligns with Rogers’ Theory of Innovation (Rogers, 1995). Rogers (1983) identified different technological aspects that influence an organisation’s adoption of specific technologies. This study used Roger’s innovation diffusion theory as a theoretical basis to study the impact of technological factors on the adoption of SM by B2B organisations.

Relative advantage

Relative advantage is “the degree to which an innovation is perceived as being better than the idea it supersedes” (Rogers, 2003; p. 229), and strongly correlates with new technology adoption (Premkumar and Roberts, 1999). “A rational adoption decision in an organisation would involve evaluating the advantages of the new technology” (Premkumar and Roberts, 1999, p. 471).

Complexity

According to Rogers (2003, p. 257) complexity is “the degree to which an innovation is perceived as relatively difficult to understand and use”. Premkumar and Roberts (1999) suggested that the more advanced technology is, the less likely it will be adopted. To encourage adoption, new technology must be simplistic to understand and use (Thong, 1999). Therefore, complexity negatively correlate with adoption of new technologies (Premkumar and Roberts, 1999).

Compatibility

Compatibility “is the degree to which an innovation is perceived as consistent with the existing values, needs, and past experiences of the potential adopter” (Rogers, 1983). A company will be more likely to adopt new technology if it is consistent with current work practices (Thong, 1999).

Technology compatibility positively relates to a company's decision to implement it (Alshamaila, Papagiannidis and Stamati, 2013).

3.2.2 Organisational context

The organisational context is an essential context for studying the innovation adoption by organisations (Ramdani, Kawalek and Lorenzo, 2009). Previous studies in IS adoption have used various organisational factors to study the adoption of new technology. This context includes four (4) factors: company size, top management support, employee knowledge, and innovativeness of the firm. This study incorporated a specific organisational factor, the firm's innovativeness because it is crucial for businesses in SM (Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020) and innovative organisations are considered to be more likely to take risks (Agarwal and Prasad, 1998).

Size

Several studies concluded that the organisation's size impacts technology adoption (Premkumar and Roberts, 1999; Thong, 1999). The size of the organisation is crucial organisational characteristic and, according to Rogers (2003), one of the strongest predictors of innovation adoption. According to Thong (1999), small companies suffer from "resource poverty" and have more barriers to IS adoption, while larger organisations have more opportunities to adopt IS due their larger scale of operations.

Top management support

Several researchers concluded that support from senior managers is a critical factor in innovation adoption in organisations (Thong, 1999; Premkumar and Roberts, 1999; Maduku, Mpinganjira and Duh, 2016). Allocating enough resources and providing a supportive atmosphere to aid the

adoption of new technology requires top management support (Low, Chen and Wu, 2011, cited in Maduku, Mpinganjira and Duh, 2016).

Innovativeness

According to Thong (1999), the organisation's innovativeness is an essential determiner of new technology adoption and reflects the organisation's receptiveness to embrace new technology for accomplishing its goals (Gutierrez, Boukrami and Lumsden, 2015). A firm's innovativeness positively correlates with SM adoption, which is why companies should invest in cultivating an innovative culture within the company (Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020).

Employees' knowledge

Employee's knowledge is another significant determiner found to influence the adoption of new technologies. According to Maduku, Mpinganjira and Duh (2016), an organisation must have highly qualified employees to oversee the implementation of technical innovation. Several studies suggested that many organisations lack internal IS specialists, forcing them to employ expensive external IS consultants (Thong, 2001; Fisher and Howell, 2004).

3.2.3 Environmental context

The addition of the environmental context absent from other organisational IS adoption theories, including the DOI theory, is a significant component of the TOE framework.

Several researchers identified various environmental factors that influence an organisation's adoption of new technologies. This study included the competitive pressure and government support factors.

Competitive pressure

Several studies concluded that competitive pressure is a significant element impacting a company's decision to adopt new technologies (Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2018; Premkumar and Roberts, 1999; Liu *et al.*, 2010). Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin (2018) argued that external pressures and, as a reaction to their competitors, will force companies to adopt SM to survive and improve their performance (Haller and Siedschlag, 2011).

Government support

The government support through legislation and initiatives significantly impact how quickly innovations are adopted or diffused in an organisation, which is one environmental factor found to influence technology adoption (Dahnil *et al.*, 2014). Government policies and procedures can drive and hinder innovation and technology adoption among businesses (Effendi, Sugandini and Istanto, 2020).

In summary, this section provided an understanding of the main theories, the DOI theory and the TOE framework, adopted to form the conceptual framework tested in this study. The following section describes Hofstede's cultural theory used as a theoretical foundation for formulating the fourth context of the proposed conceptual framework, the cultural context.

3.3 Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory- The cultural context

Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory (Figure 3.2) identified the cultural determinants that influence SM adoption by B2B organisations in Greece. As stated in Chapter 1, one research objective (RO1) was to explore the factors that influence the adoption of SM by B2B organisations operating in Greece. Therefore, it was critical to determine if any cultural dimensions or elements influence technology adoption, especially those specific to Greece. Incorporating Hofstede's

cultural dimensions into the conceptual framework offered insight into how cultural characteristics impact SM adoption in Greece.

Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov (2010, p. 4) suggested a widely used definition of culture: “Every person carries within him or herself patterns of thinking, feeling and potential acting which were learned throughout their lifetime”. Several previous studies emphasised that national culture might influence the adoption of innovations and stressed linking the IS frameworks with national culture characteristics (McCoy, Galletta and King, 2005; Prim *et al.*, 2017). There are several theoretical models for understanding national culture (Hall, 1976; Hofstede, 1984; Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1993). However, this study used Hofstede’s Cultural Dimensions theory for two reasons: first, this theory has been widely used in different disciplines; marketing, accounting, business and psychology are just a few of the disciplines that use Hofstede’s model (Søndergaard, 1994). Second, it allows the researcher to compare the study findings to earlier studies. Moreover, Hofstede’s theory is largely recognised in the relevant social sciences literature and was created as a result of a thorough investigation into the impact of culture on workplace values (Özbilen, 2017). Hofstede’s model, however, is not without critics (Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1997). According to McSweeney (2002), surveys are not the best way to analyse cultural differences, and the nations are not the appropriate units of analysis for cultural differences. Ratner and Hui (2003) have indicated that an activity theory-based or a more qualitative approach might be more appropriate.

Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov (2010) identified six (6) dimensions in which national cultures may differ: 1) power distance, 2) individualism, 3) masculinity, 4) uncertainty avoidance, 5) short-term orientation and 6) indulgence (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory (Hofstede, 2011)

Chatzithomas *et al.* (2014) used content analysis for their cross-cultural comparison of issues and trends in SM advertising techniques in the USA and Greece. Their findings show that Greece is a collectivist society that avoids unpredictable and unstructured situations, has an intermediate power distance with a lower masculinity score compared to the USA. Table 3.3 provides a definition for each cultural dimension.

Table 3.3: Definitions of Hofstede’s cultural dimensions (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010)

Cultural dimensions	Definition
Power Distance	“The extent to which the less powerful members of institutions and organisations within a country expect and accept that power is distributed unequally” (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010, p.61)
Individualism Vs Collectivism	“Individualism pertains to societies in which the ties between individuals are loose: everyone is expected to look after him- or herself and his or her immediate family”. “Collectivism pertains to societies in which people from birth onward are integrated into strong, cohesive in-groups, which throughout people’s lifetime continue to protect them in exchange for unquestioning loyalty” (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010, p. 92)
Masculinity	“The extent to which emotional gender roles are clearly distinct: men are supposed to be assertive, tough, and focused on material success, whereas women are supposed to be more modest, tender, and concerned with the quality of life” (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010, p. 140)
Uncertainty avoidance	“The extent to which the members of a culture feel threatened by ambiguous or unknown situations” (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010, p. 191)
Long/short term orientation	“Long-term orientation stands for the fostering of virtues oriented toward future rewards- in particular, perseverance and thrift”. “Short-term orientation stands for the fostering of virtues related to the past and present- in particular, respect for tradition, preservation of ‘face,’ and fulfilling social obligations” (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010, p. 239)
Indulgence	“Indulgence stands for a tendency to allow relatively free gratification of basic and natural human desires related to enjoying life and having fun”. “It’s opposite pole, restraint, reflects a conviction that such gratification needs to be curbed and regulated by strict social norms” (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010, p. 281).

Power distance (PDI)

The first dimension of Hofstede’s model assesses people’s aversion to highly concentrated power and status in a given culture (Prim *et al.*, 2017). High power distance (PDI) countries are more authoritarian, tend to be less innovative, and are more willing to accept power and economic differences (Mihet, 2013). Countries with a lower PDI prioritise equality among their citizens and encourage democratic involvement (Rinne, Steel and Fairweather, 2012). In PDI, Greece has an intermediate score of 60 (Figure 3.3) and according to Erumban and de Jong (2006), there is a negative correlation between higher power distance and ICT adoption.

Individualism vs collectivism (IND)

Previous research suggests that companies in individualistic cultures are more innovative and apt to adopt and use new technology than collectivist societies (Taylor and Wilson, 2012). Greece has a lower score of thirty-five (35) and making it a collectivist society. Individuals are members of small groups that look after one another via mutual commitment and devotion (Chatzithomas *et al.*, 2014).

Masculinity (MAS)

Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov (2010) define countries with a high masculine score as societies that value competition, performance, and success and sustain this orientation throughout their educational system and organisational life. Greece is a medium-ranking masculinity society with a score of fifty-seven (57) and is “success oriented and driven” (Hofstede, 1991; Chatzithomas *et al.*, 2014). Özbilen (2017) suggested that societies with higher masculinity scores are more innovative, frequently adopting the latest technologies to stay ahead of the competition.

Uncertainty avoidance (UAI)

The uncertainty avoidance dimension measures the willingness to deal with risk circumstances, a lack of prior knowledge, or the unpredictability of events in their life or at work (Kreiser *et al.*, 2010). Greece has the highest score of 100 in this dimension indicating that Greece is intolerant of beliefs and behaviours that differ from to the norm (Chatzithomas *et al.*, 2014). According to Tsatsou (2012) the high uncertainty avoidance of the Greek society indicates scepticism about new technologies and their implications.

Long-term vs short term orientation (LTO)

According to previous researchers long term orientation positively influences company-level adoption of new technologies (Zhao, 2013; Özbilen, 2017). In the long-term orientation dimension, Greece has an intermediate score of forty-five (45). According to Hofstede (1991), societies with low score in this dimension prefer traditions and norms and they are sceptical of societal change.

Indulgence (IND)

Indulgence is the sixth dimension of Hofstede’s model, introduced in 2010 (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010). This dimension measures how much a country's citizens can manage their urges and impulses, linked to their level of personal achievement (Prim *et al.*, 2017). Greece has a score of 50 on this dimension, indicating no apparent preference between indulgence (“weak control”) and restraint (“strong control”).

Figure 3.3: Hofstede’s score for the Greek culture (source: <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country/greece/>)

3.3 The conceptual framework adopted for this study

Based on the SLR, the integration of DOI Theory (Rogers, 1995), the TOE framework (DePietro, Wiarda and Fleischer, 1990) and Hofstede’s cultural dimensions theory (Hofstede, 1991), the researcher developed a preliminary conceptual framework to later tested in this study (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4: The preliminary conceptual framework

This conceptual framework can examine how the different technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural characteristics influence SMM adoption by Greek B2B organisations.

New additional factors emerged from the qualitative findings, added to the proposed framework (Chapter 6, Figure 6.6) and tested during the quantitative phase of this study.

3.4 Summary

This chapter provided a comprehensive summary of the conceptual framework, including the three (3) theories that generated an expanded conceptual framework. The initial theoretical framework originated from a thorough review of literature on SM adoption of B2B organisations. Prior SM adoption research relied on the DOI and TOE frameworks and Hofstede's cultural dimensions model. After evaluating the application of these theories in previous research, the researcher identified essential components of these theories and used these theories to develop the qualitative interview questions that led to the refinement of the conceptual framework. This chapter captured the significant features of the DOI and TOE framework and Hofstede's model, justifying their use for investigating SM adoption of Greek B2B organisations. The next chapter presents the decisions to conduct the research in the Greek context.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH CONTEXT- GREECE

4.1 Introduction

This study investigated the adoption of social media marketing (SMM) by the Greek B2B companies. More specifically, it explored the factors relating to the technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural contexts that influence business-to-business (B2B) SM usage and perceived benefits and barriers to SM adoption. Research on SM in Greece is underdeveloped. Therefore, presents the current economic conditions in Greece and its digital progress. To research Greek companies, it is essential to understand their environment. For example, the economic crisis significantly impacted Greek companies. The purchasing power of Greek citizens has been progressively declining, causing Greek firms to make substantial concessions and reduce spending to survive. This chapter presents the digital level of the Greeks and the digital infrastructure of the Greek economy. From prior research, it is evident that Greece is underperforming in the digital area and ranks very low among the twenty-eight (28) EU member states on the DESI index (published by the European Commission), that measures the digital progress of the EU members.

4.2 Greek economic context

Greece is an advanced (International Monetary Fund, 2014) high-income economy built on the service and industrial sectors (80% and 16%, respectively). The agricultural sector contributes around 4% of the national economic production. The Greek economy is the 51st largest globally, with a nominal gross domestic product (GDP) of \$348.349 billion per annum (World Bank, 2021), and the primary industry revolves around tourism and shipping. Greece is the 10th member of the European Union (EU) since 1981 (Bourantas and Papadakis, 1996; Giousmpasoglou, 2014) and member of the Eurozone since 2001 (Nakos and Hajidimitriou, 2009). It is the 14th largest economy

in the EU's twenty-eight (28) members as of 2021 (Eurostat, 2021). Greece no longer has an independent monetary policy as a member of the Eurozone, because it has delegated this responsibility to the European Central Bank (Nakos and Hajidimitriou, 2009). Greece has a robust democratic political system with a free market economy and limited government control (Bourantas and Papadakis, 1996).

Greece has a low rate of foreign investment and productivity; due to economic, political and social factors there is a poor rate of foreign investment and productivity and high unemployment (McKinsey & Company, 2012). According to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development's (OECD) Employment Outlook 2018 (OECD, 2018), Greece has the highest unemployment rate (18.6%) among developed countries and the highest rate (18.6%) inside the Eurozone (Eurostat, 2018). Greece has a complex administrative and tax system which creates unfavorable conditions for businesses and investments (McKinsey & Company, 2012).

According to Mouzelis (1986), Greece is a "late development semi-periphery country", with industrialization occurring after 1929 (Tsatsou, 2012) and lacks the culture and tradition of sophisticated technology adoption and use, and technology innovation (Loukis, 2011). SME's dominate the Greek economic activity, and while they have made tremendous progress, they still lag behind the European average in adapting and using new technologies (Giotopoulos *et al.*, 2017).

Since 2008, Greece has been in an "economic crisis". From April 2010, the state had to rely on three loans from the "Troika" consisting of the European Commission, the European Central Bank and the International Monetary Fund (Hausken and Welburn, 2020). It had the second highest budget deficit in the EU and the second highest debt-to-GPD ratio (Belegri-Roboli, Markaki and Michaelides, 2011). The Greek economy was beset by structural issues such as inefficient

bureaucracy and a burgeoning informal economy (Belegri-Roboli, Markaki and Michaelides, 2011).

However, according to Giannarakis and Theotokas (2011), an economic crisis redefines ties between companies and society rather than present a danger. In addition, Souto (2009) identifies a set of requirements for transforming a financial crisis from potential threat into a chance to survive and increase the company's profits in the interim and long-term. Innovation, a pleasant environment, stakeholder roles, corporate strategy, market attitude, investor confidence and in-depth internal reflection are among the requirements (Souto, 2009).

In August 2018 the eight-year adjustment program ended, but policy limits remained. It was the country's most profound and the most prolonged recession in postwar history (Alogoskoufis and Featherstone, 2021). While the Greek economy seemed to recover after 2017, the COVID-19 global pandemic, negatively impacted the country's economy in 2020, igniting yet another economic recession (Alogoskoufis and Featherstone, 2021).

Several authors conducted studies to investigate SM adoption and use of SM and ICT in Greece (Table 4.1) such as: SM (Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020; Mikalef and Pateli, 2017; Sigala and Chalkiti, 2015; Vlachvei and Notta, 2014; 2015), ICT (Giotopoulos *et al.*, 2017; Rodakinias *et al.*, 2008; Buhalis and Deimezi, 2004), cloud computing (Alshamaila *et al.*, 2013) and SM advertising (Chatzithomas *et al.*, 2014).

Table 4.1: Some studies conducted in Greece

Authors	Domain
Notta and Kitta (2021)	e-marketing
Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020	Social media
Mikalef and Pateli (2017)	Social media
Giotopoulos <i>et al.</i> (2017)	ICT
Vlachvei and Notta (2015)	Social media
Sigala and Chalkiti (2015)	Social media
Drosos <i>et al.</i> (2015)	SNS
Vlachvei and Notta (2014)	Social media
Chatzithomas <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Social media advertising
Tsimonis and Dimitriadis (2014)	Social media
Alshamaila <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Cloud computing
Rodakinias <i>et al.</i> (2008)	ICT
Buhalis and Deimezi (2004)	ICT

Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou (2020) used survey data from 106 Greek hospitality companies. They combined the Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) and the TOE framework to examine the factors affecting an organisation adopting SM. The researchers identified seven determinants and concluded that the technological factors have the most predictive power. Vlachvei and Notta (2014), based on primary and secondary data, provided evidence of the significant efforts of Greek food manufacturing companies to adopt SM and benefit from those tools. The study revealed that the top three (3) SMM benefits, are building brands, real-time information dissemination for products, contests, awards, and such; and customer service integration. Giotopoulos *et al.* (2017), based on survey data from three thousand five hundred (3,500) Greek SMEs examined the determinants influencing an organisation to adopt ICT by applying the TOE framework. They concluded that innovation and R&D activities and collaborations, trained and skilled employees,

decentralised decision-making, and visionary leadership are significant factors influencing SMEs to adopt new technologies.

4.3 Digital status in Greece

SM can improve the competitiveness of Greek's businesses by allowing them to connect with their customers and create a sense of community belonging (Kavoura and Stavrianea, 2014). Digital skills can unlock the potential for a network economy and therefore are critical enablers of economic productivity and growth development (Moustakas *et al.*, 2018). Governments worldwide design and implement ICT adoption and digital growth strategies to improve public administration efficiency and transparency, create new jobs, competitiveness, innovation, and improve citizens' quality of life (Tsakanikas *et al.*, 2014).

The Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), introduced in 2014, is used by the European Commission to track and report Member States' digital progress (European Commission, 2020). The DESI index has five dimensions: 1) *connectivity* (fixed and mobile broadband); 2) *human capital* (internet use, basic and advanced digital skills); 3) *use of internet* (citizens' use of content, communication and online transactions); 4) *integration of Digital Technology* (business digitization and e-Commerce); and 5) *digital public services* (e-Government and e-Health) (Moustakas *et al.*, 2018). In the DESI Index 2020, Greece is ranked 27th out of twenty-eight (28) EU member states (European Commission, 2020). Figure 4.1 depicts the DESI ranks of EU member states while Figure 4.2 compares Greece's rank and score to EU averages.

Figure 4.1: DESI index (European Commission, 2020)

Therefore, Greece lags behind the EU average in all dimension (Moustakas *et al.*, 2018) (Table 4.2).

Table 4.2: DESI 2020 scores for Greece (European Commission, 2020)

DESI 2020	Greece		EU
	Rank	Score	Score
Connectivity	28	33.4	50.1
Human capital	25	34.8	49.3
Use of Internet services	25	46.1	58
Integration of digital technology	24	28.2	41.4
Digital public services	27	51.5	72

1. Connectivity

While the score has improved in prior years, in 2020, Greece ranked last among the EU countries in broadband infrastructure and adoption, which may be due to pricing, as it remains considerably

high compared to the EU average (European Commission, 2020). In business, just 85% of Greek enterprises have fixed and mobile broadband connections, the lowest in the EU. Only 65% have a website or homepage, giving Greece the second-lowest ranking among European countries (Moustakas *et al.*, 2018).

2. Human capital with digital skills

A robust digital economy can aid the Greek companies to recover from the recession and boost their competitiveness. However, inadequate digital skills among employees is a critical barrier to economic growth in Greece. According to Moustakas *et al.* (2018), in 2017, 23% of Greeks had low (below basic) digital skills, while 24% had basic digital skills. The EU average for basic digital skills was 28%; therefore, the Greeks lag in basic, essential digital skills compared to other EU countries. Additionally, 22% of Greeks had beyond-advanced digital skills, compared to 31% of people in the EU, which further justifies the need to build digital skills among Greek employees.

3. Use of Internet services

In general, internet usage is significantly lower than the EU average (European Commission, 2020). However, the number of Greek internet users is increasing, as citizens use the Internet primarily for reading the news (88%), holding video calls (67%), using social networks (75%), online banking (40%) and online shopping (51%).

4. Integration of digital technology by businesses

The fourth dimension assessed a company's digitalization and use of the internet as an online and marketing channel. The adoption and implementation of digital technology can improve company productivity and, customer and business partner engagement while lowering costs (Moustakas *et al.*, 2018). On the integration of digital technology, Greece placed 24th place in the EU. Moreover, the figure below (Figure 4.2) illustrates business digitization (indicators: electronic information

sharing, RFID, SM, e-Invoices, and cloud solutions) and e-Commerce (indicators: % of SMEs selling online, e-Commerce turnover as % of the total turnover of SMEs, and the percentage of SMEs selling online cross-border) scores of Greek companies in 2020. However, the percentage of Greek businesses utilising SM decreased slightly in 2019, as did SMEs selling online.

	Greece			EU
	DESI 2018 value	DESI 2019 value	DESI 2020 value	DESI 2020 value
4a1 Electronic information sharing % enterprises	37% 2017	37% 2017	38% 2019	34% 2019
4a2 Social media % enterprises	21% 2017	21% 2017	19% 2019	25% 2019
4a3 Big data % enterprises	11% 2016	13% 2018	13% 2018	12% 2018
4a4 Cloud % enterprises	5% 2017	7% 2018	7% 2018	18% 2018
4b1 SMEs selling online % SMEs	11% 2017	11% 2018	9% 2019	18% 2019
4b2 e-Commerce turnover % SME turnover	3% 2017	4% 2018	4% 2019	11% 2019
4b3 Selling online cross-border % SMEs	7% 2017	7% 2017	4% 2019	8% 2019

Figure 4.2: DESI 2020 scores for the Integration of digital technology (European Commission, 2020)

5. Digital public services (e-Government)

Digital public services, also known as e-Government, are government services and services the government provides to the public using technology, namely information and communications technology. The transition to digital public services allows government officials, contractors, businesses, and citizens to perform tasks electronically, such as filing and paying taxes, requesting documents, and submitting forms. The former use of paper and in-person transactions limited the access and availability of government communication and services and required additional human resources. Through e-Government, these communications and services are readily available,

widely accessible, reduces government and citizen expenses and resources, and improves efficiency. The last DESI dimension assesses the digitization of public services, with a focus on e-Government and e-Health. Greece ranks second to last in the EU regarding digital public services, significantly below the EU norm, but improved 5.1 points over the previous year, in line with the EU average of five (5) points (European Commission, 2020). The number of digital public services available to businesses increased (to 63), although it still trails the EU average (88) (European Commission, 2020). Additionally, the launch of the official portal “gov.gr” by the Ministry of Digital Governance provided over five hundred (500) e-services, which accelerated the digitization of public services.

The current COVID-19 pandemic forced the Greek government to implement several digital initiatives in response to the problems and barriers posed by the health crisis, hastening the pace of digital transformation. Regarding DESI metrics, which are particularly important for the economic recovery following the COVID-19 crisis, Greece lags behind the EU average and needs to increase investments in digital skills and digitization of businesses (European Commission, 2020).

In June 2021, the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance launched the revised national digital strategy for 2020-2025. The “Digital Transformation Bible” (Ministry of Digital Governance, 2021) explains the objectives and the implementation measures of the digital transformation plan through cooperation with stakeholders from the public and private sectors, the research and academic community and the Greek society.

4.4 Summary

This chapter described the economic context of Greece and elucidated the digital level of the Greek private and public sectors. The economic context focused on the economic crisis and its impact on

the Greek economy and Greek companies. The combination of the Greek cultural context presented in Chapter 3 and the digital status of Greece discussed here define the research setting for this study. The subsequent chapter outlines the research methodology and research design adopted in this research.

CHAPTER 5-RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

5.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the research methodology and design used to investigate factors influencing the adoption of SM by the Greek business-to-business (B2B) organisations, including the perceived benefits and barriers. The first section presents the research philosophy before explaining the research design and data collection methods. The chapter also includes the sampling aspect of the study and ethical considerations.

How researchers address their research objectives is influenced by their philosophy and approach to theory development (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Wilson (2014) developed the Honeycomb Research Methodology (Figure 5.1) to define data collection and address research objectives citing the need to know the study network of the methodology. The research network includes six (6) main research elements (Figure 5.1): 1) the philosophy; 2) approaches; 3) strategy; 4) designs; 5) data collection; and 6) data analysis and interpretation techniques.

Figure 5.1: The Honeycomb Research Methodology (Wilson, 2014)

The following subsections present the methodology and research design.

5.2 Research philosophy

Philosophy refers to applying abstract ideas and beliefs to our research (Creswell, 2009) for developing knowledge in a particular field (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Understanding research philosophy affects how researchers conduct their research (Wilson, 2014) and help them recognise what they are investigating (Johnson and Clark, 2006).

In a similar approach, Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Lowe (2002) advocated that understanding philosophical issues can assist researchers with selecting appropriate research designs, and adjusting the designs to account for the limitations of various issues or knowledge structures.

There are three (3) different branches of philosophy (Figure 5.2): epistemology, ontology, and axiology

Figure 5.2: Research philosophy (Wilson 2014)

5.2.1 Epistemology

The critical question that epistemology tries to answer is, “What is acceptable knowledge?” (Wilson, 2014) and how to communicate this knowledge to others (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). Scholars suggest three epistemological assumptions in IS research (Orlikowski and Baroudi, 1991): positivism, interpretivism and pragmatism.

Positivism relates “to the philosophical stance of the natural scientist and entails working with an observable social reality to produce law-like generalisations” (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016, p. 135). The core argument of positivism is that “the social world exists externally to the researcher, and that its properties can be measured directly through observation” (Gray, 2014, p. 21). Positivist philosophy is the prevalent philosophy that has been employed in the IS research and investigates the nature of a phenomenon using quantifiable variables and hypotheses testing

(Orlikowski and Baroudi, 1991). Researchers conduct positivist research mainly to test theory founded in scientific observation and empirical research (Gray, 2014).

Positivism relates to hypothetically and deductively testing theories, and surveys are positivists' typical researcher instrument (Chen and Hirschheim, 2004). Positivists assume that scientific knowledge should be verifiable or falsifiable, and results should be generalisable. Chen and Hirschheim (2004) suggested that positivist research is mainly observed by

1. the development of hypotheses, model(s), or causal relationships between constructs,
2. the application of quantitative methods for testing hypotheses or theories, and
3. the objective and value-free interpretation of researchers.

Interpretivism focuses on the meanings humans create (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016) and those meanings must not constitute a physical phenomenon. Interpretivism criticise positivists by arguing that humans are different, so we cannot apply universal "laws" for everybody (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016) Interpretivism is an emerging paradigm in IS research and interpretivists believe that scientific knowledge should result from understanding human and social interaction and analysing participants' perspectives (Chen and Hirschheim, 2004). According to Chen and Hirschheim (2004), interpretivist studies identifiable if:

1. data are from a non-deterministic viewpoint,
2. the involvement of researchers in the specific social and cultural setting are explored, and
3. an examination is based on participants' perspectives.

Interpretivist philosophy, using qualitative methods and field research, results in a wealth of knowledge of the phenomenon (Orlikowski and Baroudi, 1991).

Pragmatism focuses on research consequences and the importance of research question(s) rather than methods (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). The research question would likely emphasise

practical results of the pragmatist approach (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Pragmatism is an approach to knowledge that considers multiple perspectives and standpoints and addresses issues that one research approach may not address (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Therefore, it is considered the primary philosophy in mixed methods research (Johnson, Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007). For pragmatists, scientific knowledge is valuable when it assists people in the creation of better organisations or better coping with the world (Fendt, Kaminska-Labbé and Sachs, 2008). According to Goles and Hirschheim (2000), pragmatism can help IS researchers increase their research rigour and relevance.

As previously mentioned, given the research objectives of this study, an exclusively interpretivist philosophy would not allow the researcher to test hypotheses and generalise the findings (Orlikowski and Baroudi, 1991). In contrast, a purely positivist approach would not permit the researcher to get an in-depth understanding of a new phenomenon through subjective interpretation and participants' perspectives (Chen and Hirschheim, 2004). Thus, this research adopted a pragmatic philosophy to provide original and imaginative insights into research work (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). The pragmatism approach is suitable when the researcher uses a mixed method approach to answer the research questions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016; Wilson, 2014). According to Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen (2014), the pragmatic research contributes to a comprehensive overview of the adoption of SMM in a B2B context. Previous studies, such as Iankova (2018), also adopted pragmatism philosophy to develop a deeper understanding of SMM in the industrial context.

5.2.2 Ontology

Ontology concerns “the nature of reality” and asks, “how we perceive the social world, or to put it another way, the way we think the world is” (Wilson, 2014, p. 11). There are two opposite

ontological stances: objectivism and subjectivism. Objectivism “incorporates the assumptions of the natural sciences, arguing that the social reality that we research is external to us and others” (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 135). On the contrary, subjectivism, “perceives that social phenomena are created from the perceptions and consequent actions of those social actors concerned with their existence” (Dudovskiy, 2018, p. 39). Table 5.1 presents the ontology of the three (3) different philosophies:

Table 5.1: Ontology of research philosophies, adapted from Dudovskiy (2018, p. 40)

Research philosophy	Ontology: the researcher’s view of the nature of reality or being
Positivism	External, objective, and independent of social actors
Interpretivism	Socially constructed, subjective, may change, multiple
Pragmatism	External, multiple, view chosen to enable answering of the research question best

This study analysed employees’ perceptions of their organisation’s (the case study company) SM adoption. The researcher recorded detailed descriptions and varying feedback regarding employees’ experiences and perceptions. Therefore, the study analysed the subjective experiences of individual employees and their perception of SMM adoption.

5.2.3 Axiology

Axiology concerns ethics and the role of values in the research process including how the researchers handle participants’ values and their own (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016, p. 128) a written statement of how the researcher’s values can help make value judgments when concluding the data and decide what is appropriate ethically. Therefore, researcher values influence researcher conduct and illustrate their findings’ value (Dudovskiy, 2018). The table below illustrates the axiology of major research philosophies and the applicable data collection methods.

Table 5.2: Axiology of research philosophies and relevant data collection techniques, adapted by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009), cited in Dudovskiy (2018, p. 36)

	Axiology	Popular data collection techniques
Positivism	Research is undertaken in a value-free way; the researcher is independent of the data, and maintains an objective stance	Highly structured, large samples, measurement, quantitative can also use quantitative
Interpretivism	Research is value laden; the researcher is biased by world views, cultural experiences, and upbringings. These effect research findings	Methods chosen must fit the subject matter. Quantitative or qualitative
Pragmatism	Values play a large role in interpreting results, the researcher adopting both objective and subjective points of view	Mixed or multiple method designs, quantitative and qualitative

This study uses pragmatism as research philosophy, which asserts values play a significant role in collecting data and interpreting the results. The researcher’s decision to collect data through face-to-face interviews as a research strategy suggests that the researcher highly values data gathering through personal interactions with participants (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). The researcher adopted subjective (face-to-face interviews) and objective (an online survey- anonymous questionnaire) viewpoints.

5.3 Research approach

There are two (2) different research approaches: **inductive** and **deductive** (Wilson, 2014). The figure below demonstrates how theory fits into the research (Wilson, 2014, p. 13)

Figure 5.3: How theory fits into your research, adapted from Wilson (2014, p. 13)

5.3.1 Inductive: from specific to general

According to Hyde (2000, p. 83) **inductive** is “a theory-building process, starting with observations of specific instances, and seeking to establish generalisation about the phenomenon under investigation”. If a researcher pursues an inductive approach to their study, they must observe their research and how it contributes to theory creation (Wilson, 2014). The inductive approach collects data and develops theory due to the data analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). This approach is frequently used in **qualitative** research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016; Wilson, 2014).

5.3.2 Deductive: from general to specific

According to Wilson (2014, p. 12), a **deductive** approach “begins with and applies a well-known theory”. Firstly, a researcher develops a hypothesis/es based on the existing theory and secondly design a research strategy to test his hypothesis/es. According to Ghauri and Grønhaug (2005, p.15), in an deductive approach, theory and hypotheses come first, influencing the remaining research process. This type of research frequently connects to quantitative research. Table 5.3 below summarises the significant distinctions between inductive and deductive approaches.

Table 5.3: Major differences between inductive and deductive research approaches (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007 cited in Wilson 2014, p. 14)

Induction emphasizes	Deduction emphasizes
Gaining an understanding of the meanings that humans attach to events	Scientific principles
Understanding of the research context	Moving from the theory to data
Collecting qualitative data	Explaining causal relationships between variables
Using a flexible structure that permits changes in research emphasis as the study progresses	Collecting quantitative data
Realising that the research is part of the process	Applying controls to ensure the validity of data
Minimising generalisations	Operationalising of concepts to ensure clarity of definition
	Creating a highly structured approach
	Remaining independent from what is being researched
	Selecting samples of sufficient size to generalise conclusions

The researcher adopted an inductive approach for analysing qualitative data collected during the first phase to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns, and build a conceptual framework (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). In the second (quantitative) phase, the researcher adopted a deductive approach and used the collected data to evaluate the hypotheses related to the conceptual framework (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

The third mode of inference or reasoning, the abductive, was developed by Peirce (1960/1979). “Abduction is about discovering new concepts, ideas and explanations by finding surprising phenomena, data, or events that cannot be explained by pre-existing knowledge” (Kennedy, Kennedy and Thornberg, 2018, p. 53). The combination of inductive and deductive approaches through abductive thinking and the employment of skills in observing people and recording behaviour (Morgan, 2007) helps the researchers solve problems by using both words and numbers

(Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). The mixed-method approach is therefore practical in the sense that it allows the researcher to use any method available to address a research problem and is the preferred mode of understanding the world (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018).

5.4 Research strategies

This section briefly discusses the two (2) primary research strategies for business research, the qualitative and quantitative and the rationale behind combining them as this study adopted a mixed-method approach. The research's strategy corresponds to the researcher's choice of research philosophies. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) advocated that both terms are used in business and management studies to differentiate the techniques for data collection and the procedures for data analysis.

5.4.1 Qualitative research strategy

Qualitative research is an interpretive (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011) and multi-method strategy involving case studies, interviews, observation, ethnographic data and insights into organisational practices and human interactions (Mertens, 1998). Qualitative research is mainly interpretive because the researchers operate in a natural context to gain access to meanings, have an in-depth understanding, and establish trust among the participants (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Qualitative research is also appropriate within the realist and pragmatist philosophies (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

Denzin and Lincoln (2005, p. 3) have offered an "initial and generic definition":

Qualitative research is a situated activity that locates the observer in the world. It consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that make the world visible. These practices transform the world. They turn the world into a series of representations, including field notes, interviews, conversations, photographs, recordings, and memos to the self. At this

level, qualitative research involves an interpretive, naturalistic approach to the world. This means that qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them.

In qualitative research, researchers establish meanings from texts and images, often exploring and clarifying participant meanings, usually through unstructured or semi-structured interviews (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Strauss and Corbin (1998) assert that interviews effectively elicit an understanding of complex human decisions and behaviours. Interviews enable participants to respond to pre-determined topics while also allowing exploring unexpected responses as they arise (Anderson and Kanuka, 2003).

5.4.1.1 Justification for using a Qualitative approach

The qualitative approach was utilised in this study for three (3) reasons. Firstly, since B2B SM adoption is still in its “infancy” (Siamagka *et al.*, 2015), this study has an exploratory nature to gain new revelations in the field and related organisational contexts (Gorman and Clayton, 2005).

Secondly, based on the interviews, the researcher developed a conceptual framework that served as the foundation for exploration, discovery, and hypothesis development.

Thirdly, most studies on SMM adoption in the industrial domain were quantitative, with data collected, from questionnaires and surveys (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021). Qualitative SMM research is emerging, but qualitative exploratory research is in its infancy (Bogea and Brito, 2018). Therefore, there was a need to acquire a deeper understanding through analysing qualitative data (Kapoor, Dwivedi and Williams, 2014).

5.4.1.2 Case study

The adoption of SMM in the B2B context is an underexplored area. Therefore, the researcher adopted a case study research strategy to study the phenomenon in its real-life context. According to LaPlaca and Lindgreen (2016, p. 1), “case method research is an in-depth investigation (description) of a specific situation or phenomena” and “it may be the only way to gain an understanding of the underlying processes involved in industrial marketing”. Using a single case study helps the researcher explore and analyse an unexplored phenomenon and have an in-depth investigation to investigate the research question and gain theoretical insights (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). Eisenhardt (1991) argues that single case studies are instrumental for exploring the phenomenon in its infancy. Benbasat, Goldstein and Mead (1987) assert that the researcher’s goals and the nature of the research topic influence the strategy selection. According to Benbasat, Goldstein and Mead (1987) the case study research is a viable design for the IS field for three (3) reasons:

1. the researcher can study IS in its natural environment and create theories through practice,
2. it enables the researcher to comprehend the complexities and the nature of the problems and provide answers to “how” and “why” questions, and
3. because of the rapid revolution of IS, new topics emerge yearly making case study research appropriate for studying an underexplored research topic.

According to Kanellis and Papadopoulos (2009, p. 18) the main criticism of case study research is that they are “problematic with respect to generalisability. As their application is restricted to a single organisation, generalisations cannot be made easily if at all”.

This case study explored how B2B organisations in Greece perceive the adoption of SM in their marketing strategies and exchanges with their business partners. The case study company is the

dominant telecommunication provider in Greece and the largest telecommunication organisation in Southeast Europe. The company was founded in 1931 and remained a state-owned monopoly until 1996. Deutsche Telekom is the largest shareholder of the company since July 2009.

During the period 2017-2019, a total of three thousand five hundred (3,500) businesses and freelancers in ten (10) cities across Greece attended the program *#GrowYourBusiness - Digital Training*, developed by the company, and learned to utilise the latest technological tools and capabilities of digital technologies (SM, e-commerce, and digital marketing). The free educational seminars were attended by businesses from sectors like commerce, catering, tourism, and services.

The case study company was appealing for this study because:

- It has adopted SMM tools. The company could be identified as a pioneer and thought leader in SMM in Greece in the B2B, B2C and the B2G business contexts.
- The company received the **Greek Social Media Brand of the Year 2019** award. In total, the company won thirteen (13) awards: six (6) Gold, two (2) Silver, and three (3) Bronze. Additionally, the company won two (2) "Grand Prix" awards, which is the highest score of the section awarded only to those nominated sections found by a jury to have performed with excellence and significantly contributed to the development of the market.

5.4.2 Quantitative research strategy

Quantitative methods emphasise collecting numerical data and include survey designs and experiments (Creswell, 2009). According to Creswell (2009), a survey can collect numerical descriptions of trends or opinions from a population sample; experiments are controlled studies that test the effect of a treatment or intervention on a group.

The survey strategy typically corresponds with the deductive research approach and uses statistical analysis to analyse quantitative data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Through the survey

strategy, the researcher collected and analysed data using descriptive and inferential statistics. The quantitative approach (phase two) validated the qualitative findings and broadened the findings through a broader sample of B2B companies.

5.4.2.1 Online survey

An online survey served as the primary quantitative data source. According to Evans and Mathur (2005), because B2B participants are busy and challenging to reach, the web can be the primary survey methodology. The online surveys are very adaptable and can assume different forms: an email containing a link to the survey URL, and an email containing an embedded survey (Evans and Mathur, 2005). Also, the participant can choose a convenient time to respond and has sufficient time to think about each answer. Some online surveys for example, Qualtrics, let the respondents start and return later to the question where they left off earlier (Qualtrics.com). Nowadays, most of the online survey software “are automatically placed into the database, and then tabulated and analysed in a coordinated, integrated manner that greatly reduces costs” (Evans and Mathur, 2005 p. 199). For more details about the online survey in this study, please see section 5.8.1.

5.4.3 Mixed-method strategy

A mixed-method approach combines two or more research method (for example, qualitative and quantitative) in a single or multi-phased study (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998). Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010) advocate that the application of more than one data source aids with the triangulation and increases the validity of the gathered information. Triangulation is “largely a vehicle for cross validation when two or more distinct methods are found to be congruent and yield comparable data” (Jick, 1979, p. 602). Denzin (1978), cited in Iankova (2018), proposed four types of triangulation methods to combine methodologies in the same study:

- *Data triangulation*- use of different sources in the same study

- *Investigator triangulation*- use of different researchers
- *Theory triangulation*- use of different theories to analyse the study results
- *Methodological triangulation*- use of different methods for studying a research problem

This study used data triangulation and methodological triangulation to examine the adoption of SM by B2B organisations in Greece from different perspectives.

As Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004, p. 14-15) advocate:

both quantitative and qualitative research is important, and the goal of mixed methods research is not to replace either of these approaches but rather to draw from the strengths and minimize the weaknesses of both in single research studies and across studies.

According to Zohrabi (2013), using different data sources can increase the validity and reliability of the data. Additionally, Bryman, Becker and Sempik (2008) examined quality criteria in mixed methods, and identified four criteria applicable to mixed method studies:

1. The mixed methods must be relevant to the research objectives
2. Mixed methods procedures must have transparency
3. The researchers must integrate or mix the findings
4. The researchers must provide a rationale for using mixed methods

According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2018), in mixed methods, the connective point between the qualitative and quantitative components is referred to as “the point of interface”. There are two different types of mixed method approaches. The explanatory sequential design (**quan→qual**) starts with a quantitative study and continues with a qualitative study. The exploratory sequential design starts with a qualitative study and continues with quantitative study (**qual→quan**) (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018).

The current study adopted the exploratory sequential approach and the point of interface happened between the qualitative and quantitative phases. The study’s priority was the qualitative component followed by a survey that further tested the theoretical framework. According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2018), this theory-development of the exploratory sequential design (notated as **QUAL→quan**) indicates that the thrust of the study is considered qualitative.

Figure 5.4: Different types of mixed method research (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018)

Several reasons justify the mixed-method approach for this study. In the diffusion and the adoption literature, the dominant research method is the quantitative approach using surveys and questionnaires (Wang *et al.*, 2011). However, other researchers, such as Rogers (2003), critiques using only one method, the surveys, to collect data. Wang, Fu and Duan (2011, p. 3) suggest mixed-method strategies and encourages the use “of more qualitative research including interviews, longitudinal studies, and action research”.

A mixed method approach can effectively address both exploratory and confirmatory questions (Venkatesh, Brown and Bala, 2013). In this study, the researcher adopted two different approaches. Initially, in the qualitative phase, the researcher employed a case study design using semi-structured interviews to build an initial understanding of the research objectives. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016), semi-structured qualitative interviews offer a more in-depth

understanding before conducting an extensive and costly survey. The generalisation of the findings are limited if the researcher uses only qualitative methods to collect data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Therefore, the researcher continued in the second phase with a survey to overcome these limitations and to confirm the qualitative findings. The online survey was conducted among B2B companies in Greece.

Additionally, Brown (2001, p. 259) argues that “you may need to decide whether it is primarily a statistical study or mainly qualitative in nature”. The researcher should decide the predominant approach. SMM in the B2B context is an underexplored area. Therefore, this study adopted a sequential exploratory mixed method approach to deeply investigate the phenomenon, answer the research questions and fulfil the study’s objectives. After completing the qualitative approach, the researcher proceeded to the quantitative approach to test or generalize the qualitative findings.

5.5 Research design

According to Tharenou, Donohue and Cooper (2007), the research design is the overall plan or structure for addressing the research objectives. Yin (2011) labelled research designs as “logical plans” that include the connections between the research objectives, the data to be collected, and the strategies for analysing the data so that the findings correspond to the research objectives. This logic also contributes to the accuracy and validity of the study. Figure 5.5 presents the schematic representation of the research design for this research:

Figure 5.5: Research design map for this research (source: by the researcher)

5.5.1 Systematic literature review

The first stage of the research design was the systematic literature review. According to Tranfield, Denyer and Smart (2003, p. 209), systematic literature reviews (SLR):

...differ from traditional narrative reviews by adopting a replicable, scientific and transparent process, in other words a detailed technology, that aims to minimize bias through exhaustive literature searches of published and unpublished studies and by providing an audit trail of the reviewers' decisions, procedures and conclusions.

According to Rousseau, Manning and Denyer (2008, p. 500), SLRs are “systematic and replicable, giving confidence to the users it informs regarding the status of present knowledge on a given question”. These SLRs involve a specific process for identifying, selecting, evaluating, and synthesizing prior research (Boell and Cecez-Kecmanovic, 2014). Atkins and Louw (2000) suggested the first SLR in IS, and Okoli and Schabram (2010) authored the original guidelines for SLRs in IS.

According to Bimrose, Barnes and Brown (2005), research questions and objectives can serve as a search strategy to generate keywords and phrases as search strings. For this systematic literature review, a series of phases were used, including but not limited to:

- *Searching*: a systematic search was conducted to identify potentially relevant studies
- *Screening*: the titles and abstracts were searched using inclusion and exclusion criteria
- *Data-extraction*: the inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to conduct an in-depth examination of the studies and to assess the quality of the study.
- *Synthesis*: the creation of a framework for analysing data and identifying key subjects
- *Reporting and dissemination*: presenting the literature review findings

1. Searching

In the first phase, the researcher searched for relevant research papers, reports, and policy documents about SMM in the B2B context. The researcher accessed documents through electronic databases and websites such as Google Scholar, Emerald, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect, among others (Table 5.4). As a result, studies on the role of SM in other fields and sectors, such as politics, management, or education, were excluded. The databases used for the SLR are below.

Table 5.4: Systematic Literature Review Database Used

Systematic Literature Review Database Used	
Emerald	Sage Journals
Science Direct	Springer Link
Google Scholar	Taylor & Francis
Web of Science	Wiley Online

Keywords were from the research objectives used as research strings. Table 5.5 provides a list of the keywords used in the SLR.

Table 5.5: Systematic Literature keyword search

Systematic Literature Review Search Strings and Keyword	
String Number	Keywords
1	Social media
2	Social media marketing
3	Social media marketing (AND) Business-to-Business Marketing
4	Social media marketing (AND) B2B Marketing
5	Social media marketing (AND) industrial context
6	Social media marketing (AND) adoption (OR) factors
7	Social media marketing (AND) Greece
8	Social media marketing (AND) factors (AND) B2B (AND) adoption (AND) use
9	Social media marketing (AND) benefits
10	Social media marketing (AND) barriers

2. Screening

Using a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria, the researcher evaluated all search string results. The use of inclusion and exclusion criteria can ensure that the literature review results are objective and unbiased (Bimrose, Barnes and Brown, 2005). The SLR contains only English-written, peer-reviewed studies published after 2006 about SMM in the B2B context. Web 2.0, identified in 2004, describes the technological advancements that made SM and social networking possible (Edosomwan *et al.*, 2011). YouTube, Facebook, and Yahoo launched in 2005, but with limited user access, Twitter followed in 2006. By 2006, these and other SM and networking platforms became widely accessible and rapidly grew in popularity and use. By the mid-2000s, businesses realised the potential of SM and began experimenting with SMM, leading to an increase in SMM research across business contexts (Edosomwan *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, the researcher excluded studies conducted before 2006 to ensure the SLR captures the evolution of business SM adoption and use of only the current trending SM platforms, such as Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter etc.

As a result, this practice identifies potential gaps in the present literature. Table 5.6 presents the inclusion and exclusion criteria for this study:

Table 5.6: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for the SLR

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Studies written in English	Studies not written in English
Studies on SMM in the B2B context	Studies about other areas of SMM or within other contexts
Studies published after 2006	Studies published prior to 2006
Peer-review publications	Non-peer reviewed publications and publications on grey literature

3. *Data extraction*

The researcher created a framework to extract, assess and analyse the data from the selected studies (Table 5.7) since it reduces the likelihood of any bias from the processes that mediate the research process and production. The framework includes the following sections: bibliographic information, the focus of the study, methodology, findings, and analysis (adapted from Bimrose, Barnes and Brown, 2005).

Table 5.7: Data extraction instrument

1. Bibliographical Information
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Author (s)• Date of publication
2. Focus of the study
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Main topics• Theoretical perspective• Demographics statistics of participants and population
3. Methodology
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Type of study• Sampling strategy• Data collection methods
4. Findings

4. *Synthesis*

Of the four hundred ten (410) articles found through the keyword search, the researcher examined seventy-five (75) articles based on the title. The researcher screened the article titles and abstracts using the inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 5.6). The researcher also read through the article citations and references to determine if the article met the inclusion criteria. The final list of documents included forty-two (42) journal articles published between 2006-2021. The inclusion criteria confined studies to those published in established and peer-reviewed journals written and reviewed by field experts before publication to insure the validity and quality of the study. To maintain homogeneity and consistency, conference papers, book chapters, Master's and PhD

dissertations were excluded. The researcher meticulously examined and synthesised the selected studies from the perspective of SM in B2B contexts and current empirical knowledge.

The literature review shows that our knowledge about SM use in B2B contexts is predominantly the result of quantitative research, as there are few qualitative and mixed-method studies.

5. Reporting and dissemination

Researchers can report and disseminate research findings from a systematic literature review using a descriptive or thematic analysis (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003).

5.6 Data collection

This section presents the two phases of the data collection process. In the first phase, a qualitative research method was employed to collect primary data from semi-structured interviews from employees of the case study company. In the second phase, a quantitative online survey was chosen over other methods for collecting data for this study.

5.6.1 Qualitative study

Following an examination of the study's research design in the preceding sections, this section outlines the actions related to the qualitative research (phase one). Figure 5.6 illustrates the qualitative research process:

Figure 5.6: The Qualitative phase

5.6.1.1 Data collection- Qualitative

In the first phase, a case study provided a baseline understanding of the phenomenon, regarding the adoption of SMM in the B2B context. The researcher conducted eleven (11) semi-structured interviews with employees from different levels and departments (B2B marketing, Social Media, and Digital Marketing department) within the case study company. These interviews enabled the researcher to qualitatively explore employees' perception of the adoption of SMM in the B2B context. The semi-structured interviews fulfilled two (2) objectives,

on one hand, the researcher wants to know the informant's perspective on the issue; on the other, they also want to know whether the informant can confirm insights and information the researcher already holds (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2011, p. 258).

According to Bulearca and Bulearca (2010), the semi-structured interviews are more suitable for SM use in a B2B context because it remains an unexplored area and the interviewee has more experience since the researcher is not as familiar with the subject. The researcher developed a preliminary conceptual framework from the literature review and the integration of the DOI Theory (Rogers, 1995), the TOE framework (DePietro, Wiarda and Fleischer, 1990) and the Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010). This conceptual framework includes the factors suggested to impact the adoption of SMM in the industrial context, which the researcher used to inform on the creation of the interview guide and later referenced during qualitative analysis. This exploratory phase aimed to identify the technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural determinants influencing the adoption decision.

The researcher created an interview guide (see Appendix A) based on the conceptual framework to establish the main questions and themes during the interviews. Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2011, p. 266) argue that the interview guide works as "a memory list to the interviewer to ensure that the same issues are addressed in every interview". Table 5.8 presents the main themes and constructs from the literature review used as links to formulate the interview questions and includes the key references.

Table 5.8: Interview instrument

Theme	Constructs	Key references
Technological	Relative advantage	Premkumar and Roberts (1999)
	Compatibility	Shaltoni (2017)
	Complexity	Alshamaila, Papagiannidis and Stamati (2013)
Organisational	Size	Mikalef and Pateli (2017)
	Top management support	Low, Chen and Wu (2011)
	Employee knowledge	Alshamaila, Papagiannidis and Li (2012)
	Innovativeness	Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou (2020)
Environmental	Competitive pressure	Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin (2018)
	Government support	Dahnil <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Cultural		Prim <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Benefits		Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011)
Barriers		Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen (2014)

5.6.1.2 Sampling

A qualitative study requires a small sample “because of the detailed and intensive work required for the study” (Anderson, 2010, p. 4). Participant selection involved purposeful sampling and willingness to participate to use also “snowball sampling” by identifying other possible participants who may fit the study criteria (Marshall, 1996). The researcher found that all SM and Business-to-Business marketing department employees were relevant to this study. The intent was to interview essential employees with familiarity and experience in the B2B and SMM field. At the end of recruitment, nine (9) interviews were from purposive sampling, and two (2) were from snowballing sampling.

To begin exploring the employee perspective, seven (7) interviews were conducted in April 2019, three (3) in July 2019 and one (1) in October 2019. The first ten (10) interviews were conducted in available rooms at the company’s offices and the final interview was conducted via Skype. Each

participant received an informed consent document informing them of relevant information about the study. Participants gave the researcher consent prior to each interview. Interviews were audio-recorded using a digital recorder and the researcher's personal smartphone as a backup. Following the suggestion of Jacob and Furgerson (2012), the researcher took only brief notes to maintain eye contact with the interviewees. The first interview lasted 2.5 hours, while the remaining interviews ranged in time between approximately 45 and 60 minutes. Building a rapport with interview participants may result in fuller responses (Jacob and Furgerson, 2012); the researcher, therefore, began each interview with casual social conversation to develop a positive relationship with the participant (Majid *et al.*, 2017). Participants answered the same set of questions, and the interviews were conducted in Greek with frequent use of English terminology around the topic of SM.

After each session, the researcher assigned participants a unique code to ensure their anonymity and maintain participant confidentiality. After the interviews, the researcher transcribed the interview responses verbatim and managed and coded the data.

In total, participants answered twenty-five (25) questions, including demographic questions, the impact of DOI and TOE factors on the decision to adopt SM, and benefits and barriers to adopting SM for a B2B organisation. The questions also included technological, organisational, and environmental issues. Additionally, one question was exploratory, related to the impact of Greek culture on the decision to adopt SMM.

5.6.1.3 Ethical considerations

According to Ritchie *et al.* (2013, p. 78) ethical considerations are the “heart” of high-quality research. In addition, Orb, Eisenhauer and Wynaden (2001, p. 93) asserts

the research process creates tension between the aims of research to make generalisations for the good of others, and the rights of participants to maintain privacy. Ethics pertains to doing good and avoiding harm.

The researcher followed appropriate ethical principles to prevent or reduce participants' "harm" (Orb, Eisenhauer and Wynaden, 2001). Before data collection, the researcher submitted a written application to Research Ethics Committee at the Business School of the University of the West of Scotland. The research was granted ethical approval (see Appendix D). The second step was to solicit permission to engage with employees from the Greek telecommunication company, which the researcher did by sending a formal letter to the Human Resources department and the Senior Manager of the B2B Marketing department. The researcher received company consent via email.

Additionally, the researcher secured participant informed consent before authorising their inclusion in the study (Ritchie *et al.*, 2013). The semi-structured individual interviews began with a brief verbal explanation of the study, and participants received a written information sheet (DeJonckheere and Vaughn, 2019) (Appendix B). This document stated the study's purpose, described their role as a participant, explained what happens to the data, details how the researcher intends to secure and dispose of the data, outlines how confidentiality will be maintained and documents their right to withdraw their consent at any time (Greener, 2008). In addition, the participants signed a brief statement referring to this documentation, the consent form. The documents were in Greek (Appendix C) with an English version attached. The researcher used a coding strategy to assign participants a pseudonym to protect participant confidentiality (Table 5.5).

The researcher sent an email containing the online survey link to all possible participants for the quantitative phase of the study (Appendix E). The online survey included an orienting paragraph

detailing the same information that interview participants received. Instead of informed consent to participate in the online survey, a mandatory response item restricted participant access until they gave consent through selecting that they understood their rights, role, and the study's purpose. Participants could withdraw by ending the survey or closing the tab. The informed consent document and mandatory response item ensured the researcher secured participant consent before data collection. Additionally, participants were reminded of their rights and given instructions on how to withdraw from participation.

5.6.1.4 Pilot study

Through the qualitative interviews, the researcher gathered detailed, rich information that promoted an understanding of participants' experiences. However, conducting interviews is difficult for inexperienced researchers, and piloting for an interview is a valuable and integral aspect of conducting qualitative research (Majid *et al.*, 2017). The researcher conducted a pilot study with two (2) Greek B2B owners and two (2) academics to test the questions, gain experience with interviewing, and examine the study design. The pilot study increases the study's reliability and validity through acquiring participants' feedback and gaining confidence in conducting interviews (Bulearca and Bulearca, 2010). According to Bryman and Bell (2015), the pilot study should be with people who share commonalities with the sample but are not eligible for participation. The pilot study results identify what improvements are necessary to meet the study's purpose (Majid *et al.*, 2017). The interviews were approximately forty (40) to forty-five (45) minutes. The pilot study improved the researcher's confidence and helped the researcher learn the interviewing skills, practice building rapport with informants, and understand the flow of the conversation. Additionally, the pilot study led to revisions and refinement of the interview guide, as some questions were rephrased or reordered.

5.6.1.5 Interviews

Moser and Kalton (1971, p. 271) described interviews as “a conversation between interviewer and respondent with the purpose of eliciting certain information from the respondent”. One significant advantage of interviews is their adaptability (Bell, 2009). Participants’ tone of voice, facial expressions, and other non-verbal indicators provided the researcher information only attainable through face-to-face interviews and not through written questionnaire responses. On the other hand, interviews are time-consuming and as Bell (2009, p. 178) suggested “...it is a highly subjective technique and therefore there is always the danger of bias”.

This study carried out face-to-face interviews with the researcher and the interviewees. The semi-structured interviews allowed for probing and clarification of issues that arose. Since the researcher conducted semi-structured interviews, the interview agenda was pre-determined. However, the semi-structured interview approach allowed the researcher to probe and gather additional data from participants.

The semi-structured interviews included many open-ended questions to generate discussions, to explore informants’ thoughts, feelings and beliefs (DeJonckheere and Vaughn, 2019) and to explore new factors (Bell, 2009) absent from current literature. The semi-structured interviews results led to an update framework that reflected the reality of SMM adoption by B2B organisations. Therefore, the researcher used the interview to clarify and generate the hypotheses and develop and structure the online survey.

5.6.2 Analysis of the qualitative data

5.6.2.1 Participants

The first step in qualitative data analysis reporting is presenting the demographic characteristics of the interview participants (Table 6.1). The characteristics of the interviewees are in Table 5.5.

Participant demographics obtained include gender, educational level, job title, department, and years of employment with their company. The following abbreviations are used in Table 5.5:

1. **Participant:** “P” stands for the interview participant
2. **Gender:** “M” stands for male and “F” for female
3. **Education level:** the level of education the participant has attained
4. **Job Title:** The position held by the participant in the company
5. **Department:** the participants belong in two different departments: the B2B Marketing Communications and the Social Media department. The last participant belongs to the DigitalMarketing4U which operates as a digital agency for other companies.

Table 5.9 below summarises the demographic characteristics of the interview participants.

Table 5.9: Participants demographic characteristics (source: by the researcher)

No	Gender	Education level	Job Title	Department	Years in the company	Interview duration
P1	Female	MBA	Senior Manager- B2B Marketing Communication	B2B Marketing	19	2h 30 min
P2	Female	MBA	Senior Product Manager- Above the Line Business Communication	B2B Marketing	20	50 min
P3	Male	MBA	Brand Manager- Above the Line Business Communication	B2B Marketing	15	1h 5 min
P4	Female	MSc in Marketing	Section Manager- Above the Line Business Communication	B2B Marketing	15	45 min
P5	Female	MSc in Marketing	Section Manager- Below the Line Business Communication	B2B Marketing	14	48 min

P6	Female	BA(Hons) in Advertising	Senior Product Manager- Below the Line Business Communication	B2B Marketing	20	46min
P7	Male	MSc in eCommerce	Section Manager- Online Marketing and Social Media	Social Media	1	1 hour
P8	Female	MSc in Media Communications	Senior Manager- Online Marketing and Social Media	Social Media	2	58 min
P9	Female	MSc in Web Design	Section Manager- Online Marketing and Social Media	Social Media	17	45 min
P10	Female	MSc in Marketing and Communications	Brand Manager- eCommerce and Websites	B2B Marketing	20	45 min
P11	Male	BA(Hons) in Computer Sciences	Senior Manager- DigitalMarketing4U	Digital Marketing	12	1hour

As documented in Table 5.5, this study had eight (8) female and three (3) male participants. All participants have higher education degrees; the majority have Master level degrees (MBA or MSc). Seven (7) participants are working in the Business-to-Business Marketing department, while three (3) are in the Social Media Department. The last participant is currently the Junior Manager of the Digital Marketing Department which runs SM campaigns for other companies.

In the first phase, data resulted from semi-structured interviews with eleven (11) employees of the case study telecommunication company. The following section contains two subsections. The first subsection describes thematic analysis, while the second subsection details the data analysis process for creating groups and themes from interview data.

5.6.2.2 Thematic analysis

As mentioned in section 5.5 (Figure 5.5) the researcher used Thematic Analysis (TA) to analyse qualitative interview data from the first phase of the study. According to Rice and Ezzy (1999, p.

258) TA is the process of identifying themes through “careful reading and re-reading of the data”. This process is a way to recognise data patterns in which developed themes (or codes) become the categories of analysis (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006; Roberts *et al.*, 2019). Boyatzis (1998, p. 1) advocates that a “good code” captures the phenomenon’s qualitative richness. Moreover, a theme is

a pattern in the information that at minimum describes and organises the possible observations and at a maximum interprets aspects of the phenomenon (Boyatzis, 1998, p. 161).

According to these types of analysis, understanding the entire data set require studying the parts; however, the parts cannot be understood apart from the whole (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010). The TA approach to qualitative analysis entails identifying themes relevant to the research focus, context, objectives, and theoretical framework and allows data to be described and interpreted for meaning (Roberts *et al.*, 2019, p. 1). TA is a frequently and widely used method to analyse qualitative data in various research fields, including the IS area (Braun and Clarke, 2006). For example, Rowley and Holliman (2014) used TA to analyse the interview data that was collected to investigate manager’s perceptions about B2B digital content marketing. This study used the TA technique to analyse the qualitative data based on the advantages identified by Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 97) (Table 5.10).

Table 5.10: Advantages of Thematic Analysis, adapted from Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 97)

	Advantages
1	Flexibility
2	It is a relatively simple and quick method to learn and implement
3	Researchers with little or no experience in qualitative research can use it
4	The results are generally available to the educated general public
5	A useful method for dealing with participants as partners in the participatory research paradigm
6	Can provide a useful summary of key features of a large body of data, and/or a “thick description” of the data set
7	Can provide unexpected insights
8	Allows both social and psychological data interpretation
9	Can be helpful for qualitative analyses that assist policy development

Thematic analysis is a flexible, versatile method capable of meeting the needs of numerous studies, and providing rich detailed accounts of complex data (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). However, when developing themes based on research data, this flexibility can lead to inconsistency and incoherence in findings (Holloway and Todres, 2003). According to King (2004), TA is a valuable method for investigating the perspectives of various research participants, emphasising similarities and differences, and yielding unexpected results.

The employment of TA allowed the researcher to identify and interpret interviewees’ perceptions of the factors influencing a Greek B2B organisation to adopt SMM and the perceived benefits and barriers. There are three types of thematic analysis: inductive, deductive, and hybrid. In the inductive or “bottom-up” approach (Braun and Clarke, 2006), the categories and themes are data-driven (Boyatzis, 1998). Thus, it is a process of coding data that does not attempt to fit it into an already existing coding frame or the researcher’s analytic preconceptions (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p. 83). The deductive approach frequently employs a priori set of codes, theoretically derived, to categorise the data (Crabtree and Miller, 1999). In hybrid analysis, the researcher integrates data-

driven and theory-driven codes to analyse the qualitative data (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006; Xu and Zammit, 2020).

This study adopted a hybrid approach to TA (both deductive and inductive) to analyse the interview data and to create the main themes and subthemes. Firstly, the research aim, the research objectives, and the conceptual framework (TOE and cultural framework) guided the interview questions. The main contexts of the conceptual framework (technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural) were identified deductively and used to “produce a set of a priori or pre-empirical codes” (Swain, 2018, p. 4). Secondly, the researcher inductively analysed data to discover themes and subthemes from within the qualitative interview data. Through inductive analysis, “theory was both a precursor to, and an outcome of, the data analysis” (Swain, 2018, p. 5). The following subsection presents the steps followed in this study for conducting the TA analysis of the collected interview data.

5.6.2.3 Data analysis process

The TA of interview data in this study built upon the general procedures of qualitative analysis suggested by Miles and Huberman (1994). Previous researchers have successfully used the work of Miles and Huberman for the qualitative analysis of a case study research (Atkinson, 2002). The interview techniques are commonly used as part of the case study method to answer “how” and “why” type research questions (Atkinson, 2002). According to Miles and Huberman (1994), the focal point of a case study is a series of propositions, which can be from reviewing the research objectives or interpreting data from the existing literature. These propositions support the development of case studies because they contribute to developing case study questions and serve as the foundation to develop the initial codes for the case study analysis (Atkinson, 2002). Figure

5.7 presents the “Codes and Coding” technique proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994), for linking the data back to research objectives.

Figure 5.7: Case study structure, adapted from Atkinson (2002, p.2)

Although the strategies for collecting data using such techniques are well defined, one of the major issues associated with any research is determining how to interpret the resulting data (Coffey and Atkinson, 1996). Miles and Huberman (1994, p. 10-12) suggested a three-step systematic approach to data analysis including (Figure 5.8): data reduction, data display and conclusion drawing and verification.

Figure 5.8: Data analysis process (Miles and Huberman, 1994, p. 12)

Before data analysis, the researcher transcribed and translated the interviews. The researcher listened to the eleven (11) audio-recorded interviews several times to transcribe the interviews verbatim, resulting in data familiarisation following the repeated listening and manually transcribing and translating the interviews. The researcher translated all the interviews from Greek into English. A Greek certified English teacher proofread the translated transcripts to verify that the English transcripts' language and linguistic features were correct.

The interview transcriptions and translations resulted in a considerable amount of textual data. The researcher imported all transcriptions into NVivo software, a qualitative software analyses program and analysed the data following Miles and Huberman's three (3) step data analysis process (Figure 5.8).

Step 1: Data reduction

The first step is data reduction. Data reduction is “the process of selecting, focusing, simplifying, abstracting and transforming the data that appear in written-up field notes or transcriptions” (Miles and Huberman, 1994, p. 10). The research objectives, data collection methods, and the study's conceptual framework guided the data reduction process (Simons, 2009). This study followed

three (3) procedures to reduce the data: familiarising with the data, identifying different themes and subthemes, and creating codes (Figure 5.9).

Figure 5.9: Data reduction process

As mentioned in the previous subsection, the transcription, translation and reading of the interview data helped the researcher to have prior knowledge of the data. These processes helped the researcher to:

- i) become familiar with the breadth and depth of the content (Braun and Clarke, 2006),
- ii) learn what participants said in each interview transcript (Braun and Clarke, 2006),
- iii) generate an initial list of ideas and identify data that relates to the research objectives and conceptual framework (Miles and Huberman, 1994), and
- iv) search for potential emerging patterns in the interview data (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The next phase involves identifying potential themes. As previously mentioned, the interview questions were developed and guided by previous research and the initial conceptual framework (Figure 3.4). The conceptual framework included four (4) different contexts based on the TOE

framework (technological, organisational, and environmental context) and the cultural context. Additionally, through the literature review, the researcher identified a list of benefits and barriers for addressing research objectives three (3) and four (4). Therefore, the researcher used six (6) primary themes to categorise deductively the interview data (Crabtree and Miller, 1999), namely technological, organisational, environmental and cultural contexts, benefits and barriers (Table 5.11).

Table 5.11: Main themes classification

	Themes
1	Technological Context
2	Organisational Context
3	Environmental Context
4	Cultural Context
5	Benefits
6	Barriers

The next phase involved the creation of the initial codes. According to Saldana (2016, p. 4),

a code in qualitative inquiry is most often a word or short phrase that symbolically assigns a summative, salient, essence-capturing, and/or evocative attribute for a portion of language-based or visual data.

The coding process allows for reorganisation of the data into groups for subsequent stages of analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). There are three (3) specific code sources (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016, p. 582):

- codes supported by data often referred to as “in vivo” codes
- researcher-developed codes that describe a specific unit of data, and
- codes founded in theory and literature, known as “a priori” codes.

Regarding the “a priori” codes in this study, nine (9) initial codes (also referred as subthemes) were identified based on the initial conceptual framework and the interview guide. The subthemes then aligned on the four (4) first themes (Table 5.7). The first theme (the technological context) included relative advantage, compatibility, and complexity, while the second theme (the organisational context) corresponded with company size, top management support, employee knowledge and innovativeness. Finally, the environmental context theme included competitor pressure and external support.

Regarding the “in vivo” codes that developed from the interview data, nine (9) new subthemes were coded and connected to the themes. The technological context included trialability, interactivity and image and the environmental context included external support. Finally, in the cultural context coded power distance, collectivism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance, and short-term orientation. Table 5.12 includes the eighteen (18) identified and emerged subthemes associated with the four (4) themes.

Table 5.12: Subthemes

No	Themes	Codes	Abbreviations
1	Technological	Relative Advantage	RA
2		Compatibility	CMP
3		Complexity	CMX
4		Interactivity*	INT
5		Trialability*	TRA
6		Image *	IMG
7	Organizational	Size	SIZ
8		Top management support	TMS
9		Employee knowledge	EPK
10		Innovativeness	INV
11	Environ-mental	Competitor pressure	CMP
12		Government support	GVS

13	Cultural	External support*	EXS
14		Power distance*	PWD
15		Collectivism*	IND
16		Masculinity*	MSC
17		Uncertainty avoidance*	UAV
18		Short-term orientation*	LTOR

Two (2) more themes, namely benefits and barriers, are included in the codebook to analyse the qualitative data. The table below lists the subthemes developed from data analysis coded under the benefits themes, and the subsequent table presents the subthemes under the barriers theme.

Table 5.13: Identified benefits

	Theme	Subthemes
1	Benefits	Interaction- engagement
2		Brand awareness
3		Performance
4		Sales
5		Communication
6		Customer care service
7		Cost-effective
8		Effective targeting
9		Promotion
10		Reach
11		Understanding customers' buying behaviour
12		e-Word of Mouth and building a community
13		Thought Leadership

Table 5.14: Identified barriers

	Theme	Subthemes
1	Barriers	Lack of knowledge of how to use them
2		Company's internal bureaucracy and complicated structure
3		Financial- budget
4		GDPR restrictions
5		Lack of ROI measurement
6		Negative comments- feedback
7		Lack of SM strategy
8		Lack of relevance with B2B sector

Step 2: Data display

According to Miles and Huberman (1994), creating data displays is the second step of this data analysis process. In this step, the data are organised and assembled into “summary diagrammatic or visual displays” (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016, p. 614), helping the researcher organise the summarised data into manageable, compact forms, such as matrices, tables, graphs or networks for generating conclusions (Miles and Huberman, 1994). Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) described matrices as tabular in shape with defined rows and columns where data are entered purposefully into the appropriate cells of such a matrix to make future data analysis easier.

This study relied primarily on tables for displaying the data and communicating the findings. Table 5.15 presents an example of how the researcher developed the codebook for analysing the technological context. Chapter 6 includes additional tables that report the findings.

Table 5.15: Coding frequency for analysing the Technological Context (source: researcher, 2020)

Name	Description	Files	References
TECHNOLOGICAL CONTEXT	Technological factors influencing the adoption of SM	11	77
Relative Advantage*	The adoption of SM gives a relative advantage to the company	11	11
Compatibility*	SM are compatible with the company's existing infrastructure and information systems	11	11
Complexity*	The adoption of SM is not complex for the company	11	11
Trialability**	The company tries different things on SM before using them	2	3
Interactivity**	SM help the company to interact with its business partners	11	12
Image**	The adoption and use of SM increases the image of the company	10	17

Figures are another example of a data display. The researcher used a word cloud of the study to demonstrate the frequency of key terms used by the interview participants.

Figure 5.12: An example of text search query (screenshot from NVivo12)

Step 3: Drawing and verifying conclusions

The final step is to identify the final meanings of the qualitative data represented in the data displays. Miles and Huberman (1994, p. 245-246) proposed thirteen (13) approaches for using a data display to generate conclusions. Briefly, these tactics include:

- 1) noting patterns and themes;
- 2) seeing plausibility;
- 3) clustering;
- 4) making metaphors;
- 5) counting;
- 6) making contrasts/comparisons;
- 7) partitioning variables;
- 8) subsuming particulars into the general;
- 9) factoring;
- 10) noting relations between variables;
- 11) finding intervening variables;
- 12) building a logical chain of evidence and
- 13) making conceptual/theoretical coherence.

This researcher used the qualitative data to understand the factors influencing a B2B company to adopt SM and the perceived benefits and barriers. The outcomes of these findings led to the refinement of the initial conceptual framework. The updated conceptual framework (presented in Chapter 6, see Figure 6.6) guided the development of the research instrument for the quantitative second phase of the study.

For the verification of the conclusions, the aim is to confront the quality of the study. Several researchers have used different criteria to evaluate the qualitative research's quality and trustworthiness (e.g., Emden *et al.*, 2001; Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2014). The following subsection presents the criteria used in this study to evaluate the trustworthiness of the qualitative analysis.

5.6.2.4 Evaluation of qualitative research

Qualitative research concerns trustworthiness and not reliability or validity (Shenton, 2004). Guba (1981) asserted four criteria for trustworthiness: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Credibility assesses the study's internal validity, which refers to whether the study accurately presents participant experiences and perceptions (Shenton, 2004). The researcher enhanced the study's credibility by informing participants of their rights and right to withdraw, role in the study, and study's purpose, which are strategies that promote participant honesty and openness. Additionally, the researcher conducted semi-structured individual interviews following a pre-written interview protocol, so participants answered the same questions, although the probing questions varied.

The transferability criteria for trustworthiness corresponds with external validity or whether findings apply to other studies (Shenton, 2004). The researcher outlined the inclusion criterion for participation, described participants in detail, and elucidated characteristics of the case study

company, which Stake (1995) contends are strategies for increasing transferability. The selection of a homogenous sample enhances transferability, as findings may be applicable to other studies when researchers compare sample characteristics.

In qualitative research, dependability relates to reliability and is associated with credibility (Guba and Lincoln, 1985). Dependability is about the researcher's chosen design and implementation (Shenton, 2004). This researcher conducted a mixed method study collecting qualitative data through semi-structured individual interviews with eleven (11) participants that met eligibility requirements. The inclusion of eleven (11) participants of interviews increases the study's dependability, as Yin (2017) and Sandelowski (2000) asserted that 10-16 interviews should result in data saturation, as further interviewing conducting will not yield new information. Interviews generated sufficient data to explore the phenomenon fully, which led to the refinement of the conceptual framework model. The researcher adhered to a pre-established process for data analyses. These strategies increase the study's dependability.

Confirmability, the final criteria for evaluating the trustworthiness of qualitative research, refers to the researcher's objectiveness throughout data collection and analyses (Patton, 2015). The researcher employed strategies to enhance the study's confirmability, including expert panel validation and piloting the interviews and survey before data collection. Reflexivity also promotes confirmability. The researcher engaged in reflexivity by verifying that the qualitative results section accurately reflects participant contributions to the study and not the researcher's thoughts or perceptions. Further, the researcher detailed the data collection and analysis processes, increasing this study's confirmability by explicitly explaining the researcher's actions (Patton, 2015).

5.6.3 Quantitative study

5.6.3.1 Online survey

As explained in the research design, section 5.5, the second research phase, was quantitative, in which an online survey was distributed to a larger sample of participants to validate the conceptual model presented in the following chapter (Chapter 6).

Quantitative methods include survey designs and experiments (Creswell, 2009). A survey can capture numeric descriptions of trends or opinions from a sample without conducting a controlled experiment to test the effect of a treatment or intervention on a group. The researcher collected quantitative data from the survey and analysed it using descriptive and inferential statistics (see Chapter 7).

The purpose of a survey is to “questioning individuals on a topic or topics and then describing their responses” (Jackson, 2011, p.17). The choice of a survey seems appropriate since this research phase required a deductive research approach (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019) to test the hypotheses developed in the first phase, the qualitative phase (Chapter 6).

A survey typically involves administering a questionnaire to gather data to test specific hypotheses on a large sample of people and measure several independent variables and one (1) or more dependent variables (Tharenou, Donohue and Cooper, 2007, p.46). Therefore, a survey aims to assess the correlations (relationships) between independent and dependent variables. According to Rindfleisch and Antia (2012), researchers commonly distributed B2B surveys through mail; however, an increasing number of B2B surveys are being managed online (Ramani and Kumar, 2008). Additionally, Poynter (2004), cited in Evans and Mathur (2005), asserts that B2B respondents’ accessibility is limited; therefore, online surveys are the predominant data source in quantitative research. An increasing number of related studies, including SMM research (Pentina,

Koh and Le, 2012; Iankova *et al.*, 2018), reflect the rising popularity of online surveys in quantitative research. Therefore, an online survey was selected as an appropriate method for collecting quantitative data and testing the research hypotheses developed in the following Chapter 6.

Due to many benefits of distributing online surveys, scholars assert that online surveys are more appropriate for collecting quantitative data than other survey methods. In their study, Evans and Mathur (2005) summarised online surveys' main strengths and potential weaknesses (Figure 5.13). The strengths include global reach, convenience, speed and flexibility, technological innovations; ease of data entry, analysis; and communication follow-ups, low administration cost; controlled sampling; access to a large sample for recruitment, question diversity, control of question ordering, control of answer formatting and required questions and knowledge of respondent vs. non respondent characteristics.

Figure 5.13: Strengths and potential weaknesses of online surveys, adapted from Evans and Mathur (2005, p. 197)

Online surveys are flexible, versatile, and easy to distribute. Researchers can distribute online surveys via email by including an access link to the survey URL or embedding the survey in the body of the email, among other distribution strategies (Evans and Mathur, 2005). Also, participants can choose a time convenient for them to sufficiently consider and respond to each question (Hogg, 2003). Given the vast availability of online survey software, online surveys can be “automatically placed into the database, and then tabulated and analysed in a coordinated, integrated manner that

greatly reduces costs” (Evans and Mathur, 2005, p. 199). Further, reputable online survey generators, such as Google forms and SurveyMonkey, simplify survey creation and distribution; provide a user-friendly, efficient form to elicit feedback and responses; and embed data analyses tools. Additionally, many survey generators are free of charge, although some offer additional features for a cost.

In this study, the researcher used Qualtrics, an advanced and sophisticated quantitative analysis software free through the University’s account. The Qualtrics software is mobile compatible and allows respondents to save their progress and resume from their save point.

According to Evans and Mathur (2005), there are potential weaknesses of online surveys. These weaknesses include sample attribute, sample selection and implementation, respondent experience and technical skills, clarity of questions and survey instructions for completion, privacy, low response rate and the impersonal nature of online respondent- only surveys. Online surveys hinder the researcher’s ability to: verify sample attributes, confirm that only intended respondents are completing the surveys, offer technical support, answer questions, or clarify instruction, guarantee privacy during survey completion, and encourage participation through human presence. The risk of a low response rate is the most significant weakness of online surveys (Kaplowitz *et al.*, 2012; Blair, Czaja and Blair, 2014).

Researchers assert that survey studies in the B2B context typically have lower than average response rates of 20-45% (Palmatier, 2008; Ganesan, Malter and Rindfleisch, 2005). A low response rate may cause a nonresponse bias and limit the researcher’s ability to make valid inferences (Schaeffer, Seltzer and Klawitter, 1991). Most B2B surveys reach a smaller sample of people or companies and may be causing a lower response rate. This weakness may challenge a researcher’s ability to utilise analytical procedures such as moderate regression analysis and

structural equation modelling (Cohen *et al.*, 2002). Consequently, “B2B scholars should design surveys that minimize the risk of nonresponse bias and assess the degree of possible bias after collecting their survey data” (Rindfleisch and Antia, 2012. p. 6).

The online survey results validated and generalised the qualitative findings yielding a robust, comprehensive understanding of the identified determinants. The questionnaire findings were integrated and cross-referenced with the qualitative findings.

5.6.3.2 Sample

The initial aim of this study was to explore the adoption of SMM by the B2B organisations that operate in Greece, which necessitated the use of an official Greek business directory. The researcher used the main Greek financial directory- the ICAP Group to identify the B2B Greek companies. The ICAP is a business services company that provides financial data for more than 60,000 registered companies in Greece based on their press annual financial statements. The ICAP annual business directory is a popular accurate database in Greece used several times for research purposes (Barbosa and Louri, 2005). Consequently, the ICAP Greek Financial Guide 2018 (ICAP, 2018) database served as the sampling frame for this study and the researcher had free online access to the data. During the preparation of the data collection, the researcher identified companies having B2B activities.

The researcher pursued simple random sampling and created an Excel spreadsheet to export a list of companies who had B2B activities and met the inclusion criteria (Table 5.16). The researcher selected one company at a time and gave a number ranging from 0 to 400 companies until reached the chosen number of companies based on the random application. The spreadsheet also included the contact phone number for each company. Additional actions were needed to complete and administrate the survey. Therefore, the researcher searched through Google Search to add the

contact email address to the Excel spreadsheet. Additional, searches were conducted on SM platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and LinkedIn to identify if the companies have an online presence. The researcher obtained email addresses for survey distribution in October 2019.

Table 5.16: Research criteria for the participated companies

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Nationality	Greek	Multinational companies
Target market	B2B B2B and B2C B2G	B2C

5.6.3.3 Questionnaire design

Quantitative techniques and surveys are the most widely used approaches for researching the ICT adoption and diffusion of new innovations (Williams *et al.*, 2009). A survey generates sufficient data to assess correlations (relationships) between independent variables and the dependent variable(s) (Tharenou, Donohue and Cooper, 2007). The online survey was developed based on the literature review and interview responses. The questionnaire (Appendix F) sought to collect required data about the adoption of SMM in the B2B context and examine the independent variables and their hypothesized relationships on a company's decision to adopt SM. The study adopted a self-administered questionnaire technique. Respondents received a cover letter enclosed in the invitation email that explained the study's purpose.

The questionnaire contained five (5) sections (Table 5.17), and the unit of analysis was the respondent's company. The first section collected demographic characteristics of the respondents (Q2-Q4) and the company (Q5-Q9) and inquired about the utilisation of SMM in the respondent's company (Q10-Q16). The second part consisted of questions related to the TOE framework

(technological, organisational, and environmental context) (Q17-Q19) and Hofstede’s model (cultural context) (Q20). The third section targeted the benefits (Q21) of SMM adoption for the respondent’s company. The fourth section focused on the barriers (Q22) to SM adoption that the respondent’s company experience(d). The final section inquired about factors that might motivate the company to adopt SM (Q23-Q25).

A five-point Linkert scale anchored at one (1) (strongly disagree) and five (5) (strongly agree) was used for the questions Q17-Q25. A Likert scale provides the researcher with a broader range of possible scores, and expands the statistical analysis available (Pallant, 2016).

Table 5.17: Survey structure

Section	Area	Question (No)	No of questions
1.	Participant’s demographic characteristics	Q2-Q4	3
	Company’s demographic characteristics	Q5-Q9	5
	Questions about SM	Q10-Q16	7
2.	Technological characteristics	Q17	1 (4)
	Organisational characteristics	Q18	1(5)
	Environmental characteristics	Q19	1(7)
	Cultural characteristics	Q20	1(10)
3.	Benefits	Q21	(12)
4.	Barriers	Q22	(14)
5.	Additional questions	Q23-Q25	3
	Total	25	

5.6.3.4 Evaluation of the Quality of the Survey

The study’s validity and reliability are essential elements for measuring the accuracy and consistency of the research instrument- the online survey. By measuring the validity and reliability, the researcher can demonstrate the quality (rigour) of the study (Heale and Twycross, 2015).

Validity and reliability are intertwined; an instrument can be reliable without being valid but cannot be valid without being reliable (Tavakol and Dennick, 2011, p. 53).

Validity

Validity indicates the extent to which an instrument measures what it should be measuring (Kothari, 2004; Hardy and Bryman, 2004; Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2005). Sürücü and Maslakçı, (2020; 2696) advocate that "...validity is determined by the meaningful and appropriate interpretation of the data obtained from the measuring instrument as a result of the analyses". Essentially, validity is related to whether the research instrument measures the intended concept. There are several distinct types of validity. This research considered the two main sub-categories of validity: content and construct validity (Iacobucci and Churchill, 2009).

Content validity: According to Bollen (1989) the content validity is a qualitative form of validity and the simplest to obtain. Content validity is "...the extent to which an instrument adequately samples the research domain of interest when attempting to measure phenomena" (Wynd, Schmidt and Schaefer, 2003, p. 509). Content validity can result from a rational analysis of the instrument by experts on the research subject or familiar with the construct of interest. Content validity occurs when questions are based on relevant literature and pre-tested through a pilot study (Wilson, 2014). Hardy and Bryman (2004, p. 12) also advocate quantitative researchers to pilot test their research instruments to ensure that the collected information meets the validity and reliability criteria.

The researcher used different approaches to establish the content validity of the research instrument. Firstly, the measuring instrument included constructs based on the exploratory interviews and the literature review. Bryman (2004) suggested that new measures should reflect the concepts researchers want to measure. Secondly, as stated in Table 5.20, the researcher used constructs (questions) based on previous empirical research in the IT literature that have been

tested and validated by previous researchers which is a common and acceptable practice (Hyman, Lamb and Bulmer, 2006). Moreover, pilot testing ensured content validity for the instrument (Fraenkel and Wallen, 1993). Several specialists reviewed the questions before the researcher finalised the instrument (Wilson, 2014). Two (2) different groups pre-tested the questionnaire, which section 5.5.3.5 details. The first group included two Greek B2B owners from the sample frame and the second group included two academics. One of the academics speaks both Greek and English fluently and offered valuable insights on the translation of the questionnaires from English to Greek. Additionally, the research supervisors (with extensive research experience) provided valuable guidance and comments for designing the research instrument and adjusting the questions order and layout. Therefore, the researcher instrument's content validity was established and depended on the judgments of specialists in the sector (Kimberlin and Winterstein, 2008). The table below illustrates the different types of validity.

Table 5.18: Types of validity, adapted from (Heale and Twycross, 2015, p. 66)

Type of validity	Description
Content validity	The extent to which a research instrument accurately measures all aspects of a construct
Construct validity	The extent to which a research instrument (or tool) measures the intended construct

Construct validity: Construct validity is essential for the empirical measures and testing hypotheses to construct theories (Mohajan, 2017). It is the process of validating the interpretations about that construct as indicated by the test score (Mohajan, 2017, p. 64). According to Tharenou, Donohue and Cooper (2007, p. 155) construct validity refers "...to whether a measure relates to other measures in ways predicted by an underlying theory of the construct". There are two (2) forms of construct validity: convergent and discriminant validity (Huck, 2007).

According to Heale and Twycross (2015, p. 66), convergent validity “shows that an instrument is highly correlated with instruments measuring similar variables”. Meanwhile, divergent validity “shows that an instrument is poorly correlated to instruments that measure different variables”. Construct validity of the instrument is evaluated by correlation analysis, factor analysis, and the Multi-trait, Multi-method Matrix of correlations (Pett, Lackey and Sullivan, 2003, cited in Mohajan, 2017). In this study, the construct validity (both convergent and divergent) was evaluated using principal component factor analysis (PCA) and the Multi-trait- Multi-method Matrix. Factor analysis is used to cluster sets of variables to create a smaller set of components that still retains as much of the original information as possible (Field, 2018; Pallant, 2007). It is a statistical technique used “to determine if the theorized items for a construct converge together for convergent validity” (Premkumar and Roberts, 1999, p. 467).

The researcher used SPSS version 25 to conduct the PCA analysis on all items in the questionnaire and applied the extraction techniques and Varimax rotation method. According to Hair *et al.* (2006), factor loadings should not have cross-loadings and exceed 0.5. Based on this criterion, eigenvalues greater than 1.0 were extracted as factors, and all items were loaded into their expected factor. The extracted factors and factors loadings are in Table 5.19.

Table 5.19: Factor analysis

Constructs	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	Factor 6	Factor 7	Factor 8	Factor 9	Factor 10
RA1	.932									
RA2	.922									
RA3	.884									
RA4	.838									
RA5	.592									
INT1		.911								
INT2		.709								
INT3		.902								
IMG1			.778							
IMG2			.902							
IMG3			.950							
TMS1				.891						
TMS2				.891						
EPK1					.787					
EPK2					.948					
EPK3					.941					
CMP1						.896				
CMP2						.896				
GVS1							.877			
GVS2							.877			
EXS1								.932		
EXS2								.932		
IND1									.939	
IND2									.939	
LTOR1										.788
LTOR2										.914
LTOR3										.934

Reliability

Reliability concerns the degree to which a measure is consistent in reflecting the construct that it is measuring (Field, 2018; Hair *et al.*, 2006) and measures the internal consistency of a test or scale

(Tavakol and Dennick, 2011). **Cronbach's α** is the most widely used measure of scale reliability (Field, 2018; Cortina, 1993). It is usually taking values between 0 (no correlation) and one (1) (maximum correlation); higher coefficient indicates higher levels of reliability (Kimberlin and Winterstein, 2008). There are different reports about the cut-off points for reliability, ranging from 0.70 to 0.95 (Bland and Altman, 1997). In this study, the possible level of reliability was assigned according to 4 criteria suggested by Hinton (2004), which include: low reliability (0.50 and below); moderate reliability (0.50-0.70); high reliability (0.70-0.90) and excellent reliability (0.90 and above). As shown in Table 5.20, the Cronbach's α coefficient ranges from 0.699 to 0.895, indicating higher reliability levels.

Table 5.20: Reliability assessment of research variables

Constructs	Items	Reliability/Cronbach's alpha
Technological		
Relative advantage	5, adapted from Shaltoni (2017)	.895
Compatibility	1, adapted from Shaltoni (2017)	Categorical
Complexity	1, adapted from Shaltoni (2017)	Categorical
Trialability	1, adapted from Kendall <i>et al.</i> (2001)	Categorical
Interactivity	3, adapted from Ainin <i>et al.</i> (2015)	.788
Image	3, adapted from Al-Qirim (2007)	.840
Organizational		
Size	1, adapted from Mikalef and Pateli (2017)	Categorical
Top management support	2, adapted from Pascucci, Ancillai and Cardinali (2018)	.736
Employee knowledge	3, adapted from Alshamaila, Papagiannidis and Li (2012)	.875
Innovativeness	1, adapted from Shaltoni (2017)	Categorical
Environmental		
Competitive pressure	2, adapted from Wang <i>et al.</i> (2010)	.754
Government support	2, adapted from Abubakar <i>et al.</i> (2017)	.699
External support	2, adapted from Mikalef and Pateli (2017)	.849
Cultural		

Power distance	1, adapted from Chatzithomas <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Categorical
Individualism	2, adapted from Kollmann <i>et al.</i> (2009)	.852
Masculinity	1, adapted from Kollmann <i>et al.</i> (2009)	Categorical
Uncertainty avoidance	1, adapted from (Sundqvist, Frank and Puumalainen, 2005)	Categorical
Short term orientation	3, adapted from Özbilen (2017)	.855

5.6.3.5 Pilot study

The researcher performed a pilot study of the online survey by distributing two (2) questionnaires to B2B owners in Greece and two (2) questionnaires to academics. Participants provided their feedback in understanding and answering the questionnaire (Hair *et al.*, 2013), and the researcher applied the recommended changes. The pilot study allowed the researcher to observe respondent perceptions and reactions to the researcher-created questions. It also helped identify potential errors and problems that the researcher might not have otherwise anticipated. Two (2) questions were rewritten to improve language clarity and simplicity. The pilot study increased the internal validity of the questionnaire, ensured that the sought data was gathered, and delivered higher-quality data (Bowden *et al.*, 2002).

5.6.3.6 Questionnaire distribution

The researcher distributed the online survey as a clickable link via the survey software Qualtrics. This link, emailed to each selected company, informed them of the study's purpose and asked for their participation. To avoid misunderstanding and misinterpretation, Brace (2008), proposed that surveys should be written in a language that participants can comprehend. The questionnaire was translated into Greek to overcome linguistic and cultural differences (Dwivedi, Choudrie and Brinkman, 2006).

Therefore, the email and the questionnaire were in Greek. Along with the link, the email included a cover letter to provide the participants with sufficient information about the study and the

researcher's contact details (Kaplowitz *et al.*, 2012) (Appendix E). To incentivise participation, the researcher offered access to a report with the survey results. The researcher emailed representatives of four hundred (400) B2B Greek companies a letter inviting them to participate and complete the online survey, which generated 40 responses. Four (4) weeks after the original email to four hundred (400) B2B Greek company representatives, the researcher sent a reminder email to representatives who had not yet completed the online survey. This action resulted in ten (10) additional responses from companies.

The low response rate led to the researcher's use of online methods and SM to increase awareness of the study using alternative approaches to contacting eligible respondents. Manohar *et al.* (2018) found that online methods for participant recruitment gaining in popularity as quantitative researchers are transitioning to SM platforms. Additionally, researchers may use the word-of-mouth method for participant recruitment (Manohar *et al.*, 2018).

While the researcher purposefully selected eligible participants and contacted them directly, the researcher also used word of mouth sampling using online methods. The researcher emailed the link to trusted acquaintance with access to Greek B2B company representatives, who disseminated the survey electronically through email to their contacts. Additionally, the researcher shared the link on Facebook with additional acquaintances, which led to the further dissemination through electronic means to B2B company contacts. The distribution through word-of-mouth generated an additional thirty-two (32) responses.

Through the combination of word-of-mouth and purposeful sampling through online methods, the researcher recruited participants representing eighty-two (82) companies. However, ten (10) company surveys were incomplete and discarded. The final sample included responses from seventy-two (72) B2B Greek companies (Table 5.21).

Data collection spanned six (6) months from November 2019 to April 2020. Data recruitment and collection occurred concurrently with the global pandemic in March and April, which led to Greek B2B company closures. It is possible that invitations sent to participants during these months were overlooked or discarded, given the urgency in responding to COVID-19.

Table 5.21: Survey responses

Data collection	Number of responses	Percent of responses
Responses	82	100%
Valid	72	87,8%
Non- valid	10	12,2%
Total responses for analysis	72	

5.6.3.7 Data analysis techniques

The researcher used SPSS Statistics software (version 25) for storing, coding, and analysing the survey data. All survey questions were encoded and entered into SPSS. The researcher used several statistical techniques to analyse the survey data: PCA, Cronbach's α , Goodness-of-fit, Pearson's Correlation and binary Logistic Regression (see Chapter 7). All the selected data (questionnaires, emails, interviews) were stored in University's OneDrive server. The encoded data in SPSS and NVIVO will remain stored in the researcher's personal computer with password protection for one year after completing the study.

5.7 Summary

In summary, this chapter focused on discussing the research design and methodology adopted in this study. It started by identifying pragmatism as the adopted research philosophy and followed by explaining the research approach. Both interpretivist and positivist research approaches were justified, leading to a mixed method strategy to collect the data. It also presented the use of sequential exploratory mixed method as the selected research design and outlined the two phases

of the study. Additionally, the researcher detailed the implementation of each phase. In the qualitative phase, semi-structured interviews with key informants from the case study company were conducted to evaluate and validate the proposed conceptual framework. The qualitative findings resulting from thematic analysis led to conceptual framework updates and hypotheses development.

The data for the quantitative phase was collected using an online survey, and the data was analysed using Logistic Regression. The researcher used Logistic Regression to analyse the online survey data collected during the quantitative phase. Chapter 6 details the qualitative phase and results, while Chapter 7 presents the quantitative phase and findings. The following Figure 5.14 presents a summary of the research methodology adopted in this study.

Phase	Procedure	Outcome
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Case study selection</div> <p style="text-align: center;">↓</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Purposefully sampling selection of participant (N=9) -Snowballing sampling (N=2) 	Interviews (N=11)
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Qualitative Data Collection</div> <p style="text-align: center;">↓</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -11 Semi-structured interviews 	Text data (interview transcripts)
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Qualitative Data Analysis</div> <p style="text-align: center;">↓</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Thematic analysis and coding - NVivo qualitative software 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Codes and themes -Similar and different themes - Visual data display
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Quantitative Data Collection</div> <p style="text-align: center;">↓</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -On-line survey (N=72) 	Numeric data
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Quantitative Data Analysis</div> <p style="text-align: center;">↓</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Data screening (univariate, multivariate) -Factor analysis - Frequencies -Logistic regression -SPSS 11, quantitative software 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Descriptive statistics - Linearity, normality, multicollinearity -Factor loadings -Frequency, valid percent -Chi-square, coefficients, ANOVA -Correlation matrix, Collinearity statistics, Logistic Regression
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Interpretation of entire analysis</div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Explanation of the meaning of qualitative results -Explanation of the meaning of the quantitative results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussion - Recommendations for future research and studies

Figure 5.14: Summary of the Research Methodology (source: by the researcher)

CHAPTER 6 – THE QUALITATIVE STUDY

6.1 Introduction

The previous chapters provided a systematic review of relevant literature and outlined the research methods adopted in this study. This chapter presents an analysis of participants responses obtained through semi-structured interviews with eleven (11) employees of the largest telecommunication company in Greece used as the “case” in this current study.

As noted in Chapter 5, interviews served to foster an understanding of employees’ perceptions of factors that influence a Business-to-Business (B2B) organisation in Greece to adopt and use SM for marketing purposes and explore various perceived benefits and barriers to SM adoption.

This chapter presents the findings following interview data analysis. The first section outlines factors influencing a B2B organisation to adopt and use SMM are discussed (section 6.2). Section 6.3 documents the perceived benefits and barriers to SMM adoption. Next, section 6.4 presents the proposed hypotheses based on the interview findings. Finally, this chapter concludes with a discussion of the qualitative findings (section 6.5).

6.2 Factors influencing the adoption of social media marketing by B2B organisations

This section presents the interview findings related to factors influencing a Greek B2B organisation to adopt SMM. The study addressed the following research objective:

RO1: To critically explore a B2B organisation’s perceptions on the factors influencing the adoption of SMM.

The initial **deductive** codes were based on previously identified factors in the literature review and guided the development of the interview guide. In turn, these factors were from the TOE

(technological, organisational, and environmental context) framework and Hofstede’s Cultural model (cultural context). After adding additional **inductive** codes derived from the interview data analysis, themes were finalised (Figure 6.1). The findings of the exploratory qualitative study were later tested and validated through the quantitative study described in Chapter 7.

The analysis identified factors that influence a B2B company to adopt SMM. Of the factors, there were: six technological (relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, interactivity, and image), four organisational (size, top management support, employee knowledge, and innovativeness), three environmental (government support, competitive pressure, and external support) and five cultural (power distance, collectivism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance and short-term orientation) factors. Figure 6.1 presents the resulting conceptual framework from the analysis, and each “context” is discussed separately in the following sections.

Figure 6.1: The updated conceptual framework (source: by the researcher)

6.2.1 Technological context

The theme of technological context (Figure 6.2) includes three (3) subthemes identified in the literature (relative advantage, compatibility and complexity) (Rogers, 2003) and three (3) subthemes that developed from thematic analysis (trialability, interactivity and image).

Figure 6.2: Technological factors

**inductive codes

Table 6.1 presents an example of the *NVivo* codebook and shows coding frequencies for the deductive and inductive codes. Additionally, the table includes a description of each theme.

Table 6.1: Coding frequency for analysing the Technological Context (Source: researcher, 2020)

Name	Description	Files ¹	References ²
TECHNOLOGICAL CONTEXT	The adoption of SM is influenced by technological considerations	11	77
Relative Advantage*	SM adoption provides the company with a relative advantage	11	11
Compatibility*	SM are compatible with the company's existing infrastructure and information systems	11	11

¹ The number of people who discussed the theme

² How many times the theme was discussed across all interviews

Complexity*	The adoption of SM is not complex for the company	11	11
Interactivity**	SM help the company to interact with its business partners	11	12
Trialability**	The company tries different things on SM before using them	2	3
Image**	The adoption and use of SM increases the image of the company	10	17

* deductive codes

**inductive codes

1. Relative advantage

Results of qualitative analysis confirm that **relative advantage** influences a B2B organisation to adopt SMM. SM may increase company brand awareness, disseminate information about its products, and generate leads through performance campaigns, which should increase sales. Most interviewees acknowledge how SM provides a relative advantage for companies who have adopted it over those who have not or misuse it. SM Section Manager (P7), asserts that SM

is a great weapon for everyone who has secured a good presence in them” and “it has a tremendous advantage over businesses that do not have a presence or who have very little presence or who have a presence but do not do it properly.

Another participant, a B2B Marketing Senior Product Manager (P6), suggested that adoption alone is not necessarily an advantage, as “the most important thing is the management of SM”. Since competitors are also likely to adopt SM, the advantage results from skilful management of SM tools and the company’s SM strategy, which requires consideration of the available budget or planning and following a SM strategy. A Digital Marketing Senior Manager (P11) believed that

because other companies have also adopted SM, what matters is “how you handle the medium [and] how you manage the SM”.

Upon analysis, the researcher found relative advantage was a significant driving force in SM adoption at the case study’s company. The adoption of SM has helped the company increase its image, build brand awareness, reach, and interact with customers and business partners, increase sales, reduce cost, and improve targeting. Findings from this study reinforce findings from previous research on the adoption of SM and new technologies (Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020; Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2018; Christodoulides, Siamagka and Michaelidou, 2015; Shaltoni, 2017), who found a positive relationship between the relative advantage and the adoption intention. It is also consistent with Notta and Kitta's (2021) findings, who used a sample of 102 Greek agri-food companies to examine the factors affecting them to adopt e-marketing. They concluded that relative advantage is a top priority for these companies to enhance their job effectiveness, increase their productivity, improve their work quality, and help them to do their job easier.

This finding may suggest that the expected benefits from SM usage will impact a B2B organisation to adopt SM. Thus, this may further support Araújo and Zilber's (2016, p. 281) view that the benefits resulting from SM adoption in business processes lead to their extensive use in the organisation.

However, the relative advantage was not necessarily considered as an adoption driver for the B2B Marketing Senior Product Manager (P6). She suggested that the relative advantage does not come merely from the adoption itself but rather from the company’s SM strategy and the skilful management of SM tools. This viewpoint may indicate that a B2B company must have a SM plan and a strategy to achieve it before realising a relative advantage from adopting SM compared to its competitors.

These results suggest that a company's awareness of SM benefits might help business adopt and use these technologies. The hypothesis developed from this result is:

H1: Increased perceived **relative advantage** of SM may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

2. Compatibility

This study demonstrates how SM is compatible with the company's existing infrastructure because most of the SMM tools are free to use, and because the company is a "great telecom provider" (P5, B2B Marketing Section Manager). All participants confirmed this **compatibility** of SM with the company's existing infrastructure and believed that there is no need for additional investment to start using SM. Overall, they believed that SM platforms are easy to adopt and have low infrastructure requirements. The B2B Marketing Brand Manager (P10) explained that they "had to do some Google Analytics reports and to put Facebook pixels on our site, but it was not a major investment. These actions performed to better report and monitor our actions". Additionally, the P2, a Senior Product Manager, explained, "we didn't make new investments, we just added them in the media". However, he further explained, "we invested in people who know, who can teach us, so that we can move on". In other words, companies invested in experts to facilitate SM adoption and ensure companies use SM effectively. The B2B Marketing Senior Manager confirmed the compatibility of SM with their company explaining how they "needed to include SM with buttons on our pages that did not exist, but it was not a big investment". However, the volume of followers created "the need to hire an agency company to do the monitoring of the SM platforms and deal with the comments". Thus, SM is compatible with the company's technological infrastructure and values. Having additional personnel or an external partner might help the company adopt and use SM.

This study found compatibility to be a significant determinant of SM adoption. The case study company is a telecommunication company with the necessary infrastructure to support SM adoption, so there was no need for extra investments. The researcher found compatibility of SM with its procedures and values is a significant factor in adopting SM. These findings align with previous studies suggesting that perceived compatibility is associated with SMM adoption within a B2B organisation (Shaltoni, 2017; Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2018), possibly because anyone with an internet connection can use SM. Therefore, SM is a simple, compatible, and easily adoptable technology by any organisation and this study proposed:

H2: Increased perceived **compatibility** of SM may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

3. Complexity

Most interviewees believed that SM is easy to use today, as most people are familiar with SM platforms. The B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) noted that while the adoption itself may not be complex, using it right might be as she explained,

Simply making a page is a very easy step, but you must have the right people and the right partners to make a good plan because it can prove to be a disaster if you do not know how to manage it. I would say it is not only about the content, but also the context in which you upload something.

Other participants expressed similar views, noting how general use of SM is easy, but “it changes continuously, (...) you always have to keep up” and “be constantly alert” (P3, Brand Manager-B2B Marketing).

The SM Senior Manager (P8) explained that the complexity for her and her department

“is not to create clutter and calibration of campaigns in the same media and in the same audiences. My day is an incredible jigsaw puzzle to keep one campaign from falling over to another one, into the same audience and making us unsubscribe and unfollow. And we want our campaigns to be effective without spending too much money and not essentially cannibalizing each other’s campaigns”.

The study also revealed that SM could be complex for a large company because of the company’s internal complicated structure:

There is no flexibility; we are a very big organisation, we have too many people, every division has its own needs and sometimes you have to force yourself to modify your own plans because you cannot have a presence on SM at the time you want to have it (P4, Section manager- B2B Marketing).

This finding indicates that a highly complex, centralised, and bureaucratic structure may hinder innovation adoption. Thus, it may be necessary to simplify the structure, policies, rules, and company procedures to promote employee creativity and innovation.

Participants did not identify the complexity factor as a SM adoption barrier. This result is consistent with Shaltoni's (2017, p. 1014) previous study, which found no significant relationship between the perceived complexity and the adoption of internet marketing in the industrial context because “the internet marketing technologies are becoming easier to implement”. However, some participants offered three reasons for the complexity in the implementation phase of SM:

1. planning and monitoring SM campaigns are complicated processes that necessitate hiring an advertising company to do the job,

2. the disruptive nature of this technology makes it hard for companies to remain up to date, and
3. the company's complicated structure makes it challenging to implement SM campaigns in the desired way and time because of insufficient flexibility.

Considering these arguments, it is proposed:

H3: Increased perceived **complexity** of SM may negatively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

4. Interactivity

The first technological factor to emerge from the study was interactivity. Interactivity creates a two-way dialog between the company and the SM users and may offer a unique value to its followers. When discussing the value of such interaction, the B2B Marketing Section Manager (P2) stressed:

if we organise a contest, they can immediately respond and take part, while, in another case they would have seen it on TV, on the radio or seen a link or a URL and it would not be as immediate.

The participants who mentioned this factor also noted that interactivity through SM allows the company to capture valuable data and feedback that may guide future SMM strategies. In other words, as P11 noted, interactivity ultimately provides “actionable insights”:

The number one with SM, is the interaction. That means that we can use it not only to get feedback from our customers, but also (which is very important) to get feedback on which we can act, that is, to have actionable insights (P11, Senior Manager- Digital Marketing)

On the other hand, the B2B Marketing Brand Manager (P3) noted how interactions in the industrial context and communications with B2B customers are more and complicated than with retail customers. He believes several factors and many people are involved in this interaction, which can distort the general picture because, “in companies that involve different people who manage the data, the business profile page can’t be completely clear”. Therefore, the communication “between these two B2B business channels is more complicated”.

Interactivity was another factor resulting from interview data analysis. SM platforms provide two-way communication between the company and its customers and business partners and provide an avenue for collecting valuable feedback to inform on future SMM strategies. This finding is in line with that of Ainin *et al.* (2015), who found that interactivity was a significant factor affecting the use of Facebook in organisations. Additionally, Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011) confirmed B2B company’s use of SM for customer communication and creating customer value. The interactivity of SM is a crucial consideration for the companies who choose to use SM platforms for their marketing activities (Odoom, Anning-Dorson and Acheampong, 2017). The interview results suggest that the interactive nature of SM platforms and their low costs help B2B companies fulfil their goals and improve their business efficiently (Lashgari *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, SM experts and SMM firms need to increase awareness to B2B managers and business owners about the benefits of the interactive nature of SM platforms to increase the adoption percentage.

These results suggest that interactivity through SM may help a brand increase its reach and performance while positioning the company as an authority in its industry. Therefore, the hypothesis is:

H4: Increased **interactivity** of SM may influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

5. Trialability

Another factor affecting SMM adoption and use was trialability, which relates to ease of use. To sum, ease of use positively correlates with the number of users. Further, participants reported personal familiarity with SM use (P2 and P4), which might account for their awareness of SM benefits. Consequently, this familiarity might have contributed to the decision to adopt SM for the business. Further, *large* companies have the available funds and resources to try new SM tools before these tools are officially launched on SM platforms. As the B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) reported, the company's pioneering position in the telecommunications industry in Greece and the company budget allows them to test new SM tools first. As such, budgeting and resources may "help you with your results and your image" (P1, Senior Manager- B2B Marketing). The Digital Marketing Senior Manager (P11) also supported that SM help the company to

test things and very easily read the pulse of our customers, that is, with a post, with an add, we can test and run different things and see what sits our customers. It also enables us to see customer buying behaviours. For example, recently the new iPhone came out, we had the pulse, and we knew the people's reactions before the product launch.

The case study company's adoption of SM was influenced by trialability, which emerged as an essential technology factor. The results suggest that the trial of new SM tools and features was essential for the company and gave it a competitive advantage over its competitors. Many previous studies (for example, Alshamaila *et al.*, 2012 and Kendall *et al.*, 2001) found trialability positively affects the company's decision to adopt new technologies. Additionally, Wong (2012) supported that personal Facebook usage positively impacts business usage and facilitates SM adoption in businesses. This finding means that the familiarity and the personal experience of the Greeks on SM in their personal life may assist their decision to adopt them in their businesses too.

Additionally, another possible explanation for why trialability influences the adoption decision is that Greece has the highest uncertainty avoidance score (112) in the cultural context (Hofstede, 1984). Therefore, B2B companies may be reluctant to adopt new technologies and require reassurances that they are appropriate for their business. The resulting hypothesis of this result finding is:

H5: Trialling SM platforms may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

6. Image

Image is another determinant of SMM adoption by B2B companies that resulted from the analysis of the interview data. The company's SM strategy and presence may broaden its audiences and build reputation and image. The participants emphasised how the company uses SM to build brand awareness and image on a smaller budget than required for "traditional" marketing platforms, such as TV and newspaper advertisements. As the B2B Marketing Manager reflected:

generally, SM has considerably helped the company's image ... and it has helped us at the level of awareness. We have many products and it's a very easy way to build awareness for our products at a significantly lower budget compared to TV for example (P1, Senior manager- B2B Marketing).

The use of SM contributes to brand awareness because by posting insightful and well-written content on SM the company communicates the desired image. In short, the company uses specific "campaigns and actions that are purely to enhance the company's brand image" (P4, Section Manager- B2B Marketing).

The interview results provided evidence that the adoption and use of SM platforms by the case study company helped create a positive public image of the company and enhance its reputation

as a thought leader in the Telecommunication industry in Greece. The qualitative findings are consistent with Siamagka *et al.* (2015), who found that B2B companies appreciate the use of SM in enhancing their brand image. The study results might suggest that the Greek B2B companies will increase their investments in SM to strengthen their brand image. Still, they must be cautious because there is a risk of destroying their image if they do not handle them carefully and correctly (Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011). Based on this, it is possible to hypothesise that:

H6: Increased **image** of SM platforms may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

Section summary

This study concluded that the technological context is a contributing area to SMM adoption by Greek B2B companies. Relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, interactivity, trialability and image are all factors that were included in the preliminary framework (6.6) and later tested in the second phase of the study (see Chapter 7). The next section presents on the organisational context.

6.2.2 Organisational context

This section contains findings linked to the second theme of the framework, namely the organisational context. This theme includes four subthemes: size, top management support, and employee knowledge as well as company's innovativeness (Figure 6.3).

Figure 6.3: Organisational factors (source: by the researcher)

Table 6.2 presents an example of *NVivo* codebook and shows coding frequencies for the deductive codes.

Table 6.2: Coding frequency for analysing the Organisational context (Source: researcher, 2020)

Name	Description	Files ³	References ⁴
ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXT	Organisational factors influencing SMM adoption	11	55
Size	The size of the company affects the adoption of SM	11	11
Top Management Support	The top management team supports the adoption of SM and allocates adequate resources	11	12
Employee knowledge	The employees have the appropriate knowledge and technological skills	10	11
Innovativeness	The innovativeness of the company affects the adoption of SM	11	11

7. Size

³ The number of people who discussed the theme

⁴ How many times the theme was discussed across all interviews

As expected, the participants agreed that the **size** of a company had a significant impact on the adoption of SM by B2B companies. The larger the company and the budget, the more likely the company is to spend on SMM. As the SM Manager (P8) explained, “the bigger and better-known a company is, the bigger digital footprint it has and, therefore, it is logical to have SM”. Considering the benefits of using SMM, a large company “couldn’t be missing out from a such a dynamic medium” (P2, Senior Product Manager).

Although it may be easier for larger companies to adopt SM due to their budget, overall, company size was not considered a barrier, as all companies may have a SM presence. Initially, small and medium-sized companies may struggle to initiate SM usage, but “they can easily use SM and the internet for their sales” (SM Senior Manager, P8) without having to spend much money on qualified experts.

However, a small number of those interviewed (2) suggested that the size of their company (17,000 employees) and the complicated structure that characterises the company may negatively affect SM use. The B2B Marketing Section Manager shared, “there is no flexibility, in comparison to other organisations that have much greater flexibility because they employ 200 people, not 17,000”.

Additionally, the SM Section Manager (P7) believed that “the size of the company should have helped to have a larger SM department, to invest in this department, to be able to staff it with more people who know the subject naturally”. He also expressed the view that “you would expect that a company with so many employees would be able to have the flexibility to bring in some people to engage in new technologies and SM”.

The qualitative phase of the study uncovered conflicting results regarding the impact of firm size on SM adoption in the industrial context. On the one hand, the firm size was proved to be a

significant factor affecting the decision to adopt SM, and larger firms have the financial means to invest in SM. This result was consistent with the study of Mikalef and Pateli (2017), who found that firm size had a significant and positive impact on the degree of SM adoption by a firm. Goode and Stevens (2000) advocate that size is an adoption factor that applies equally to large and small companies. Smaller companies can still adopt SM, as more simplistic applications do not necessitate significant investment and are flexible enough to meet their needs.

On the other hand, some interviewees advocated that the large size of their firm can be a barrier to the proper implementation of SM because of bureaucratic problems. This finding may indicate that a complicated organisational structure may negatively influence a B2B company's decision to adopt and use SM. Therefore, this hypothesis is:

H7: The **size** of the company may have a positive impact on the adoption of SMM by B2B companies

8. Top management support

The support of **top management** is another organisational factor that plays a role in the adoption of SM. Management support may include either financial support, where the management monitors the allocation of sufficient resources to adopt SM, or the management team's commitment and involvement. The impact of this factor on the adoption and use of SMM was viewed differently by participants. Most of the participants (8 participants) believed that top management support the adoption of SM whereas three (3) participants stressed the lack of human resources and the need for additional investments in the SM department.

The B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1), for example, believed that the top management team fully supported the adoption of SM, primarily due to their technological background that results in their personal interest and curiosity about how SM works and how it can help the company. As

she noted, “most of them have worked in technology companies for many years so they believe that SM is the evolution of evolution; it is something very important for them”. The Brand Manager from the B2B Marketing department (P3) also indicated the receptiveness and commitment of management towards the adoption of SM, but noted how slow the process is and believed that:

this is something that happens step by step; the SM team started with one person and now there are three people, and that number may grow at some point. There is constant support from the top management team, and it will be even greater in the future.

The B2B Marketing Section Manager (P4) also acknowledged the role of management commitment, and believed that budget and goal restrictions, for example “goals to reduce staff and costs”, may affect the allocation of adequate resources for new staff specialised in SM. Senior managers play an essential role in integrating different resources, overcoming internal barriers, and changing company’s vision and commitment.

Top management awareness of the SMM perceived benefits is essential for providing adequate resources (financial and human resources), and without their support the company is less likely to adopt and use SM. The SM Senior Manager (P8) also indicated a lack of human resources and shared how her department is understaffed: “...but this is a management issue, so we can either reduce the campaigns or increase the resources – I mean, it is a matter for discussion”. The SM Section Manager (P7), in turn, believed that while the top management team understands the necessity to hire more people for the SM department, they do not understand it to the extent needed. He believed their company is a special case because it used to be a public company and now is under the Deutsche Telecom and is going through a transitional stage; “the company is trying to get rid of old practices, procedures and so on, and apply more up-to-date practices on the basis of

DT's instructions". The lack of human resources for the SM department was also expressed by the SM Section Manager (P9):

I believe that while they know we must be on SM, this department has not been staffed as it should have been. That is, more employees are needed because this is still very much in development. We are three people and for a very long time we were only two.

From the above arguments, the researcher concludes that top management support significantly contributes to a company's adoption of SMM, and that adoption of SMM is prevalent among innovative managers.

According to the study's findings, support for SM adoption from top level managers is a critical determinant of B2B SM adoption. Consistent with previous studies conducted in Greece (Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020; Vlachvei and Notta, 2014; Giotopoulos *et al.*, 2017), this finding illustrates that top management support, notably managers' characteristics, is a significant determinant of SM adoption. The case study company is in telecommunications, and the top management team has a technological background and a personal interest in SM and its impact on company's performance. However, participants mentioned that its previous background as a public company and the financial restrictions from the mother company had minimised their investment in human resources for the SM department. This finding suggests that top managers serve to integrate different resources and overcome internal barriers. It also may mean that top management awareness of SM perceived benefits is essential for providing adequate resources (financial and human resources). Without their support, a company is less likely to adopt and use SM. Therefore, it is proposed that:

H8: Top management support may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

9. Employee knowledge

Employee knowledge also affects a company's decision to adopt SM. Employee knowledge, in this case, refers to the technical knowledge and skills of existing employees, gained from previous use of SM and familiarity with these tools. The interview findings indicate that because employee knowledge is an important antecedent of SM adoption, the company regularly invests in employee training. The SM Senior Manager (P8) explained, for example, that "the company has the resources and the culture to train you whenever the need arises". Participant (P3) explained that the company is either "attracting and recruiting new, already trained employees" or engaging third-party partners and "training the old [existing]", employees (P3, Brand Manager- B2B Marketing).

The lack of appropriate employee knowledge can be a barrier to effective SM adoption. Thus, employees from the SM department must have the appropriate knowledge, and "each communication team should be staffed with a digital person who would better understand SM and all the digital ecosystems" (SM Section Manager, P7).

These results indicate that inadequate employee knowledge on SMM may be a barrier to SM adoption, necessitating an investment in training and/or the need to outsource some of the SMM tasks to external specialists.

Employee knowledge was identified as a fundamental antecedent for the adoption of SM by a B2B company. This finding is consistent with that of Giotopoulos *et al.* (2017) and in line with that of Mikalef and Pateli (2017), suggesting that prior employee knowledge and the firm's human capital with scientific background increases the probability of the Greek SMEs to adopt SM or any form of ICT application. Nevertheless, the company acknowledged the impact of inadequate knowledge, which is why they invest in employee training, recruitment of skilled employees, and/or outsourcing to monitor, optimise, and evaluate their SM campaigns. This finding may

indicate that companies with qualified employees have a higher percentage of adopting SM than companies with less skilled human capital. Based on these findings, the following hypothesis formed:

H9: Increased **employee knowledge** on SM may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

10. Innovativeness

Innovativeness is another factor of the firm found to contribute to SMM adoption. Most participants expressed how their company is a telecommunications company, so it is natural for them to exploit and use new technologies. SM adoption is essential, as P (8), the SM Senior Manager explained:

SM has come to complement the company's innovation part and we are trying to be innovative there as well. Because innovation is in our nature, in the nature of the brand and in the core essence of the company, we try to be there too (P8).

When discussing this issue, the B2B Marketing Section Manager (P4) added, "innovation is one of our brand values and a part of our culture and our lives" and, therefore, company innovativeness influenced the adoption of SM. The B2B Marketing Brand Manager (P3) also believed that since "telecommunications are, by default, innovative", the company could not ignore new technology such as SM; they had to use SM and actively participate in SMM as much as they could.

However, the B2B Marketing Section Manager (P5) raised concerns about the impact of company size on its ability to innovate. She felt that larger companies inadvertently create company processes that impede or restrain innovation and their ability to remain current, which illustrates how company size influences its innovativeness.

The SM Section Manager (P7) and Digital Marketing Senior Manager (P11) were neutral when questioned about the impact of the company's innovativeness on the decision to adopt and use SM. P7 supported the view that the company operates at a basic level of SM adoption, stating "the company's innovativeness does not mean that it is transferred into other departments, for example, SM". Additionally, P(11) explained how the company is innovative "we followed the trend that all major companies are on SM" regarding SM adoption. In short, innovative B2B companies are aware of the possibilities of new technology, thereby increasing their likelihood to adopt SMM.

The results showed a positive relationship between the innovativeness of the firm and the adoption of SMM. This finding is consistent with previous studies (Pascucci, Ancillai and Cardinali, 2018; Fosso Wamba and Carter, 2014; Shaltoni, 2017). It also aligns with the study by Siamagka *et al.* (2015), who found that organisational innovativeness is one of the main predictors of SM adoption by B2B companies in developed countries. Furthermore, Giotopoulos *et al.* (2017) suggested that being involved in R&D and innovation activities, participating in research projects or collaborations increases the likelihood of Greek SMEs to adopt ICTs. A possible explanation of this positive effect is that innovative companies have the necessary IT infrastructure, tend to be early adopters of new technologies and devote adequate resources to develop new products (Tarafdar and Vaidya, 2006). The proposed hypothesis, therefore, is:

H10: The **innovativeness** of the firm may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

Section summary

Derived from analysis, understanding the adoption of SMM by Greek B2B companies requires consideration of the organisational context. The organisational factors include size, top management support, employee knowledge and the innovativeness of the firm. The following section presents another context for consideration, namely the environmental context.

6.2.3 Environmental context

Interview participants discussed three (3) environmental factors that influence a B2B organisation’s decision to adopt SMM: competitive pressure, government support, and external support (Figure 6.4).

Figure 6.4: Environmental factors (source: by the researcher)

**inductive code

Table 6.3 presents an example of the *NVivo* codebook showing both the inductive and deductive codes related to environmental context.

Table 6.3: Coding frequency for analysing the Environmental Context (Source: Author’s analysis 2020)

Name	Description	Files ⁵	References ⁶
ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT	The environmental factors affecting the adoption of SMM	11	50
Government support	The Government encourages and supports the adoption of SM by the companies	11	11
Competitive pressure	The company will lose its customers to its competitors if will not adopt SM	11	11
External support- agency	An external support-agency help the company to adopt the SM	4	6

⁵ The number of people who discussed the theme

⁶ How many times the theme was discussed across all interviews

11. Government support

The analysis did not reveal any role of **government support** in the decision to adopt SM. A common viewpoint among participants was that there is no government support to motivate Greek B2B companies to adopt SM, as expressed in the following extract:

I think the government is stone-cold indifferent. The Greek government has not been interested in business at all, neither in the big ones, as we are, nor in the small ones; when taxes have reached 70%, it is not interested in investment, innovation, or anything else (P5, Section Manager- B2B Marketing).

This finding may be the result of the Greek government's financial problems following the 2008 recession. However, the economy and government changed after the national elections on the 7th of July 2019. During the last interview conducted in October 2019 after the July elections, the government introduced the Ministry of State and Digital Governance, a specific ministry designed to promote nationwide digital transformation. Unlike most participants previously interviewed, the Digital Marketing Senior Manager (P11) asserted the new government policy offered some financial incentives for developing their company websites and adopting digital marketing, stating:

Recently, we had several contacts with customers who had a subsidy that included creating an online presence and promoting through ESPA (a programme funded from the EU). And the government itself has also begun to use these tools. For example, there has been a big shift in the taxation with the use of the TAXIS e-platform.

On the other hand, the B2B Marketing Brand Manager (P3) mentioned that the Greek government issued special regulations that do not allow the Greek companies to use Facebook leads. Therefore, he expressed his opinion that these government regulations tend to hinder the adoption of SM.

Most interviewees (10 participants) cited insufficient support (financial, regulatory policies, or IT investments) from the Greek government to help Greek companies adopt new technologies and SM. However, participants contend government support would significantly impact how Greek companies diffuse new technologies and innovations. During the last interview conducted in October 2019, after the election of a new government in July 2019, the participant confirmed how the new government started giving financial incentives to Greek companies to adopt SM marketing and started to use these tools. Several previous studies (Abubakar *et al.*, 2017 and Alrawabdeh, 2014), document how crucial government support is for encouraging the adoption of SM and mobile commerce, respectively. This finding suggests that the Greek government must introduce actions to raise awareness about SM (for example, workshops, reports, and projects) to educate the companies about the possibilities provided by SMM. The study proposed that:

H11: Increased **government support** may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

12. Competitive pressure

There were mixed views on **competitive pressure** as a factor influencing the adoption of SM. Some participants, for example, did not believe competitive pressure is an influencing factor because their company is the leader in the market and has an established competitive advantage in the telecommunication industry. The SM Section Manager (P7), for example, explained that “there is not much pressure, because in the KPIs of SM and in the number of subscribers, and in the reach of our posts, in all of these key metrics, we are more prominent”. The same participant (P7) described how the company primarily relies on its technological superiority and does not feel pressure from competitors to adopt SM, even though SM is a widely available channel.

However, most participants perceived competitive pressure as being among the key factors influencing SM adoption, even to the extent of feeling, “if we don’t use it, we will definitely lose”

(P2, Senior Product Manager- B2B Marketing). Evident from most of the interviews is that, from the business perspective, competitive pressure encourages the adoption of SM, facilitates performance improvements, increases the likelihood of staying in business. The B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) explained that the failure of a company to use SM might result in customer attrition, especially among younger people stating, “our competitors will find a gap and they’ll get a share” (P9, Section Manager- SM).

Qualitative analysis revealed mixed results about the competitive pressure as a determinant for SM adoption. Some participants believed that their company is already the leader in their industry with a competitive advantage. In contrast, most participants assert that competitive pressure, out of fear of losing customers or the business, influences the company to adopt SM. The findings of the interview data suggest that perceived competitive pressure is an important determinant influencing a B2B company to adopt SM. This finding corresponds to previous studies (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021; Shaltoni, 2017; Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011; Siamagka *et al.*, 2015). Pascucci, Ancillai and Cardinali (2018) also found that the influence of competitors is an important determinant of SM adoption by B2B companies. Furthermore, Alrawabdeh (2014) found that the competitive pressure from other companies in the Jordan telecommunication industry forces competitors to adopt new technologies to add value to their products and differentiate them from the others. Competition is a crucial factor influencing SM adoption, and the developed hypothesis is as follows:

H12: Increased **competitive pressure** may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

13. External support

External support from an agency and specialists emerged as another factor. Additionally, there was a link between companies adopting SM and available external support by the agency company

and media shop. Notably, one identified reason for this was that the company adopted SM because its agency company had a presence on SM. As the B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) explained, “the agency started to bring forward proposals that were social-media-oriented”. The agency is a large multinational Telecommunication Group member with immediate access to new trends and best practices from within the network. Additionally, the agency company evaluates, optimises, and monitors its SM platforms. B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) explains, “the advertising company does the monitoring and is necessary when you expand and when you upgrade so much your SM presence”. Participants also commented on how external support from SMM consultancy companies helped their company design and monitor SMM campaigns. In addition, the agency is responsive on SM “because there is a cost to answering all the messages and so the advertising company does it for us”. The necessity to respond to message justifies the need for external support, possibly due to inadequate time and human resources.

The external support from experts and specialists emerged as a significant factor influencing the case study B2B company to adopt SM. The results are congruent with Alshamaila's *et al.* (2012) work, as they concluded availability of external support positively influences the SMEs in the North East of England to adopt cloud computing. Mikalef and Pateli (2017) also found that the degree of SM adoption by the examined companies in Greece and Cyprus was increased by their collaboration with external entities to gain access to new knowledge resources and capabilities. The findings of the qualitative phase strongly indicate the importance of external support for the successful utilisation of SM in B2B companies. This finding suggests that managers of Greek B2B companies should focus their efforts on providing adequate external support from SM experts and SMM companies to increase the adoption and use of SM by their companies. Therefore, this study proposed that:

H13: Increased **external support** may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

Section summary

The preliminary framework, outlined in Section 6.7 identifies the three (3) environmental factors (competitive pressure, government support, and external support), that were included and later tested in the quantitative phase of the study (see Chapter 7).

6.2.4 Cultural context

During the interviews, participants discussed the possible influence of Greek culture on SMM adoption. As outlined in Section 3.6, the question about culture was exploratory. The interview results revealed that the Greek culture influences the adoption of SMM by a Greek B2B company. Moreover, the qualitative findings offer supporting evidence for five cultural dimensions of Hofstede's cultural model (Hofstede, 1991): power distance, collectivism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance and short term orientation. The interview data did not support the sixth cultural dimension of "indulgence" and was not included in the updated framework because it was irrelevant to this research context. Hofstede's Model is robust and applied in many IS studies (Tsatsou, 2012). Studies by Hasan and Ditsa (1999) and Lee, Trimi and Kim (2013) among others, suggest that national culture is significantly related to technology adoption.

Figure 6.5: Cultural factors (source: by the researcher)

**inductive codes

Table 6.4 presents an example of the *NVivo* codebook showing the inductive and deductive codes related to Cultural Context.

Table 6.4 Coding frequency for analysing the Cultural Context (source: researcher, 2020)

Name	Description	Files ⁷	References ⁸
CULTURAL CONTEXT	The cultural factors that influence SMM adoption	12	26
Power distance	The opinion of the Manager/Owner is the most important in the business	4	4
Collectivism	It is critical to establish trusting and long-lasting relationships	5	5
Masculinity	High competitiveness is a key element of success in the businesses	8	8
Uncertainty Avoidance	Fear for the future- many rules and extremely structured lives	6	8
Short-term orientation	Short-term planning for the future	4	4
Greek culture	Greek culture is affecting the adoption of SMM	11	13

⁷ The number of people who discussed the theme

⁸ How many times the theme was discussed across all interviews

14. Power distance

Power distance is the first dimension of Hofstede's Cultural model. In cultures with high power distance, decision-makers may be less innovative and less open to consultation and change (Hasan and Ditsa, 1999; Prim *et al.*, 2017). During the interviews, participants confirmed that the management decisions are primarily centralised and hierarchical. The participant (P6) mentioned that "we don't have the decision-making power to upload their SM campaigns on the time we want".

Additionally, the B2B Marketing Section Manager (P4) explained how employees in top management use the budget to determine the size of the SM department. However, the SM Senior Manager (P8) reported having an understaffed department due to a lack of human resources, but staffing is a centralised management decision beyond their control.

According to Hofstede (1991), Greece has a high-power distance culture, and management decisions are primarily centralised and hierarchical. Additionally, Greek people are ready to accept wider differences in power (Tsatsou, 2012). Interview data confirmed Greece's high-power distance culture and reinforces the finding that management decisions are centralised and hierarchical. The results align with the findings of Prim *et al.* (2017), who found that Greece has high indices of power distance and the predominant feature in its culture is hierarchy because it has centralised power structures (Mihet, 2013). This result might indicate that the Greek culture's high centralisation and resistance to change negatively influence the Greek B2B organisations to adopt new technologies and SM, respectively. Prior literature (for example, Özbilen, 2017; Harzing and Hofstede, 1996) details the negative association between power distance and resistance to change. Therefore, to empirically test this factor, the proposed hypothesis is:

H14: Higher **Power Distance** may negatively affect the adoption of SMM by Greek B2B organisations

15. Collectivism

The results of this study confirmed the prevalent **collectivist** background of Greek culture and the existence of the “philotimo” concept, or the “love for honour” and solidarity may limit individual autonomy (Tsatsou, 2012). The Greek society reflects collectivism, where the “we” is more important than the “I” (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010). As the B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) recounted how through SM during the Big Fire in Mati in July 2018, Greeks exemplified collectivism as they stood in solidarity with their fellow citizens:

during the Big Fire this element of solidarity was evident, and we all together acted as a huge group and tried to improve this situation. Greeks show solidarity to a great extent, hospitality and all these elements, so it is understood that by watching and studying SM the Greek culture comes out very intensively. In many things we see it in everyday life.

In organisations, the autonomy of its members and their accountability in light of the outcomes can measure the degree of individualism (Prim *et al.*, 2017). Four participants explained that their organisation has a bureaucratic structure and a lower level of independence and autonomy. For example, the SM Section Manager (P9) explained how, when selecting an advertising company to collaborate with, the decision is centralised, so there is no freedom to act independently. She contended, “if there are more choices, we can do our job better”.

Erumban and de Jong (2006) asserted that collectivist countries are likely to have lower ICT adoption rates or be slower in adopting technology because adopting something new can go against group norm (Özbilen, 2017).

Concerning the low individualism/collectivism dimension, Hofstede's work suggested that the Greek society is collectivistic with a score of 35 in this dimension (Hofstede, 1991). In highly collectivist cultures, companies have lower grade of technology adoption (Özbilen, 2017). The results from the analysis of the interviews suggest that the Greek society is resistant to change and highly collectivist. This result is inconsistent with the study of Zhao (2013), which found that countries with higher individualism cultures tend to perform better in e-government adoption. Therefore, the results of the qualitative data suggest that the lower level of independence and autonomy in the Greek organisations does not favour an environment that encourages the adoption of new technologies and innovation. Therefore, the following hypothesis is put forward:

H15: Collectivism may negatively affect the adoption of SMM by Greek B2B organisations

16. Masculinity

According to Hofstede (1984), Greece is a medium ranking masculine society (score: 57) driven by competition, achievement, and success. Men regard caring for their family as a personal honor, and the success of a family member adds social value to the entire in-group (Hofstede, 1991). Therefore, countries with higher masculinity may have a higher success orientation and are driven at the business level to be the best in the market (Hasan and Ditsa, 1999). This assertion suggests that businesses will be more innovative and willing to invest in new technologies to be more competitive. Most of the participants (8) perceived competition as a critical antecedent that influenced their company's adoption of SM. The B2B Marketing Senior Product Manager (P6) shared "it is necessary to use SM to compete in the telecommunication industry". She also noted that more active companies on SM have the edge over their competitors because consumers now decide on telecommunication services based on advice found on SM. If their company is not active, "we will lose our customers" (P6).

The cultural factor of masculinity positively effects the case study B2B company's adoption of SM. Countries with higher masculinity should have a higher success orientation and be driven at the business level to be the best in the market (Hasan and Ditsa, 1999), suggesting a willingness to pursue superior innovation and investment in new technologies, thereby increasing their competitive advantage. This finding supports work by Eitle and Buxmann (2020). They found that high masculinity and intense competition pressure positively influence the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) applications by companies in Germany and the United States. The interview results might suggest that intense local competition expedites Greek B2B company's adoption of SM out of fear of losing customers or competitive advantage. Based on this finding, the resulting hypothesis is:

H16: Higher **Masculinity** score may positively influence B2B companies' adoption of SMM

17. Uncertainty avoidance

As previously noted, **Uncertainty Avoidance** may affect Greek B2B companies' adoption of SM. Societies with high uncertainty avoidance have numerous laws, rules, and bureaucracy designed to reduce uncertainty and risk (Hofstede, 1991). The economic crisis heavily affected the Greek economy, and the society is not comfortable in ambiguous situations (Tsatsou, 2012). Thus, uncertainty avoidance may cause resistance towards new technologies and innovations. The B2B Marketing Senior Product Manager (P2) explained that the economic crisis had played a negative role because "we are a bit left-behind in the digital age and we are not early adopters, we are late adopters". Also, Greeks "do not like change" and "resist change".

The connection between the economic crisis and uncertainty avoidance was also evident in B2B Marketing Section Manager's (P5) interview when she discussed how the last eight to nine years

have been difficult with considerable political and economic uncertainty. Therefore, it is natural for individuals and companies to proceed cautiously during uncertainty, taking steady steps.

Another indication of uncertainty avoidance is the Greek's need for security, as residents pursue jobs that offer security (Tsatsou, 2012), namely jobs in the public sector. This case study company was formerly a public company, and the average employment tenure with this company among participants was 15 years.

The interview results suggest that Greek society avoids uncertainty and ambiguity situations. Companies competing and operating in cultures that are uncomfortable dealing with uncertainty tend to take fewer risks than companies in other cultures (Kreiser *et al.*, 2010). According to Erumban and de Jong (2006), there is a close link between national culture and the pace of ICT adoption. The cultural dimensions of uncertainty avoidance and power distance have the most significant influence on ICT adoption. The interview results are consistent with Tsatsou's (2012, p. 177) study, which found that the uncertainty avoidance of Greek culture discourages technological development and innovation and explains the persistently low level of Internet adoption in Greece. She also suggested that the Greek society has “an identity of reaction and negativism to technology and change”. Additionally, researchers (Harzing and Hofstede, 1996; Özbilen, 2017; Gales, 2008) suggest that resistance toward change in high uncertainty avoidance societies impedes adopting new technologies and innovations. Since SM is a new technology, it presents as a form of change, so Greek B2B company resistance should be expected. Therefore, it is proposed:

H17: High Uncertainty Avoidance may negatively affect Greek B2B organisations' decision to adopt SMM

18. Short-term orientation

Countries with a high long-term orientation take a more pragmatic approach and are more focused on the future. On the other hand, countries that have a low score on this dimension tend to value social obligations and traditions and are generally past- and present-oriented (Hofstede *et al.*, 2010). Greeks are known to revere traditions, have a slightly reduced proclivity to save for the future and concentrate on achieving quick results (Tsatsou, 2012). The B2B Marketing Senior Product Manager (P2) believed Greeks “do not have a long-term orientation”, as they are interested in the present and do not make long-term plans. Additionally, the SM Section Manager (P9) explained that the lack of long-term orientation and the fact that “Greeks (...) are afraid of uncertainty” impact businesses and the adoption of new technologies in general. The B2B Marketing Senior Product Manager (P6) also commented on this topic stating, “the economic crisis has affected people and they are not taking risks”. She also explained that the economic crisis beginning to affect businesspeople in their thirties (30s) and forties (40s) who should be more willing to innovate, take risks, and explore new technologies. Therefore, the findings of this study reinforce how the Greek society is more short-term oriented since citizens demonstrate risk avoidance through slow innovation and technology adoption.

The impact of long-term/short term orientation on new technology adoption is a newer dimension recently added to Hofstede’s cultural model; thus, extensive analysis of its impact on the adoption of new technologies is lacking (Özbilen, 2017). According to Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov (2010), societies that score low on this dimension are considered normative societies that view societal change with suspension. They prefer to maintain time-honoured traditions and norms. Societies with a higher score on this dimension have a more pragmatic approach, readily adapt to changing conditions (Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov, 2010), and are more likely to adopt new technologies (Özbilen, 2017). Greece has a lower score of forty-five (45) in this dimension and is

a short-term oriented society (Hofstede, 1991). The interview results suggested a negative relation between the adoption of new technologies and SM respectively and the short-term orientation of the Greeks. This result is contrary to previous findings (for example, Gales, 2008; Erumban and de Jong, 2006) that assert how long-term orientation negatively impacts the adoption of new technology. This finding suggests that the short-term orientation of the Greek society negatively affects Greek B2B companies without a long-term vision, less willing to take risks, and do not see the long-term benefits of SM and new technologies. The formed hypothesis is:

H18: Short-term orientation may negatively affect Greek B2B organisations to adopt SMM

Section summary

In summary, five cultural determinants (power distance, collectivism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance and short-term orientation) emerged from the analysis. The updated preliminary model (Figure 6.6) includes the five dimensions of the Hofstede Model and validation results (validated or not) from the survey (Chapter 7).

Table 6.5 summarises the four contexts that emerged from data analysis of the interview data, namely the technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural contexts.

Table 6.5: A summary of factors influencing the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations in Greece (source: researcher, 2020)

Theme	No	Subthemes	Support	Evident in interviews
Technological context (TC)	1	Relative advantage	Supported	P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P9, P10, P11
	2	Compatibility	Supported	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11
	3	Complexity	Supported	P4, P6, P11
	4	Interactivity	Emergед	P1, P2, P3, P5, P6, P8, P9, P10, P11
	5	Trialability	Emergед	P1, P9, P11
	6	Image	Emergед	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11
Organizational context (OC)	7	Size	Supported	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11
	8	Top management support	Supported	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P9, P10, P11
	9	Employee knowledge	Supported	P2, P3, P5, P9, P10, P11
	10	Innovativeness	Supported	P1, P3, P4, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10
Environmental Context (EC)	11	Competitive pressure	Supported	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P9, P10
	12	Government support	Supported	P11
	13	External support	Emergед	P2, P4, P5, P7, P9
Cultural context (CC)	14	Power distance	Emergед	P4, P5, P6, P9
	15	Collectivism	Emergед	P1, P4, P5, P6, P9
	16	Masculinity	Emergед	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P9, P10
	17	Uncertainty avoidance	Emergед	P2, P4, P5, P6, P9, P10
	18	Short term orientation	Emergед	P2, P6, P9, P10

As a result of the thematic analysis of the interview data, nine initial subthemes were identified and coded in alliance with the themes of the preliminary conceptual framework (Figure 3.4). The technological theme included relative advantage, compatibility, and complexity. The organisational theme included size, top management support, employee knowledge and innovativeness. The subthemes competitive pressure and government support were also associated with the environmental theme.

Additionally, nine new subthemes emerged from the interview findings and were coded to the four main themes. Three subthemes related to the technological theme, including interactivity, trialability and image, while the subtheme of external support connected with to the environmental theme. The cultural theme included five emerged subthemes: power distance, collectivism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance and short-term orientation. Finally, no new subthemes emerged for the organisational theme.

6.3 Research Hypotheses

This section summarises the proposed hypotheses listed in Table 6.6 regarding factors influencing a B2B Greek organisation to adopt SMM. Interview data drove the formation of the proposed hypotheses that reference four different contexts: three contexts relate to the TOE framework, and one relates to Hofstede's Cultural model (see Section 6.2).

The table includes factors based on the literature review and those that emerged from the interviews later added to the conceptual framework and tested in the second study.

Table 6.6: Proposed hypotheses

Context	Hypothesis	Hypothesis statement
Technological	H1	Increased perceived relative advantage of SM may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
	H2	Increased perceived compatibility of SM may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
	H3	Increased perceived complexity of SM may negatively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
	H4*	Increased interactivity of SM may influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
	H5*	Trialling SM platforms may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
	H6*	Increased image of SM platforms may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
Organisational	H7	The size of the company may have a positive impact on the adoption of SM marketing by B2B companies
	H8	Top management support may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
	H9	Increased employee knowledge on SM may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
	H10	The innovativeness of the firm may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
Environmental	H11	Increased government support may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
	H12	Increased competitive pressure may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
	H13*	Increased external support may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
Cultural	H14*	Higher Power Distance may negatively affect the adoption of SMM by Greek B2B organisations
	H15*	Collectivism may negatively affect the adoption of SMM by Greek B2B organisations
	H16*	Higher Masculinity score may positively influence B2B companies' adoption of SMM
	H17*	High Uncertainty Avoidance may negatively affect Greek B2B organisations' decision to adopt SMM
	H18*	Short-term orientation may negatively affect Greek B2B organisations to adopt SMM

*new factors emerged from the interview findings

The conceptual framework was updated to include the 18 new factors that emerged from the interview data analysis (Figure 6.6) and validated to a larger B2B Greek organisations sample in the second study, discussed in detail in Chapter 7.

Figure 6.6: The updated preliminary framework of SMM adoption by Greek B2B organisations

The following section presents and interprets the interview findings related to the third research objective concerning the potential benefits of adopting SMM in a B2B organisation.

6.4 Benefits of adopting social media marketing in a B2B organisation

The focus of this study was on SMM adoption by B2B organisations within the Greek context, and the analysis of the interview data revealed several benefits of adopting and using SMM. Based on the results, this section helps to address Research Objective 3, namely:

RO3: To critically identify the potential benefits from the adoption of SMM for B2B organisations.

SM presence is a vital marketing requirement, but there are additional business benefits for being active on SM. Following analysis, it was evident that the case study company relies heavily on SMM to interact with customers and business partners, build brand awareness, and improve its reach. Table 6.7 presents the NVivo output for the theme of *Benefits* of SMM with its 13 subthemes. The following subsections present these various benefits.

Table 6.7: Benefits of social media marketing (source: researcher, 2020)

No	Subthemes	Description	Files ⁹	References ¹⁰
1	Interaction-engagement	SM help the company to interact and engage with its customers	11	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11
2	Brand awareness	SM help to create brand awareness	10	P1, P2, P3, P4, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11
3	Performance	SM help with the company's performance	8	P1, P3, P4, P6, P7, P8, P10, P11
4	Sales	SM help with sales	5	P1, P2, P4, P7, P8
5	Communication	SM help the company to communicate with its customers and business partners	4	P1, P2, P10, P11
6	Customer care service	SM help the company to provide faster and better service to its customers	4	P1, P7, P8, P9
7	Cost-effective	SM are a cost-effective way to get your sales back	3	P5, P7, P9
8	Effective targeting	SM help to select media that will lead you exactly to the audience you want to target	3	P3, P6, P8
9	Promotion	SM help to promote our products	3	P3, P4, P11
10	Reach	SM help to increase reach to the right people	3	P1, P2, P8
11	Understanding customers' buying behaviour	SM help the company to understand the customer's buying behaviour	2	P1, P11
12	Word of Mouth and building a community	SM creates eWOM and help to build a community around the company	3	P2, P6, P11
13	Thought Leadership	SM can establish the company as a thought leader	1	P1

1. Interaction- engagement

As Table 6.7 demonstrates, the most discussed benefit was company **interaction** and **engagement** with its SM audience. Engagement is crucial, as it helps the company develop favourable relationships with new customers and business partners that produce positive brand experiences.

⁹ The number of people who discussed the theme

¹⁰ How many times the theme was discussed across all interviews

All participants (11) of the qualitative study believed that SM allows the company to interact directly with its customers and business partners through “two-way communication” (P1, Senior Manager- B2B Marketing). Apart from other benefits, it demonstrates that the company cares about customer satisfaction and is always available to answer their questions. SM may also provide the company with valuable customer insights based on how the users interact with ads and campaigns. Additionally, SMM tools enable the company to receive feedback, deliver customer service to resolve problems, answer questions, and influence customer purchase decisions. For example, businesses can use SM accounts to elicit customer feedback, demographic statistics, interests, and brand opinions. As the Digital Marketing Senior Manager (P11) noted, “we can also use SM not only to get feedback from our customers but also (which is very important) to get feedback on which we can act, that is, to have actionable insights”. Therefore, customer insights can help the company engage their customers more effectively with their content and advertising.

However, the B2B Marketing Brand Manager (P3) stressed that B2B interaction is more difficult because many factors and many people involved can distort the general picture. Companies employ several people to manage data making the business profile page vulnerable to discrepancies:

you can create an image, but it depends on who is currently handling the page, who it will be tomorrow, what are third party interventions that may be higher in the hierarchy and so on. Consequently, communication between these two B2B business channels that sell in a business I think, is more complicated.

2. Brand awareness

The second most frequently discussed benefit was **brand awareness**. SMM helps the company gain recognition and is an easy and effective way to build the brand. The benefit of SMM over

traditional marketing is that it can access customers efficiently, which makes it an ideal way to communicate the company's mission and vision.

SM presence increases the company's visibility and helps both the existing and the potential customers find and connect with the brand (P8, Senior Manager- SM). SM are also a great place to share the brand's story and mission and spread the word about its products. As the B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) explained:

it's a very easy way to build awareness for our products and the brand image. We have a lot of products and it's a very easy way to build awareness for our products at a significantly lower budget compared to TV advertising for example.

3. Performance

Performance, described by 8 participants when answering questions about the benefits of SMM, was believed to be one of the main reasons the company decided to use SM. Performance campaigns offer the company the ability to reach its target audience at scale, generate leads, and increase sales and conversions. The B2B Marketing Section Manager (P4) describes these benefits in the following extract:

we run performance campaigns that end in leads and there is a track there is a flow of understanding how many of these leads become actual sales. Therefore, through the performance campaigns, which have tangible results, we can see how it has affected us in sales.

The B2B Marketing Brand Manager (P3) explained how the company uses the performance campaigns for generating leads and eventually sales:

we are running performance campaigns, campaigns that have the goal of “buy now” as a sales tool. In essence we divide the campaigns into two categories: the first category called awareness phase and the second category is called performance. With the performance campaigns our goal is to deliver results, primarily leads and in some cases where sales are made online, we drive them to the online platforms, and we do online activations (P3, Brand Manager- B2B Marketing).

Additionally, the company uses different metric tools to measure the cost per lead and the cost per sale and to make corrective changes to improve the performance: by changing materials, messages, landing pages on which they send their campaigns, or even changing entire campaigns to improve their efficiency (P3, Brand Manager- B2B Marketing).

4. Sales

Another benefit of SM is “the increase in sales”, even though “sales cannot be the primary goal”. The B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) shared the view that sales are a benefit that “...you enjoy from other things such as the brand awareness, the content you create and share for free and etc”. A combination of organic and paid tactics through SM platforms may help the company expand the reach and attract more leads. A lead generation is an excellent tool for B2B marketers, and a percentage of those leads may convert into sales. This finding is evident in the following account from the B2B Marketing Senior Product Manager (P2):

through the SM platforms, you can have reach, which means that you can reach some people, and this leads to awareness and lead generation and at the end could result in some sales.

5. Communication

SM may also benefit the company's communication with its customers. Through SM the company may frequently communicate with its customers and promote its products at a minimal cost; the customers will also have an easy-to-use channel to get in touch with the company. B2B Marketing Product Manager (P2) believes "SM is another tool in our hands to communicate new products, sales, competitions or anything else we would like to share with our customers", illustrating the communication benefits of SM. Also, as P10 (Brand Manager- SM) noted, "with a very small budget we can communicate and do both awareness and performance".

The Senior B2B Marketing Product Manager (P2) also believed that SM adds value to the company and "...gave us a different way of communicating with the customer base and that has both positive and negative results" (P2, Senior Product Manager- B2B Marketing). The customers can communicate their likes and dislikes about the company and its products and services.

6. Customer care service

SM platforms, particularly *Facebook*, can be used for customer care since they are an accessible channel for customers to promptly reach the company. SM Section Manager (P7) highlighted the use of SM as a care channel when he stressed:

customers can ask something or say their complaint through SM... It is less time consuming for them to ask something or complain over Facebook rather than to wait on the phone an hour to connect with a representative from the customer care department.

This immediacy with customers also changes the image that they people have of the company because "we have 5 million customers, and it is difficult to serve them anyway. So, the immediacy of the Facebook works as a customer care tool" (P1, Senior manager- B2B Marketing).

The SM Senior Manager (P8) also added that although it was not in their initial plans to use SM as a customer service tool, it gradually became one. As he noted, “before the SM, we used to have only the call centre. Now we are using additionally the chat box on SM and especially on Facebook”.

7. Cost effective

Another significant benefit is that SMM is more **cost-effective** than traditional marketing methods. The B2B Marketing Section Manager (P5) noted how it is cheaper to promote a SM post online “than take out a full-page advertisement on ten (10) or more newspapers or pay for expensive prime time on TV”. SMM “is a way to get your sales back” (P7, SM Section Manager) and “to have a return on investment” (P1, Senior Manager- B2B Marketing). It is also easier for smaller businesses to compete with large companies now than it used to be when the traditional marketing models were prevalent.

8. Effective targeting

Another benefit of SMM is that it helps the company **target** the right audience. On SM, “you can select the media that will lead you exactly to the audience you want to target, and you are not wasting a lot of money on clicks that will not lead to sales” (P3, Brand Manager- B2B Marketing). Some SM platforms offer in-depth targeting tools that enable the company to target only users who are most likely to be interested in the company’s products and services, which is difficult to achieve through traditional marketing. For example, on Facebook a company can target its audience based on demographics, behaviour, connections, interests, and geolocation. This kind of tools makes it “very convenient to find the right people, at the right time, at the right place to serve them the right product” (SM Senior Manager, P8).

9. Promotion

SM platforms can be an effective business tool to promote its services and prove its expertise, ultimately expanding its audience. As the B2B Marketing Section Manager (P4) explained, SM can drive traffic to their website and help people “...to get to know us”. Promotion and advertising through SM platforms are more effective and more affordable than traditional marketing. As the B2B Marketing Brand Manager (P3) shared,

SM has a low cost to use, a lower cost (than the traditional marketing) for promotion and advertising and a low cost of materials creation.

10. Reach

As emerging throughout the above discussions, through SM platforms, the company can directly “reach its audience where they are and at a time that is convenient for the user” (P11, Senior Manager- Digital Marketing). SMM helps the company promote its products and services more creatively. It is an opposite approach to the traditional push marketing, as here a company can have a pull approach and draw customers to its products by establishing a loyal following:

With SM we can reach our customers and business partners in a more creative way. The way before it was push and now with the two-way communication through SM, the communication became more pull (B2B Marketing Brand Manager, P3).

The SM Senior Manager (P8) also believed that SM campaigns help the company reach its target audience and explained that companies could also monitor the number of users that their campaign reaches and establish valuable demographic characteristics of these users. Understanding the audience characteristics, in turn, helps to tailor future campaigns. As a result, as the SM Section Manager (P7) pointed out, “in Greece we are first in KPIs (Key Performance Indicator) in front of our competitors not only in the number of subscribers but also in the reach that our posts have”.

Regarding the various audiences that one can reach with SMM, “with Facebook advertising and with the same budget you have the same chance to get a customer in England and someone in Athens” (SM Senior Manager, P8). She further explained that a company can achieve considerable exposure at a relatively low costs with SM platforms, so “a local company can go global with a budget can handle it locally”.

11. Understanding customers buying behaviour

SM can be an effective tool for gaining marketplace insights. Direct communication with the audience enables the companies to understand the customers’ needs and interests and, consequently, generate insights into customer buying behaviour. As the Digital Marketing Senior Manager (P11) noted, “with SM we can easily read the pulse of our customers, we can see what suits them and enables us to see customers buying behaviour”. He also believed that companies could use SM to “test things, to know the people’s reactions to a new product before the launch and to generate revenue”.

12. Word of Mouth and building a community

SM platforms can be an excellent tool for generating word of mouth (WOM) and recommendations for the company. As the B2B Marketing Senior Product Manager (P2) reflected:

the digital word of mouth builds the company’s image that is a brand close to people and out there. I believe that the Word-of-Mouth is an essential element; it helps with the shares and creates virality. Great content can go viral and can reach hundreds or thousands of people fast.

Further, she explained how people tend to trust recommendations from family, friends, and online reviews from other customers; therefore, the company regularly engages with influencers and

bloggers to stimulate eWOM on different SM platforms and influence customer purchasing decisions.

The WOM approach also bolsters the company fan base that creates “a community around the brand and talk and listen to the customer” (P11, Senior Manager- Digital Marketing). Engaged customers buy more often, and the company can generate a high customer lifetime loyalty. The Digital Marketing Senior Manager (P11) discussed how, through SM, customers “can easily and quickly communicate with the company and with the world about its products”. Meanwhile, the company has “direct access to the customers and respond quickly with the necessary information sought” (P11, Senior Manager- Digital Marketing).

13. Thought Leadership

Finally, the company uses SM platforms to generate content and share its knowledge and industry insights to build its reputation as a thought leader in the telecommunication industry. Specifically, the B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) mentioned,

SM help[s] the company to showcase its industry expertise and is a source of information on topics related to the telecommunication industry.

Being a thought leader helps the company “gain the trust of its customers and business partners”, as well as may “benefit the company when potential customers and business partners will seek for a qualified partner” (P1, Senior Manager- B2B Marketing).

Notwithstanding these various benefits of SM for the business, the participants also extensively discussed barriers to SM adoption that a company may face and discussed in the following section.

6.5 Barriers to the adoption of social media marketing

This section addresses the following research objective:

RO4: To critically examine the barriers faced by B2B organisations for the adoption of SMM

According to the interview results, the main barriers to SM adoption faced by B2B companies in Greece include a lack of knowledge on how to use SM, internal bureaucracy, lack of digital culture in Greece, and available budget for SM. Table 6.8 presents these and the remaining barriers to SM adoption that emerged during thematic analysis. Each barrier is discussed in subsequent subsections.

Table 6.8: Barriers to social media marketing adoption (source: researcher, 2020)

No	Barriers	Description	Files ¹¹	References ¹²
1	Lack of knowledge of how to use them	They don't know how to use SM	5	P1, P4, P6, P7, P9
2	Company's internal bureaucracy and complicated structure	Internal Bureaucracy- Complicated organizational structure	4	P4, P5, P6, P9
3	Financial- budget	The available budget to spent for hiring a specialist and for promotion	3	P4, P7, P8
4	GDPR restrictions	GDPR restrictions to use lead ads	2	P3, P8
5	Lack of ROI measurement	They can't measure the ROI of their investment	2	P1, P11
6	Negative comments- feedback	Fear for bad criticism and negative comments	2	P2, P4
7	Lack of SM strategy	Lack of SM strategy by the companies	1	P1
8	Lack of relevance with B2B sector	Perception that you don't need to use SM in B2B	1	P1

¹¹ The number of people who discussed the theme

¹² How many times the theme was discussed across all interviews

1. Lack of knowledge of how to use SM

Not surprisingly, the lack of knowledge of how to use SM emerged as the main barrier to SMM adoption. In the following extract, the B2B Marketing Section Manager (P4) reflects on the various areas of SM expertise that may pose difficulties:

I believe that the biggest barrier for the Greek companies and especially for the small ones is the lack of knowledge of how to use them and the unawareness of its benefits. They don't know where to go, who can help them, how to set up a SM account, what to upload, what a post should be about, what to write under a photo, what day they should post something etc.

As P1 (Senior Manager- B2B Marketing) explained, "if you don't have the knowledge and the right people, (...) you have the uncertainty of how to do it". Thus, there is a need to either train the current staff or hire people who already have SMM skills.

2. Company's internal bureaucracy and complicated structure

Four participants recognized that the company's internal bureaucracy might be another barrier to SM adoption, not least because it hinders risk taking and creativity. The bureaucratic processes tend to affect the ability of individual departments to act independently and make decisions without approval from other departments or from above, reflected in the following comment made by the B2B Marketing Section Manager (P4):

There is no flexibility, we are a very large organisation, we are too many people, every division has its own needs, but unfortunately, we are very much affected by the company's SM calendar.

These same participants later expressed a view that the process of getting approval is usually time-consuming and complicated and may ultimately affect the company's commercial goals:

For example, we want (the B2B department) to launch three campaigns in a month, but the SM department tell us that we can post only one because other departments for e.g., the B2C wants to post their campaigns too. This internally process is very complex and there is no alternative. You are forcing yourself to modify your own plans because you cannot have the presence you want in SM.

3. Financial- budget

SMM, generally perceived as a cost-effective tool, can help a B2B company gain brand awareness and contribute to lead generation, conversion, and revenue growth. However, running a more sophisticated and effective campaign may be expensive. As the B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P4) explained, rather than uploading content organically, one must spend some money on promoting this content. She also noted that “after the economic recession the available budget is an issue for many companies in Greece”. However, as the SM Senior Manager (P8) suggested, “the budget for SMM (...) is much lower than the tradition media”.

Another interviewee, the B2B Marketing Brand Manager (P3), raised concerns about LinkedIn which offers the most effective targeting functions but is also one of the most expensive adverting platforms. As he explained, “there is a minimum of 2500 euros that you have to invest for a campaign on LinkedIn and that means that is very difficult for a company and especially for a small business to afford it”.

The availability of adequate resources and budget for either hiring specialised employees or outsourcing the SMM campaigns is another challenge. As the SM Section Manager (P7) reflected:

Another barrier is the company's budget to staff a department to run SM. For example, our company has 17000 employees, but the SM department has only three people to manage the entire volume of all the SM of the group.

4. GDPR restrictions

Privacy is vital, and European Union (EU) has the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for all businesses providing their services to the EU countries. Greece is the only member of the EU where a company cannot use Facebook lead ads to generate sales. As the B2B Marketing Brand Manager (P3) explained:

the lead ads are an excellent Facebook tool, but it can't yet be used in Greece for legal reasons. Obviously, it has to do with the GDPR, it has to do with the protection of personal data. We are the only ones that still get negative responses from the legal department.

The SM Senior Manager (P8) also highlighted that GDPR is a barrier because they cannot collect data for their users:

It's a huge blow for those who want to sell on SM and get leads, because you can't ask for one's personal details, because it's not GDPR friendly.

5. Lack of ROI measurement

Another challenge in adopting SMM is the inability to measure the Return on Investment (ROI) of the company's SMM efforts on their business and revenues. ROI is also an indication of what is working and what is not and helps the company build and refine its SMM strategy. Few companies in Greece are using tools to measure their SM ROI, and instead they use intuition. They do not have the data to understand if it was worth the money they invested, emphasised in the following comment by the Digital Marketing Senior Manager (P11):

Most of the companies have not adopted any measurement tools. They don't know with numbers what each of their ads do, they work with intuition. It is very difficult when someone works only with the feeling, and the decision making hasn't been done based on data.

The B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) also pointed to differences in how small and large companies perceive SM ROI. As she explained, while small businesses want to quantify SM's success and they want to know "...how much will I get back if I run this campaign, if I make this page, if I set up an e-shop?", larger companies tend to understand the qualitative value of SM for the brand, better and that SM "brought me the awareness, improved the customer satisfaction etc." (P1, Senior Manager- B2B Marketing)

The employees (or marketers) need to prove how much the ROI is from SM to get approval for future budget requests. ROI is also an indication of what is working and what is not and helps the company build and refine its SMM strategy. How to measure ROI, in turn, depends on the strategy and the goals value (brand awareness, customer satisfaction) or profit (sales).

6. Negative comments- feedback

Another barrier to using SM can be the negative comments "... that the company may receive when it uploads something" (P4, B2B Marketing Section Manager). Companies can control the content of their posts or ads but there is no guarantee of how the stakeholder will respond to them or how they will share the content. Communication via SM is a double-edged sword; negative comments can spread exponentially, making it difficult for the company to control them. According to *the* B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1):

we do not control it; SM is not controllable, and I think that is the main problem. You cannot even control if a campaign will go super, and you cannot control something that can

go wrong. Because they can write underneath whatever they want. It's just like a wave and people share it; you cannot stop it.

People use SM platforms to post content they like and share their experiences with other users. Every time a user shares a bad experience that he/she had with a company or gives negative feedback, he/she potentially affects the brand's reputation that may prevent the company from doing business or establishing relationships with customers and business partners. Therefore, the company must address and deal with negative feedback and criticism promptly. As such,

...we ought to have a team to answer them and many times these people, who are isolated cases, create bad publicity. Of course, we deal with it, but it is bad for us because an answer to something bad can also go viral (P1, Senior Manager- B2B Marketing).

The company works with an agency that monitors the company's SM platforms and replies to all comments in a professional manner. In the case of negative comments, "...we address them, we apologize for the perceived bad experience or mistake and take the conversation offline to address the issue." (P1, Senior Manager- B2B Marketing).

Although some companies choose to delete negative comments, the case company's approach is to retain them, except for "the abusive ones" (P1, the B2B Marketing Senior Manager). Also, as P1 further explained, there are "some cases where our users themselves will answer to other people negative comments; we did not have to answer them".

7. Lack of SM strategy

Investing in a SM presence without a clear strategy waste time and resources. A clear SM strategy provides a framework for planning, prioritizing, executing, measuring, and optimising SM campaigns. As the B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) explained "everyone has to start with

what they want to do on their page, create a plan and have a suitable person to manage it all”. As P1 further explained, “without knowing your goals you can’t measure your success and the return on investment”. As previously noted, there are various benefits of using SM, but it is not enough to “just be on SM” (P1) or randomly post content without a strategy.

8. Lack of relevance with B2B sector

The participants reported a shared belief among the B2B marketers that SM are irrelevant with the B2B sector because the B2B buying process requires an individual approach with face-to-face interactions not achievable online. Therefore, there is a perception that one does not need to spend on communication with the B2B customers. The B2B Marketing Senior Manager (P1) articulated this perception stating, “B2B needs other tactics and not so much communication with the concept we give to B2C; needs other type of actions more direct and less advertising”. She also explained that there is a mentality that, in B2B, one can still rely on more traditional tactics such as cold calling and attending business networking conferences. She also commented that “B2B never need a big budget because salespeople are talking to them directly, what can we tell them now, what can we communicate to them? (P1, Senior Manager- B2B Marketing). This perception is a barrier, but many companies now understand the need to use SMM; otherwise, they will have removed an asset from the equation (P1, Senior Manager- B2B Marketing).

In summary, the study provides insights into barriers to adopting and using SMM. The barriers include lack of knowledge of how to use them, accessibility, ambiguity, high cost, mistargeting, fear to use SM, GDPR restrictions, internal bureaucracy, lack of control over communication, lack of creativity on B2B campaigns, mentality about B2B marketing, lack of digital culture, lack of ROI measurement, lack of SM strategy and negative feedback. The following section provides a discussion of the qualitative findings about the benefits and barriers.

6.6 Discussion on the qualitative findings about the benefits and barriers

6.6.1 Benefits

As noted in section 6.3, the most important benefit of SM usage for the case study company is the interaction and engagement with its SM users. The company can use SM to interact and communicate more rapidly and effectively with its customers and business partners (Rapp *et al.*, 2013). Previous studies on SM use to build strong relationships with customers (Sashi, 2012) and business partners (Iankova *et al.*, 2018) document the importance of engagement. The interviewees also identified brand awareness as an essential benefit, which coincides with findings from previous research (Järvinen *et al.*, 2012; Michaelidou *et al.*, 2011; Cawsey and Rowley, 2016; Karjaluoto *et al.*, 2015), namely studies that found that B2B companies use SM platforms to build brand awareness among customers and stakeholders.

The qualitative data revealed how SM applications helped the company enhance its business performance (Wang, Pauleen and Zhang, 2016) in different areas. SMM bolsters company sales (Wood and Khan, 2016), establishes two-way communication with SM users (Fraccastoro, Gabriellsson and Pullins, 2020), improves customer service (Agnihotri *et al.*, 2012), and reduces costs for marketing and advertising (Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2015).

The participants also considered targeting an advantage. This result is consistent with Tsimonis and Dimitriadis (2014). They found that SM help the Greek companies to access new audiences in a more targeted way and implement their SM strategies according to their user's profiles. Moreover, SM usage helps the companies promote their brand and their marketing activities efficiently and effectively (Tsimonis and Dimitriadis, 2014).

SM platforms can help B2B companies reach new audiences and business partners (Vasudevan and Kumar, 2018) and their end-users (Lashgari *et al.*, 2018) more effectively. In addition, the

empirical findings suggest that B2B companies can use SM platforms to understand their customers and discover their needs (Buratti, Parola and Satta, 2018). The interview results also suggested that B2B companies can benefit from eWOM (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2011) and can use influencers and bloggers to influence consumer attitudes and purchasing decisions (Cawsey and Rowley, 2016; Salo, 2017). Finally, the case study company uses SM tools to constantly generate and distribute valuable content to position its brand as a thought leader in its highly competitive industry (Magno and Cassia, 2020; Brennan and Croft, 2012).

6.6.2 Barriers

The most significant barrier that prevents a Greek B2B organisation from adopting SMM is the lack of knowledge of how to use it. This finding is in line with the results of Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011), which found that the most significant barriers preventing B2B SMEs in the UK from using SM were a lack of staff familiarity and technical skills. Another critical barrier for adopting and using SM by the case study company was its internal bureaucracy and complex structure. The company used to be a state-owned company which means high bureaucracy, inertia and risk avoidance (Loukis, Spinellis and Katsigiannis, 2011). Restrictive rules and complex business structures affect larger companies (Atanassova and Clark, 2015). Thompson (1965) suggests the conditions within a bureaucratic organisation are inappropriate for creativity, and alterations to the business structure are essential to increase the firm's innovativeness.

Another essential element preventing a B2B company from adopting SM is a lack of resources (Verheyden and Goeman, 2013; Jussila, Kärkkäinen and Aramo-Immonen, 2014; Kuikka and Äkkinen, 2011; Gazal *et al.*, 2016). Greek companies are likely affected, as the economic recession has tightened company budgets.

Another barrier impeding B2B company's use of SM is the GDPR restrictions. Companies should pursue compliance with these regulations; thus, marketers need to change their way of acquiring, using, and protecting customers' information. However, marketing activities can benefit from the data management requirements because they can improve the reliability of customer data. The lead numbers can be lower, but the lead quality would be higher. Therefore, the data privacy regulations can help marketers connect with people who want to hear from them.

Consistent with previous studies (Gazal *et al.*, 2016; Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011; Järvinen *et al.*, 2012), this study found that the B2B companies face some challenges when calculating SM's return on investment (ROI). Although there are several (quantitative and qualitative) metrics to measure the ROI, it is difficult for B2B companies to identify what benefits of SM would be used to calculate ROI (Gazal *et al.*, 2016). According to the interview results, the majority of the B2B companies in Greece using SM do not measure ROI at all.

Fear of negative comments and criticism is another element that could negatively affect a B2B company to adopt SM. Any negative feedback can damage a company's image (Alshamaila, 2018) and result in irreversible or expensive damage (Bulearca and Bulearca, 2010).

Moreover, the interview results revealed that a lack of SM strategy negatively affects the adoption of SM by a B2B company. A company's marketing activities might be ineffective if they lack a proper SM strategy (Hassan *et al.*, 2015). Lashgari *et al.* (2018) suggested that B2B companies need to have clear goals for using SM platforms, choosing the right SM tools, and post the relevant material to reach the right audience.

Finally, B2B companies are reluctant to use SM, as the perceived belief among B2B marketers is that SM are not relevant to the B2B sector (Michaelidou *et al.*, 2011; Swani and Brown, 2011). The B2B marketing professionals believe that SM and online communications cannot replace the

individual, traditional marketing approach, and this negative perception prevents companies from adopting SMM (Lacka and Chong, 2016)

6.7 Conclusion

This chapter presented the findings from semi-structured interviews with 11 employees from the case study company- a telecommunication company in Greece. The results were analysed using thematic analysis and organised based on deductive codes proposed in the conceptual framework (Figure 3.4). Additionally, new themes and inductive codes emerged from the interview data. The findings provided insights into the following issues:

9. The factors influencing a Greek B2B company to adopt and use SMM.
10. The benefits of adopting SMM.
11. The barriers that a B2B organization may face in adopting SM for marketing purposes.

The findings contributed to understanding factors that the participants believed to have influenced their company to adopt and use SMM. The identified factors include technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural factors. Based on the qualitative analysis, eighteen (18) hypotheses were developed, added to the conceptual framework (Figure 6.6), and tested in the quantitative phase. Additionally, this study explored the benefits and barriers to adopting SMM, as experienced by a Greek B2B case study organisation. In summary, there were thirteen (13) benefits and eight (8) barriers reported by participants. The next chapter presents the findings from the quantitative phase.

CHAPTER 7 – THE QUANTITATIVE STUDY

7.1 Introduction

Chapter 7 presents the statistical analysis of the results gathered through the online survey with B2B companies operating in Greece. The quantitative study builds on the qualitative findings to assess the results of the hypotheses testing in relation to the theoretical framework used to examine the SMM adoption by B2B organisations in Greece. There are three main sections in this chapter. Section 7.2. reveals the sample's descriptive statistics, followed by section 7.3. which presents the inferential statistics to test the hypotheses, and 7.4. concludes this chapter by describing the outcomes of the statistical analysis discussed in sections 7.2 and 7.3.

7.2 Descriptive statistics: Characteristics of the sample

This section presents the descriptive statistical analysis for the first part of the quantitative questionnaire. Descriptive statistics describe the basic features of the data in a quantitative study and provide a simple summary of the study measures and sample (Trochim, 2000). The descriptive analysis provides the demographic characteristics of survey respondents and their companies; demographics present on SM adopters and non-adopters. SM adopters are those who have adopted SM for more than two years, and non-adopters have fewer than two years of SM adoption or have not yet adopted SM. This classification based on adoption time, was made because only N=9 companies of the sample (12.5%) had not adopted SM yet (as depicted in section 7.2.2.7), deriving a not adequate sample to perform inferential statistics. To justify this categorization, companies that have adopted SM in the B2B context for over two years may be considered more experienced in the use of SM and more knowledgeable about the actual benefits and challenges of its use than more recent or future adopters. Moreover, the benefits of a company's SM presence are not

instantaneous but rather revealed over time (Foroudi *et al.*, 2020). Another essential factor for the grouping of non-adopters with recent adopters is the intention of the former to adopt SM in the immediate future (see 7.2.2.8).

7.2.1 Respondent's characteristics

This section presents the demographic characteristics of the 72 respondents that participated in the online survey. These characteristics include job status, age, and education level. Table 7.1 summarizes the demographic characteristics and the analysis for adopters (65.3%) and non-adopters (34.7%).

Table 7.1: Descriptive statistics on respondent's demographic characteristics

Demographics	Frequency	%	Adopters	%	Non adopters	%
Respondent's job status						
Owner	27	37.5	17	36.2	10	40.0
Senior Manager	10	13.9	8	17.0	2	8.0
Junior Manager	19	26.4	13	27.7	6	24.0
Other	16	22.2	9	19.1	7	28.0
Respondent's age						
Less than 20	0	0	0	0	0	0
20-29	3	4.2	1	2.1	2	8.0
30-39	20	27.8	13	27.7	7	28.0
40-49	40	55.6	26	55.3	14	56.0
50-59	8	11.1	6	12.8	2	8.0
More than 60	1	1.4	1	2.1	0	0
Education level						
Primary	0	0	0	0	0	0
Secondary	17	23.6	10	21.3	7	28.0
Higher education	55	76.4	37	78.7	18	72.0
Total adopters			47		65.3%	
Total non-adopters			25		34.7%	

7.2.1.1 Job status

Among the participants, most held a leadership position (40.3%) or were business owners (37.5%). The remaining 16 respondents (22.2%) were employees in different departments, as shown in Figure 7.1. Thus, based on participants' reported job status, more than three-quarters of the participants make decisions for the companies; therefore, responsible for the adopting of SMM.

Figure 7.1: Respondent's job status

7.2.1.2. Age

Participants reported their age within one of six groups provided (Figure 7.2). Participants aged 40 to 49 years old accounted for more than half of all participants (55.6%), whereas those between the ages of 30 and 39 years old (27.8%) comprised the second largest group. No participant reported being under 20 years of age. The three remaining groups accounted for 16.7% of the sample and included those between 20 to 29, 50 to 59, and over 60. These findings align with the recent statistics from the Hellenic Statistical Authority- ELSTAT (2020) that the 30 to 64 years old group is the largest in Greece (Figure 7.3).

Figure 7.2: Respondent's age

(In thousands)

		Employed	Unemployed	Inactive	Unemployment rate (%)	Labour force rate (%)
	Total⁽²⁾	3,926.8	756.4	4,394.1	16.2	51.6
SEX	Males	2,268.4	340.8	1,764.7	13.1	59.7
	Females	1,658.4	415.6	2,629.4	20.0	44.1
AGE	15 - 19	16.0	10.7	544.6	40.0	4.7
	20 - 24	136.9	68.7	264.4	33.4	43.7
	25 - 29	332.0	120.8	109.0	26.7	80.6
	30 - 44	1,536.7	292.4	277.9	16.0	86.8
	45 - 64	1,805.1	254.5	944.5	12.4	68.6
	65+	100.1	9.4	2,253.8	8.6	4.6

Figure 7.3: Table of employment status in Greece, 3rd Quarter 2020 (ELSTAT, 2020)

7.2.1.3. Education level

Participants shared their highest level of education (Figure 7.4). About three-quarters (76.4%) have a higher education degree (University degree), while approximately one-quarter (23.6%) reported their highest education was at the secondary level (High School- Lykeio). When evaluating the highest education level among adopters and non- adopters, 78.7% of the adopters reported having

a higher education degree, which might signify that those with higher education understand the benefits of SM and chose to adopt SMM.

Figure 7.4: Education level

7.2.2 Companies' demographics

The online survey also examined the demographic characteristics of the sampled companies. Table 7.2 presents the relevant summary data regarding the size of the company (number of employees), the profits (annual sales), years since establishment, industry in which the company operates, and market scope. The companies vary in number of employees, turnover, industry, and market scope. However, almost all companies have been in business for more than five years (94.4%) and most are B2B and B2C (75%) companies.

Table 7.2: Descriptive statistics on company's demographic characteristics

Demographics	Frequency	%	Adopters	%	Non adopters	%
Number of employees						
1-9	25	34.7	14	29.8	11	44.0
10-49	18	25.0	9	19.1	9	36.0
50-249	12	16.7	7	14.9	5	20.0
More than 500	17	23.6	17	36.2	0	0
Turnover						
Less than 25,000€	6	8.3	4	8.5	2	8.0
25,000€- 100,000€	9	12.5	6	12.8	3	12.0
100,000€-250,000€	5	6.9	2	4.3	3	12.0
250,000€-1,000,000€	13	18.1	6	12.8	7	28.0
1,000,000€-5,000,000€	14	19.4	7	14.9	7	28.0
More than 5,000,000€	24	33.3	21	44.7	3	12.0
Company age						
Less than 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 3 years	1	1.4	0	0	1	4.0
3 to 5 years	3	4.2	1	2.1	2	8.0
More than 5 years	68	94.4	46	97.9	22	88.0
Company orientation						
B2B	19	26.4	12	25.5	7	28.0
B2B and B2C	54	75.0	36	76.6	18	72.0
B2G	16	22.2	12	25.5	4	16.0
Industry						
Manufacturing	5	6.9	3	6.4	2	8.0
Construction	2	2.8	1	2.1	1	4.0
Finance & insurance	2	2.8	1	2.1	1	4.0
Banking	4	5.6	4	8.5	0	0
Tourism	2	2.8	0	0	2	8.0
Food/ Beverage	21	29.2	13	27.7	8	32.0
Clothing	1	1.4	0	0	1	4.0
Wholesale & retail	11	15.3	5	10.6	6	24.0
IT & Communication	17	23.6	16	34.0	1	4.0
Education	1	1.4	1	2.1	0	0

Government	1	1.4	0	0	1	4.0
Health Services	4	5.6	2	4.3	2	8.0
e-commerce	1	1.4	1	2.1	0	0
Market scope						
Local	27	37.5	16	34.0	11	44.0
Regional	30	41.7	15	31.9	15	60.0
National	34	47.2	25	53.2	9	36
International	24	33.3	20	42.6	4	16.0
SM use						
Less than 6 months	1	1.4	0	0	1	4.0
6 to 12 months	1	1.4	0	0	1	4.0
1-2 years	14	19.4	0	0	14	56.0
More than 2 years	47	65.3	47	100.0	0	0

7.2.2.1 Size of the company

The highest proportion (34.70%) of the sampled companies were classified as micro-companies (less than 10 employees), which aligns with the given definition of Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the European Union and Greece (Table 7.3). Most of the sampled companies (76.4%) have fewer than 250 employees. SMEs in Greece represent 99.9% of the entire private sector of the country, and micro enterprises (1 to 5 employees and below €1mil. revenues) represent 96.6% of the private sector and 56% of the total employment of the Greek economy (GSEVEE, 2014).

Table 7.3: EU SMEs definition (Source: <http://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/business-friendly-environment/>)

Company category	Staff headcount	Turnover	Balance sheet total
Medium-sized	< 250	≤ € 50 m	≤ € 43 m
Small	< 50	≤ € 10 m	≤ € 10 m
Micro	< 10	≤ € 2 m	≤ € 2 m

The proportion of companies who fell in the small-company category (less than 50 employees) represent a quarter (25%) of the sample and 16.70% fell in the SMEs category (50 to 250

employees). The remaining 23.6% of the sample are large companies with more than 500 employees (Figure 7.5).

Figure 7.5: Size-Number of employees

Table 7.4 presents the crosstabulation between the number of employees and SM adoption. Chi-square test of independence shows that there is statistically significant association between the number of employees and SM adoption ($\chi^2(3) = 12.101, p = 0.007 < 0.01$), where companies with more than 5000 employees are more likely to be adopters (100%) compared to 50%-58.3% of companies with less employees.

Table 7.4: Crosstabulation between Number of employees and SM adoption

Number of Employees	Adoption				Total
	Non-adopters		Adopters		
	N	%	N	%	N
1-9	11	44.00%	14	56.00%	25
10-49	9	50.00%	9	50.00%	18
50-249	5	41.67%	7	58.33%	12
5000+	0	0.00%	17	100.00%	17

7.2.2.2. Profits

As far as the profits generated, 52.7% of the sampled companies report profits exceeding €1 million (19.4% between €1 and €5 million and 33.3% exceeded €5 million). Among the companies, 8.3% had less than € 25,000 turnover, 12.5% had profits between €25,000 and €100,000, and the remaining 6.9% of the companies had profits between €100,000 and €250,000 (Figure 7.6).

Figure 7.6: Turnover

Table 7.5 presents the crosstabulation between turnover and SM adoption. Chi-square test of independence shows that there is statistically significant association between turnover and SM adoption ($\chi^2(5) = 10.687$, exact $p=0.046 < 0.05$), where companies with very high turnover (>5.000.000€) are more likely to be adopters (87.5%) compared to 40% - 66.67% of companies with smaller turnover.

Table 7.5: Crosstabulation between Turnover and SM adoption

Turnover	Adoption				Total
	Non-adopters		Adopters		
	N	%	N	%	N
less than 25.000€	2	33.33%	4	66.67%	6
25.000€ to 100.000€	3	33.33%	6	66.67%	9
100.000€ to 250.000€	3	60.00%	2	40.00%	5
250.000€ to 1.000.000€	7	53.85%	6	46.15%	13
1.000.000€ to 5.000.000€	7	50.00%	7	50.00%	14
more than 5.000.000€	3	12.50%	21	87.50%	24

7.2.2.3. Company's age

Regarding the years that the sampled companies have been operating in the Greek market, the survey data revealed that most of the companies are “established” and operating for more than five (5) years (94.4%). The other two categories (3 to 5 years) and (1 to 3 year) account for 4.2% and 1.4% of the sample, respectively. Additionally, there were no start-up companies (less than one year) among the sampled companies (Figure 7.7).

Figure 7.7: Company's age

7.2.2.4. Company orientation

Regarding the company's orientation, the survey data (Figure 7.8) revealed that nineteen (19) companies (26.4%) had B2B orientation, twelve (12) SMM adopters and seven (7) non-adopters. Most of the sampled companies (75%, N=54) had Business-to-Business (B2B) and Business-to-Consumer (B2C) activities, including thirty-six (36) adopters and eighteen (18) not-adopters. Additionally, sixteen (16) companies (22.2%) had a Business-to-Government (B2G) orientation, twelve (12) adopters, and four (4) non-adopters.

Figure 7.8: Company orientation

Table 7.6: Crosstabulation between Company orientation and SM adoption

Company orientation	Adoption				Total
	Non-adopters		Adopters		
	N	%	N	%	N
B2B	7	36.84%	12	63%	19
B2B and B2C	18	33.33%	36	67%	54
B2G	4	25.00%	12	75%	16

Table 7.6 presents the crosstabulation between Company orientation and SM adoption. Chi-square test of independence shows that there is no significant association between Company orientation and SM adoption ($\chi^2(2) = 0.589, p = 0.745 > 0.05$).

7.2.2.5 Industry

The participated companies were trading in different industries. Most of the sample companies were from the food/beverage industry (29.2%), followed by companies in IT & Communication (23.6%) and the Wholesale & retail industry, representing 15.3% of the sample. The remaining companies (32.1%) were from other industries, including manufacturing, construction, finance & insurance, banking, tourism, clothing, education, government, health services and e-commerce (Figure 7.9).

Figure 7.9: Industry

Table 7.7: Crosstabulation between Industry and SM adoption

Industry	Adoption				Total
	Non-adopters		Adopters		
	N	%	N	%	N
Manufacturing	2	40.00%	3	60%	5
Construction	1	50.00%	1	50%	2
Finance and Insurance	1	50.00%	1	50%	2
Banking	0	0.00%	4	100%	4
Tourism	2	100.00%	0	0%	2
Food/Beverage	8	38.10%	13	62%	21
Clothing	1	100.00%	0	0%	1
Wholesale and Retail	6	54.55%	5	45%	11
IT and Communication	1	5.88%	16	94%	17
Education	0	0.00%	1	100%	1
Government	1	100.00%	0	0%	1
Health Services	2	50.00%	2	50%	4
E-commerce	0	0.00%	1	100%	1

Table 7.7 presents the crosstabulation between Industry and SM adoption. Chi-square test of independence reveals a significant association between Industry and SM adoption ($\chi^2(12) = 20.295$, $p = 0.013$), where companies in the industry of banking, IT and Communication, Education and E-commerce are more likely to adopt SM (94%-100%) compared to companies from other industries.

7.2.2.6 Market scope

Regarding the market scope of the sampled companies, the survey results indicate that 37.5% of the companies focussed only on their local market, 41.7% focussed on their local and regional market, and 47.2% also focussed on their national market. Another 33.3% of the sampled companies had an international scope on their business activities, and only 15.3% focussed on the global market. Additionally, the results revealed that most companies who reported having an

international and global scope also reported that they have already adopted SMM (82.85% with national scope and 83% with global scope, respectively).

Table 7.8: Crosstabulation between Company scope and SM adoption

Company scope	Adoption				Total
	Non-adopters		Adopters		
	N	%	N	%	N
Local	11	40.74%	16	59%	27
Regional	15	50.00%	15	50%	30
National	9	26.47%	25	74%	34
International	4	16.67%	20	83%	24
Global	2	18.18%	9	82%	11

Table 7.8 presents the crosstabulation between Company scope and SM adoption. Chi-square test of independence shows a marginally significant association between Company scope and SM adoption ($\chi^2(4) = 9.352, p = 0.053$). Companies with international and global scopes are more likely to be adopters (83% and 82%, respectively) than companies with local, regional, and national scopes (50%-74% adoption of SM). This result may suggest that the Greek companies with a more international view understand the benefits of adopting SMM for their businesses more than those with a focus inside the country. Further, more than half of the companies that focussed their business activities inside the country (61.5%) were also adopters of SMM.

7.2.2.7 Social media adoption

The survey also included a section with questions related to SM adoption. The first question asked whether the participant companies are adopters or non-adopters of SMM Table 7.9 presents the results. From the seventy-two (72) collected questionnaires, sixty-three (63) companies (87.5%) have adopted SMM while nine companies have not. However, a sample of nine (9) non-adopters was too small to apply inferential statistics. Therefore, the researcher classified companies who

have not adopted SMM yet (nine companies) and the early adopters- those who have adopted SMM for less than two (2) years- into the non-adopter's category together the companies resulting in sixteen (16) companies (Table 7.9). The new classification resulted in twenty-five (25) non-adopters and forty-seven (47) adopters of SM (Table 7.10).

Table 7.9: Non-adopters' classification

			How long has your company been using SM?			
adoption2			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Non-adopters	Valid	less than 6 months	1	4.0	6.3	6.3
		6 to 12 months	1	4.0	6.3	12.5
		1 to 2 years	14	56.0	87.5	100.0
		Total	16	64.0	100.0	
		No adoption at all	9	36.0		
Total of non-adopters			25	100.0		
Adopters	Valid	more than 2 years	47	100.0	100.0	100.0

Table 7.10: Adopters versus Non-adopters

Company type	Frequency	%
Adopters	47	65.3
Non adopters	25	34.7
Total	72	

The second question targeted adopter's companies asking respondents to identify which SM platforms were adopted by their business activities. The most popular SM platform was Facebook, used by sixty-two (62) companies (86.1%). Table 7.11 and Figure 7.10 depict the popularity ranking of SM platform used by the sampled Greek B2B companies. Nearly half of the adopter companies (52.8%) reportedly use Instagram, and the third most widely adopted SM platform was LinkedIn at 38.9%. Additionally, 30.6% of the forty-seven (47) Greek B2B companies reportedly use the YouTube platform, and only the 16.7% of those companies use Twitter.

Table 7.11: Adopted SM platforms

SM platform	Frequency	Percent %
Facebook	62	86.1%
Instagram	38	52.8%
LinkedIn	28	38.9%
YouTube	22	30.6%
Twitter	12	16.7%
WhatsApp	6	8.3%
Blogs	6	8.3%
Skype	5	6.9%
Pinterest	4	5.6%

Figure 7.10: Adopted SM platforms

Finally, the third question focused on using SM by the sampled Greek B2B companies (Figure 7.11). The survey results revealed that the Greek B2B companies use SM platforms mainly for advertising and promotion purposes (70.8%) because these platforms are less expensive than traditional marketing. Over half of the adopter companies (55.6%) indicated that they use SM to build their brand awareness and general marketing purposes. The results also show that the adopter

companies use SM to acquire new customers (51.4%), develop customer relationships (43.1%), communicate with their customers/suppliers (40.3%) and for providing customer service and obtaining customer feedback (31.9% and 30.6%, respectively). A smaller percentage of the sampled companies (27.8%) use SM for sales and share content to act as Thought Leaders in their industry (13.9% and 12.5%, respectively).

Table 7.12: Purposes of SMM use

Purposes of SM use	Frequency	Percent %
Advertising & Promotion	51	70.8%
Brand awareness	40	55.6%
Marketing	40	55.6%
Acquisition of new customers	37	51.4%
Develop customer relationships	31	43.1%
Communication with customers/ suppliers	29	40.3%
Customer service	23	31.9%
Customer feedback	22	30.6%
Sales support	20	27.8%
Product Demos	16	22.2%
Conduct market research	13	18.1%
Recruitment	13	18.1%
Share content	10	13.9%
Thought Leadership	9	12.5%

Figure 7.11: Purposes of SM use

7.2.2.8 Non-adopters

The survey questionnaire also included two questions (Q14-Q15) aimed at companies that have not yet adopted SM. As stated in Section 7.2.2.7, 34,7% (N=25) of the sampled B2B companies have not adopted SM yet, 44% (N=11) of them expressed intention to adopt SMM, and 24% (N=6) of them are not intending to adopt SMM in the future (Table 7.13). From the nine (9) companies

who have not adopted SM at all (Table 7.14), 20% (5 companies) planned to adopt SM within the next six (6) months, three (3) companies (12%) within the next 6 to 12 months, and one (1) company (4%) has no plans to adopt SMM.

Table 7.13: Intention of the company in terms of adoption of SMM

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	we intend to adopt SM	11	44.0	64.7	64.7
	we do not intend to adopt SM in the future	6	24.0	35.3	100.0
	Total	17	68.0	100.0	
Missing	System	8	32.0		
Total		25	100.0		

Table 7.14: When they intend to use SMM

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	in less than 6 months	5	20.0	55.6	55.6
	from 6 to 12 months	3	12.0	33.3	88.9
	no plans yet	1	4.0	11.1	100.0
	Total	9	36.0	100.0	
Missing	System	16	64.0		
Total		25	100.0		

7.2.2.9 Benefits and barriers of SM adoption

Participants rated several benefits of SM use for their company (Q21-Q22). Table 7.15 presents the mean values and standard deviations for adopters, non-adopters, and the entire sample. Based on the mean values, the most important benefits are advertising (M=4.39, SD=0.834), marketing (M=4.34, SD=0.808) and strengthening of company's reputation (M=4.07, SD=0.974). Analysis

of Variance (ANOVA) indicated no significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in perceived benefits of SM between adopters and non-adopters.

Table 7.15: Benefits of SMM adoption

			Non-adopters				P
	M	SD	Adopters				
			M	SD			
Added value	3.88	1.000	3.64	1.093	4.00	0.943	0.162
New business opportunities	3.96	1.028	3.73	1.077	4.07	0.998	0.207
Improved competitiveness	3.90	1.010	3.68	1.086	4.00	0.966	0.227
Reduced costs	3.06	1.157	3.00	1.069	3.09	1.208	0.774
Increased profitability	3.56	1.164	3.36	1.177	3.65	1.159	0.343
Improved the communication with customers/suppliers	3.94	0.844	3.91	0.811	3.96	0.868	0.830
Enhanced internal relationships	3.09	0.942	2.91	0.811	3.17	0.996	0.282
Enhanced external relationships	3.95	0.831	3.95	0.785	3.95	0.861	1.000
Strengthened company's reputation	4.07	0.974	3.91	1.192	4.16	0.852	0.335
Advertising	4.39	0.834	4.27	1.032	4.44	0.725	0.433
Marketing	4.34	0.808	4.23	0.869	4.40	0.780	0.415
Secure environment for information sharing	3.53	0.948	3.36	0.727	3.61	1.039	0.316

Moreover, Table 7.16 presents mean values and standard deviations for perceived barriers of SM adoption for adopters, non-adopters, and the whole sample. Based on the mean values, the most significant barriers are lack of sufficient financial resources ($M=3.82$, $SD=1.180$), goal achievement without SM ($M=2.93$, $SD=1.172$) and Lack of ROI measurement ($M=2.70$, $SD=1.243$). Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) indicated several significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in perceived barriers between adopters and non-adopters. Non-adopters view lack of time, lack of communication control, lack of ROI measurement, company size, and lack of SM strategy as more important barriers than adopters.

Table 7.16: Barriers of SM adoption

	M	SD	Non-adopters		Adopters		P
			M	SD	M	SD	
No added value	2.18	1.05	2.38	0.97	2.07	1.087	0.253
Lack of knowledge about SM	2.44	1.309	2.83	1.09	2.23	1.379	0.068
Lack of technological skills	2.28	1.289	2.58	1.248	2.12	1.295	0.156
Lack of time	2.54	1.295	3.17	1.167	2.19	1.239	0.002
Lack of sufficient financial resources	3.82	1.18	3.83	1.007	3.81	1.277	0.949
Lack of communication control	2.4	1.169	2.83	1.049	2.16	1.174	0.023
Lack of ROI measurement	2.7	1.243	3.21	0.977	2.42	1.295	0.012
Company size	2.12	1.066	2.63	1.096	1.84	0.949	0.003
Lack of relevance with company's goals	2.25	1.318	2.42	1.283	2.16	1.344	0.454
Negative comments or criticism	2.67	1.429	2.62	1.469	2.7	1.423	0.844
Goal achievement without SM	2.93	1.172	3.08	1.283	2.84	1.111	0.414
Inappropriate use of company's content	2.41	1.095	2.57	1.237	2.33	1.017	0.401
Lack of SM plan	2.43	1.144	2.88	1.076	2.19	1.118	0.017
Lack of SM strategy	2.43	1.171	2.88	1.076	2.19	1.16	0.020

Relative to the proposed steps for the adoption of SM (Q23), providing studies and reports (75%), using external consultants (76.4%), and SM training of the company’s employees (79.2%) are all considered efficient methods to facilitate SM adoption (Table 7.17).

Table 7.17: Ways to facilitate SM adoption

		Studies and reports			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	2	2.8	3.0	3.0
	Neither Agree nor Disagree	11	15.3	16.4	19.4
	Agree	39	54.2	58.2	77.6
	Strongly Agree	15	20.8	22.4	100.0
	Total	67	93.1	100.0	
Missing	System	5	6.9		
Total		72	100.0		

External Consultants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	2	2.8	3.0	3.0
	Disagree	3	4.2	4.5	7.5
	Neither Agree nor Disagree	7	9.7	10.4	17.9
	Agree	39	54.2	58.2	76.1
	Strongly Agree	16	22.2	23.9	100.0
	Total	67	93.1	100.0	
Missing	System	5	6.9		
Total		72	100.0		

SM training

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	1.4	1.5	1.5
	Neither Agree nor Disagree	8	11.1	12.1	13.6
	Agree	40	55.6	60.6	74.2
	Strongly Agree	17	23.6	25.8	100.0
	Total	66	91.7	100.0	
Missing	System	6	8.3		
Total		72	100.0		

Section summary

This section presented the descriptive analysis of the characteristics of the participants and their sampled companies. The next portion of this section communicates the findings of the inferential statistical analysis regarding the determinants of SMM adoption by Greek B2B companies.

7.3 Inferential statistics- Logistic Regression

Inferential statistics refer to the statistical analysis of a sample to make conclusions from these analyses about the target population from which the sample was selected (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). There are two (2) types of inferential statistics. **Difference inferential statistics**

(e.g., analysis of variance or *t*-test) test for the differences between groups, and the **Associational inferential statistics** (e.g., multiple regression analysis or correlation) test for relationships or associations between variables (Leech, Barrett and Morgan, 2005). The following section provides details and justifies the use of binary logistic regression (LR) to analyse the data from the online survey.

Regression analysis is a set of statistical methods used to estimate the relationships between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. It is perhaps the most frequently used technique in business and economics (Moy, Chen and Kao, 2015). In simple linear regression, one independent variable is used to predict the value of a dependent variable (Burns and Burns, 2008), while multiple linear regression is used to determine the relationship between a dependent variable and several (more than one) independent variables (Lee, Trimi and Kim, 2013; Burns and Burns, 2008). Nevertheless, linear regression methods are applied only in cases where the dependent variable is a continuous variable. If the dependent variable is not continuous, logistic regression is the preferable method of analysis. More specifically, logistic regression is a predictive modelling technique used when the response variable is categorical (Wilson and Lorenz, 2015). Binary logistic regression is an analysis used when the dependent variable is **dichotomous/ binary** (i.e., categorical with two categories) including values like 0/1, Yes/No, True/False (Leech, Barrett and Morgan, 2005). A binary logistic regression model predicts the probability that an observation falls into one of the two categories of the dependent variable. In logistic regression analysis, the independent variables can be either continuous or categorical.

Concerning the research objectives of the present study and the binary nature of the dependent variable (1=adoption and 0=non-adoption of SMM), logistic regression was chosen to investigate the effect of TOE and cultural factors (independent variables) on the B2B companies' decision to

adopt SMM (dependent variable). Previous empirical investigations in ICT studies and SM have used logistic regression (LR) to forecast the adoption of innovations. For example, Beier and Früh (2020) and Beier and Wagner (2016) used LR to examine the adoption of SM by Hospitals in Switzerland and Swiss SMEs, respectively. Zhu *et al.* (2003) used LR to estimate the adoption of electronic business by European firms and Alshamaila, Papagiannidis and Stamati (2013) used LR to examine the factors influencing cloud computing adoption by companies in Greece. The equation for the logistic regression is:

$$\text{Logit}(Y) = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_nX_n$$

- where **Y** represents the dependent variable; in this study, the Y variable showing whether the B2B companies will adopt or not SMM
- **b_0** represents the coefficient of the intercept (sometimes referred as constant)
- **b_1, b_2** are the coefficients of the independent variables of the model
- **b_n** represents the coefficient of the last independent variable
- **n** is the total number of the factors included in this study
- **X_1, X_2** and **X_n** are the independent variables; for the present study they denote the 18 factors included in the model.

Fernandes *et al.* (2020; 18-19) mentioned five steps for conducting a logistic regression analysis (1) identify a research question in which the dependent variable is naturally dichotomous, such as a B2B company's decision to adopt or not adopt SM, (2) the technical requirements must be observed, for example, problems of multicollinearity (= high levels of correlation between independent variables), (3) estimate and fit the model- for example, by comparing the null model (just the intercept) with the model that incorporates the independent variables, (4) interpret the results and (5) validate the results.

In summary, this section justified using LR as the appropriate statistical technique for analysing the survey data. It summarised the five (5) steps that a researcher needs to follow to undertake a regression analysis. The following section presents the second and third steps and the data requirements to ensure valid statistical inferences (Fernandes *et al.*, 2020).

7.3.1 Assessing the Logistic Regression Model accuracy

Several methods can be used to assess the accuracy of the logistic regression model before reaching definitive conclusions from the results (Stoltzfus, 2011). The main concern is that the statistical model should represent the collected data as closely as possible or, in other words, how well our model fits the observed data (Field, 2018). The overall significance of an LR model can be attended by (a) accessing the model's predictive accuracy of, (b) overall model assessment, and (c) assessing the collinearity between the variables (Peng, Lee and Ingersoll, 2002).

a. Model's predictive accuracy

The main aim of the LR is to ensure the highest prediction accuracy of the dependent variable (Hair *et al.*, 2006). On comparing LR with other similar techniques, for example, with linear regression, the logistic model offers the advantage of satisfying fewer assumptions to produce higher predictive accuracy (Domínguez-Almendros, Benítez-Parejo and Gonzalez-Ramirez, 2011).

A LR model provides a better fit to the data when it demonstrates an improvement over the intercept-only model, which is also called the null or baseline model (Peng, Lee and Ingersoll, 2002). The null model is simplest (and worst fitting) and includes only the constant and no predictors (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). The predictive accuracy of a LR model can be assessed with the use of the classification table. The results of the LR analysis in SPSS first present this classification table. The classification table is a measure of predictive power of the model

(Premkumar, 2003). In this study (Table 7.18), the base rate for the adopters is 65.3% (Yes: 47/72 and No:25/72), which means that the null model has a 65.3% overall correction prediction (Table 7.18).

Table 7.18: Classification table- Null model (Baseline model)

Observed		Predicted		
		Adoption		Percentage Correct
		No	Yes	
Adoption	No	0	25	.0
	Yes	0	47	100.0
Overall Percentage		65.3		

The full model is more complex (and “best”- fitting) and includes the constant and all predictors (independent variables) (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). This study used the SPSS statistical software program to compare the constant-only model with the full model. The full model (Table 7.19) included all eighteen (18) variables. A statistically significant difference between the null and full model indicates that the explanatory variables help to predict the dependent variable’s occurrence (Fernandes *et al.*, 2020). In this study, the omnibus test (Appendix G) for the full model was statistically significant ($\chi^2= 46.283$, $p= 0.001$). The observed value of the overall accuracy rate was 87.5%, indicating that the predictive accuracy of the model has improved by 22% (baseline model=65.3%). For adopters, the model correctly predicted 91.5% of adopters’ cases and 80% of the non-adopters’ cases. In conclusion, the Full model classification has greater discriminating power than the null method, meaning that the independent variables help predict adoption of SM in the B2B context.

Table 7.19: Classification table- Full model

Observed		Predicted		
		Adoption		Percentage Correct
		No	Yes	
Adoption	No	20	5	80.0
	Yes	4	43	91.5
Overall Percentage		87.5		

b. Goodness-of-fit of the Model

Goodness-of-fit statistics assess the fit of a logistic regression model against the data (Peng and So, 2002). This study used four different statistical tests to determine the goodness of fit (Hair and Anderson, 2010) including the Likelihood Ratio, the Hosmer-Lemeshow test, the Cox and Snell R^2 and the Nagelkerke R^2 index.

The **Likelihood ratio test** (often referred to as **-2LL**) is a test based on the difference in deviances: the deviance in the null (baseline) model minus the deviance with the full model (Peng and So, 2002). A lower deviation of the full model shows a better model fit (Field, 2018). For this study, the -2LL of the null model was 46.699, higher than the -2LL 46.283 of the full model (see Appendix G), which suggests that the new model (the research model) provided a more accurate fit to the data than the baseline/null model and, as a result, explained SMM adoption in a better way.

Another diagnostic test to determine the goodness-fit of the LR model is the **Hosmer and Lemeshow** (H-L) chi-squared test (Hosmer and Lemeshow, 2000; Field, 2018). The H-L test is more powerful than a common chi-square test when the predictive variables are constant variables or when the sample's size is small (Çokluk, 2010; Fernandes *et al.*, 2020) and only used for binary response variables. A small p-value under 0.05 means that the model is not a good fit (Field, 2018).

In this study, the value for the H-L chi-square test (Appendix G) is 5.783, $df=8$ and with $p=0.672>0.05$, indicating that the model fits the data well.

There are more indicators to guide the researcher regarding the model's predictive/explanatory power (Fernandes *et al.*, 2020). The **Cox and Snell R^2** and the **Negelkerke R^2** indices are frequently used. These two (2) indices present the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable that predictors can explain in the model (Peng, Lee and Ingersoll, 2002). In this study, the values are 0.474 and 0.654 (Appendix G), respectively, indicating that the overall model explains a significant proportion of the variance in the dependent variable.

After establishing that the model has a high level of predicted accuracy and fits the data well, the next step is conducting the multicollinearity diagnostic test to examine the correlation among the independent variables (Hair *et al.*, 2006).

c. Multicollinearity

Collinearity is a term used to describe the non-independence of predictor variables (Dormann *et al.*, 2013) or the strong correlation between the predictors (Field, 2018). Although there is no precise definition in the literature (Mason and Perreault, 1991), collinearity exists when we have an approximately linear relationship among two predictor variables. When we have a linear relationship between more than two predictors, we call it multicollinearity (Lin, 2008). This study used the multicollinearity term since the research model had 18 predictors. Multicollinearity represents a well-recognised issue, and its effect is well documented in the literature (Mason and Perreault, 1991). The failure to identify and report multicollinearity could result in misleading interpretations of the results (Vatcheva *et al.*, 2016).

The study used two different methods (through SPSS) to measure the multicollinearity between the independent variables. Firstly, the study used the **Pearson Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r)** to measure first-order correlations among the independent variables. Based on a criterion recommended by Cohen *et al.* (2002), a Pearson r coefficient above 0.9 indicates multicollinearity. A classic method of identifying multicollinearity uses the Correlation Matrix (Table 7.20) to understand the linear relationship among the variables (Field, 2018 and Cohen *et al.*, 2002). The Correlation Matrix can summarise the correlations between each pair of predictors and the correlation between each predictor and the dependent variable (Cohen *et al.*, 2002). In this study, the highest value of correlation is 0.850 (< 0.9) and therefore, there is no multicollinearity issue.

Table 7.20: Correlation Matrix

	RA	CMP	CMX	TRA	INT	IMG	SIZ	TMS	EPK	INV	CPR	GVS	EXS	PWD	IND	MSC	UAV	LTOR
RA	1																	
CMP	.49**	1																
CMX	-.082	-1.07	1															
TRA	.386**	.654**	.007	1														
INT	.758**	.570**	.016	.455**	1													
IMG	.850**	.536**	-.038	.379**	.684**	1												
SIZ	.179	.353**	.056	.319**	.201	.240*	1											
TMS	.562**	.682**	-.154	.420**	.488**	.640**	.393**	1										
EPK	.335**	.340**	-.438**	.329**	.354**	.204**	-.116	.128	1									
INV	.402**	.388**	-.122	.248*	.293*	.326**	.313**	.521**	.326**	1								
CPR	.528**	.359**	-.099	.166	.520**	.480**	.326**	.392**	.120	.308**	1							
GVS	.059	-.020	.127	-.138	.101	-.115	.054	-.161	.236**	.051	.016	1						
EXS	.225	.389**	-.057	.118	.294*	.265*	.284*	.353**	.001	.230	.401**	.075	1					
PWD	.007	.259*	.103	.173	.062	.087	.171	.242*	-.108	-.102	.105	-.096	.031	1				
IND	.353**	.448**	.037	.274*	.217	.403**	.204	.459**	.089	.289*	.257*	-.125	.128	.193	1			
MSC	.296*	.264*	-.015	.208	.251*	.295*	.185	.397**	.121	.253*	.274*	-.002	-.006	.308*	.560*	1		
UAV	.181	.258*	.095	.158	.250*	.249*	.222	.191	.133	.284*	.169	.159	.214	.046	.365*	.328**	1	
LTOR	.114	.132	.317**	.268*	.100	.079	.112	.099	-.057	.095	.033	.080	-.075	.442*	.156	.274*	.423**	1

*Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Through SPSS Statistics, two additional tests were conducted to measure the degree of multicollinearity among the predictors by calculating the following indices:

- (a) the **Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)**, which indicates whether a predictor has a strong linear relationship with the other predictor(s), and
- (b) the **Tolerance (TOL)** statistic, which is its reciprocal ($1/VIF$) (Field, 2018, p. 402)

The **Variance Inflation factor (VIF)** is a well-known statistic that measures multicollinearity (Hatzinikolaou and Katsarou, 2019). Chatterjee and Hadi (2006, p. 238) advocate that “a VIF in excess of 10 is an indication that multicollinearity may be causing problems in estimation”. This study applied criteria established by Menard (1995) and Field (2018). According to these scholars, a tolerance value of less than 0.1 indicates serious multicollinearity problems, and a VIF value greater than 10 also shows evidence of serious multicollinearity problems. If Tolerance is below 0.2 indicates a potential problem (Field, 2018).

Table 7.21 reveals that all tolerance values are greater than 0.1 ranging from 0.157 to 0.640, and all VIF values are below ten (10) ranging from 1.564 to 6.389. Therefore, these results indicate that the model in this study is free from any multicollinearity problems.

Table 7.21: Collinearity statistics- TOL & VIF

Independent variables	Tolerance (TOL)	VIF
Relative advantage	.157	6.389
Compatibility	.264	3.788
Complexity	.552	1.813
Trialability	.393	2.546
Interactivity	.284	3.515
Image	.189	5.281
Size	.604	1.655
Top management support	.278	3.597
Employee knowledge	.398	2.513

Innovativeness	.503	1.989
Competitor pressure	.535	1.868
Government support	.623	1.605
External support	.640	1.564
Power Distance	.556	1.799
Individualism	.474	2.112
Masculinity	.531	1.884
Uncertainty Avoidance	.518	1.932
Short term orientation	.463	2.160

7.4 Findings

The findings for each independent variable included in the binary LR analysis are presented in this section, along with an explanation of how they contributed to the overall model results. Binary LR included 18 factors (independent variables) that influence the adoption (dependent variable) of SMM among Greek B2B organisations. Table 7.22 shows the results of the binary Logistic Regression, and it offers a complete list of variables in the full model and the hypotheses testing. This study applied the following criteria established in the literature (Field, 2018; Hair *et al.*, 2006):

-A p value less than 0.05 indicates that there is a significant relationship between one independent variable and the dependent variable.

-A p value of 0.05 or more indicates that an independent variable has no significant impact on the dependent variable.

The factors (predictors) found to be statistically significant include interactivity (OR=0.019, 95% CI .000-.742), innovativeness (OR=3.762, 95% CI 1.144-12.368), masculinity (OR=4.958, 95% CI 1.172-20.969, and short-term orientation (OR=.099, 95% CI .099-.565).

Table 7.22: Logistic Regression

Independent Variables	β	S.E. (Standard error)	Wald	df	Sig. (Significance)	Exp (B)	95% C.I. for EXP (B)	
							Lower	Upper
Technological								
Relative advantage	1.725	1.672	1.064	1	.302	5.613	.212	148.748
Compatibility	.547	.891	.378	1	.539	1.729	.302	9.909
Complexity	.988	.543	3.306	1	.069	2.685	.926	7.788
Interactivity	-3.990	1.884	4.487	1	.034*	.019	.000	.742
Trialability	.548	.725	.572	1	.449	1.730	.418	7.160
Image	.483	1.550	.097	1	.755	1.621	.078	33.838
Organisational								
Size	-.934	.551	2.875	1	.090	.393	.134	1.157
Top management support	-.864	.796	1.177	1	.278	.422	.089	2.007
Employee knowledge	.091	.697	.017	1	.896	1.096	.280	4.292
Innovativeness	1.325	.607	4.760	1	.029*	3.762	1.144	12.368
Environmental								
Competitor pressure	.745	.642	1.345	1	.246	2.105	.598	7.411
Government support	1.300	.761	2.917	1	.088	3.668	.825	16.299
External support	.509	.411	1.533	1	.216	1.663	.743	3.723
Cultural								
Power distance	.242	.600	.163	1	.687	1.274	.393	4.133
Individualism	1.758	1.148	2.344	1	.126	5.804	.611	55.112
Masculinity	1.601	.736	4.734	1	.030*	4.958	1.172	20.969
Uncertainty avoidance	-.731	.678	1.165	1	.280	.481	.128	1.816
Short-term orientation	-2.317	.891	6.766	1	.009*	.099	.017	.565
Constant	-11.854	5.432	4.736	1	.029	.000		
C2 Hosmer and Lemeshow Test	5.783							
Initial -2 Log likelihood	46.283							
-2 Log likelihood	46.699							

Cox and Snell R ²	.474	
Nagelkerke R ²	.654	

*= $p < 0.05$, variables are significant at the 0.05 level of significance

**= $p < 0.01$, variables are significant at the 0.01 level of significance

7.4.1 Technology Context

This study tested six technology-related variables in the LR analysis for defining the factors influencing a Greek B2B organisation to adopt SMM: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, interactivity, and image. Table 7.23 summarises the hypotheses regarding the technological factors. The results from the LR show that only interactivity, has a p value of less than 0.05, thereby indicating that this variable significantly impacts the adoption of SMM by the Greek B2B organisations. The results for the interactivity ($\beta = -3.990$ and $p = 0.034 < 0.05$) suggest that interactivity has a negative impact on early adoption of SMM, indicating that early adopters did not consider interactivity as important as the non-adopters (including recent and future adopters). The p value for interactivity is $0.030 < 0.05$ and therefore leads to accepting hypothesis H4.

Table 7.23: Hypotheses related to the technological context

	Hypothesis
H1	Increased perceived relative advantage of SM may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
H2	Increased perceived compatibility of SM may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
H3	Increased perceived complexity of SM may negatively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
H4	Increased interactivity of SM may influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
H5	Trialling SM platforms may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
H6	Increased image of SM platforms may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

It was found that the other five technological variables (relative advantage, compatibility, complexity trialability, and image) have no significant effect on the adoption decision. More

specifically, relative advantage ($p= 0.302$), compatibility ($p= 0.539$), complexity ($p= 0.069$) trialability ($p=0.449$) and image ($p= 0.755$) resulted in significance levels greater than 0.05, implying that they had no influence on the decision of the sampled B2B companies to adopt SMM. Therefore, there was no support for hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H5 or H6, and these hypotheses were rejected.

7.4.2 Organisational Context

The logistic regression model (LR) tested four organisational factors including size, top management support, employee knowledge, and innovativeness. Table 7.24 presents the hypotheses regarding the organisational factors. The LR analysis revealed that only the innovativeness was significant regarding the adoption of SMM. The results for innovativeness ($\beta= 1.325, p= 0.029$) show the statistical significance, and therefore, innovativeness is a crucial factor when it came to early SMM adoption by B2B organisations, leading to the acceptance of hypothesis H10.

Table 7.24: Hypotheses related to the organisational context

	Hypothesis
H7	The size of the company may have a positive impact on the adoption of SM marketing by B2B companies
H8	Top management support may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
H9	Increased employee knowledge on SM may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
H10	The innovativeness of the firm may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

In this study, the remaining three organisational variables (size, top management, and employee knowledge) were not found to be significant predictors of SMM adoption. The results show that size ($p=0.090$), top management support ($p=0.278$) and employee knowledge ($p=0.896$) resulted in significance levels greater than 0.05, implying that they had no influence on the decision of the

sampled B2B companies to adopt SMM. As a result, there was no support for hypotheses H7, H8 or H9, and these hypotheses were rejected.

7.4.3 Environmental Context

Under the environmental context, this quantitative study explored the effect of three variables: competitor pressure, government support and external support. The hypotheses related to environmental factors are listed in Table 7.25. The LR analysis revealed that none of these variables were significant regarding the adoption of SMM. The results reveal that competitor pressure ($p= 0.246$), government support ($p=0.088$), and external support ($p=0.216$) resulted in significance levels greater than 0.05, showing a lack of relevance in terms of their impact on the sampled B2B companies' decision to adopt SMM. As a result, it may be inferred that hypotheses H11, H12 or H13 are not supported, and were rejected.

Table 7.25: Hypotheses related to the environmental context

	Hypothesis
H11	Increased government support may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
H12	Increased competitive pressure may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM
H13	Increased external support may positively influence B2B companies to adopt SMM

7.4.4 Cultural context

This study also tested five cultural factors in the logistic regression model: power distance, individualism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance, and short-term orientation. Table 7.26 summarises the hypotheses regarding the cultural factors. The results from the LR show that only two variables, masculinity, and short-term orientation, have a p value of less than 0.05. The results for masculinity ($\beta=1.601, p=0.030$) indicate that masculinity is positively associated with the early adoption of SMM. Additionally, the results for the short-term orientation ($\beta=-2.317, p=0.009$)

reveal that the high degree with which the B2B companies do not have a long-term plan in their businesses suggest that the short-term orientation has a negative effect on adoption, indicating that early adopters did not adopt SMM based on a long-term plan. Therefore, these findings lead to the acceptance of hypotheses H16 and H18.

Table 7.26: Hypotheses related to the cultural context

	Hypothesis
H14	Higher Power Distance may negatively affect the adoption of SMM by Greek B2B organisations
H15	Collectivism may negatively affect the adoption of SMM by Greek B2B organisations
H16	Higher Masculinity score may positively influence B2B companies' adoption of SMM
H17	High Uncertainty Avoidance may negatively affect Greek B2B organisations' decision to adopt SMM
H18	Short-term orientation may negatively affect Greek B2B organisations to adopt SMM

The other three cultural variables (power distance, individualism, and uncertainty avoidance) have no significant effect on the adoption decision. More specifically, power distance ($p= 0.687$), individualism ($p= 0.126$), and uncertainty avoidance ($p= 0.280$) resulted in significance levels greater than 0.05, implying that they had no influence on the decision of the sampled B2B companies to adopt SMM. Thus, hypotheses H14, H15 or H17, are not supported and were rejected.

As mentioned above, the LR results suggest evidence for the importance of interactivity, innovativeness, masculinity, and short-term orientation in the adoption decision of SMM by the Greek B2B organisations. Table 7.27 offers a summary of the accepted and rejected hypotheses.

Table 7.27: Summary of hypotheses

Hypothesis	Variables	Outcomes
Technological		
H1	Relative advantage	Rejected
H2	Compatibility	Rejected
H3	Complexity	Rejected
H4	Interactivity	Accepted
H5	Trialability	Rejected
H6	Image	Rejected
Organizational		
H7	Size	Rejected
H8	Top management support	Rejected
H9	Employee knowledge	Rejected
H10	Innovativeness	Accepted
Environmental		
H11	Government support	Rejected
H12	Competitor pressure	Rejected
H13	External support	Rejected
Cultural		
H14	Power distance	Rejected
H15	Individualism	Rejected
H16	Masculinity	Accepted
H17	Uncertainty avoidance	Rejected
H18	Short-term orientation	Accepted

7.5 Discussion on the quantitative findings

This section discusses the findings of the quantitative study. The current study attempted to examine the key factors that may potentially influence SMM adoption by B2B organisations in the Greek context by utilising the TOE and Hofstede's framework.

This section contains six subsections. Each of the first four subsections explains the findings regarding a specific context of the theoretical framework presented in Figure 6.6 (TOE and cultural

contexts). Two (2) additional sections discuss the findings for the potential benefits and barriers. The quantitative results indicate that the proposed conceptual framework is a solid foundation for investigating the factors influencing SMM adoption in the industrial context. Among the predictors, the current study suggests that the technological, organisational, and cultural factors are important determinants of SMM adoption. Additionally, the results indicate that the environmental factors are less important compared to other three (3) contexts.

7.5.1 Technological context

As mentioned in section 7.4, only interactivity significantly influenced the B2B companies to adopt SMM. The other five factors in the technological context (relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and image) were not statistically significant. This subsection presents the discussions related to the results of each factor.

1. Relative advantage

Relative advantage is one of the most consistent predictors adopting innovations and SM (Ahmad, Abu Bakar and Ahmad, 2019). Unexpectedly, in the current phase of the study, it was not a significant predictor of SMM adoption. This result differs from most of the published studies in the IT and SM adoption literature, as previous researchers contend relative advantage is an essential and robust predictor across a range of innovations in B2B organisations (Ainin *et al.*, 2015; Al-Qirim, 2007; Buratti, Parola and Satta, 2018; Shaltoni, 2017; Eid, 2009; Eid, Abdelmoety and Agag, 2020). Companies are more likely to adopt an innovation when they perceived that this innovation would offer them a relative advantage (Rogers, 2003). However, the result from the current study concerning relative advantage corroborates the results from prior studies (e.g., Ahmad, Abu Bakar and Ahmad, 2019; Al Rahbi, 2017) who found no significant relationship between relative advantage and SM adoption intention. Therefore, the benefits of SMM did not

influence the decision to adopt SMM among the Greek B2B organisations, probably because they have not realised its significance for operating their businesses. This finding is also consistent with Chui *et al.* (2012), who suggested that many companies who have adopted SM have not realised the benefits deriving from this adoption. This finding further indicates that B2B companies that do not perceive SMM to benefit or give them a competitive advantage have fewer chances to adopt SM positively, which supports the findings of Low, Chen and Wu (2011). Low, Chen and Wu (2011) studied the determinants influencing cloud computing adoption by high-tech industry companies in Taiwan. They suggested that companies realise the relative advantage of applying cloud computing. However, their lower level of cloud computing know-how and the implementation cost negatively affect relative advantage. Chatzoglou *et al.* (2010) also contend that the level of easiness of a new technology influences Greek employee. Further, there is a general reluctance, especially in older individuals, to use new technologies. These researchers suggested that people decide to switch from traditional methods to new technologies only when they believe that this will make their job easier.

2. Compatibility

Regarding compatibility, there was no significant relationship with SMM adoption. This result is inconsistent with other published studies (Premkumar, 2003; Zhu, Kraemer and Xu, 2003; Shaltoni, 2017; Abubakar *et al.*, 2017; Araújo and Zilber, 2016) who suggested that compatibility is a critical predictor of SM adoption. According to Rogers (1995, p. 240), compatibility is an essential factor in the decision to adopt an innovation and “is the extent to which an innovation or new technology is recognised as harmonious with current values, past experience and the requirements of potential adopters”. Ahmad, Abu Bakar and Ahmad (2019, p. 98) suggested that a possible reason for the insignificant relationship may be that SM is compatible with most existing

organisational infrastructure. Its “ease of use could therefore have negated the impact of compatibility on behavioural intention”. However, this inconsistency does not mean that Greek B2B companies think that SMM adoption does not have technology compatibility. One possible explanation for this being insignificant is the lack of digital culture in Greece as was mentioned by the Digital Marketing Manager in the qualitative study. Therefore, there is a lack of understanding and organisational support for adopting SM and new technologies.

3. Complexity

This study presents evidence that increased complexity was not negatively related to the adoption of SMM. This finding is inconsistent with previous research (Ahmad, Abu Bakar and Ahmad, 2019; Wang, Wang and Yang, 2010; Konstantinidis, 2016). According to Rogers (2003, p. 230), “adoption will be less likely if the innovation is considered as being more challenging to use”. Companies are less likely to adopt new technology if it requires a high level of new skills by the employees (Thong, 1999). The results are in line with some studies (Low, Chen and Wu, 2011; Shaltoni, 2017) that complexity was not a significant predictor for cloud computing and internet marketing adoption, respectively. For the current study, this finding may have resulted from the familiarity of Greeks with SM in their daily life for personal use, which participants mentioned in their qualitative interviews.

4. Interactivity

The quantitative analysis results, as presented in section 7.4, show that interactivity is a significant predictor of B2B companies’ adoption of SMM. This result is consistent with earlier findings, in this case of Ainin *et al.* (2015), who found that the interactive nature of Facebook and the two-way communication with the public influenced SMEs’ adoption of SM. The results from the qualitative study also provided evidence that interactivity of SM has a strong effect on the adoption

intention and was one of the primary reasons the case study company used SMM. However, some studies, such research by Al Rahbi (2017), indicated that interactivity is an integral factor in the use of SM by SMEs, as it may limit SMEs' ability to comprehend the interactive characteristics of each platform by utilising more than one SM platform.

5. Trialability

There was no significant relationship between trialability and adoption of SM. This result is consistent with earlier findings, in this case of Ahmad, Abu Bakar and Ahmad (2019), who found that a lack of relationship with trialability may be because SM can be adopted at a low cost, minimising the risk of its use. A possible explanation for this result is that SM platforms are viral among Greeks personally and may have increased their use among Greek companies. However, this result is inconsistent with the findings of Chong (2004), who identified a positive relationship between trialability and intention to adopt e-commerce. Additionally, Ramdani *et al.* (2009) stated that getting a trial version of an enterprise system before adopting is essential to the enterprise.

6. Image

Regarding the final technological factor, the image was not a significant predictor for the adoption of SM. This finding differs from other studies, as Al Rahbi (2017) and Al-Qirim (2007) concluded that image was perceived to have an impact on SMEs' adoption of SM and websites, respectively. According to Ramayah *et al.* (2013), perceived image influences SMEs' adoption of new technology. A possible explanation of this inconsistency is the lack of awareness of SM benefits and ROI measurement by the Greek companies as was stated in the qualitative interviews.

7.5.2. Organisational context

As mentioned in Section 7.4, innovativeness significantly influenced B2B companies to adopt SMM. The other three factors in the organisational context (size, top management support and employee knowledge) were not proven significant in the current study. Below is the discussion related to the results of each factor.

7. Size

Size is the first organisational factor. Size is one essential characteristic of an innovator company (Rogers, 2003). The interviews revealed how the organisation's size is an essential determinant for SM adoption among B2B companies, which is consistent with previous studies citing size as a predictor influencing SM adoption in B2B companies (Pascucci, Ancillai and Cardinali, 2018; Brennan and Croft, 2012). Järvinen *et al.* (2012) suggested that sizable B2B companies may consider SMM a crucial strategy. Fosso Wamba and Carter (2014) concluded that larger SMEs tend to use SM more because they have adequate resources to invest in those tools. Additionally, based on a survey with 120 companies operating in Greece and Cyprus, Mikalef and Pateli (2017) found that firm size positively impacts SM adoption. Larger firms have more resources to invest in SM and are not subject to as much risk as smaller companies.

However, the results from the quantitative study, interestingly, showed that the company's size is not a significant predictor of SM adoption. This result is consistent with Vlachvei and Notta (2014) study, which found no link between firm size and adoption by Greek SMEs. Additionally, Goode and Stevens (2000) found no association between the size of a company and its adoption of the World Wide Web. While the case study company is a large organisation with higher financial capability and more skilled employees, a few interview participants were concerned that internal

bureaucracy might be unfavourable for implementing SMM to the expected level of a large company.

8. Top management support

Concerning the top management support (the second organisational factor), the quantitative phase of the study found that it is not a statistically significant predictor of the adoption of SM. This finding contradicts the results of most previous studies, which assert that top management support is critical for SM adoption and new technologies (Pascucci, Ancillai and Cardinali, 2018; Fosso Wamba and Carter, 2014; Ahmad, Abu Bakar and Ahmad, 2019; Abubakar *et al.*, 2017; Pateli, Mylonas and Spyrou, 2020; Matikiti *et al.*, 2018; Abdullahi, Husin and Baharudin, 2021). Vlachvei and Notta (2014) suggested that managers with higher education levels create “a favourable atmosphere” to adopt of SM and innovative tools by Greek food firms. Additionally, Giotopoulos *et al.* (2017, p. 66), in a sample of 3500 Greek SME’s found that companies “who have visionary leadership committed to growth-driven goals for the business” are more likely to adopt and use ICTs. Knowledgeable managers with experience capitalising on new technologies to establish a competitive advantage are more apt to encourage technology adoption (Awa, Ukoha and Igwe, 2017). Additionally, Hoffmann, Lutz and Meckel (2013) suggested that the employees need top management support to implement a SM project successfully. Their support can include financial resources (Ahmad, Abu Bakar and Ahmad, 2019), investment in IT infrastructure, and providing training to build necessary IT skills for adopting and using SM (Themistocleous, 2004).

However, the findings of this study aligns with the results of Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin (2018) and Wang *et al.* (2010), who found that support from top management is not a significant factor affecting the adoption of SM and RFID technology, respectively. A possible explanation for this result may be that the SM adoption by B2B companies is still in its infancy (Siamagka *et al.*, 2015;

Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011). As such, the Greek managers may not understand how adopting these tools is beneficial and contributes to their businesses. Additionally, Greece experienced a “great depression” from 2010-2018 and an economic shock from the COVID-19 pandemic, which significantly impacted the financial resources of Greek companies and the Greek economy. Inadequate resources might be encouraging managers prioritise other projects within the company (Jussila *et al.*, 2014).

9. Employee knowledge

Employee knowledge was not found to be a major predictor of SMM adoption by B2B companies in Greece. This result supports the findings of Alshamaila *et al.* (2012) and Al Rahbi (2017), who found employee prior knowledge and experience with SM and cloud computing, respectively, is not an important antecedent to the adoption for two possible reasons. One reason is that SM’s perceived ease of use may require only general scientific knowledge and not specific ICT skills. Second, the level of knowledge tends to be more crucial in integrating and using SMM tools, where more specialised knowledge is necessary than during the initial adoption.

10. Innovativeness

The final organisational factor, the firm’s innovativeness, positively correlated with B2B companies’ intention to adopt SM. According to Rogers (2003; 990) innovativeness is “the degree to which an individual or other unit of adoption is relatively earlier in adopting new ideas than other members of a social system”. This result aligns with Shaltoni (2017), who identified a positive relationship between organisational innovativeness and internet marketing adoption. Innovativeness of the organisation regarding openness towards new ideas and new technologies is positively related to the adoption of SM (Fosso Wamba and Carter, 2014; Pascucci *et al.*, 2018). Based on this positive effect in the logistic regression, it is clear that the adoption of SM requires

innovative oriented firms and employees who are more prone to undertake risks (Agarwal and Prasad, 1998).

7.5.3 Environmental context

As stated in section 7.4.3. none of the environmental factors were significant predictors of SMM adoption by the sampled B2B companies. These results are in line with the study of Araújo and Zilber (2016), as they did not find a significant relationship between the environmental influences and the adoption of SM by Brazilian companies. Discussed below are the results related to each predictor.

11. Competitive pressure

Competitive pressure had no significant effect on SM adoption by the sampled B2B companies. However, this result differs from prior research on various technologies, such as studies by Mikalef and Pateli (2017); Shaltoni, (2017); Matikiti *et al.* (2018); Pateli *et al.* (2020); Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011); Siamagka *et al.* (2015); Alrawabdeh (2014) and Dwivedi *et al.* (2021). A possible explanation for the insignificance of this predictor may be that many B2B companies are unaware of SM benefits but adopted it for fear of being left behind by their competitors or because of its popularity. Alternatively, this inconsistency may be related to the Greek financial crisis of 2010-2018 that left the country in a prolonged recession period. According to Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), Greece ranks 27th place among the other EU countries (European Commission, 2020), reflecting the reduced penetration and use of technological solutions. Therefore, Greek companies may be focusing on survival rather than competition, for which SM adoption may be a means for survival.

12. Government support

The second environmental factor considered was government support, which was also not a significant predictor in the adoption of SM by B2B companies in Greece. This outcome differs from some previous studies (Abubakar *et al.*, 2017; Alrawabdeh, 2014). Government support referees to the level of national infrastructure (Alrawabdeh, 2014) and governmental assistance (Kim, Jang and Yang, 2017) to increase the adoption of SM within organisations. This study suggests that government support does not have a significant impact on the adoption of SM and does not explain any difference in SM adoption amongst adopters and non-adopters B2B companies in Greece. A possible explanation is that investment in SM adoption is not expensive and does not require to receive financial government support. Additionally, regulations changed under each government official for the past decade, which hindered the creation of favourable and consistent business environments indicating the need to reconsider government policy (Kim, Jang and Yang, 2017).

13. External support

The final environmental factor is external support which had a negative correlation with SM adoption. This finding contradicts the results of previous studies, for example, Alshamaila *et al.* (2012) and Mikalef and Pateli (2017), who found the availability of external support to be positively related to adoption of cloud computing and SM, respectively. A possible explanation for this inconsistency is the lack of awareness of the Greek companies and the SMEs about available support from specialists and SMM agencies. Therefore, it is vital for specialists and agencies to regularly conduct marketing programs, such as promotional activities and provide incentives to business associations for their members to adopt SM.

7.5.4. Cultural context

The survey questionnaire relied on Hofstede's (1991) work to expand on the cultural dimensions that influence a B2B company to adopt SM. As mentioned in section 7.4., masculinity and short-term orientation significantly influenced the sampled B2B companies to adopt SMM. This section presents a discussion of the outcomes of each cultural factor.

14. Power distance

Regarding the first cultural factor, the study provides empirical evidence that power distance does not significantly impact the decision to adopt SM. Power Distance refers to “the extent to which less powerful members of a society accept unequal power distribution” (Sørnes *et al.*, 2004). Greece has an intermediate score of 60, indicating that it has centralised decision structures and authority, and a higher inequality of power distribution that discourages technological advancements (Chatzithomas *et al.*, 2014). Tsatsou (2012) suggested that the dominance of “power distance” has created a less autonomous and active society that is less likely to take the initiative. This study may suggest that the unequal distribution of power within the Greek society and an organisation does not affect the companies’ SMM adoption. Moreover, differences of status are not associated with the Greek companies’ decision to adopt SMM.

15. Collectivism

This study did not find lower individualism/collectivism a significant predictor of SM adoption by the sampled B2B companies. Individualism refers to societies with loose individual ties and where everyone tends to their family and themselves (Sørnes *et al.*, 2004). Collectivism refers to societies where people belong “in groups”, and their loyalty to their group(s) lasts a lifetime (Hofsted *et al.*, 2010). At an individualist score of 35, Greece is a collectivist culture society (Hofstede, 1991). The current study suggests Greeks prefer groups that take care of the individuals and family

members. However, this preference does not affect the adoption of SM by B2B companies. This finding coincides with the work of Leidner *et al.* (2006) and Kollmann *et al.* (2009), who found that the empirical findings for this cultural dimension are insignificant regarding the adoption of IT.

16. Masculinity

Masculinity was the first cultural factor to positively influence the sampled B2B companies to adopt SM. Masculinity is associated with a focus on accomplishments and achievements, leading to SM adoption because of status effects (Kollmann *et al.*, 2009). Greece is a medium-ranking Masculine society with a score of 57. This finding aligns with Olasina and Mutula's (2015) study, which concluded that masculinity impacts e-parliament adoption. A possible explanation for this result being significant because, with a higher masculinity level in Greece, the B2B companies might have sufficient stimuli to adopt SM to be the best in their sector or industry. Perhaps there is also intense local competition. However, as Kollmann *et al.* (2009) suggested, in high masculinity cultures such as Greece, SM and general e-business projects should be aligned with a supportive and non-competitive organisational culture to foster the potential success of these projects..

17. Uncertainty avoidance

Contrary to expectations, uncertainty avoidance was not a significant predictor. Greece is a society that avoids uncertainty and has the highest score of 100. Hofstede (1991, p. 113) defined uncertainty avoidance as “the extent to which the members of a culture feel threatened by uncertain or unknown situations”. Uncertainty avoidance refers “to practices adopted and encouraged within the framework of a society in order the uncertainty existing among its members, often at the expense of experimentation and in favour of strict rules and strong legislation” (Papalexandris,

2007, p. 787). Many previous studies found that societies with high uncertainty avoidance take longer to adopt new technology and rely more on learning from early adopters' experiences (Sundqvist *et al.*, 2005). The Greek society has a high uncertainty avoidance, and it is challenging to integrate new ways of behaving and living (Voulgaris and Sotiropoulos, 2002) and has an identity of reaction and negativism to technology and change (Tsatsou, 2012). A possible explanation for this factor to be insignificant is that Greeks have positive feelings about SM in their everyday life because it enables sociability and enhances their social prestige. Therefore, this positive feeling may make Greeks feel that organisational usage of SM is not disrupting well-established customs and patterns of life.

18. Short-term orientation

The analysis of the survey data revealed that short-term orientation negatively influences Greek B2B companies to adopt SM. As mentioned in section 3.3, Greece has an intermediate score of 45 on long-term orientation. The societies with a culture that scores low in this dimension, are described as normative societies and prefer to maintain time-honored norms and traditions while viewing societal change with suspicion (Hofstede *et al.*, 2010). The finding from this study contradicts the results of a previous study by Özbilen (2017), who found an adequate positive impact of long-term orientation on new technology adoption at the firm-level. A possible explanation for the result of this study might be the lack of a SM strategy by the Greek companies and long-term planning on SM adoption, as was mentioned by participants in the qualitative interviews.

7.5.5 Benefits

Most identified benefits (Table 7.15) were qualitative benefits of using SMM, such as enhancing the company's advertising and marketing. SM enables B2B companies to combine traditional and

innovative tools into their marketing strategy and enhance and complement their promotional tools of advertising (Melanthiou and Papasolomou, 2015). Another benefit of adopting SMM is that it helps create awareness and strengthen the brand reputation (Rowley and Holliman, 2014; Cawsey and Rowley, 2016). This finding is consistent with the study of Tsimonis and Dimitriadis (2014), who found that SM helps Greek companies gain brand awareness and generate positive word of mouth (WOM).

This study also revealed how the adoption of SM by the sampled B2B companies had increased business opportunities generating new sales and marketplace opportunities (Wood and Khan, 2016). As Mangold and Faulds (2009, p. 357) advocate, SM is “the new hybrid of the marketing mix” and has provided companies with the opportunity to increase their sales through user-generated content and positive WOM (Wood and Khan, 2016; Kozinets, 2002).

Another important finding is how SM adoption can help B2B companies improve communications with their customers and business partners. This finding is in agreement with the study by Wang *et al.* (2016). They suggested that B2B companies can use SM as a channel to communicate with their customers and to improve their business performance from three distinct perspectives: marketing, innovation, and collaboration. Additionally, B2B companies can use SM to communicate effectively with their suppliers and their partners in the distribution channel (Ylimaula and Ulkuniemi, 2013).

SM tools can also help B2B companies enhance their external and internal relationships. SM can serve as a two-way communication platform between sellers and buyers or business partner (Lacka and Chong, 2015). B2B companies can use SM as a tool to improve supplier relationship management and share ideological and ethical thoughts with them (Ylimaula and Ulkuniemi, 2013). Additionally, SM tools can improve employee training by adopting a more interactive

training style, regardless of geographical distance. SM, used as a tool, can foster cooperation and collaboration within the same organisation (Kane *et al.*, 2010).

Additional benefits from SM adoption reported by the sampled B2B companies include improved competitiveness, added business value, increased profitability, a secured environment for information sharing internally and externally, and reduced business costs.

7.5.6 Barriers

From the descriptive results presented in section 7.7.2.9. (Table 7.16) insufficient financial resources is the most crucial barrier reported by adopters and non-adopters for the adoption of SM. This result validates observations by Meske and Stieglitz (2013) and Jussila *et al.* (2014). These researchers concluded that inadequate resources appear to be impede the use of SM. This finding may indicate that increased earnings or financial support, for example, from the Greek government, could foster the adoption of SM by B2B companies.

Another identified barrier is the perceived irrelevance of SM with the company's goals which aligns with Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011), who argue that relevance perceptions prevail as a significant barrier to SM usage by B2B SMEs in the UK.

Furthermore, the lack of measurement of the return on investment (ROI) is another significant barrier for SM adoption (Beier and Wagner, 2016; Kärkkäinen *et al.*, 2010; Järvinen *et al.*, 2012). This finding is in line with the findings of Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011), who found that the majority of B2B companies do not evaluate the impact of SM in boosting their brands. The B2B companies have yet to fully realise the benefits of SM making it difficult to measure and evaluate its benefits (Jussila *et al.*, 2013; Kärkkäinen *et al.*, 2010). The inability to measure of SM effectiveness may explain why some Greek B2B companies still question the value of SM and have yet to adopt it.

In addition, the findings of this study illustrate how negative comments and reviews are a critical barrier to SM adoption. This result is consistent with Alshamaila's (2018) work concluding fear of negative comments and reviews was the primary concern of businesses and managers in Jordan for adopting Social Network Sites. Greek B2B companies may be afraid to adopt SM for fear that negative feedback will damage the company image. However, they could use these errors to attract customer attention creatively.

Other barriers to adopting SM marketing by the sampled Greek B2B companies include lack of time, knowledge using SM, SM plan and strategy, communication control, and technological skills by the employees. Additional barriers are the fear of inappropriate use of company content, low perceptions of added value, and company size.

7.6 Revised Research Framework

As was presented in section 5.5.2, this was a mixed-methods study conducted in two phases, qualitative and quantitative. The qualitative phase involved conducting semi-structured interviews with employees from a Greek B2B organisation to determine the factors influenced the adoption of SMM in their company. Based on the interview findings (Figure 6.6), a preliminary conceptual framework was developed, comprised of four (4) contexts (technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural) and eighteen (18) predictors.

The preliminary conceptual framework was further examined empirically in the second phase of the study, through an online survey. The online survey tested the model on a larger scale. Based on the results of the logistic regression (LR) of the eighteen (18) factors, only five (5) have a significant impact on the adoption of SMM by the sampled Greek B2B companies. Figure 7.12 presents the revised conceptual framework, which includes only factors within the technological, organisational, and cultural context.

The quantitative results illustrate the strength of technological and cultural factors (2 predictors for each context) to influence the adoption decision. Regarding the organisational context, the results indicate less importance for the organisational factors (only one predictor).

These findings are consistent with the Al Rahbi's (2017) findings, which revealed that the SM adoption by SMEs is driven more by technological than by organisational factors. Moreover, other previous studies (for example, Hasan and Ditsa, 1999; Lee, Trimi and Kim, 2013; Chai and Pavlou, 2004; Özbilen, 2017 and Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021) confirmed that national culture affects companies' decision to adopt new technologies and innovations.

Additionally, the revised framework found no support for the importance of environmental factors in influencing B2B organisations' adoption of SMM. This finding is consistent with previous research, for example, the study of Alshamaila, Papagiannidis and Li (2012), as environmental factors did not significantly influence the adoption of cloud computing by SMEs in North East of England.

Figure 7.12: The Revised conceptual research framework of social media marketing adoption by Greek B2B organisations

7.7 Summary of the chapter

This chapter presented and explained the research activities used for analysing the data derived from the online survey with 72 B2B organisations in Greece. These activities included analysing descriptive statistics regarding respondent characteristics, specific characteristics of respondent's company and justification for using binary Logistic Regression for testing the research hypotheses. This chapter presented the results for each hypothesis, benefits, and barriers, followed by a detailed discussion of the findings located in the last part of this chapter.

CHAPTER 8- CONCLUSION

8.1 Introduction

This study sought to explore the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations and develop a conceptual framework theoretically grounded in the TOE framework and Hofstede's cultural model. This study also examined the benefits and barriers of SM adoption by B2B organisations. The study addressed the research objectives and tested the research hypotheses formed and proposed deductively in section 6.2 (Table 6.6). The hypotheses were developed based on the proposed conceptual framework (Figure 6.6) to examine the influence of eighteen (18) factors on the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations in Greece.

The study followed a pragmatic approach (Overdevest, 2011; Morgan, 2007; Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2005) and used a mixed-method sequential research design that was qualitative dominant (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). Adopting a mixed-method approach allowed a better understanding of the research problem and added value to the study's findings and interpretations. At the qualitative phase of the study, the largest Greek telecommunication company served as the case study, and eleven (11) employees from the B2B Marketing and SM department participated in a semi-structured individual interview. At the quantitative phase, a sample of seventy-two (72) B2B Greek companies completed an online survey to test and empirically validate the conceptual framework in a larger sample.

The research results identify how several contexts (technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural) influence a B2B organisations' decision to adopt SM for marketing purposes. Therefore, this study affirms that the TOE framework and Hofstede's model are robust theories

that can be applied to investigate the adoption of SM and general of innovations among B2B companies.

8.2 Results against the research objectives

In this section, the main findings regarding the research objectives are listed and summarised in the following subsections:

RO1: To critically explore a B2B organisation's perceptions on the factors influencing the adoption of SMM

An empirical qualitative study (Chapter 6) tested the preliminary conceptual framework developed from the literature review (Chapter 3, Figure 3.4) with employees from the case study company. The preliminary framework included the TOE framework and Hofstede's cultural model, and the study suggested that four (4) different contexts influence SMM adoption. Through the qualitative phase of the study, support was found for the initial nine factors, while nine more emerged during thematic analysis resulting in an expanded conceptual framework (Figure 6.6). In summary, there were eighteen (18) factors found to influence a Greek B2B organisation's adoption of SMM: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, interactivity, image (technological context), size, top management support, employee knowledge, innovativeness (organisational context), government support, competitive pressure, external support (environmental context), power distance, collectivism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance and short-term orientation (cultural context).

RO2: To critically examine the factors that influence the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations by testing the developed conceptual framework quantitatively with a larger sample of companies.

In the quantitative phase of the study, Logistic Regression (LR) was used to test the hypotheses and examine the influence of the eighteen (18) factors identified in the qualitative phase on the adoption of SM by the Greek B2B organisations. The statistical analysis revealed that four (4) out of the eighteen (18) hypotheses were statistically significant in influencing the adoption decision. The study results support that only factors from the technological, organisational, and cultural context influence the adoption decision. The factors include interactivity, innovativeness, masculinity, and short-term orientation. The study also found that the environmental factors (competitor pressure, government support and external support) were insignificant for influencing SM adoption.

RO3: To critically identify the potential benefits from the adoption of SMM for B2B organisations.

The research also investigated the main benefits from the adoption of SM. Qualitative research yielded thirteen (13) identified benefits. The results suggest that the B2B organisation uses SM primarily for interaction and engagement for building brand awareness among its customers and stakeholders. Additionally, SM helped the company increase business performance and sales, establish two-way communication with its SM users, improve customer service, and reduce marketing and advertising costs. Improved targeting to reach new audiences and promote the brand is among the benefits of SM adoption. Finally, SM helps a B2B company understand its customers and discover their needs while benefiting from positive electronic word of mouth (eWOM) and generating valuable content to position its brand as a thought leader.

In addition, the results from the quantitative phase of the research identified that SM use amplified the competitiveness of the sampled B2B companies. Some participants also perceived SM platforms are secure environments for information sharing.

RO4: To critically examine the barriers faced by B2B organisations for the adoption of SMM

This study also examined the main barriers to SM adoption by B2B organisations in Greece. The qualitative data identified eight (8) barriers from which the most important were the lack of knowledge and technical skills of using SM and the bureaucratic and complex structure of the company. Other vital barriers were inadequate resources (mainly financial), GDPR restrictions, lack of ROI measurement, fear for negative comments and feedback, deficits in SM strategy and perceptions that SM are irrelevant in the B2B sector. In addition, the quantitative results revealed that the adoption of SM does not increase company value, as a company can achieve its goals without the use of SM. Moreover, participants identified firm size, insufficient time, and fear of inappropriate use of company's content as barriers to adopting SM by Greek B2B companies.

RO5: To develop an empirical framework for studying the adoption of SMM by B2B organisations in the Greek context.

This study developed a conceptual framework of the factors influencing B2B organisations to adopt SMM, including technological characteristics, the organisation itself and the organisation's external environment, and the country's cultural characteristics in which a B2B organisation operates. This research integrated the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory (Rogers, 1983) and the TOE framework (DePietro, Wiarda and Fleischer, 1990); both are widely used and frequently cited theories and frameworks. The DOI theory often frames research into the adoption and diffusion of innovations, while TOE framework guides examinations into factors that influence a company's decision to adopt IT. This study broadened the TOE framework by adding a fourth context based on Hofstede's cultural model (Hofstede, 1984) to provide a more comprehensive insight into SM adoption. Hofstede's model is perhaps the most influential one among various

cross-cultural frameworks. As a source of behaviours and attitudes, national culture influences how people think and act regarding technology adoption (Nguyen, 2016).

The TOE is a framework for research from the organisation-level perspective. An organisation's decision to adopt a technological innovation is based not only on the characteristics of the technology itself but also on its perceived usefulness in the organisation. Therefore, the organisations need to identify the advantages of adopting the new technology for their businesses. The organisational context refers to the organisation's characteristics and potential influence on the adoption of new technologies. Companies must consider whether their resources and capabilities are sufficient to support the adoption. The environmental context refers to the environment in which a company operates. Environmental factors are external to the organisation and represent both the opportunities and challenges for the adoption of new technologies. Pateli *et al.* (2020) contend that the dynamics of the business environment in which companies operate exert pressure on them to adopt new technologies.

In addition, this research expanded the conceptual framework to reflect the influence of national culture on the SM adoption. Cultural differences may influence the adoption rate of new technologies and therefore it is important to connect the innovation adoption frameworks with national culture constructs (Eitle and Buxmann, 2020). Compared to other IT innovations, SM is a disruptive IT innovation with the potential to transform the way we do business today (Fosso Wamba and Carter, 2014). Identifying the factors that influence SM adoption will aid in making appropriate recommendations for improving the adoption of SMM (Matikiti, Mpinganjira and Roberts-Lombard, 2018). Thus, this study proposed an empirical framework for assessing new technology adoption such as SM by B2B organisations (Matikiti, Mpinganjira and Roberts-Lombard, 2018). The framework includes three categories of factors that can influencing the

adoption decision by the B2B organisations: technological, organisational, and cultural characteristics.

8.3 Theoretical contributions

The study contributes to theory and practice. This study propels the scant research in industrial contexts by developing and testing a conceptual framework to explore SM adoption and determine factors that promote the adoption and use of SMM among B2B organisations in Greece. Further, it triangulates qualitative interview findings with quantitative survey data collected from within Greek B2B companies to understand the primary determinants, barriers, and benefits of SMM adoption. Therefore, future researchers can use this study as a foundation for creating new theories and guidelines for B2B organisations in adopting SMM.

This research adds to the literature on technology adoption by examining SM in the B2B context as an example of technology adoption. Other areas of technology adoption in the B2B sector may benefit from this model when used as a foundation and expanded upon to meet company needs.

This study is among the first to theorise from the combined TOE framework and Hofstede's model to understand the adoption of SMM in the B2B context. As previously stated, the TOE framework is one of the most influential adoption theories. This study broadens the TOE framework by incorporating additional factors and the cultural context. National culture was one of the primary themes discussed throughout the interviews in the qualitative phase. The quantitative phase confirmed this finding, as two (2) (masculinity and short-term orientation) of the five (5) cultural factors have a significant impact on B2B's companies' intention to utilize SM. The study also extended the original TOE framework of DePietro, Wiarda and Fleischer (1990), as four (4) new factors resulted from the qualitative phase, namely trialability, interactivity, image, and external support. The quantitative phase further confirmed that interactivity positively influences the

adoption decision. Therefore, this research enhances our understanding of the factors that influence a B2B company's decision to adopt SMM. It also strengthens our understanding of how cultural factors influence B2B companies' intention to adopt SM platforms.

This study responded to the recommendations of Foroudi *et al.* (2020; 164) to further the current body of literature, suggesting “the research about the importance of SM in a B2B context remains rather limited.” To the best of the researcher's knowledge, this is one of the first studies investigating the adoption of SMM in the B2B context in Greece. This research is also among the first to theorise and test all five cultural dimensions of Hofstede's model to understand technology adoption and usage at the business level. Most previous studies (for example, Kreiser *et al.*, 2010) excluded the short-term orientation dimension. The study contributes to the literature by offering support for the negative relationship between short-term orientation and new technology adoption at the business level. It is essential to examine all five cultural dimensions to understand how national culture impacts the adoption of SM applications (Hoehle *et al.*, 2015).

8.4 Practical contributions

The previous sections summarised the results against the research objectives and the theoretical contributions of the research. In line with the sixth (RO6) research objective of the study, this section provides the practical implications for B2B managers and policy makers. Additionally, implications for academics have been provided at subsection 8.4.3.

8.4.1 Implications for B2B companies

The empirical findings from this study have several implications for the Greek B2B companies. The proposed model may help managers and business owners to evaluate the factors influencing the adoption decision and increase their awareness of the perceived benefits and barriers.

There are some general implications resulting from the qualitative interviews. First, B2B should consider investing in training in employee training and hiring new staff with technological skills and relevant scientific backgrounds. Second, a less internal bureaucratic and complicated structure and supportive top managers are crucial for allocating adequate resources for the adoption of SM. Third, insufficient financial resources negatively impact SM adoption since Greek companies are more cautious about their capital spending and investment. Therefore, B2B managers should adopt free or low-cost SM tools and focus on specific SM platforms rather than depleting their budget on multiple SM platforms. Fourth, B2B companies can use free analytical tools such as Google Analytics to measure the ROI of their SM campaigns. Measuring SM ROI is critical and allows B2B companies to understand SM benefits better and refine their SM strategy over time to improve returns as they learn. Fifth, the B2B companies should not avoid negative feedback and listen carefully to their customers' comments. They should respond publicly to demonstrate transparency and be helpful and attentive in meeting customers' needs. Moreover, having a clear SM strategy and setting their business goals and objectives could help the B2B companies prioritise their activities and use the right SM tools, tactics, and actions to adopt SMM successfully.

The empirical findings show that interactivity is a major technological determinant in B2B SM adoption. Considering the interactive nature of SM (Tajudeen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2018), SMM is more effective than traditional marketing in building relationships and two-way communication with its SM users. B2B organisations should consider using SM to build strong relationships with their customers and business partners.

In terms of the empirical findings related to the organisational context, this study has one implication. The empirical analysis suggests that the innovativeness of a firm affects the adoption of SM positively. Innovative organisations tend to be early adopters and are more likely to adopt

SM and new technologies. Interaction via SM platforms is likely to spark new ideas and improve a company's intellectual capacity (Lam *et al.*, 2016). SM can facilitate the flow of external information through online networking communities allowing B2B businesses to refresh their knowledge and generate new ideas.

The study's findings also emphasise the significance of two specific cultural factors. The masculinity dimension of the Greek culture plays an integral role in the adoption decision, which suggests that a competitive environment is likely to stimulate the adoption of SM and new technologies among B2B companies to propel their industry ranking. Another implication of the cultural context is the negative relationship between a short-term orientation and the adoption decision. B2B companies need to have a "forward-thinking mindset" (Zhao, 2013) and be willing to develop a long-term SM strategy to realise the long-term benefits of SMM.

In addition, the findings of this study provide a solid understanding of the benefits of SMM adoption by Greek B2B companies. The most important benefit is the interaction between the company and its SM users (customers and business partners). B2B companies can get valuable feedback through blogs and product ratings, helping the companies to improve their products and services. Therefore, the B2B companies should raise awareness of the benefits of SM usage among their top managers and employees. The information about the benefits from this study could enable the B2B companies to increase their awareness of how SM can help them build their brand, effectively and efficiently promote their company, and increase their sales.

Finally, another implication from this study is that B2B companies may encounter barriers when adopting SMM, such as those identified from this study. B2B companies need to reduce the uncertainty of how to use SMM. A lack of resources, technological skills, time and ROI measurement and fear of negative comments and feedback are the primary barriers B2B companies

consider when adopting SMM. Therefore, business associations and policy makers should limit the identified barriers' impact by providing appropriate support to the B2B companies, elaborated in section 8.4.3.

8.4.2 Implications for policy makers

As mentioned in Chapter 4, the Ministry of Digital Governance is the primary government policy maker in charge for designing, coordinating, and implementing Greece's digital transformation strategy. The Greek government revised the national digital strategy and launched the new strategy, "Digital Transformation Bible", in June 2021. Three (3) of the seven (7) national Digital Transformation strategy objectives (3, 4, and 5) elucidate the Greek government's intention to support the development of digital skills among citizens, transform enterprises to digital enterprises, and bolster digital innovation through creating new Digital Innovation Hubs (Ministry of Digital Governance, 2021). Therefore, the Greek Ministry may advance its Digital Transformation strategy by creating incentives for Greek companies to adopt new technologies or improve technology use, especially SM, based on the findings of this study.

The most significant implications of this study include the new model containing factors that influence the adoption of SMM by Greek B2B organisations and the list of benefits and barriers to SM adoption. The proposed model demonstrates how five factors within the technological, organisational, and cultural contexts impact the company's decision to adopt SM. The study indicated that the perceived complexity of SMM is a significant factor that hinders the adoption decision by the Greek B2B companies. Therefore, the Greek government should formulate appropriate strategies and provide programs to help the organisations develop the necessary skills to overcome knowledge barriers and use SM more widely. The results also indicate that the masculinity dimension of the Greek culture can be a factor that can influence positively Greek

companies to adopt SM. Policymakers can take advantage of the “competitive nature” of the Greeks to influence them to adopt SMM to assess larger markets and become more competitive both locally and globally, thereby assisting the country’s economic recovery and progress.

However, the government’s “good intentions” are not always sufficient to compel companies “to invest at a level commensurate with the government’s policy settings” (Papazafeiropoulou, 2004, p. 15). The government should regularly dialogue with local professional bodies and associations who know the company’s needs and market for designing an effective policy for adopting new technologies.

Additionally, policymakers should also include professional bodies, like Chambers of Commerce and educational institutes, for example, universities. The key benefit is that both stakeholders have direct communications and contact with the companies, and therefore, can suggest an appropriate implementation of a SM policy. Moreover, the government can support universities by financing research in SM and new technologies field. On the other hand, the universities can help the companies by offering educational programs about SM and new technologies to individuals and companies.

The study also identified that the main barriers to the adoption of SM are the lack of knowledge of how to use it and the lack of resources (financial, employees with technical skills). Professional bodies and the Chambers of Commerce can offer knowledge and consultancy services at local or national levels.

As previously mentioned, one of the governments’ objectives is to help the Greek companies to transform into digital enterprises. However, companies must first understand the benefits of SMM, get examples of successful SMM use, get financial support for investing on these new tools and follow the government regulation settings.

In addition to the vital role of the Ministry of Digital Governance, other government organisations, for example, the General Secretariat of Research and Innovation, should sponsor campaigns and training sessions in collaboration with local communities. The Chambers of Commerce should also help B2B companies increase investments in new technologies and innovations and identify and capitalise on their competitive advantage.

Finally, the study occurred during the crisis of the COVID-19 pandemic. During this crisis, Greek companies (both B2B and B2C) continued running their business processes via the Internet to meet their customers' demands. The Greek government should respond by providing financial support to affected companies and stimulus tax relaxation for B2B companies.

8.4.3 Implications for Academics

The empirical findings of this study are valuable and have significant implications for academics and the research community. Firstly, ample literature exists on the adoption of SMM in the B2C context, but there are less studies on SM adoption by B2B organisations. This thesis contributes to the limited literature on B2B SMM by empirically testing the concepts of new technology adoption, SM adoption and B2B companies within the Greek context. The limited SMM and B2B research in Greece has overlooked the benefits and barriers that result from the adoption and use of SM. Additionally, there is limited research in Greece on the cultural factors that affect the adoption of SM in the industrial context. Greece is a late development “country of the semi-periphery” that historically lacks sophisticated technology adoption and use (Loukis, Spinellis and Katsigiannis, 2011) with unique cultural characteristics. Therefore, it is vital to understand the factors that influence Greek B2B companies' ability to adopt SMM. As a result, this research has contributed to analysing and theorising the factors, benefits, and barriers that enable or inhibit

Greek B2B companies from adopting new technologies, especially SM, for their marketing activities.

Secondly, from the methodological perspective, this study has successfully used a sequential exploratory mixed-method design to explore SM adoption in the industrial context. As a result, the study intends to encourage B2B marketing researchers to use various research methods to uncover new insights using a complementary combination of methods (Snelson, 2016). This study answers the call from previous studies, for example (Siamagka *et al.*, 2015, p. 96), who suggest that “future studies could adopt a more inductive approach, with researcher being more open to new factors that could emerge from a qualitative research design”. Therefore, this study investigated the adoption of SM using semi-structured interviews (qualitative method) and an online survey (quantitative method) to confirm and validate the qualitative results empirically.

Thirdly, from the research findings perspective, this research revealed the importance of specific technological, organisational, and cultural factors influencing the adoption decision of SM by B2B companies. More specifically, the findings highlighted the interactive nature of SM. The qualitative results revealed that it was the main reason that influenced the B2B case study company to adopt SM. In addition, the results indicated the important impact of national culture and especially of masculinity and short-term orientation dimensions on a B2B company’s intention to adopt new technologies and SM. Moreover, both phases of the study highlighted several barriers to adopting SMM by B2B companies, but there are significant simultaneous benefits from this adoption. Therefore, future researchers should test these conclusions in other contexts.

Finally, this research developed a conceptual framework based on the TOE framework for understanding the adoption of SM by Greek B2B companies. Therefore, the study confirmed the

applicability of the TOE framework on studying the adoption of new technology, in this case, SM and expanded the model by adding a fourth context, the cultural context.

8.5 Research limitations

This research adds to our understanding of the adoption of SM by B2B organisations for marketing purposes. However, there are several study limitations. Firstly, the study's small sample in both study phases limits generalisability. The online survey for the quantitative phase returned seventy-two (72) responses from Greek B2B companies. However, the survey took place during anxious times for most Greeks because of the COVID-19. Therefore, the survey's response rate was negatively impacted by the pandemic. Additionally, eleven (11) individuals completed a semi-structured individual interview for the qualitative phase of data collection. The researcher was unable to acquire a larger sample size due to time and financial constraints for PhD research, which would have improved the generalisability of the study. As such, future researchers should use a larger sample size to allow greater confidence in the results and achieve broader generalisation.

Furthermore, this study employed a sample from a single country, Greece, limiting the study's findings. Therefore, the proposed model may be specific to the Greek context and not generalisable to B2B companies in other countries. Consequently, more empirical research in different countries is required for comparative analysis.

Another limitation is that the study's proposed framework does not include all potential factors that may influence a B2B organisation to adopt SM. For example, factors such as observability (Araújo and Zilber, 2016), customer pressure (Shaltoni, 2017), environment uncertainty (Pateli *et al.*, 2020) and trust (Abubakar *et al.*, 2017), associated with the adoption of SM and new technologies and found in the literature were not included and tested in this study. Therefore, the current study is constrained because it did not test all previously identified relevant factors that

influence the adoption of new technology at the business level. Additionally, this study examined only the relationship between the independent variable (adoption of SM) with the 18 dependent variables from the four (4) contexts of the TOE-Hofstede's framework. Therefore, this study did not examine relationships between the dependent variables within the same context or dependent variables from different contexts.

Finally, the researcher relied on participants responses to interview and online survey questions for this study. Self-reporting is an established limitation inherent in interviews and surveys (Seidman, 2013; Stangor, 2011; Yin, 2014). The likelihood of being influenced by bias is the main limitation of these types of self-report measurements. For example, participants may inflate their responses to present the company favourably or misrepresent facts (Polit *et al.*, 2001). Furthermore, participants may guard information they do not wish to disclose or overstate their responses (Stangor, 2011).

8.6 Recommendations for future research

Although the study met its aims and objectives, more empirical research is needed to expand on the findings and address the limitations highlighted in the previous section (see section 8.5). For example, this study used a case study company to recruit participants for the qualitative phase. Although this approach is useful to get the perception of a B2B's organisation about the factors influencing the adoption decision, future researchers could also use other approaches. A future researcher can organise multiple case studies with B2B companies belonging to the same industry to make more accurate comparisons and understand the industry trends.

Although this study used a mixed-method approach to test and validate the proposed framework and examine the perceived benefits and barriers, additional research is needed to understand these issues. As Foroudi *et al.* (2020) suggested, awareness about the benefits of the adoption of SM

takes time. Therefore, longitudinal research would advance the knowledge and understanding of how companies make judgement throughout the decision-making process. However, this kind of research requires time and financial resources.

This study could also stimulate future research that focuses on the use of SM by B2B customers and business partners. This research found that B2B companies can benefit from two-way communication and interaction with their SM users. Therefore, future researchers should investigate the critical role of SM in the B2B context for both sides of the marketing channel dyad (buyers and sellers). Moreover, a future researcher can use a netnographic research approach (Kozinets, 2002; 2012) by incorporating group interactions between buyers and sellers to provide insights into the development of business relationships stemming from various SM networks.

As was mentioned in section 8.5, this study did not examine the interactions between the independent variables to explore how each one affects the others. Therefore, future research could use Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) (Field, 2018) to examine the inter-relationships between the TOE-Hofstede's factors. Finally, future research is necessary to explore factors that influence SM adoption and the perceived benefits and barriers in different countries and geographical regions and groups of organisations, such as the SMEs, representing 99.9% of Greece's entire private sector. Moreover, other researchers may use the framework from this study as a foundation for understand the adoption of different types of technology in the B2B context.

8.7 Summary

This mixed-method study explored the adoption of SMM among Greek B2B companies. Additionally, it generated a conceptual framework future researcher may use for investigating technology adoption by B2B companies. The resulting conceptual framework merges the TOE framework with Hofstede's cultural model. This study expanded the TOE framework to include

trialability, interactivity, image, and external support. These four (4) new factors supplement the three (3) contexts (technological, organisational, and environmental contexts) of the TOE framework and complement the five cultural dimensions of Hofstede's model. This study confirmed the legitimacy of applying the TOE framework and Hofstede's cultural model in research on SM and innovation adoption in B2B companies.

This study relied on interview data from eleven (11) employees of the case study company, a leading telecommunications company in Greece, for the qualitative phase and survey responses from participants of seventy-two (72) Greek B2B companies for the quantitative phase. This study evaluated the influence of eighteen (18) factors influencing the adoption of SMM in B2B Greek organisations and identified thirteen (13) benefits and eight (8) barriers to SMM adoption.

This study demonstrates the need for B2B organisation decision-makers to evaluate the technological, organisational, environmental, and cultural contexts when determining the appropriateness, benefits, and barriers of SMM adoption. Planning is a prerequisite to adopting and integrating SMM and new technologies, as businesses cannot realise the benefits of technology integration without forethought in implementation.

B2B organisations' decision-makers should evaluate how the company can capitalise on SMM adoption, innovation, and new technologies. More than ever, businesses should consider their technologies and technological intentions given society's heavy reliance on SM use.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, I. N., Husin, M. H. and Baharudin, A. S. (2021) 'Factors Influencing the Adoption of Facebook as a Marketing Channel among SMEs in Nigeria as a Developing Country: A Conceptual Framework', *Jurnal Intelek*, 16(1), pp. 99–107. doi: 10.24191/ji.v16i1.369.
- Abubakar, M. K., Patricia, M. N., Samuel, O. O. and Totolo, A. (2017) 'Factors affecting adoption of social media by women ' s non-governmental organisations (WNGOs)', *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 9(9), pp. 96–106. doi: 10.5897/IJLIS2017.0783.
- Agarwal, N. and Yiliyasi, Y. (2010) 'Information quality challenges in social media', *International Conference on Information Quality, ICIQ 2010*.
- Agarwal, R. and Prasad, J. (1998) 'A Conceptual and Operational Definition of Personal Innovativeness in the Domain of Information Technology', *Information Systems Research*, 9(2), pp. 204–215. doi: 10.1287/isre.9.2.204.
- Agnihotri, R., Kothandaraman, P., Kashyap, R. and Singh, R. (2012) 'Bringing “social” into sales: The impact of salespeople’s social media use on service behaviors and value creation', *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 32(3), pp. 333–348. doi: 10.2753/PSS0885-3134320304.
- Agnihotri, R., Dingus, R., Hu, M., Y. and Krush, M., T. (2016) 'Social media: Influencing customer satisfaction in B2B sales', *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier B.V., 53(August), pp. 172–180. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2015.09.003.
- Ahamat, A., Shahkat Ali, M. S. and Hamid, N. (2017) 'Factors Influencing the Adoption of Social Media in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)', *IJASOS- International E-journal of Advances in Social Sciences*, (January 2021), pp. 338–348. doi: 10.18769/ijasos.336544.

Ahmad, S. Z., Abu Bakar, A. R. and Ahmad, N. (2019) 'Social media adoption and its impact on firm performance: the case of the UAE', *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 25(1), pp. 84–111. doi: 10.1108/IJEER-08-2017-0299.

Ahmad, S. Z., Ahmad, N. and Abu Bakar, A. R. (2018) 'Reflections of entrepreneurs of small and medium-sized enterprises concerning the adoption of social media and its impact on performance outcomes: Evidence from the UAE', *Telematics and Informatics*. Elsevier, 35(1), pp. 6–17. doi: 10.1016/j.tele.2017.09.006.

Ainin, S., Parveen, F., Moghavvemi, S., Jaafar, N., I. and Shuib, N., L., M. (2015) 'Factors influencing the use of social media by SMEs and its performance outcomes', *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 115(3), pp. 570–588. doi: 10.1108/IMDS-07-2014-0205.

Ajzen, I. (1985) 'From intention to actions: A theory of planned behavior', in Kuhl, J. and Beckman, J. (eds) *Action control: From cognition to behavior*. New York: Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 11–39.

Ajzen, I. and Fishbein, M. (1980) *Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.

Al-Qirim, N. (2007) 'The adoption of eCommerce communications and applications technologies in small businesses in New Zealand', *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 6(4), pp. 462–473. doi: 10.1016/j.elerap.2007.02.012.

Alogoskoufis, G. and Featherstone, K. (2021) *GREECE AND THE EURO: From Crisis to Recovery*. Edited by G. Alogoskoufis and K. Featherstone. London, UK: Hellenic Observatory, London School of Economics and Political Science. Available at: <https://www.lse.ac.uk/Hellenic-Observatory/Publications/Staff-Books-and-Publications>.

Alrawabdeh, W. (2014) 'Environmental Factors Affecting Mobile Commerce Adoption- An Exploratory Study on the Telecommunication Firms in Jordan', *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(8), pp. 151–164.

Alshamaila, Y. (2018) 'Social Network Site Usage by Small- and Medium-Sized Businesses: Understanding the Motivations and Barriers', *Modern Applied Science*, 12(3), p. 41. doi: 10.5539/mas.v12n3p41.

Alshamaila, Y., Papagiannidis, S. and Li, F. (2012) 'Cloud computing adoption: An exploratory study', in *8th International Conference on Web Information Systems and Technologies (WEBIST)*, pp. 518–524. doi: 10.5220/0003884105180524.

Alshamaila, Y., Papagiannidis, S. and Stamati, T. (2013) 'Cloud computing adoption in Greece', in *UK Academy for Information Systems Conference Proceedings 2013*, pp. 1–17.

Alves, H., Fernandes, C. and Raposo, M. (2016) 'Social Media Marketing: A Literature Review and Implications', *Psychology and Marketing*, 33(12), pp. 1029–1038. doi: 10.1002/mar.20936.

Ananda, A., Hernández-García, Á. and Lamberti, L. (2016) 'N-REL: A comprehensive framework of social media marketing strategic actions for marketing organizations', *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 1(3), pp. 170–180.

Anderson, C. (2010) 'Presenting and Evaluating Qualitative Research', *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 74(8), pp. 1–7.

Anderson, T. and Kanuka, H. (2003) *e-Research Methods, Strategies, and Issues*. Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon.

Andersson, S. and Wikström, N. (2017) 'Why and how are social media used in a B2B context,

and which stakeholders are involved?', *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 32(8), pp. 1098–1108. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-07-2016-0148.

Andzulis, J. M., Panagopoulos, N. G. and Rapp, A. (2012) 'A Review of Social Media and Implications for the Sales Process', *Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management*, 32(3), pp. 305–316. doi: 10.2753/PSS0885-3134320302.

Araújo, J. B. and Zilber, S. N. (2016) 'What Factors Lead Companies to Adopt Social Media in their processes: Proposal and Test of a Measurement Model', *Brazilian Business Review*, 13(6), pp. 260–290. doi: 10.15728/bbr.2016.13.6.5.

Atanassova, I. and Clark, L. (2015) 'Social media practices in SME marketing activities: a theoretical framework and research agenda', *Journal of Customer Behaviour*, 14(2), pp. 163–183.

Atkins, C. and Louw, G. (2000) 'Reclaiming Knowledge: A Case for Evidence Based Information Systems', *Ecis*, (2000). Available at: <http://aisel.aisnet.org/ecis2000/28>.

Atkinson, J. (2002) 'Four Steps to Analyse Data from a Case Study Method', *Australasian (ACIS)*, pp. 1–12. Available at: <http://aisel.aisnet.org/acis2002/38>.

Awa, H. O. and Ojiabo, O. U. (2016) 'A model of adoption determinants of ERP within T-O-E framework', *Information Technology and People*, 29(4), pp. 901–930. doi: 10.1108/ITP-03-2015-0068.

Awa, H. O., Ukoha, O. and Igwe, S. R. (2017) 'Revisiting technology-organization-environment (T-O-E) theory for enriched applicability', *Bottom Line*, 30(1), pp. 2–22. doi: 10.1108/BL-12-2016-0044.

Barbosa, N. and Louri, H. (2005) 'Corporate performance: Does ownership matter? A comparison

of foreign- and domestic-owned firms in Greece and Portugal’, *Review of Industrial Organization*, 27(1), pp. 73–102. doi: 10.1007/s11151-005-4920-y.

Barnes, D., Clear, F., Dyerson, R., Harindranath, G., Harris, L. and Rae, A. (2012) ‘Web 2.0 and micro-businesses: An exploratory investigation’, *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 19(4), pp. 687–711. doi: 10.1108/14626001211277479.

Beier, M. and Früh, S. (2020) ‘Technological, organizational, and environmental factors influencing social media adoption by hospitals in Switzerland: Cross-sectional study’, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(3), pp. 1–15. doi: 10.2196/16995.

Beier, M. and Wagner, K. (2016) ‘SOCIAL MEDIA ADOPTION: BARRIERS TO THE STRATEGIC USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN SMES’, in *Research Papers, ECIS 2016 Proceedings*.

Belegri-Roboli, A., Markaki, M. and Michaelides, P. G. (2011) ‘Labour productivity changes and working time: The case of Greece’, *Economic Systems Research*, 23(3), pp. 329–339. doi: 10.1080/09535314.2011.595777.

Bell, S. E. (2009) *DES daughters: Embodied knowledge and the transformation of women’s health politics*. Philadelphia, PA: Temple University Press.

Benbasat, I., Goldstein, D. K. and Mead, M. (1987) ‘The Case Research Strategy in Studies of Information Systems’, *MIS Quarterly*, pp. 369–386.

Bernard, M. (2016) ‘The impact of social media on the B2B CMO’, *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 31(8), pp. 955–960. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-10-2016-268.

Berthon, P. R., Pitt, L., F., Plangger, K. and Shapiro, D. (2012) ‘Marketing meets Web 2.0, social media, and creative consumers: Implications for international marketing strategy’, *Business*

Horizons. ‘Kelley School of Business, Indiana University’, 55(3), pp. 261–271. doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2012.01.007.

Biemans, W. G. (2010) *Business to Business Marketing: A value-driven approach*. London: McGraw Hill Higher Education.

Bimrose, J., Barnes, S. and Brown, J. (2005) ‘A Systematic Literature Review of Research into Interventions for Higher Education’, *Hecsu*, (November), p. 77. doi: 10.1016/j.jelechem.2013.01.015.

Blaikie, N. (2010) *Designing Social Research*. 2nd edn. John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

Blair, J., Czaja, R. F. and Blair, E. (2014) *Designing surveys: a guide to decisions and procedures*. 3rd edn. SAGE. doi: 10.5860/choice.42-5623.

Bland, J. M. and Altman, D. G. (1997) ‘Statistics notes: Cronbach’s alpha’, *BMJ*, 314, p. 572.

Blumberg, B., Cooper, D. R. and Schindler, P. S. (2005) *Business Research Methods*. Maidenhead: McGraw-Hill.

Blumberg, B., Cooper, D. R. and Schindler, P. S. (2011) *Business Research Methods*. 3rd edn. London: McGraw-Hill Higher Education. doi: 10.22573/spg.020.bk/s/026.

Bodnar, K. and Cohen, L. J. (2012) *The B2B Social Media Book*. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Boell, S. K. and Cecez-Kecmanovic, D. (2014) ‘On being “Systematic” in Literature Reviews in IS’, *Journal of Information Technology*, pp. 161–173. doi: 10.1057/jit.2014.26.

Bogea, F. and Brito, E. P. Z. (2018) ‘Determinants of social media adoption by large companies’, *Journal of Technology Management and Innovation*, 13(1), pp. 11–18. doi: 10.4067/S0718-

27242018000100011.

Bollen, K. (1989) *Structural Equations with Latent Variables*. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc. Chen.

Bourantas, D. and Papadakis, V. (1996) 'Greek Management: Diagnosis and Prognosis', *International Studies of Management and Organization*, 26(3), pp. 13–30. doi: 10.1080/00208825.1996.11656685.

Bowden, A., Fox-Rushby, J., A, Nyandieka, L. and Wanjau, J (2002) 'How to do (or not to do) . . . Methods for pre-testing and piloting survey questions : illustrations from the KENQOL survey of health-related quality', *Health Policy and Planning*, 17(3), pp. 322–330.

Boyatzis, R. E. (1998) *Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Brace, I. (2008) *Questionnaire design: How to Plan, Structure and Write Survey Material for Effective Market Research*. Edited by K. P. Publishers. doi: 10.1136/adc.72.1.76.

Brancheau, J. and Wetherbe, J. (1990) 'The Adoption of Spreadsheet Software: Testing Innovation Diffusion Theory in the Context of End- User Computing', *Information Systems Research*, 1(2), pp. 115–143.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77–101.

Brennan, R., Canning, L. and Mcdowell, R. (2014) *Business-to-Business Marketing*. 3rd edn. SAGE.

Brennan, R. and Croft, R. (2012) 'The Use of Social Media in B2B Marketing and Branding',

Journal of Customer Behaviour, 11(2), pp. 101–115. doi: 10.1097/QCO.0000000000000205.

Brink, T. (2017) ‘B2B SME management of antecedents to the application of social media’, *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 64, pp. 57–65. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2017.02.007.

Brown, J. D. (2001) *Using surveys in language programs*. Cambridge: CUP.

Bruhn, M., Schnebelen, S. and Schäfer, D. (2014) ‘Antecedents and consequences of the quality of e-customer-to-customer interactions in B2B brand communities’, *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier B.V., 43(1), pp. 164–176.

Bruque, S. and Moyano, J. (2007) ‘Organisational determinants of information technology adoption and implementation in SMEs: The case of family and cooperative firms’, *Technovation*, 27(5), pp. 241–253. doi: 10.1016/j.technovation.2006.12.003.

Bryman, A. (2004) *Social research methods*. 2nd edn. New York: Oxford University Press.

Bryman, A., Becker, S. and Sempik, J. (2008) ‘Quality criteria for quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods research: A view from social policy’, *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 11(4), pp. 261–276. doi: 10.1080/13645570701401644.

Bryman, A. and Bell, E. (2015) *Business Research Methods*. 4th edn. Oxford: Oxford University Press. doi: 10.22573/spg.020.bk/s/026.

Buhalis, D. and Deimezi, O. (2004) ‘E-Tourism Developments in Greece: Information Communication Technologies Adoption for the Strategic Management of the Greek Tourism Industry’, *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 5(2), pp. 103–130. doi: 10.1057/palgrave.thr.6040011.

Bulearca, M. and Bulearca, S. (2010) 'Twitter: a Viable Marketing Tool for SMEs?', *Global Business and Management Research: An International Journal*, 2(4), pp. 296–309.

Buratti, N., Parola, F. and Satta, G. (2018) 'Insights on the adoption of social media marketing in B2B services', *TQM Journal*, 30(5), pp. 490–529. doi: 10.1108/TQM-11-2017-0136.

Burns, R. B. and Burns, R. A. (2008) *Business Research Methods and Statistics using SPSS*. Padstow, Cornwall: SAGE Publications.

Campbell, C., Pitt, L., F., Parent, M. and Berthon, P., R. (2011) 'Understanding consumer conversations around ads in a Web 2.0 world', *Journal of Advertising*, 40(1), pp. 87–102. doi: 10.2753/JOA0091-3367400106.

Canovi, M. and Pucciarelli, F. (2019) 'Social media marketing in wine tourism: winery owners' perceptions', *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 36(6), pp. 653–664. doi: 10.1080/10548408.2019.1624241.

Carr, C. T. and Hayes, R. A. (2015) 'Atlantic Journal of Communication Social Media: Defining, Developing, and Divining', *Atlantic Journal of Communication*, 23(1), pp. 46–65. doi: 10.1080/15456870.2015.972282.

Cartwright, S., Davies, I. and Archer-Brown, C. (2021) 'Managing relationships on social media in business-to-business organisations', *Journal of Business Research*. Elsevier Inc., 125, pp. 120–134. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.11.028.

Castronovo, C. and Huang, L. (2012) 'Social Media in an Alternative Marketing Communication Model', *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*, 6(1), pp. 117–134.

Cawsey, T. and Rowley, J. (2016) 'Social media brand building strategies in B2B companies',

Marketing Intelligence and Planning, 34(6), pp. 754–776. doi: 10.1108/MIP-04-2015-0079.

Chai, L. and Pavlou, P. A. (2004) ‘From “ancient” to “modern”: A cross-cultural investigation of electronic commerce adoption in Greece and the United States’, *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 17(6), pp. 416–423. doi: 10.1108/17410390410566706.

Chatterjee, S. and Hadi, A. S. (2006) *Regression Analysis by Example*. 4th edn. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc. Available at: www.wiley.com.

Chatzithomas, N., Boutsouki, C., Hatzithomas, L. and Zotos, Y. (2014) ‘Social Media Advertising Platforms: A Cross-cultural Study’, *International Journal of Strategic Innovative Marketing*, 01, pp. 74–90.

Chatzoglou, P. D., Vraimaki, E., Diamantidis, A. and Sarigiannidis, L. (2010) ‘Computer acceptance in Greek SMEs’, *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 17(1), pp. 78–101. doi: 10.1108/14626001011019143.

Chen, W. and Hirschheim, R. (2004) ‘A paradigmatic and methodological examination of information systems research from 1991 to 2001’, *Info Systems Journal*, 14, pp. 197–235.

Chi, H.-H. (2011) ‘Interactive Digital Advertising vs. Virtual Brand Community’, *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 12(1), pp. 44–61. doi: 10.1080/15252019.2011.10722190.

Chiu, C.-Y., Chen, S. and Chen, C.-L. (2017) ‘An integrated perspective of TOE framework and innovation diffusion in broadband mobile applications adoption by enterprises’, *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences (IJMESS)*, 6(1), pp. 14–39.

Chong, A. Y- L., Lin, B., Ooi, K-B. and Raman, M. (2009) ‘Factors affecting the adoption level of c-commerce: An empirical study’, *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 50(2), pp. 13–22.

doi: 10.1080/08874417.2009.11645380.

Chong, J. L. L. and Olesen, K. (2017) 'A technology-organization-environment perspective on eco-effectiveness: A meta-analysis', *Australasian Journal of Information Systems*, 21, pp. 1–26.

doi: 10.3127/ajis.v21i0.1441.

Chong, S. (2004) 'Electronic Commerce Adoption By Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Australia: an empirical study of influencing factors', in *Proceedings of the 13th European Conference on Information Systems, The European IS Profession in the Global Networking Environment, ECIS 2004*.

Christodoulides, G., Siamagka, N. T. and Michaelidou, N. (2015) 'A Model For The Adoption of Social Media by B2B Organizations', in K., K. (ed.) *Proceedings of the Academy of Marketing Science*. Springer, Cham, pp. 578–581. doi: 10.1126/science.202.4366.409.

Chroni, Z. M. and Balaraman, P. (2018) 'Adoption of social media in business-to-business (B2B) small medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Greece', in *Conference Proceedings of 3rd International Conference of Development and Economy (ICODECON)*, pp. 171–179.

Chui, M., Manika, J., Bughin, J., Dobbs, R., Roxburgh, C., Sarrazin, H., Sands, G. and Westergren, M. (2012) *The Social Economy: Unlocking Value and Productivity Through Social Technologies: McKinsey Global Institute Report*.

Chuttur, M. (2009) 'Overview of the Technology Acceptance Model: Origins, Developments and Future Directions', *Sprouts: Working Papers on Information Systems*, 9(37), pp. 1–22.

Coffey, A. and Atkinson, P. (1996) *Making sense of qualitative data. Complementary research strategies*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.

Cohen, J., Cohen, P., West, S., G. and Aiken, L., S. (2002) *Applied Multiple Regression/Correlation Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. 3rd edn. New York: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9781410606266.

Çokluk, Ö. (2010) 'Logistic regression: Concept and application', *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Bilimleri*, 10(3), pp. 1397–1407.

Constantinides, E. (2014) 'Foundations of Social Media Marketing', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. Elsevier B.V., 148, pp. 40–57. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.07.016.

Cortina, J. M. (1993) 'What Is Coefficient Alpha? An Examination of Theory and Applications', *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 78(1), pp. 98–104. doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.78.1.98.

Crabtree, B. F. and Miller, W. L. (1999) *Doing Qualitative Research*. 2nd edn, *Doing Qualitative Research*. 2nd edn. SAGE Publications, Inc. doi: 10.4324/9781315435978-2.

Creswell, J. W. (2009) *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. 3rd edn. SAGE Publications, Inc.

Creswell, J. W. and Plano Clark, V. L. (2018) *Designing and conducting mixed methods research approach*. 3rd edn. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Creswell, J. W. and Plano Clark, V. L. (2006) *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. Thousand Oaks, Calif.: SAGE Publications. doi: 10.1111/j.1753-6405.2007.00096.x.

Dahnil, M. I., Marzuki, K., M., Langgat, J. and Fabeil, N., F. (2014) 'Factors Influencing SMEs Adoption of Social Media Marketing', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. Elsevier B.V., 148, pp. 119–126.

Daj, A. (2013) 'Economic and Legal Aspects of Introducing Novel Ict Instruments: Integrating

Sound Into Social Media Marketing - From Audio Branding To Soundscaping.’, *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov. Series V: Economic Sciences*, 6(2), pp. 15–24.

Davis, F. D. (1986) *A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems: theory and results*. Massachusetts Institute of Technology. doi: 10.1126/science.146.3652.1648.

Davis, F. D. (1989) ‘Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology’, *MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems*, 13(3), pp. 319–340. doi: 10.2307/249008.

DeJonckheere, M. and Vaughn, L. M. (2019) ‘Semistructured interviewing in primary care research: A balance of relationship and rigour’, *Family Medicine and Community Health*, 7(2), pp. 1–8. doi: 10.1136/fmch-2018-000057.

Delamont, S., Atkinson, P. A. and Parry, O. (2000) *The doctoral experience: success and failure in graduate school*. London: Falmer Press.

Denzin, N. K. (1978) *The Research Act: A Theoretical Introduction to Sociological methods*. 2nd edn. New York: McGraw Hill.

Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (2011) ‘Introduction: The discipline and practice of qualitative research’, in Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (eds) *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research*. 4th edn. London: Sage, pp. 1–19.

DePietro, R., Wiarda, E. and Fleischer, M. (1990) ‘The context for change: organization, technology and environment’, in Tornatzky, L. G. and Fleischer, M. (eds) *The Process of Technological Innovation*. Lexington: Lexington Books, pp. 151–175.

Domínguez-Almendros, S., Benítez-Parejo, N. and Gonzalez-Ramirez, A. R. (2011) ‘Logistic regression models’, *Allergologia et Immunopathologia*, 39(5), pp. 295–305. doi: 10.1016/j.aller.2011.05.002.

Dormann, C. F., Elith, J., Bacher, S., Buchmann, C., Carl, G., Carré, G., García Marquéz, J., R., Gruber, B., Lafourcade, B., Leitão, P., J., Münkemüller, T., McClean, C., Osborne, P., E., Reineking, B., Schröder, B., Skidmore, A., K., Zurell, D. and Lautenbach, S. (2013) ‘Collinearity: A review of methods to deal with it and a simulation study evaluating their performance’, *Ecography*, 36(1), pp. 27–46. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0587.2012.07348.x.

Drosos, D., Tsotsolas, N., Chalikias, M., Skordoulis, M. and Koniordos, M. (2015) ‘A survey on the use of social networking sites in Greece’, in Kravets *et al.* (ed.) *Creativity in Intelligent Technologies & Data Science*. Springer International Publishing Switzerland, pp. 556–570.

Drummond, C., McGrath, H. and O’Toole, T. (2018) ‘The impact of social media on resource mobilisation in entrepreneurial firms’, *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier, 70(June 2017), pp. 68–89. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2017.05.009.

Dudovskiy, J. (2018) *The Ultimate Guide to Writing a Dissertation in Business Studies: A Step-by-Step Assistance*. Business Research Methodology.

Dwivedi, Y. K., Ismagilova, E., Rana, N., P. and Raman, R. (2021) ‘Social Media Adoption, Usage And Impact In Business-To-Business (B2B) Context: A State-Of-The-Art Literature Review’, *Information Systems Frontiers*. Springer. doi: 10.1007/s10796-021-10106-y.

Dwivedi, Y. K., Choudrie, J. and Brinkman, W. P. (2006) ‘Development of a survey instrument to examine consumer adoption of broadband’, *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 106(5), pp. 700–718. doi: 10.1108/02635570610666458.

Dwivedi, Y. K., Kapoor, K. and Chen, H. (2015) 'Advertsing in Social Media', *The Marketing Review*, 15(3), pp. 289–309.

Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Lowe, A. (2002) *Management research: An introduction*. London: SAGE Publications.

Edosomwan, S., Prakasan, S., K., Kouame, D., Watson, J. and Seymour, T. (2011) 'The History of Social Media and its Impact on Business', *The Journal of Applied Management & Entrepreneurship*, 16(3), pp. 79–91.

Effendi, M. I., Sugandini, D. and Istanto, Y. (2020) 'Social Media Adoption in SMEs Impacted by COVID-19: The TOE Model*', *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(11), pp. 915–925. doi: 10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no11.915.

Eid, R. (2009) 'Extending TAM and IDT to predict the adoption of the Internet for B-to-B marketing activities: An empirical study of UK companies', *International Journal of e-Business Research*, 5(4), pp. 68–85. doi: 10.4018/jebr.2009040605.

Eid, R., Abdelmoety, Z. and Agag, G. (2020) 'Antecedents and consequences of social media marketing use: an empirical study of the UK exporting B2B SMEs', *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 35(2), pp. 284–305. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-04-2018-0121.

Eisenhardt, K. M. (1991) 'Better Stories and Better Constructs: The Case for Rigor and Comparative Logic', *Academy of Management Review*, 16(3), pp. 620–627.

Eitle, V. and Buxmann, P. (2020) 'Cultural Differences in Machine Learning Adoption: An International Comparison between Germany and the United States', *Proceedings of the 28th European Conference on Information Systems*.

Emden, C., Hancock, H., Schubert, S., and Darbyshire, P. (2001) 'A web of intrigue: The search for quality in qualitative research. Nurse Education in Practice', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 1, pp. 204–211.

Erumban, A. A. and de Jong, S. B. (2006) 'Cross-country differences in ICT adoption: A consequence of Culture?', *Journal of World Business*, 41(4), pp. 302–314. doi: 10.1016/j.jwb.2006.08.005.

European Commission (2018) *Athens is the European Capital of Innovation 2018*. Lisbon. Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=newsalert&year=2016&na=na-080416>.

European Commission (2020) *Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) Country Report: Greece.*, European Commission. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/scoreboard/greece>.

Eurostat (2018) *Euro area unemployment at 8.1%*, *Eurostat: Newsrelease Euroindicators*. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/2995521/10663786/3-30102020-CP-EN.pdf/f93787e0-0b9a-e10e-b897-c0a5f7502d4e>.

Eurostat (2021) *Gross domestic product at market prices*. Luxembourg. Available at: <http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/setupDownloads.do>.

Evans, J. R. and Mathur, A. (2005) 'The value of online surveys', *Internet Research*, 15(2), pp. 195–219. doi: 10.1108/10662240510590360.

Felix, R., Rauschnabel, P. A. and Hinsch, C. (2017) 'Elements of strategic social media marketing: A holistic framework', *Journal of Business Research*. Elsevier Inc., 70, pp. 118–126. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.05.001.

Fendt, J., Kaminska-Labbé, R. and Sachs, W. M. (2008) 'Producing and socializing relevant management knowledge: Re-turn to pragmatism', *European Business Review*, 20(6), pp. 471–491. doi: 10.1108/09555340810913502.

Fereday, J. and Muir-Cochrane, E. (2006) 'Demonstrating Rigor Using Thematic Analysis: A Hybrid Approach of Inductive and Deductive Coding and Theme Development', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 5(1), pp. 80–92. doi: 10.1177/160940690600500107.

Fernandes, A. A. T., Filho, D., B., F., da Rocha, E., C. and Nascimento, W., S. (2020) 'Read this paper if you want to learn logistic regression', *Revista de Sociologia e Política*, 28(74), pp. 1/1-19/19. doi: 10.1590/1678-987320287406EN.

Field, A. (2018) *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics*. 5th edn. SAGE Publications, Inc.

Filo, K., Lock, D. and Karg, A. (2015) 'Sport and social media research: A review', *Sport Management Review*. Sport Management Association of Australia and New Zealand, 18(2), pp. 166–181. doi: 10.1016/j.smr.2014.11.001.

Fischer, E. and Reuber, A. R. (2011) 'Social interaction via new social media: (How) can interactions on Twitter affect effectual thinking and behavior?', *Journal of Business Venturing*. Elsevier Inc., 26(1), pp. 1–18. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusvent.2010.09.002.

Fishbein, M. and Ajzen, I. (1975) *Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior: An introduction to theory and research*. Don Mills, Ontario: Addison-Wesley Pub. Co.

Fisher, S. L. and Howell, A. W. (2004) 'Beyond user acceptance: An examination of employee reactions to information technology systems', *Human Resource Management*, 43(2–3), pp. 243–

258. doi: 10.1002/hrm.20018.

Foroudi, P., Marvi, R., Foroudi, M., M., Ziyadin, S. and Munkhbat, S. (2020) 'Against the Odds: Consequences of Social Media in B2B and B2C', *Beyond Multi-channel Marketing*, pp. 163–189. doi: 10.1108/978-1-83867-685-820201013.

Fosso Wamba, S. and Carter, L. (2014) 'Social media tools adoption and use by SMEs: An empirical study', *Journal of End User and Organisational Computing*, 26(1), pp. 1–16. doi: 10.1002/bit.21019.

Fraccastoro, S., Gabrielsson, M. and Pullins, E. B. (2020) 'The integrated use of social media, digital, and traditional communication tools in the B2B sales process of international SMEs', *International Business Review*. Elsevier Ltd, 30(4), p. 101776. doi: 10.1016/j.ibusrev.2020.101776.

Fraenkel, J. R. and Wallen, N. E. (1993) *How to design and evaluate research in education*. 2nd edn. Boston, MA: McGraw Hill.

Gales, L. (2008) 'The role of culture in technology management research: National Character and Cultural Distance frameworks', *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management - JET-M*, 25(1–2), pp. 3–22. doi: 10.1016/j.jengtecman.2008.01.001.

Ganesan, S., Malter, A. J. and Rindfleisch, A. (2005) 'Does distance still matter? Geographic proximity and new product development', *Journal of Marketing*, 69(4), pp. 44–60. doi: 10.1509/jmkg.2005.69.4.44.

Gáti, M., G. (2015) 'Influencing factors of small and medium-sized enterprises' marketing activities- In particular as regards on online marketing activities', pp. 1–29.

- Gazal, K., Montague, I., Poudel, R. and Wiedenbeck, J. (2016) 'Forest Products Industry in a Digital Age: Factors Affecting Social Media Adoption', *Forest Products Journal*, 66(5–6), pp. 343–353.
- Ghauri, P. and Grønhaug, K. (2005) *Research Methods in Business Studies: A Practical Guide*. 3rd edn. Pearson.
- Giannarakis, G. and Theotokas, I. (2011) 'The Effect of Financial Crisis in Corporate Social Responsibility Performance', *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 3(1), pp. 2–10. doi: 10.5539/ijms.v3n1p2.
- Giotopoulos, I., Kontolaimou, A., Korra, E. and Tsakanikas, A. (2017) 'What drives ICT adoption by SMEs? Evidence from a large-scale survey in Greece', *Journal of Business Research*. Elsevier, 81(December 2016), pp. 60–69. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.08.007.
- Giousmpasoglou, C. (2014) 'Greek management and culture', *European J. of Cross-Cultural Competence and Management*, 3(1), p. 51. doi: 10.1504/ejccm.2014.063403.
- Goles, T. and Hirschheim, R. (2000) 'The paradigm is dead, the paradigm is dead...long live the paradigm: the legacy of Burrell and Morgan', *Omega The International Journal of Management Science*, 28, pp. 249–268. Available at: <http://www.markd.nl/content/references/2000Goles.pdf>.
- Goode, S. and Stevens, K. (2000) 'An analysis of the business characteristics of adopters and non-adopters of World Wide Web technology', *Information Technology and Management*, 1–2(1), pp. 129–154. doi: 10.1023/A:1019112722593.
- Gorman, G. E. and Clayton, P. (2005) *Qualitative Research for the Information Professional: A Practical Handbook*. 2nd edn. London: Facet Publishing.

- Gray, D. E. (2014) *Doing Research in the real world*. 2nd edn. SAGE.
- Greener, S. (2008) *Business Research Methods*. Ventus Publishing ApS.
- Greenhalgh, T., Robert, G., MacFarlane, F., Bate, P. and Kyriakidou, O. (2004) 'Diffusion of innovations in service organizations: Systematic review and recommendations', *Milbank Quarterly*, 82(4), pp. 581–629. doi: 10.1111/j.0887-378X.2004.00325.x.
- Guba, E. G. (1981) 'Criteria for Assessing the Trustworthiness of Naturalistic Inquiries', *Educational Communication and Technology*, 29(2), pp. 75–91.
- Guba, E. and Lincoln, Y. (1985) *Naturalistic inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: SAGE.
- Guesalaga, R. (2016) 'The use of social media in sales: Individual and organizational antecedents, and the role of customer engagement in social media', *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 54, pp. 71–79.
- Gummesson, E. (2008) 'Quality, service-dominant logic and many-to-many marketing', *TQM Journal*, 20(2), pp. 143–153. doi: 10.1108/17542730810857372.
- Gunelius, S. (2011) *30 - Minute Social Media Marketing*. New York: Mcgraw Hill. Heim., New York: Mcgraw Hill. Heim.
- Gutierrez, A., Boukrami, E. and Lumsden, R. (2015) 'Technological, Organisational and Environmental Factors Influencing Managers' Decision to Adopt Cloud Computing in the UK', *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 28, pp. 788–807.
- Habibi, F., Hamilton, C., A., Valos, M., J. and Callaghan, M. (2015) 'E-marketing orientation and social media implementation in B2B marketing', *European Business Review*, 27(6), pp. 638–655. doi: 10.1108/EBR-03-2015-0026.

- Hair, J. F., Black, W., C., Babin, B., J. and Anderson, R., E. (2013) *Multivariate Data Analysis. Pearson New International Edition*. Pearson Ne. Pearson Higher Ed.
- Hair, J. J. F., Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., Anderson, R.E. and Tatham, R.L. (2006) *Multivariate Data Analysis*. New Jersey: Pearson-Prentice Hall.
- Hall, E. T. (1976) *Beyond Culture*. Garden City, NY: Anchor Press/Doubleday.
- Haller, S. A. and Siedschlag, I. (2011) ‘Determinants of ICT adoption: Evidence from firm-level data’, *Applied Economics*, 43(26), pp. 3775–3788. doi: 10.1080/00036841003724411.
- Hampden-Turner, C. and Trompenaars, F. (1993) *The Seven Cultures of Capitalism: Value Systems for Creating Wealth in the United States, Japan, Germany, France, Britain, Sweden, and the Netherlands*. New York, NY: Doubleday Business.
- Hampden-Turner, C. and Trompenaars, F. (1997) ‘Response to Geert Hofstede’, *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 21(1), pp. 149–159. doi: 10.1016/s0147-1767(96)00042-9.
- Hanna, R., Rohm, A. and Crittenden, V. L. (2011) ‘We’re all connected: The power of the social media ecosystem’, *Business Horizons*. ‘Kelley School of Business, Indiana University’, 54(3), pp. 265–273. doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2011.01.007.
- Hardy, M. and Bryman, A. (2004) ‘Handbook of Data Analysis’. doi: 10.4135/9781848608184.
- Harzing, A.-W. and Hofstede, G. (1996) ‘Planned change in organizations: The influence of national culture’, *Research in the Sociology of Organizations*, 14(1), pp. 297–340.
- Hasan, H. and Ditsa, G. (1999) ‘The Impact of Culture on the Adoption of High Technology Products’, *Journal of Global Information Management*, 1, pp. 5–15. doi: 10.1108/eb010276.
- Hasani, T., Bojei, J. and Dehghantanha, A. (2017) ‘Investigating the antecedents to the adoption

of SCRM technologies by start-up companies’, *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(5), pp. 655–675.
doi: 10.1016/j.tele.2016.12.004.

Hassan, S., Nadzim, S. Z. A. and Shiratuddin, N. (2015) ‘Strategic Use of Social Media for Small Business Based on the AIDA Model’, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. Elsevier B.V., 172, pp. 262–269. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.363.

Hatzinikolaou, D. and Katsarou, K. (2019) ‘An Account of Principal Components Analysis and Some Cautions on Using the Correct Formulas and the Correct Procedures in SPSS’, *International Journal of Statistics and Applications*, 9(5), pp. 160–169. doi: 10.5923/j.statistics.20190905.05.

Hausken, K. and Welburn, J. W. (2020) ‘Assessing the 2010–2018 financial crisis in Greece, Portugal, Ireland, Spain, and Cyprus’, *Journal of Economic Studies*. doi: 10.1108/JES-08-2020-0406.

Heale, R. and Twycross, A. (2015) ‘Validity and reliability in quantitative studies’, *Evidence Based Nursing*, 18(3), pp. 66–67. doi: 10.1136/eb-2015-102129.

Henderson, A. and Bowley, T. (2010) ‘Authentic dialogue? The role of ““friendship”” in a social media recruitment campaign.’, *Journal of Communication Management*, 14(3), pp. 237–257.

Hennig-Thurau, T., Malthouse, E.C., Friege, C., Gensler, S., Lobschat, L., Rangaswamy, A. and Skiera, B. (2010) ‘The impact of new media on customer relationships’, *Journal of Service Research*, 13(3), pp. 311–330.

Hinton, P. (2004) *Statistics Explained: A Guide for Social Science Students*. Taylor & Francis.

Hoehle, H., Zhang, X. and Venkatesh, V. (2015) ‘An espoused cultural perspective to understand continued intention to use mobile applications: A four-country study of mobile social media

application usability’, *European Journal of Information Systems*, 24(3), pp. 337–359. doi: 10.1057/ejis.2014.43.

Hoffmann, C. P., Lutz, C. and Meckel, M. (2013) ‘Social Media Readiness in Public Administration’, *IRSPM Conference*, pp. 1–31.

Hofstede, G. (1984) ‘Cultural Dimensions In Management And Planning’, *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, pp. 81–99.

Hofstede, G. (1991) *Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind*. London: McGraw-Hill.

Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G. J. and Minkov, M. (2010) *Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind*. 3rd edn, *McGraw Hill*. 3rd edn. New York: McGraw Hill. doi: 10.1177/030630709201700409.

Hofstede, G., Jan Hofstede, G. and Minkov, M. (2010) *Cultures and Organizations, Cultures and Organizations*. doi: 10.1007/s11569-007-0005-8.

Hogg, A. (2003) ‘Web efforts energize customer research’, *Electric Perspectives*, (September-October), pp. 81–83.

Holloway, I. and Todres, L. (2003) ‘The status of method: flexibility, consistency and coherence’, *Qualitative Research*, 3(3), pp. 345–357.

Hosmer, W. D. and Lemeshow, S. (2000) *Applied Logistic Regression*. 2nd edn. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Hossain, M. A. and Quaddus, M. (2011) ‘The adoption and continued usage intention of RFID: An integrated framework’, *Information Technology and People*, 24(3), pp. 236–256. doi: 10.1108/09593841111158365.

Huck, S. W. (2007) *Reading Statistics and Research*. 5th edn. New York, NY: Allyn & Bacon.

Huotari, L., Ulkuniemi, P., Saraniemi, S., Mäläskä, M. (2015) 'Analysis of content creation in social media by B2B companies', *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 30(6), pp. 761–770. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-05-2013-0118.

Hutt, M. D. and Speh, T. W. (2014) *Business Marketing Management: B2B*. 11th edn. Andover. Available at: Cengage Learning EMEA.

Hyde, K. F. (2000) 'Recognising deductive processes in qualitative research', *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 3(2), pp. 82–90. doi: 10.1108/13522750010322089.

Hyman, L., Lamb, J. and Bulmer, M. (2006) 'The Use of Pre-Existing Survey Questions : Implications for Data Quality', *European Conference on Quality in Survey Statistics*, pp. 1–8.

Iacobucci, D. and Churchill, G. A. (2009) *Marketing Research: Methodological Foundations*. 10th edn. South-Western College Pub ISBN-13:

Iankova, S., Davies, I., Archer-Brown, C., Marder, B. and Yau, A. (2018) 'A comparison of social media marketing between B2B, B2C and mixed business models', *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier, (January), pp. 1–11. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2018.01.001.

Iankova, S. (2018) 'Social Media in Business-to-Business Marketing: A Mixed Methods Approach', in *Academy of Marketing Doctoral Colloquium*. At: Stirling University.

Iankova, S., Davies, I., Archer-Brown, C., Marder, B. and Yau, A. (2019) 'A comparison of social media marketing between B2B, B2C and mixed business models', *Industrial Marketing Management*, 81, pp. 169–179. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2018.01.001.

ICAP (2018) *GREEK FINANCIAL GUIDE 2018*. Available at:

<https://dir.icap.gr/mailimages/flipbooks/EOO/2018>.

Ifinedo, P. (2011) 'An empirical analysis of factors influencing internet/e-business technologies adoption by smes in Canada', *International Journal of Information Technology and Decision Making*, 10(4), pp. 731–766. doi: 10.1142/S0219622011004543.

International Monetary Fund (2014) *WEO Groups and Aggregates Information*. Washington, D. C. Available at: <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/weo/2014/01/weodata/groups.htm#ae>.

Itani, O. S., Agnihotri, R. and Dingus, R. (2017) 'Social media use in B2b sales and its impact on competitive intelligence collection and adaptive selling: Examining the role of learning orientation as an enabler', *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier, 66(July), pp. 64–79. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2017.06.012.

Jackson, S. L. (2011) *Research Methods and Statistics: A Critical Approach*. 4th edn. Cengage Learning.

Jacob, S. A. and Furgerson, S. P. (2012) 'Writing Interview Protocols and Conducting Interviews: Tips for Students New to the Field of Qualitative Research', *The Qualitative Report Teaching*, 17(42), pp. 1–10. doi: 10.1136/fmch-2018-000057.

Järvinen, J. J., Tollinen, A., Karjaluoto, H. and Jayawardhena, C (2012) 'Digital and Social Media Marketing Usage in B2B Industrial Section.', *Marketing Management Journal*, 22(2), pp. 102–117.

Jick, T. D. (1979) 'Mixing Qualitative and Quantitative Methods: Triangulation in Action', *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 24(4), pp. 602–611. doi: 10.1088/0953-8984/10/45/011.

Johnson, B. R. and Onwuegbuzie, A. . (2004) 'Mixed Methods Research: A Research Paradigm

Whose Time Has Come’, *Educational Researcher*, 33(7), pp. 14–26.

Johnson, P. and Clark, M. (2006) *Business and Management Research Methodologies*. 6th edn, *Business and Management Research Methodologies*. 6th edn. SAGE Publications Ltd. doi: 10.4135/9781446260906.

Johnson, R. B., Onwuegbuzie, A. J. and Turner, L. A. (2007) ‘Toward a Definition of Mixed Methods Research’, *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(2), pp. 112–133. doi: 10.1177/1558689806298224.

Jussila, J. (2015) *Social Media in Business-to-Business Companies ’ Innovation*.

Jussila, J. J., Kärkkäinen, H. and Aramo-Immonen, H. (2014) ‘Social media utilization in business-to-business relationships of technology industry firms’, *Computers in Human Behavior*. Elsevier Ltd, 30, pp. 606–613. doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2013.07.047.

Jussila, J. J., Kärkkäinen, H. and Leino, M. (2011) ‘Benefits of social media in business-to-business customer interface in innovation’, *Proceedings of the 15th International Academic MindTrek Conference on Envisioning Future Media Environments - MindTrek ’11*, p. 167. doi: 10.1145/2181037.2181065.

Jussila, J. J., Kärkkäinen, H. and Maija, H. (2013) ‘Innovation-related benefits of social media in Business-to-Business customer relationships’, *International Journal of Advanced Media and Communication*, 5(1), pp. 4–18.

Kane, K., Robinson-Combre, J. and Berge, Z. L. (2010) ‘Tapping into social networking: Collaborating enhances both knowledge management and e-learning’, *Vine: The Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 40(1), pp. 62–70. doi:

10.1108/03055721011024928.

Kanellis, P. and Papadopoulos, T. (2009) 'Conducting research in Information Systems: An Epistemological journey', in *Information Systems Research Methods, Epistemology and Applications, Information Science Reference*. New York: Hersey, pp. 1–34.

Kaplan, A. M. and Haenlein, M. (2010) 'Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media', *Business Horizons*, 53(1), pp. 59–68. doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2009.09.003.

Kaplan, A. M. and Haenlein, M. (2011) 'Two hearts in three-quarter time: How to waltz the social media/viral marketing dance', *Business Horizons*. 'Kelley School of Business, Indiana University', 54(3), pp. 253–263. doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2011.01.006.

Kaplowitz, M. D., Lupi, F., Couper, M., P. and Thorp, L. (2012) 'The Effect of Invitation Design on Web Survey Response Rates', *Social Science Computer Review*, 30(3), pp. 339–349. doi: 10.1177/0894439311419084.

Kapoor, K. K., Dwivedi, Y. K. and Williams, M. D. (2014) 'Rogers' Innovation Adoption Attributes: A Systematic Review and Synthesis of Existing Research', *Information Systems Management*, 31(1), pp. 74–91. doi: 10.1108/EJIM-08-2012-0083.

Karjaluoto, H., Mustonen, N. and Ulkuniemi, P. (2015) 'The role of digital channels in industrial marketing communications', *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 30(6), pp. 703–710. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-04-2013-0092.

Kärkkäinen, H., Jussila, J. and Väisänen, J. (2010) 'Social Media Use and Potential in Business-to-Business Companies' Innovation', in *Proceedings of the 14th International Academic*

MindTreck Conference; Envisioning Future Media Environment, pp. 228–236. doi: 10.4018/jaci.2013010104.

Katona, Z. and Sarvary, M. (2014) ‘Berkeley-haas case series Maersk line: B2B social media-"it's communication,not marketing"’, *California Management Review*, 56(3), pp. 142–156. doi: 10.1525/cmr.2014.56.3.142.

Kavoura, A. and Stavrianea, A. (2014) ‘Economic and Social Aspects from Social Media’s Implementation as a Strategic Innovative Marketing Tool in the Tourism Industry’, *Procedia Economics and Finance*. Elsevier B.V., 14(14), pp. 303–312.

Keinänen, H. and Kuivalainen, O. (2015) ‘Antecedents of social media B2B use in industrial marketing context: customers’ view’, *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 30(6), pp. 711–722.

Kendall, J. D., Tung, L., L., Chua, K., H., Ng, C., H., D. and Tan, S., M. (2001) ‘Receptivity of Singapore’s SMEs to electronic commerce adoption’, *Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 10(3), pp. 223–242. doi: 10.1016/S0963-8687(01)00048-8.

Kennedy, B. B. L., Kennedy, B. L. and Thornberg, R. (2018) *Deduction , Induction , and Abduction In : The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Data Collection, The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Data Collection*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Khan, M. F. and Jan, A. (2015) ‘Social Media and Social Media Marketing: A Literature Review’, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management* Ver. I, 17(11), pp. 2319–7668. doi: 10.9790/487X-171111215.

Kietzmann, J. H., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I., P. and Silvestre, B., S. (2011) ‘Social media? Get

serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media’, *Business Horizons*. ‘Kelley School of Business, Indiana University’, 54(3), pp. 241–251. doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2011.01.005.

Kim, H. D., Lee, I. and Lee, C. K. (2013) ‘Building Web 2.0 enterprises: A study of small and medium enterprises in the United States’, *International Small Business Journal*, 31(2), pp. 156–174. doi: 10.1177/0266242611409785.

Kim, S. H., Jang, S. Y. and Yang, K. H. (2017) ‘Analysis of the Determinants of Software-as-a-Service Adoption in Small Businesses: Risks, Benefits, and Organizational and Environmental Factors’, *Journal of Small Business Management*, 55(2), pp. 303–325. doi: 10.1111/jsbm.12304.

Kimberlin, C. L. and Winterstein, A. G. (2008) ‘Validity and reliability of measurement instruments used in research’, *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy*, 65(23), pp. 2276–2284. doi: 10.2146/ajhp070364.

King, N. (2004) ‘Using templates in the thematic analysis of text’, in Cassell, C. and Symon, G. (eds) *Essential guide to qualitative methods in organizational research*. London, UK: Sage, pp. 257–270.

Kollmann, T., Kuckertz, A. and Breugst, N. (2009) ‘Organizational Readiness and the Adoption of Electronic Business - The Moderating Role of National Culture in 29 European Countries’, *Data Base for Advances in Information Systems*, 40(4), pp. 117–131. doi: 10.1145/1644953.1644961.

Konstantinidis, M. (2016) ‘An Empirical Investigation of Factors Affecting Electronic Commerce Adoption among SME ’ s in Greece’, *THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS & MANAGEMENT*, 4(10), pp. 391–400.

Kothari, C. R. (2004) *Research Methodology: Methods & Techniques*. 2nd edn. New Delhi: New Age International (P) Ltd, Publishers.

Koufaris, M. (2002) 'Applying the Technology Acceptance Model and flow theory to online Consumer Behavior', *Information Systems Research*, 13(2), pp. 205–223. doi: 10.1287/isre.13.2.205.83.

Kozinets, R. V. (2002) 'The Field Behind the Screen: Using Netnography for Marketing Research in Online Communities', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 39(1), pp. 61–72. doi: 10.1509/jmkr.39.1.61.18935.

Kozinets, R. V. (2012) 'Marketing Netnography: Prom/ot(Ulgat)ing a New Research Method', *Methodological Innovations Online*, 7(1), pp. 37–45. doi: 10.4256/mio.2012.004.

Kreiser, P. M., Marino, L., D., Dickson, P. and Weaver, K. M. (2010) 'Cultural influences on entrepreneurial orientation: The impact of national culture on risk taking and proactiveness in SMEs', *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 34(5), pp. 959–983. doi: 10.1111/j.1540-6520.2010.00396.x.

Kuikka, M. and Äkkinen, M. (2011) 'Determining the Challenges of Organizational Social Media Adoption and Use', in *ECIS 2011 Proceedings*, pp. 1–13. doi: 10.1016/S0014-5793(97)00750-3.

Kumar, V. and Raheja, G. (2012) 'Business to business (B2B) and business to consumer (B2C) management', *International Journal of Computer & Technology*, 3(3), pp. 447–451.

Kumar, V. and Reinartz, W. (2012) *Customer Relationship Management: Concept, Strategy, and Tools*. Springer.

Lacka, E. and Chong, A. (2016) 'Usability perspective on social media sites' adoption in the B2B

context’, *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 54, pp. 80–91. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2016.01.001.

Lai, L. S. L. and Turban, E. (2008) ‘Groups formation and operations in the web 2.0 environment and social networks’, *Group Decision and Negotiation*, 17(5), pp. 387–402. doi: 10.1007/s10726-008-9113-2.

Lai, P. (2017) ‘The Literature Review of Technology Adoption Models and Theories for the Novelty Technology’, *JJISTEM- Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management*, 14(1), pp. 21–38. doi: 10.4301/s1807-17752017000100002.

Lam, H. K. S., Yeung, A. C. L. and Cheng, T. C. E. (2016) ‘The impact of firms’ social media initiatives on operational efficiency and innovativeness’, *Journal of Operations Management*. Elsevier Ltd, 47–48(April 2018), pp. 28–43. doi: 10.1016/j.jom.2016.06.001.

LaPlaca, P. J. and Lindgreen, A. (2016) ‘Letter from the Editors’, *Industrial Marketing Management*, 54, pp. 1–3.

Lashgari, M., Sutton-Brady, C., Søylen, K., S. and Ulfvengren, P. (2018) ‘Adoption strategies of social media in B2B firms: a multiple case study approach’, *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 33(5), pp. 730–743. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-10-2016-0242.

Le, V. H., Rowe, F., Truex, D. and Huynh, M., Q (2012) ‘An Empirical Study of Determinants of E-Commerce Adoption in SMEs in Vietnam’, *Journal of Global Information Management*, 20(3), pp. 23–54. doi: 10.4018/jgim.2012070102.

Leake, W., Vaccarello, L. and Ginty, M. (2012) *Complete B2B Online Marketing*. Hoboken, N. J.: J. Wiley & Sons.

Lee, S. G., Trimi, S. and Kim, C. (2013) 'The impact of cultural differences on technology adoption', *Journal of World Business*. Elsevier Inc., 48(1), pp. 20–29. doi: 10.1016/j.jwb.2012.06.003.

Leech, N., Barrett, K. and Morgan, G. A. (2005) *SPSS for Intermediate Statistics*. 2nd edn, *SPSS for Intermediate Statistics*. 2nd edn. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc. doi: 10.4324/9781410611420.

Leek, S., Canning, L. and Houghton, D. (2016) 'Revisiting the Task Media Fit Model in the era of Web 2.0: Twitter use and interaction in the healthcare sector', *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier B.V., 54, pp. 25–32. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2015.12.007.

Lehtimäki, T., Salo, J., Hiltula, H. and Lankinen, M. (2009) *Harnessing Web 2.0 for Business To Business Marketing - Literature Review and an Empirical Perspective from Finland*, University of Oulu WP.

Leidner, Dorothy, E. and Kayworth, T. (2006) 'Review: a review of culture in Information Systems research: toward a theory of Information Technology culture conflict', *MIS Quarterly*, 30(2), pp. 357–399.

Lilien, G. L. and Grewal, R. (2012) *Handbook of business-to-business marketing*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

Lin, F. J. (2008) 'Solving multicollinearity in the process of fitting regression model using the nested estimate procedure', *Quality and Quantity*, 42(3), pp. 417–426. doi: 10.1007/s11135-006-9055-1.

Lin, W. L., Yip, N., Ho, J., A. and Sambasivan, M. (2020) 'The adoption of technological

innovations in a B2B context and its impact on firm performance: An ethical leadership perspective’, *Industrial Marketing Management*, 89 (December 2019), pp. 61–71. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2019.12.009.

Lipiäinen, H. S. M. and Karjaluoto, H. (2015) ‘Industrial branding in the digital age’, *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 30(6), pp. 733–741. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-04-2013-0089.

Liu, H., Ke, W., Wei, K., K., Gu, J. and Chen, H. (2010) ‘The role of institutional pressures and organizational culture in the firm’s intention to adopt internet-enabled supply chain management systems’, *Journal of Operations Management*, 28(5), pp. 372–384. doi: 10.1016/j.jom.2009.11.010.

Loukis, E., Spinellis, D. and Katsigiannis, A. (2011) ‘Barriers to the adoption of B2B e-marketplaces by large enterprises: Lessons learned from the hellenic aerospace industry’, *Information Systems Management*, 28(2), pp. 130–146. doi: 10.1080/10580530.2011.562129.

Low, C., Chen, Y. and Wu, M. (2011) ‘Understanding the determinants of cloud computing adoption’, *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 111(7), pp. 1006–1023. doi: 10.1108/02635571111161262.

Maduku, D. K., Mpinganjira, M. and Duh, H. (2016) ‘Understanding mobile marketing adoption intention by South African SMEs: A multi-perspective framework’, *International Journal of Information Management*. Elsevier Ltd, 36(5), pp. 711–723. doi: 10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2016.04.018.

Magno, F. and Cassia, F. (2020) ‘Establishing thought leadership through social media in B2B settings: effects on customer relationship performance’, *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 35(3), pp. 437–446. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-12-2018-0410.

- Majid, M. A. A., Othman, M., Mohamad, S., F., Lim, S., A., H. and Yusof, A. (2017) 'Piloting for Interviews in Qualitative Research: Operationalization and Lessons Learnt', *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(4). doi: 10.6007/ijarbss/v7-i4/2916.
- Mallat, N., Rossi, M., Tuunainen, V., K. and Öörni, A. (2006) 'The impact of use situation and mobility on the acceptance of mobile ticketing services', *Proceedings of the 39th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 2(C), pp. 1–10. doi: 10.1109/HICSS.2006.472.
- Mangold, W. G. and Faulds, D. J. (2009) 'Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix', *Business Horizons*, 52(4), pp. 357–365. doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2009.03.002.
- Manohar, N., Macmillan, F., Steiner, G., Z. and Arora, A. (2018) 'Recruitment of Research Participants', in Liamputtong, P. (ed.) *Handbook of Research Methods in Health Social Sciences*. Springer Nature Singapore Pte Ltd, pp. 1–28. doi: 10.1007/978-981-10-2779-6.
- Marshall, M. N. (1996) *Sampling for qualitative research*, *Family Practice* © Oxford University Press. Available at: <https://academic.oup.com/fampra/article/13/6/522/496701>.
- Mason, C. H. and Perreault, W. D. (1991) 'Collinearity, Power, and Interpretation of Multiple Regression Analysis', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 28(3), pp. 268–280. doi: 10.2307/3172863.
- Matikiti, R., Mpinganjira, M. and Roberts-Lombard, M. (2018) 'Application of the Technology Acceptance Model and the Technology–Organisation–Environment Model to examine social media marketing use in the South African tourism industry', *SA Journal of Information Management*, 20(1), pp. 1–12. doi: 10.4102/sajim.v20i1.790.
- McCoy, S., Galletta, D. F. and King, W. R. (2005) 'Integrating National Culture into IS Research: The Need for Current Individual Level Measures', *Communications of the Association for*

Information Systems, 15(February). doi: 10.17705/1cais.01512.

McKinsey & Company (2012) *Greece 10 Years Ahead Defining Greece 's new growth model and strategy*, Report #1/15. Athens. Available at: https://www.mckinsey.com/~//media/mckinsey/locations/europe_and_middle_east/greece/overview/greece_10_years_ahead/greece_10_years_ahead.pdf.

McSweeney, B. (2002) 'Hofstede's model of national cultural differences and their consequences: A triumph of faith - A failure of analysis', *Human Relations*, 55(1), pp. 89–118. doi: 10.1177/0018726702551004.

Mehmet, M. I. and Clarke, R. J. (2016) 'B2B social media semantics: Analysing multimodal online meanings in marketing conversations', *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 54, pp. 92–106. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2015.12.006.

Melanthiou, Y. and Papasolomou, I. (2015) 'Social media uptake in Cyprus-or is it just a new fad?', *International Journal*, (JANUARY). doi: 10.1504/IJTMKT.2015.070660.

Melanthiou, Y., Papasolomou, I. and Komodromos, M. (2015) 'Social media uptake in Cyprus - or is it just a new fad?', *International Journal of Technology Marketing*, 10(3), p. 312. doi: 10.1504/IJTMKT.2015.070660.

Menard, S. (1995) *Applied Logistic Regression Analysis: Sage University Series on Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Mertens, D. M. (1998) *Research methods in education and psychology: Integrating diversity with quantitative and qualitative approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.

Meske, C. and Stieglitz, S. (2013) 'Adoption and Use of Social Media in Small and Medium-Sized

Enterprises’, in *Harmsen, F. and Proper, H.A. (Eds): PRET, LNBIP*. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 61–75. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-38774-6.

Michaelidou, N., Siamagka, N. T. and Christodoulides, G. (2011) ‘Usage, barriers and measurement of social media marketing: An exploratory investigation of small and medium B2B brands’, *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 40(7), pp. 1153–1159. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2011.09.009.

Mihet, R. (2013) ‘Effects of culture on firm risk-taking: A cross-country and cross-industry analysis’, *Journal of Cultural Economics*, 37(1), pp. 109–151. doi: 10.1007/s10824-012-9186-2.

Mikalef, P. and Pateli, A. (2017) ‘Social Media for Open Innovation : A Study of Adoption Determinants’, *Twenty First Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems, Langkawi 2017*, (July).

Miles, M. B. and Huberman, A. M. (1994) *Qualitative Data Analysis*. 2nd edn. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications.

Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M. and Saldaña, J. (2014) *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Methods Sourcebook*. 3rd edn. SAGE Publications, Inc.

Ministry of Digital Governance (2021) *Digital Transformation Bible 2020-2025 (in Greek)*. Available at: https://digitalstrategy.gov.gr/vivlos_pdf.

Mohajan, H. K. (2017) ‘Two Criteria for Good Measurements in Research: Validity and Reliability’, *Annals of Spiru Haret University. Economic Series*, 17(4), pp. 59–82. doi: 10.26458/1746.

Mohammadian, M. and Mohammadreza, M. (2012) ‘Identify the Success Factors of Social Media

(Marketing Perspective)', *International Business and Management*, 4(2), pp. 58–66. doi: 10.3968/j.ibm.1923842820120402.1120.

Molina-Azorín, J. F. and Cameron, R. (2010) 'The Application of Mixed Methods in Organisational Research: A Literature Review', *The Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 8(2), pp. 95–105.

Moon, J. W. and Kim, Y. G. (2001) 'Extending the TAM for a World-Wide-Web context', *Information and Management*, 38(4), pp. 217–230. doi: 10.1016/S0378-7206(00)00061-6.

Moore, J. N., Hopkins, C. D. and Raymond, M. A. (2013) 'Utilization of Relationship-Oriented Social Media in the Selling Process: A Comparison of Consumer (B2C) and Industrial (B2B) Salespeople', *Journal of Internet Commerce*, 12(1), pp. 48–75. doi: 10.1080/15332861.2013.763694.

Moretti, A. and Tuan, A. (2014) 'Social media marketing and relationship marketing: Revolution or evolution? A first step analysis', *Sinergie Italian Journal of Management*, 93(93), pp. 115–137. doi: 10.7433/SRECP.2013.16.

Morgan, D. L. (2007) 'Paradigms Lost and Pragmatism Regained: Methodological Implications of Combining Qualitative and Quantitative Methods', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(1), pp. 48–76. doi: 10.1177/2345678906292462.

Moser, C. A. and Kalton, G. (1971) *Survey Methods in Social Investigation*. 1st edn. London: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9781315241999.

Moustakas, A., Athanasiadis, A., Papamathaiou, A. and Tsakanikas, A. (2018) *Measuring the Economic Impact of Digital Skills in Greece : Challenges Ahead*. Athens.

Mouzelis, N. P. (1986) 'Politics in the Semi-Periphery: Early Parliamentarism and Late Industrialisation in the Balkans and Latin America', *The Journal of Development Studies*.

Moy, R. L., Chen, L. and Kao, L. (2015) *Study Guide for Statistics for Business and Financial Economics - A Supplement to the Textbook by Cheng-Few Lee, John C. Lee and Alice C. Lee*. Springer International Publishing Switzerland. Available at: <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9783319119960>.

Mudambi, S. M., Sinha, J. I. and Shae Taylor, D. (2019) 'Why B-to-B CEOs Should Be More Social on Social Media'. doi: 10.1080/1051712X.2019.1565144.

Nakara, W. A., Benmoussa, F. Z. and Jaouen, A. (2012) 'Entrepreneurship and social media marketing: evidence from French small business', *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 16(4), p. 386. doi: 10.1504/IJESB.2012.047608.

Nakos, G. and Hajidimitriou, A. Y. (2009) 'Conducting Business in Greece: A Brief for International Managers', *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 24(4), pp. 70–83.

Namankani, H., Moxham, C. and Tickle, M. (2016) 'A Conceptual Review of Social Media Adoption in SMEs', in Dwivedi, Y. *et al.* (ed.) *Social Media: The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly*. I3E 2016. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Cham: Springer, pp. 240–250.

Nguyen, N. A. (2016) 'A Cross-Cultural Study on e-Government Services Delivery', *Electronic Journal Information Systems Evaluation*, 19(2), pp. 121–134.

Notta, O. and Kitta, A. (2021) 'Factors Affecting e-Marketing Adoption and Implementation in Food Firms: An Empirical Investigation of Greek Food and Beverage Firms', in Tsounis, N. and Vlachvei, A. (eds) *Advances in Longitudinal Data Methods in Applied Economic Research*.

ICOAE 2020. *Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics*. Springer, Cham. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-63970-9_35.

Nowell, L. S., Norris, J., M., White, D., E. and Moules, N. J. (2017) 'Thematic Analysis: Striving to Meet the Trustworthiness Criteria', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 16, pp. 1–13. doi: 10.1177/1609406917733847.

O'Reilly, T. (2007) 'What is web 2.0?: Design patterns and business models for the next generation of software', *Communications & Strategies*, 65, pp. 17–37.

Odoom, R., Anning-Dorson, T. and Acheampong, G. (2017) 'Antecedents of social media usage and performance benefits in small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)', *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 30(3), pp. 383–399. doi: 10.1108/JEIM-04-2016-0088.

OECD (2018) *OECD Employment Outlook 2018*. Paris: OECD Publishing. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1787/empl_outlook-2018-en.

Okoli, C. and Schabram, K. (2010) 'A Guide to Conducting a Systematic Literature Review of Information Systems Research', *Sprouts: Working Papers on Information Systems*, 10(26), pp. 1–50. doi: 10.2139/ssrn.1954824.

Olasina, G. and Mutula, S. (2015) 'The influence of national culture on the performance expectancy of e-parliament adoption', *Behaviour and Information Technology*, 34(5), pp. 492–505. doi: 10.1080/0144929X.2014.1003326.

Oliveira, T. and Martins, M. (2011) 'Literature review of Information Technology Adoption Models at Firm Level', *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems Evaluatio*, 14(1), pp. 110–121.

Onwuegbuzie, A. and Leech, N. (2005) 'On becoming a pragmatic researcher: The importance of combining quantitative and qualitative research methodologies', *International Journal of Social Research Methodology: Theory and Practice*, 8(5), pp. 375–387. doi: 10.1080/13645570500402447.

Orb, A., Eisenhauer, L. and Wynaden, D. (2001) 'Ethics in qualitative research', *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 33(1), pp. 93–96. doi: 10.1111/j.1547-5069.2001.00093.x.

Orlikowski, W. J. and Baroudi, J. J. (1991) 'Studying information technology in organizations: Research approaches and assumptions', *Information Systems Research*, 2(1), pp. 1–28. doi: 10.1287/isre.2.1.1.

Overdevest, C. (2011) 'Towards a more pragmatic sociology of markets', *Theory and Society*, 40(5), pp. 533–552. doi: 10.1007/s11186-011-9149-1.

Özbilen, P. (2017) 'The Impact of Natural Culture on New Technology Adoption by Firms: A Country Level Analysis', *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 8(4), pp. 299–305. doi: 10.18178/ijimt.2017.8.4.745.

Palen, L. (2008) 'Online Social Media in Crisis events', *Educause Quarterly*, 31(3), pp. 76–78. doi: 10.9774/gleaf.978-1-909493-82-7_4.

Pallant, J. (2007) *SPSS Survival Manual: A Step by Step Guide to Data Analysis Using SPSS*. Allen & Unwin.

Pallant, J. (2016) *SPSS Survival Manual: A Step By Step Guide to Data Analysis Using SPSS Program*. 6th edn. London, UK: McGraw-Hill Education.

Palmatier, R. W. (2008) 'Interfirm relational drivers of customer value', *Journal of Marketing*,

72(4), pp. 76–89. doi: 10.1509/jmkg.72.4.76.

Pandey, N., Nayal, P. and Rathore, A. S. (2020) ‘Digital marketing for B2B organizations: structured literature review and future research directions’, *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 35(7), pp. 1191–1204. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-06-2019-0283.

Papalexandris, N. (2007) ‘Greece: From Ancient Myths to Modern Realities’, in Chhokar, Jagdeep, S., Brodbeck, Felix, C., and House, Robert, J. (eds) *Culture and Leadership Across the World: The GLOBE Book of In-Depth Studies of 25 Societies*. New York: Psychology Press, pp. 767–802. doi: 10.4324/9781003015864-7.

Papazafeiropoulou, A. (2004) ‘Inter-country analysis of electronic commerce adoption in south eastern Europe: Policy recommendations for the region’, *Journal of Global Information Technology Management*, 7(2), pp. 54–69. doi: 10.1080/1097198X.2004.10856372.

Parker, C. M. and Castleman, T. (2009) ‘Small firm e-business adoption: A critical analysis of theory’, *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 22(1–2), pp. 167–182. doi: 10.1108/17410390910932812.

Parveen, F. (2012) ‘Impact of social media usage on organizations’, *Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems (PACIS)*, p. 12. Available at: <http://aisel.aisnet.org/pacis2012/192>.

Parveen, F., Jaafar, N. I. and Ainin, S. (2015) ‘Social media usage and organizational performance: Reflections of Malaysian social media managers’, *Telematics and Informatics*. Elsevier Ltd, 32(1), pp. 67–78. doi: 10.1016/j.tele.2014.03.001.

Pascucci, F., Ancillai, C. and Cardinali, S. (2018) ‘Exploring antecedents of social media usage in B2B: a systematic review’, *Management Research Review*. Emerald Group Publishing Ltd., pp.

629–656. doi: 10.1108/MRR-07-2017-0212.

Pateli, A., Mylonas, N. and Spyrou, A. (2020) ‘Organizational adoption of social media in the hospitality industry: An integrated approach based on DIT and TOE frameworks’, *Sustainability*, 12(17), pp. 1–20. doi: 10.3390/su12177132.

Patton, M. Q. (2015) *Qualitative research & evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice*. 4th edn. SAGE Publications, Inc.

Peirce, C., S. (1960/1979) *Collected Papers of Charles Sanders Peirce Vol. I: Principle of Philosophy; Vol. II: Elements of Logic*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Peng, C.-Y. J. and So, T.-S. H. (2002) ‘Logistic Regression Analysis and Reporting: A Primer’, *Understanding Statistics*. Informa UK Limited, 1(1), pp. 31–70. doi: 10.1207/s15328031us0101_04.

Peng, C. Y. J., Lee, K. L. and Ingersoll, G. M. (2002) ‘An introduction to logistic regression analysis and reporting’, *The Journal of Educational Research*, 96(1), pp. 3–14. doi: 10.1080/00220670209598786.

Pentina, I., Koh, A. C. and Le, T. T. (2012) ‘Adoption of social networks marketing by SMEs: exploring the role of social influences and experience in technology acceptance’, *International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising*, 7(1), p. 65. doi: 10.1504/IJIMA.2012.044959.

Pett, M., Lackey, N. and Sullivan, J. (2003) *Making Sense of Factor Analysis: The Use of Factor Analysis for Instrument Development in Health Care Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA. Available at: SAGE Publications.

Polit, D., Beck, C. and Hungler, B. (2001) *Essentials of nursing research: Methods, appraisal,*

and utilization. 5th edn. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

Poynter, R. (2004) *If the internet is so clever, why aren't we all rich!* Available at: www.virtualsurveys.com/news/papers/paper_11.asp.

Premkumar, G. (2003) 'A meta-analysis of research on information technology implementation in small business', *Journal of Organizational Computing and Electronic Commerce*, 13(2), pp. 91–121. doi: 10.1207/S15327744JOCE1302_2.

Premkumar, G. and Roberts, M. (1999) 'Adoption of new information technologies in rural small businesses', *Omega*, 27(4), pp. 467–484. doi: 10.1016/S0305-0483(98)00071-1.

Prim, A. L., Filho, L., S., Zamur, G., A., C., and Di Serio, L. C. (2017) 'The Relationship Between National Culture Dimensions And Degree Of Innovation', *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 21(1). doi: 10.1142/S136391961730001X.

Quinton, S. and Wilson, D. (2016) 'Tensions and ties in social media networks: Towards a model of understanding business relationship development and business performance enhancement through the use of LinkedIn', *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 54, pp. 15–24. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2015.12.001.

Al Rahbi, H. S. (2017) *Factors Influencing Social Media Adoption in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)*. Brunel University London. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2016.1196571>.

Ramani, G. and Kumar, V. (2008) 'Interaction orientation and firm performance', *Journal of Marketing*, 72(1), pp. 27–45. doi: 10.1509/jmkg.72.1.27.

Ramayah, T., Mohamad, O., Omar, A., Marimuthu, M. and Leen, J., Y., A. (2013) 'Determinants

of technology adoption among Malaysian SMEs: an IDT perspective’, *Journal of ICT*, 12, pp. 103–119.

Ramdani, B., Kawalek, P. and Lorenzo, O. (2009) ‘Predicting SMEs’ adoption of enterprise systems’, *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 22(June 2020), pp. 10–24. doi: 10.1108/17410390910922796.

Rapp, A., Beitelspacher, L., S., Grewal, D. and Hughes, D., E. (2013) ‘Understanding social media effects across seller, retailer, and consumer interactions’, *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 41(5), pp. 547–566. doi: 10.1007/s11747-013-0326-9.

Ratner, C. and Hui, L. (2003) ‘Theoretical and Methodological Problems in Cross-National Research’, *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 33(1), pp. 67–94. doi: 10.1111/j.1467-9523.1969.tb00606.x.

Rėklaitis, K. and Pilelienė, L. (2019) ‘Principle Differences between B2B and B2C Marketing Communication Processes’, *Management of Organizations: Systematic Research*, 81(1), pp. 73–86. doi: 10.1515/mosr-2019-0005.

Rice, P. L. and Ezzy, D. (1999) *Qualitative Research Methods: A Health Focus*. South Melbourne (Australia): Oxford University Press.

Rindfleisch, A. and Antia, K. (2012) ‘Survey research in B2B marketing: Current challenges and emerging opportunities’, *Handbook of Business-to-Business Marketing*, pp. 699–714. doi: 10.4337/9781849801423.00050.

Rinne, T., Steel, G. D. and Fairweather, J. (2012) ‘Hofstede and Shane Revisited: The Role of Power Distance and Individualism in National-Level Innovation Success’, *Cross-Cultural*

Research, 46(2), pp. 91–108. doi: 10.1177/1069397111423898.

Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., McNaughton, N., C. and Ormston, R. (2013) *QUALITATIVE RESEARCH PRACTICE: A GUIDE FOR SOCIAL SCIENCE STUDENTS AND RESEARCHERS*. SAGE. doi: 10.2118/40002-ms.

Roberts, K., Dowell, A. and Nie, J. B. (2019) ‘Attempting rigour and replicability in thematic analysis of qualitative research data; A case study of codebook development’, *BMC Medical Research Methodology*. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 19(1), pp. 1–8. doi: 10.1186/s12874-019-0707-y.

Robinson, P. J., Farris, C. W. and Wind, Y. (1967) *Industrial Buying and Creative Marketing*. Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon.

Rodakinias, P., Skayannis, P. and Zygoura, A. (2008) ‘Greek SMEs in the Information Society: ICT Use and Integration in the Region of Dytiki Makedonia’, (June), p. 18.

Rogers, E. (1995) *Diffusion of Innovations*. 4th edn. New York, NY, USA: The Free Press.

Rogers, E. M. (1983) *Diffusion of innovations*. 3rd edn, *An Integrated Approach to Communication Theory and Research, Third Edition*. 3rd edn. The Free Press. doi: 10.4324/9780203710753-35.

Rogers, E. M. (2003) *Diffusion of Innovations*. 5th edn. New York: Free Press.

Rooderkerk, R. P. and Pauwels, K. H. (2016) ‘No Comment?! The Drivers of Reactions to Online Posts in Professional Groups’, *Journal of Interactive Marketing*. *Marketing EDGE.org.*, 35, pp. 1–15. doi: 10.1016/j.intmar.2015.12.003.

Rousseau, D. M., Manning, J. and Denyer, D. (2008) ‘Evidence in Management and

Organizational Science: Assembling the Field's Full Weight of Scientific Knowledge Through Syntheses', *The Academy of Management Annals*, 2(1), pp. 475–515. doi: 10.1080/19416520802211651.

Rowley, J. and Holliman, G. (2014) "'Business to business digital content marketing: marketers' perceptions of best practice'", *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 8(4), pp. 269–293. doi: 10.1108/JRIM-02-2014-0013.

Saha, S. K., Islam, A. and Rodela, R. S. (2014) 'A Comparative Study On B2B Vs. B2C Based On Asia Pacific Region', *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 3(9), pp. 294–298.

Saldana, J. (2016) *The Coding Manual of Qualitative Researchers*. 3rd edn. SAGE Publications Ltd. doi: 10.1002/9780470975220.ch1.

Salo, J. (2017) 'Social media research in the industrial marketing field: Review of literature and future research directions', *Industrial Marketing Management*. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2017.07.013.

Sandelowski, M. (2000) 'What's in a name? Qualitative description revisited', *Research in Nursing & Health*, 33(1), pp. 77–84.

Sashi, C. M. (2012) 'Customer engagement, buyer-seller relationships, and social media', *Management Decision*, 50(2), pp. 253–272. doi: 10.1108/00251741211203551.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2007) *Research Methods for Business Students*. 4th edn. Edinburgh Gate, Harlow: Financial Times Prentice Hall.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2009) *Research Methods for Business Students*. New

York: Pearson.

Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2016) *Research Methods for Business Students*. 7th edn, *Research Methods for Business Students*. 7th edn. Pearson Education Limited.

Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2019) *Research Methods for Business Students*. 8th edn. Harlow, UK: Pearson Education Limited.

Schaeffer, N. C., Seltzer, J. A. and Klawitter, M. (1991) 'Estimating Nonresponse and Response Bias: Resident and Nonresident Parents' Reports about Child Support', *Sociological Methods & Research*, 20(1), pp. 30–59. doi: 10.1177/0049124191020001002.

Seidman, I. (2013) *Interviewing as Qualitative Research : A Guide for Researchers in Education and The Social Sciences*. 4th edn, *Teachers College Press*. 4th edn. Teachers College Press.

Shaltoni, A. M. (2017) 'From websites to social media: exploring the adoption of internet marketing in emerging industrial markets', *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 32(7), pp. 1009–1019. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-06-2016-0122.

Shenton, A. K. (2004) 'Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects', *Education for Information*, 22(2), pp. 63–75. doi: 10.3233/EFI-2004-22201.

Siamagka, N. T., Christodoulides, G., Michaelidou, N. and Valvi, A. (2015) 'Determinants of social media adoption by B2B organizations', *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 51, pp. 89–99. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2015.05.005.

Sigala, M. and Chalkiti, K. (2015) 'Knowledge management, social media and employee creativity', *International Journal of Hospitality Management*. Elsevier Ltd, 45, pp. 44–58. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2014.11.003.

Snelson, C. L. (2016) 'Qualitative and mixed methods social media research: A review of the literature', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 15(1), pp. 1–15. doi: 10.1177/1609406915624574.

Søndergaard, M. (1994) 'Research Note: Hofstede's Consequences: A Study of Reviews, Citations and Replications', *Organization Studies*, 15(3), pp. 447–456. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/017084069401500307>.

Sørnes, J.-O., Stephens, K., K., Sætre, A., S. and Browning, L., D. (2004) 'The reflexivity between ICTs and business culture: Applying Hofstede's theory to compare Norway and the United States', *Informing Science Journal*, 7, pp. 1–30. doi: 10.28945/500.

Souto, D. B. F.-F. (2009) 'Crisis and Corporate Social Responsibility: Threat or Opportunity?', *International Journal of Business and Economic Sciences Applied Research (IJBESAR)*, 2(1), pp. 36–50.

Srinivasan, R. (2012) 'Marketing Metrics in B2B Firms', in Lilien, G. L. and Grewal, R. (eds) *Handbook of Business-to-Business Marketing*. Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 715–730.

Stake, R. E. (1995) 'Case studies', in Denziin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (eds) *Handbook of qualitative research*. Sage, pp. 236–247.

Stangor, C. (2011) *Research Methods for the behavioral sciences*. 4th edn. Wadsworth.

Statista (2021) *Facebook: number of monthly active users worldwide 2008-2021*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/264810/number-of-monthly-active-facebook-users-worldwide/>.

Steyn, P., Salehi-Sangari, E., Pitt, L., Parent, M. and Berthon, P. (2010) 'The Social Media Release

as a public relations tool: Intentions to use among B2B bloggers’, *Public Relations Review*, 36(1), pp. 87–89. doi: 10.1016/j.pubrev.2009.09.005.

Stockdale, R., Ahmed, A. and Scheepers, H. (2012) ‘Identifying Business Value From the Use of Social Media: an Sme Perspective’, in *PACIS 2012 Proceedings*, pp. 1–14.

Stokes, D. and Nelson, C. (2013) ‘Word of Mouth to Word of Mouse: Social Media and the Entrepreneur’, in Sethna, Z., Jones, R., and Harrigan, P. (eds) *Entrepreneurial Marketing: Global Perspectives*. Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing Ltd.

Stoltzfus, J. C. (2011) ‘Logistic regression: A brief primer’, *Academic Emergency Medicine*, 18(10), pp. 1099–1104. doi: 10.1111/j.1553-2712.2011.01185.x.

Sträub, E. T. (2009) ‘Understanding Technology Adoption : Theory and Future Directions for Informal Learning’, *Review of Educational Research*, 79(2), pp. 625–649.

Strauss, A. and Corbin, J. (1998) *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. 2nd edn. Sage Publications, Inc.

Strauss, J. and Frost, R. (2009) *E-Marketing*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.

Sundqvist, S., Frank, L. and Puumalainen, K. (2005) ‘The effects of country characteristics, cultural similarity and adoption timing on the diffusion of wireless communications’, *Journal of Business Research*, 58(1), pp. 107–110. doi: 10.1016/S0148-2963(02)00480-0.

Sürücü, L. and Maslakçı, A. (2020) ‘Validity and Reliability in Quantitative Research’, *Business & Management Studies: An International Journal*, 8(3), pp. 2694–2726. doi: 10.15295/bmij.v8i3.1540.

Swain, J. (2018) ‘A Hybrid Approach to Thematic Analysis in Qualitative Research: Using a

Practical Example’, *SAGE Research Methods Cases Part 2*, pp. 1–28. doi: 10.4135/9781526435477.

Swani, K., Milne, G. R., Brown, B. P., Assaf, A. G. and Donthu, N. (2017) ‘What messages to post? Evaluating the popularity of social media communications in business versus consumer markets’, *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 62, pp. 77–87. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2016.07.006.

Swani, K. and Brown, B. P. (2011) ‘The effectiveness of social media messages in organisational buying contexts’, in *American Marketing Association 2011 AMA Educators’ Proceedings*.

Swani, K., Brown, B. P. and Milne, G. R. (2014) ‘Should tweets differ for B2B and B2C? An analysis of Fortune 500 companies’ Twitter communications’, *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 43(5), pp. 873–881. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2014.04.012.

Swani, K., Milne, G. and Brown, B. P. (2013) ‘Spreading the word through likes on Facebook Evaluating the message strategy effectiveness of Fortune 500 companies’, *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 7(4), pp. 269–294.

Tabachnick, G. B. and Fidell, S. L. (2013) *Using Multivariate Statistics*. 6th edn. New Jersey: Pearson Education, Inc.

Tajudeen, F. P., Jaafar, N. I. and Ainin, S. (2018) ‘Understanding the impact of social media usage among organizations’, *Information and Management*. Elsevier, 55(3), pp. 308–321. doi: 10.1016/j.im.2017.08.004.

Tarafdar, M. and Vaidya, S. D. (2006) ‘Challenges in the adoption of E-Commerce technologies in India: The role of organizational factors’, *International Journal of Information Management*,

26(6), pp. 428–441. doi: 10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2006.08.001.

Tashakkori, A. and Teddlie, C. (1998) *Mixed Methodology: Combining Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. SAGE Publications, Inc. doi: 10.2307/2655606.

Tashakkori, A. and Teddlie, C. (2010) *Sage Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social & Behavioral Research*. 2nd edn. SAGE Publications.

Tavakol, M. and Dennick, R. (2011) ‘Making sense of Cronbach’s alpha’, *International journal of medical education*, 2, pp. 53–55. doi: 10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd.

Taylor, M. Z. and Wilson, S. (2012) ‘Does culture still matter?: The effects of individualism on national innovation rates’, *Journal of Business Venturing*. Elsevier Inc., 27(2), pp. 234–247. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusvent.2010.10.001.

Tehrani, S. R. and Shirazi, F. (2014) ‘Factors influencing the adoption of cloud computing by Small and Medium size Enterprises (SMEs)’, in Yamamoto, S. (ed.) *Human Interface and the Management of Information. Information and knowledge in Applications and Services. HIMI 2014. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Cham: Springer, pp. 631–642. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-07863-2_60.

Tharenou, P., Donohue, R. and Cooper, B. (2007) *MANAGEMENT RESEARCH METHODS*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

Themistocleous, M. (2004) ‘Justifying the decisions for EAI implementations: A validated proposition of influential factors’, *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 17(2), pp. 85–104. doi: 10.1108/17410390410518745.

Thompson, V. A. (1965) ‘Bureaucracy and innovation’, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 10(1),

pp. 1–20.

Thong, J. Y. L. (1999) ‘An integrated model of information systems adoption in small businesses’, *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 15(4), pp. 187–214. doi: 10.1080/07421222.1999.11518227.

Thong, J. Y. L. (2001) ‘Resource constraints and information systems implementation in Singaporean small businesses’, *Omega*, 29(2), pp. 143–156. doi: 10.1016/S0305-0483(00)00035-9.

Tranfield, D., Denyer, D. and Smart, P. (2003) ‘Towards a Methodology for Developing Evidence-Informed Management Knowledge by Means of Systematic Review *’, 14.

Trochim, W. M. K. (2000) *The Research Methods Knowledge Base*. 2nd edn. Cincinnati: Atomic Dog Publishing.

Tsakanikas, A., Danchev, S., Giotopoulos, I., Korra, E. and Pavlou, G. (2014) *ICT Adoption and Digital Growth in Greece*. Available at: www.iobe.gr.

Tsatsou, P. (2012) ‘The Role of Social Culture in Internet Adoption in Greece: Unpacking “I Don’t Want to Use the Internet” and Frequency of Use’, *Information Society*, 28(3), pp. 174–188. doi: 10.1080/01972243.2012.670190.

Tsimonis, G. and Dimitriadis, S. (2014) ‘Brand strategies in social media’, *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, 32(3), pp. 328–344. doi: 10.1108/MIP-04-2013-0056.

Tuten, T. L. and Solomon, M. R. (2015) *Social Media Marketing*. 2nd edn. Sage.

Vasudevan, S. and Kumar, F. J. P. (2018) ‘Social media and B2B brands: An Indian perspective’, *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 9(9), pp. 767–775.

- Vatcheva, P. K., Lee, M., McCormick, B., J. and Rahbar, H.M. (2016) ‘Multicollinearity in Regression Analyses Conducted in Epidemiologic Studies’, *Epidemiology: Open Access*, 06(02), pp. 1–9. doi: 10.4172/2161-1165.1000227.
- Veldeman, C., Van Praet, E. and Mechant, P. (2017) ‘Social Media Adoption in Business-to-Business: IT and Industrial Companies Compared’, *International Journal of Business Communication*, 54(3), pp. 283–305. doi: 10.1177/2329488415572785.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M., G., Davis, G., B. and Davis, F., D. (2003) ‘User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View’, *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), pp. 425–478.
- Venkatesh, V., Brown, S. A. and Bala, H. (2013) ‘Bridging the qualitative–quantitative divide: Guidelines for conducting mixed methods research in information systems’, *MIS Quarterly*, 37(1), pp. 21–54. doi: 10.25300/MISQ/2013/37.1.02.
- Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F. D. (1996) ‘A model of the antecedents of perceived ease of use: Development and test.’, *Decision Sciences*, 27(19), pp. 451–481.
- Verheyden, M. and Goeman, K. (2013) ‘Does (Company) Size Matter? Differences in Social Media Usage for Business Purposes’, *Journal of Applied Quantitative Methods*, 8(4), pp. 3–16.
- Vlachvei, A. and Notta, O. (2014) ‘Social Media adoption and managers’ perceptions’, *International Journal of Strategic Innovative Marketing*, 01, pp. 61–73. doi: 10.15556/IJSIM.01.02.001.
- Vlachvei, A. and Notta, O. (2015) ‘Understanding Social Media ROI in SMEs IRC-2015 Understanding Social Media ROI in SMEs’, *Proceedings of International Organization for Research and Development – IRC2015*, (c), pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://docplayer.net/18629797->

Understanding-social-media-roi-in-smes.html.

Voulgaris, Y. and Sotiropoulos, D. A. (2002) 'Information society, sociology and technology [in Greek]', *Operational Programme for the Information Society. Athens, Greece.*

Wang, R., Fu, Z. and Duan, Y. (2011) 'Understanding ICTs adoption from an evolutionary process perspective', in *Management and Service Science (MASS), 2011 International Conference. IEEE*, pp. 1–4.

Wang, W. Y. C., Pauleen, D. J. and Zhang, T. (2016) 'How social media applications affect B2B communication and improve business performance in SMEs', *Industrial Marketing Management*. Elsevier Inc., 54, pp. 4–14. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2015.12.004.

Wang, Y., Rod, M., Ji, S. and Deng, Q. (2017) 'Social media capability in B2B marketing: toward a definition and a research model', *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 32(8), pp. 1125–1135. doi: 10.1108/JBIM-10-2016-0250.

Wang, Y. M., Wang, Y. S. and Yang, Y. F. (2010) 'Understanding the determinants of RFID adoption in the manufacturing industry', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. Elsevier Inc., 77(5), pp. 803–815. doi: 10.1016/j.techfore.2010.03.006.

Wang, Y., S., Wang, Y., M., Lin, H., H., and Tang, T., I. (2003) 'Determinants of user acceptance of internet banking: An empirical study', *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 14(5), pp. 501–519.

Webster, F. E. J. (1978) 'Management Science in Industrial Marketing: A review of models and measurement techniques—new rigor, new sophistication', *Journal of Marketing*, 42(1), pp. 21–27. doi: 10.1177/002224297804200106.

Weinberg, T. (2009) *The New Community Rules: Marketing on the Social Web*. 1st edn. California.: O'Reilly.

Williams, M., D., Dwivedi, Y., K., Lal, B. and Schwarz, A. (2009) 'Contemporary trends and issues in IT adoption and diffusion research', *Journal of Information Technology*, 24(1), pp. 1–10. doi: 10.1057/jit.2008.30.

Wilson, D. (1999) *Organizational Marketing*. International Thomson Business Press. doi: 10.4135/9781452229669.n2494.

Wilson, J. (2014) *Essentials of Business Research Methods. A Guide to Doing Your Research Project*. 2nd edn. SAGE Publications. doi: 10.4324/9781315704562.

Wilson, J. R. and Lorenz, K. A. (2015) *Short History of the Logistic Regression Model*. In: *Modeling Binary Correlated Responses using SAS, SPSS and R*.

Wong, C. B. (2012) 'Facebook Usage by Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise: The role of Domain-Specific Innovativeness', *Global Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, 12(4), pp. 52–59. <http://computerresearch.org/stpr/index.php/gjcst/article/viewArticle/1020>.

Wood, J. and Khan, G. F. (2016) 'Social business adoption: An empirical analysis', *Business Information Review*, 33(1), pp. 28–39. doi: 10.1177/0266382116631851.

World Bank (2021) *Gross domestic product 2020, PPP*. Available at: https://databank.worldbank.org/data/download/GDP_PPP.pdf.

Wright, R. (2004) *Business-to-Business Marketing : A Step-by- Step Guide*. Financial Times Press.

Wynd, C. A., Schmidt, B. and Schaefer, M. A. (2003) 'Two quantitative approaches for estimating content validity', *Western Journal of Nursing Research*, 25(5), pp. 508–518. doi:

10.1177/0193945903252998.

Xu, W. and Zammit, K. (2020) 'Applying Thematic Analysis to Education: A Hybrid Approach to Interpreting Data in Practitioner Research', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19(April), pp. 1–9. doi: 10.1177/1609406920918810.

Yin, R. K. (2011) *Qualitative Research from Start to Finish*, THE GUILFORD PRESS.

Yin, R. K. (2014) *Case study research: Design and methods*. 5th edn. SAGE.

Yin, R. K. (2017) *Case study research and applications: Design and methods*. SAGE Publications.

Ylimaula, K.-A. and Ulkuniemi, P. (2013) 'Exploring the Potential of Social Media in Supplier Relationship Management', in *IMP2013 Conference*, pp. 1–23. Available at: <https://www.impgroup.org/uploads/papers/8012.pdf>.

Zeiller, M. and Schauer, B. (2011) 'Adoption, motivation and success factors of social media for team collaboration in SMEs', *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Knowledge Management and Knowledge Technologies - i-KNOW '11*, pp. 1–8. doi: 10.1145/2024288.2024294.

Zhao, F. (2013) 'An empirical study of cultural dimensions and e-government development: Implications of the findings and strategies', *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 32(3), pp. 294–306. doi: 10.1080/0144929X.2011.644580.

Zhu, K., Kraemer, K. and Xu, S. (2003) 'Electronic business adoption by European firms: A cross-country assessment of the facilitators and inhibitors', *European Journal of Information Systems*, 12(4), pp. 251–268. doi: 10.1057/palgrave.ejis.3000475.

Zohrabi, M. (2013) 'Mixed Method Research: Instruments, Validity, Reliability and Reporting

Findings', *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 3(2), pp. 254–262. doi: 10.4304/tpis.3.2.254-262.

Appendix A

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Social media (SM) platforms:

Can you please introduce yourself?

(Name, position, how long you have been working for the company, role)

1. When did your company start using SM?
2. Why did your company decide to use SM?
3. What are the uses of SM by your company? Can you give me three examples?
4. Can you illustrate, with examples, how this has contributed or added value to the company's objectives?
5. Do you think SM platforms help the organisation interact with its business partners?
6. Do you think SM platforms are suitable for B2B companies?
7. What SM platforms would you think are most suitable for B2B marketing?
8. What do you think are the main factors that are affecting the adoption and use of SM between your organisation and its business partners?
9. From your personal perspective, what do you think are the key benefits from the use of SM by your company?
10. What do you think are the main barriers for the adoption and use of SM?

Technological context:

11. Do you think that the adoption of SM gives a relative advantage to your company?

12. Are SM platforms compatible with the company's existing infrastructure and information systems?
13. Do you consider the adoption of SM complex by your company?
14. Are there any other technological factors that you think have an impact on the decision of adoption of SM by your company?

Organisational context:

15. Do you think that the size of your company affects the decision to adopt SM? If so, why?
16. Do you think the top management team has allocated adequate resources for the adoption of new technologies? If so, what is the top management support for the adoption of SM platforms in your company?
17. Do you believe that your company is innovative? If yes, do you think the innovativeness of your company impacted the adoption of SM?
18. Do the employees of the company have the appropriate knowledge and technological skills for the adoption and use of SM?
19. Do you think there are any other organisational/management factors that have an impact on your company's perception about SM?

Environmental context:

20. Has Government policy encouraged or supported the adoption of SM by the businesses?
Could you please give me some examples?
21. Do you think it is essential to use SM to compete in the telecommunication industry and if you don't adopt SM, do you think you will lose customers to your competitors?
22. What other environmental factors do you think impact the adoption of SM in your company? Why?

Culture:

23. Do you think that the Greek culture plays a role in the adoption of SM? If yes, could you please give me some examples?

General:

24. How would you score your company between 1-10, with regards to adoption of SM? What do you think should be done to increase the score to the maximum score of 10?

25. Where do you see the company in 5-10 years regarding the use of SM platforms?

Appendix B

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it involves. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please feel free to ask questions if anything you read is not clear or you would like additional information or clarity. Take your time in deciding whether you want to take part. Thank you for reading this.

What is the purpose of this investigation?

The purpose of this research is to investigate the factors influencing the adoption of social media marketing (SMM) by Business-to-Business (B2B) organisations in Greece and the perceived benefits and barriers of this adoption.

Do you have to take part?

Participation in this study is voluntary. I will describe the study and go through the information sheet, which I will give you. I will then ask you to sign a consent form documenting your agreement to voluntarily participate. At any time, you are free to withdraw without giving a reason. This decision will not affect the standard of care you receive.

What will you do in the project?

You will be required to attend an interview lasting approximately forty-five (45) minutes to one (1) hour.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been invited to take part because of your specific job in the organisation I want to research.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

During the research you will be not exposed to any physical, psychological or legal risk or harm.

The Interview and its questions have been semi structured in such a way so that your privacy will be protected, and no pressure will be put on you to answer sensitive questions. All information pertaining to you as an individual and your organisation will be anonymised and kept confidential.

The data you provide will not compromise your position in the organisation at any point in time.

What happens to the information in the project?

The information I record, and document will be kept safely on University's OneDrive and no one else can access the files. Once I have analysed the results, they will be put into my thesis and upon submission and successful completion of Doctorate degree I will destroy the notes.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the General Data Protection Regulation and the Data Protection Act 2018. All personal data on participants will be processed in accordance with the provisions of this legislation.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in this project, please sign the consent form to confirm this. If you do not wish to be involved, thank you very much for your time.

Researcher Details:

Zoe.Chroni: [REDACTED]

Supervisor Details:

Dr Pravin Balaraman: [REDACTED]

Appendix C

CONSENT FORM

Please tick where appropriate.

	Please initial box
1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving reason.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. I agree to take part in the above study.	<input type="checkbox"/>

The following statements should be ticked, if appropriate. If not, please *ignore*.

	Please initial box	
	Yes	No
4. I agree to the interview being audio recorded	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. I agree to the use of anonymised quotes in publications	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. I agree that my research data may be used for a further project in anonymous form, but I am able to opt out of this if I wish.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

_____	_____	_____
Name of Participant	Date	Signature
_____	_____	_____
Researcher	Date	Signature

This project is supervised by Dr Pravin Balaraman

Researcher's Name and Contact: Zoe Chroni, [REDACTED]

Appendix D

29/01/2019

Dear Maria Zoitsa Chroni,

Your application 6110: Factors influencing social media adoption by Business-to-Business organisations in Greece. A case study approach., submission 4888, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Appendix E

Dear Sir/Madam

My name is Zoe Chroni, and I am a PhD student at the University of West of Scotland, UK. My doctoral research focuses mainly on factors that influence the Greek Business-to-Business (B2B B2B) companies to adopt social media (SM) as a marketing tool as well as the possible benefits and barriers of such adoption. I believe that the results will be valuable not only for individual companies but will also help the competent authorities to identify and better understand the factors that are needed to help Greek B2B companies become more competitive in the new digital age.

To date, there is insufficient academic input on this subject, and I am conducting this research as part of my PhD. Obtaining my PhD, in part, depends on your cooperation.

I recognize the value of your time and sincerely appreciate your efforts to take part in this study. The information you provide will be strictly confidential. Your identity will not be revealed and only I and my Supervisor, Dr Pravin Balaraman, will be able to examine your answers. All data collected by participants will be analyzed together so that it is impossible to locate your personal or company information. The research results will be included in my doctoral dissertation and may later be published in academic journals.

I would like to thank you in advance for agreeing to participate in this research. Click this link to complete the search:

http://uwsbusinessschool.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_0p9IDrEHzhs9yfj

If you have questions about this study or the questionnaire, please contact me using the information below:

Zoe M. Chroni

PhD Researcher

University of the West of Scotland

email: [REDACTED]

Appendix F

ONLINE SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Thank you in advance for your answers to this anonymous survey. Your participation will help us understand the factors that influence the Greek B2B companies to adopt and use social media (SM) and the benefits and barriers they face for this adoption. Should you agree to participate, this online survey will take approximately 15-20 minutes to complete. There are no right or wrong answers. Please select the first checkbox to confirm you agree to participate and understand that this survey is entirely anonymous if you wish to participate.

- I agree to participate and understand that this research is anonymous
- I choose not to participate

1.Respondent's job status:

- Owner
- Senior Manager
- Junior Manager
- 'Other (Please specify)

2. Age:

- under 20
- 20- 29 years
- 30- 39 years
- 40- 49 years
- 50- 59 years
- over 60

3. Education level:

- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education

4. How old is the company?

- less than 1 year
- 1-3 years
- 3-5 years
- more than 5 years

5. Industry:

- Manufacturing
- Construction
- Finance and Insurance
- Banking
- Tourism
- Food / Drinks
- Clothing
- Real estate
- Mining and quarrying
- Wholesale and retail
- Information Technology (IT) and communication
- Education
- Government
- Health services
- Transport and storage
- Marketing and advertising
- Ecommerce
- Other (please specify)

6. Company orientation:

- Business to Business (B2B)
- Business to Consumer (B2C)
- Business to Business and Business to Consumer (B2B and B2C)
- Business to Government (B2G)
- Other (Please specify)

7. Number of employees:

- 1-9
- 10- 49
- 50- 249
- 250- 499
- 500-999
- 1000- 4999
- more than 5000

8. Turnover:

- less than 25,000 €
- 25,000 € to 100,000 €
- 100,000 € to 250,000 €
- 250,000 € to 1,000,000 €
- 1,000,000 to 5,000,000 €
- More than 5,000,000 €

9. Market area (select all that apply):

- local market
- regional market
- national market
- international market
- worldwide market
- Other (Please specify)

10. Does your company have presence in SM?

- Yes
- No

(If your answer is No, please skip to Questions 14, 15, and 16)

11. How long has your business been using SM?

- less than 6 months

- 6 to 12 months
- 1 to 2 years
- over 2 years

12. Please indicate which of the following SM platforms your company uses (select all that apply)?

- Facebook
- Instagram
- LinkedIn
- Twitter
- YouTube
- Pinterest
- WhatsApp
- Blogs
- Instant messaging (Skype)
- Other (Please specify)

13. For what purpose does your company use SM? (Select all that apply)

- Brand awareness
- Marketing
- Advertising and promotion
- Product demos
- Share content
- Acquisition of new clients
- Develop customer relationships
- Communication with customers / suppliers
- Conducting market research
- Customer feedback
- Customer service
- Sales support
- Building thought leadership

- Recruitment
- Other (please specify)

14. Which of the following statements best describes the purpose of your business in terms of SM?

- we intend to adopt SM
- we do not intend to adopt SM in the future

15. If your business intends to use SM, when do you think this will happen?

- in less than 6 months
- from 6 to 12 months
- from 1 to 2 years
- more than 2 years
- no plans yet

16. If your business does not intend to adopt SM, could you identify the reasons?

17. Technological factors

The purpose of this section is to identify the technological factors that influence the adoption of SM by your business. Indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with each of the following:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The use of SM gives a relative advantage to the company	○	○	○	○	○

SM platforms are compatible with the company's existing IT infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>				
SM platforms are too complicated to understand and use	<input type="radio"/>				
The company was able to test the SM platforms before using them	<input type="radio"/>				

18. Organisational factors

The purpose of this section is to identify the factors related to the organisation influencing the adoption of SM in your business.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The size of the company has influenced the decision to adopt SM	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The cost required to implement SM platforms is too high for our company	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Top management supports the adoption of SM	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Top management allocated adequate resources for the adoption of SM	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Our employees have the necessary knowledge and understanding of SMM	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

19. Environmental factors

The aim of this section is to identify the environmental factors (the internal and external environment) that influence the adoption of SM in your business.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Compared to other businesses in our industry, our company is very innovative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Our company is under pressure from competitors to adopt SMM	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If we do not adopt SM, we will lose our customers to our competitors	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The government has effective laws to combat cyber crime	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The company is using/or used the support of a consulting company for SMM	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

20. Cultural factors

The purpose of this section is to identify the cultural factors that influence the adoption of SM from your business.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The Greek culture has an impact on the adoption of SM	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The opinion of the CEO/Manager/Owner is the most important opinion in the business	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The top management team is willing to accept the opinion of IT specialists on SM	<input type="radio"/>				
It is important for the company to achieve credibility with its business partners	<input type="radio"/>				
It is important for the company to build trust and long-lasting relationships with its business partners	<input type="radio"/>				
High competitiveness is a key element of success in the businesses	<input type="radio"/>				
The company has created laws and rules for tackling change and uncertainty in the external environment	<input type="radio"/>				
The company maintains some links with its past while confronting the present challenges	<input type="radio"/>				
The company prefers to maintain timeless traditions	<input type="radio"/>				
The company prefers to maintain timeless rules	<input type="radio"/>				

21. Benefits

The purpose of this section is to determine the benefits of adopting and using SM for your business

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The use of SM added value to the company	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The use of SM led to new business opportunities for the company	<input type="radio"/>				
The use of SM has improved our competitiveness	<input type="radio"/>				
The use of SM has led to lower costs	<input type="radio"/>				
The use of SM increased the profitability	<input type="radio"/>				
The adoption of SM has helped the company better communicate with its business partners and customers	<input type="radio"/>				
The use of SM has enhanced internal relationships	<input type="radio"/>				
The use of SM has enhanced external relationships	<input type="radio"/>				
The use of SM has strengthened the business reputation	<input type="radio"/>				
The use of SM helps with advertising and marketing	<input type="radio"/>				
The SM platforms used by the company provide a secure environment for information sharing	<input type="radio"/>				

22. Barriers

The purpose of this section is to identify the main barriers to the adoption and use of SM by your business.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
SM cannot add value to the company	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The company does not have enough the technological skills to adopt SM	<input type="radio"/>				
The company does not have enough time to adopt SM	<input type="radio"/>				
The company does not have sufficient financial resources	<input type="radio"/>				
The company cannot control communication through SM	<input type="radio"/>				
The company cannot measure the SM return on investment (ROI)	<input type="radio"/>				
The size of the business has a negative impact on the adoption of social	<input type="radio"/>				
SM are not relevant to the company's goals	<input type="radio"/>				
The company is afraid of negative comments or criticism	<input type="radio"/>				
The company can achieve its goals without SM	<input type="radio"/>				
The content posted on company's SM platforms could be used inappropriately	<input type="radio"/>				
The company does not have a specific SM plan	<input type="radio"/>				
The company does not have a specific SM strategy	<input type="radio"/>				

23. Which of the following methods would help your business (during this or next year) use SM?

- Seminars and other events on the use of SM by companies
- Studies and reports about the topic in Greece and elsewhere on the adoption of SM by businesses
- Support of a Consulting company of how to use SM

- Internet forums providing information and participation in discussions about the topic
- Getting information about various tools and their suppliers

24. Would you like a summary of the research findings?

- Yes
- No

25. If yes, please fill in your email address:

26. Comments / Suggestions:

Appendix G

Goodness-fit-statistics

Classification Table^{a,b}

			Predicted		
			Adoption		Percentage Correct
			No	Yes	
Step 0	Observed				
	Adoption	No	0	25	.0
		Yes	0	47	100.0
Overall Percentage				65.3	

a. Constant is included in the model.

b. The cut value is .500

Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step 1	Step	46.283	20	.001
	Block	46.283	20	.001
	Model	46.283	20	.001

Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	46.699 ^a	.474	.654

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 7 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.

Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

Step	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	5.783	8	.672

Classification Table^a

			Predicted		
			Adoption		Percentage Correct
			No	Yes	
Step 1	Observed				
	Adoption	No	20	5	80.0
		Yes	4	43	91.5
Overall Percentage				87.5	

The cut value is .500